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JOANNES PAULUS TOLENTINO HERNANDEZ

COVID-19 INFODEMIC IN THE TWITTERVERSE: CHARACTERIZATION OF MISINFORMATION SPREAD AND TWITTER BOT ACTIVITY BY CRITICAL MASS, ENERGY DECAY, ENTANGLEMENTS, AND NODE SYNCHRONIZATION USING MULTILAYER AND SPECTRAL GRAPH VISUALIZATIONS, KURAMOTO MODELING, SONIFICATION, AND WAVEFUNCTION SIMULATION

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This paper prepared by **JOANNES PAULUS TOLENTINO HERNANDEZ** with the title: **“COVID-19 INFODEMIC IN THE TWITTERVERSE: CHARACTERIZATION OF MISINFORMATION SPREAD AND TWITTER BOT ACTIVITY BY CRITICAL MASS, ENERGY DECAY, ENTANGLEMENTS, AND NODE SYNCHRONIZATION USING MULTILAYER AND SPECTRAL GRAPH VISUALIZATIONS, KURAMOTO MODELING, SONIFICATION, AND WAVEFUNCTION SIMULATION”** is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Doctor of Communication.

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Biographical Sketch

The Researcher is a Registered Nurse in the Philippines and United States of America (Connecticut, New York, and Florida). He was a graduate of UPOU's Master of Arts in Nursing (MAN) Program (Adult Health Nursing) in 2012 (his BSN at Emilio Aguinaldo College, Manila in 2005). He became a clinical and simulation lab faculty of Advanced Adult Care and Critical Care Nursing in the College of Nursing at Ha'il University, Saudi Arabia until 2020. From 2020 to 2021, he worked as a Chronic Dialysis RN II at DaVita Lynbrook Dialysis Center, NY, USA. He is a member of Sigma Theta Tau International Honor Society of Nursing and International Association for Human Caring since 2019.

In the final completion of the DComm Program, the Researcher holds a full-time, faculty coordinator position for nursing lab simulations at the Swedish Institute College of Health Sciences, New York, USA, and where he got featured on Pix11 Morning News (available at <https://pix11.com/news/morning/swedish-institute-trains-next-class-of-nursing-heroes/> [stream at 1:17-1:18 and 1:47-1:48]). His computer savviness and interest in data mining led him to teach Nursing Informatics at Helene Fuld College of Nursing, NY, USA.

The Researcher was a recipient of two awards, namely: the Professional Conference Award from Chi Nu Sigma Chapter in March 2021 and then the Edith Anderson Leadership Education Grant from Sigma Foundation in April 2021 for the co-authored PechaKucha presentation, titled as "Humanoid Ethics in the Post Humanistic Era: Perspective from Rogerian Science of Unitary Human Beings" in Sigma's 32nd International Nursing Research Virtual Congress from July 21 to 23, 2021.

The Researcher's innovativeness with simulation technology in Nursing Education resonated during the COVID-19 pandemic. He became a Plenary Speaker about "Global Perspectives on Clinical Learning Experiences" at the 62nd Annual (Virtual) Convention and General Assembly of the Association of Deans of Philippine Colleges of Nursing, Inc. anchored on the theme: "Sustaining Quality Nursing Education amidst the Pandemic". Only two Filipino US-based Nursing Faculty were invited to this event from separate educational institutions: Swedish Institute College of Health Sciences; and New York University Rory Meyers College of Nursing.

Another milestone of achievement for the Researcher was when his doctoral dissertation earned a grant. This study was funded in part by **The Vicente Teves Locsin, Jr. Award for Scholarship in Advancing the Theory of Technological Competency as Caring in Nursing** on March 14, 2022 through the International Association for Human Caring based in Michigan, USA.

Dedication

To God be the glory for the success of this scholarly work. What abounds in its future direction is by Will of the same Almighty God. Here on earth, this work is dedicated to the following: my parents, Mrs. Irma Tolentino-Hernandez and Mr. Renato Onda Hernandez, who were the first to believe I can be an astronaut and nonetheless, a great scientist; my younger sister, Jan Cressa Tolentino Hernandez, for her emotional support for my every struggle and victory; and my wife, Grace Dianne Peliño-Hernandez and her immediate family members, who believe I could win a Nobel Prize (in Physics) in the course of my career; and my Colleagues mostly in the Nursing academe, who believed nurses can exceed what society has (n)ever thought to be achievable.

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Abstract

No communication framework for “infodemiology” or investigative techniques within the discipline of communication have covered measurement of Twitter bots’ “virality” and (massive) “misinformation spread” by energy and mass equivalence because these belong to quantum mechanics.

To posit infodemical measurements, this study of “COVID-19 infodemic” on Twitter characterized misinformation spread and Twitter bot activity by critical mass, energy decay, entanglements, and node synchronization using multilayer and spectral graph visualizations, Kuramoto modeling, sonification, and wavefunction simulation. The Python-based analytics pipeline was developed based on fundamental conceptualizations of 7 communication theories and quantum mechanics.

Simulation and (stochastic) modeling were implemented to investigate the intra- and interlayer relationships between bots, humans, and tweets. This study endeavored on (1) theorizing “virality” and bot activity, (2) data mining using Hoaxy[®] and bot detection set at ≥ 0.43 using Botometer[®], and (3) comprehensive data analysis using state-of-the-art techniques and statistics.

Misinformation spreads more frequently with user replies than with retweets and faster through interlayer edges. Super spreaders were detected using centrality-based metrics. Bots that had high betweenness and eigenvector centralities, random walk score, and PageRank score were false human accounts.

Bot cliques emerged inconsistently by edge entanglement with humans. False human accounts were central spreaders and were detectable by an increase in percolation centrality, random walk and PageRank scores. Spammers were peripheral spreaders with scores decreased or unchanged whenever connected

indirectly to human hubs. False human accounts connect by power-law distribution. Many cross-links were shown between bots and humans. Overall, bots (re)produced the intrinsic “virality” of tweets with human users.

Bots synchronized (partially) around 400 seconds (6.67 minutes) at peak before reaching 200 seconds (3.33 minutes). Time to critical mass can be anticipated at .00025 seconds when bots have synchronized. Based on wavefunction simulation, a 13.55% tweet increase can generate a 29.45% network energy inflation at .70 (70%) bot “virality” within 9 months (peaked at 7th month).

Energy from critical mass due to bots can equal to 9.61×10^6 J, which can start to decay at .0015 seconds. Bots oscillated from <25 dB to 94.12 dB at 2090.91 Hz with 2 plateaus throughout the cycle. Bots maybe disbanded within .26 seconds at 50 J counter energy. On the other hand, a bot mass of 9.51×10^{-30} can equal to 1.58×10^{-13} J of kinetic energy per 2.14×10^{-18} J energy increment in the network or as much as .02 micro-Sievert/hour of ionizing radiation produced by a plain chest-x-ray.

A full-length Twitter data sonification is required to validate these findings while all logical and seed values have to be standardized. Model validation must be conducted in the future.

Keywords: COVID-19 infodemic; misinformation; Twitter bots; virality; critical mass; energy decay; entanglements; complex graph visualizations; spectral graph visualizations; node synchronization; wavefunction simulation; sonification

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

The phenomena of “**misinformation**” and “**virality**” are quantified by approximation of the aftermath of information cascades. The suggested value of misinformation in the study of communication is “information wastage” according to Flor (2007). Analysis of transmitted information via social media networks like Twitter has remained faithful to the standard model schematized by Shannon and Weaver in 1949 and to another model conceptualized by Moore and Shannon in 1956 (Sharma et al., 2020).

Thus, velocity of transmission is underscored wherein network statistics have been calculated based on established metrics for the following elements: (a) the pathways or edges using path length measured by the distances between nodes and its directionality; (b) node influence according to position and interrelationships among hubs or clusters using centrality measures; and (c) community detection using modularity or equivalent (similarity) index. Structural or topological intricacies are often highlighted when explaining the dynamics, but intricacies themselves neither always provide extraordinary revelation supporting early detection of misinformation nor opportunities for studying its footprint (after becoming viral) in order to valorize any consensus made about empirical “virality” as it is supposed to be a consequence of emergent dynamics. However, simulation of dynamics is run based on classical physics which will produce linear representations of mass diffusion and “entropy”.

The lens for investigating the phenomenon of “**misinformation**” and “**virality**” should condense over the mechanisms of (a) misinformation generation, (b) misinformation transmission, and (c) misinformation decay using a new framework since there is a dearth of explanations in spite of the available literature, which are replicated monotonously. The mode of deciphering entails a rethink of what has been laid down as fundamental, reiterating what is deemed essential in creating a network of misinformation, and repurposing the outstanding network theories by substantiating or complimenting them with modern physics theories. However, the latter can pose daunting challenges for acceptance among Communication Scholars.

All methods devised in this study and results obtained are not imposed as ultimate fillers of knowledge gaps rather they will serve as motivations for a future validation study (including the rethink of other plausible code implementations). This study offers a leeway to get more granular details lingering inside the “**Twitterverse**” especially about the behavior of its matrices from the temporal conglomeration of nodes, edges, and information shaping the network. It is understandable that assorting various network metrics can be expensive computationally and the demand for technical savviness has to be considered when facing reluctance in adopting innovative techniques. However, this study will prove that it is worthwhile to invest a profound curiosity even involving a higher level of computation to represent phenomena that are governed by enigmatic rules of the quantum world. Integrating different algorithms is challenging, but this has to be endeavored in the most judicious way.

Statement of the Problem

There was a massive misinformation spread since the onset of COVID-19 pandemic which made a huge impact on international health, economics, and politics. However, responding to misinformation related to healthcare and pandemics have been difficult since understudied (Sharma et al., 2020). Furthermore, the river of data is endless while making 'logical sense' (decoding) of it per bit of information is impractical on a small-scale computing.

For network anomaly detection, network visualization and analysis have to keep up mostly with unwieldiness of anomalies prospected due to infodemic nonstationarity and the sophistication of social media bots. The latter statement demands customization of techniques. Hence, infodemic management has to evolve far robust than current state of infodemic, but scalable.

Moving from information theory to informatics, from informatics to information technology, from information technology to data science, and from data science to network science will not herald "infodemiology" just the next science or advanced nomenclature out of such trail. It is proposed in this study to be the special field in communication. Explicitly, "infodemiology" ties together (a) **digital information**, (b) **bot accounts** (the analysis of artificial intelligence at play), (c) **human users**, and (d) **networks** as a system in chaos until (the quantum phenomenon of) "virality" emerges. The quantitative detection of misinformation and disinformation (infodemics) are rendered according to random fluctuations (in value, trend, threshold or level, phase, state) indicating anomalies, but underscoring the evolution of: complex entanglements; quantization of energy; and wave mechanics. Therefore, "**infodemiology**" should be offered as theoretical and experimental or applied science.

The “**COVID-19 infodemic**” thrived on information cascade. The enormous challenge faced against veracity of information is processing the big data. On the other hand, “virality” (massive misinformation spread) from dissemination of questionable COVID-19 information (misinformation) is network contagious by faster diffusability and will be unimaginable that any “anti-virus” like remedy is deployable neither for immediate containment nor threats eradication. It is “macro-lethal” (as to diversity and magnitude of network effects) where the “butterfly effect” (as to chaos theory) makes content expression worse. For example, the engendered skepticisms about vaccination have swept out pandemic control consensus to dwindle early.

COVID-19 vaccinations have been deliberately fluxed by distorted beliefs that were solicited on social media platforms and the rest were conspired politically and then raged on social media. Pandemic narratives constituting vaccination policies, (to be) imposed by healthcare agencies and governments, were discoursed back and forth with the increasing “anti-science” online. Other than the divisive propaganda was brute a force of influence, the growth of disinformation networks was amplified by weaponized bots.

Why study social media platforms? Twenty percent (i.e., one out of five) of adults rely on social media as a primary source of information as it constitutes a more rapidly disseminated (Godfrey, 2020) source of updates in the new economy than print news with 16% (Shearer, 2018). Moreover, the largest number (71%) of news consumers is on Twitter (Hughes & Wojcik, 2019); moreover, public data are accessible in the form of tweets. It was shown that dependence on online information has increased owing to the imposed social distance (Sharma et al., 2020) and home quarantine during the COVID-19 pandemic. Twitter is the most susceptible to

misinformation out of the mainstream media (Shahi et al., 2021). Asymmetry of Twitter user connection is an advantage (Kearney, 2019) in spreading (mis)information.

The major pitfall of most misinformation detectors is getting it done early. For example, algorithms require the fake news article to be in circulation during detection. The same is true in finding user responses and propagation patterns, which occur only after the spread. (Qian et al., 2018)

What is the main contribution of this study in the light of WHO's public health research agenda for infodemic management? The framework developed by WHO (2021c) is composed of five streams: (1) measurement and monitoring of the infodemics impact during health emergencies; (2) detection and understanding the spread and impact of infodemics; (3) response and deployment of interventions that protect against the infodemic and mitigate its harmful effects; (4) evaluation of infodemic interventions and strengthening resilience of individuals and communities to infodemics; and (5) promoting development, adaptation and application of tools for managing infodemics. This study falls in the second stream. Specifically, this study adds scientific knowledge on how misinformation (a) originates (theoretical formation), (b) evolves (pattern of immutable waves of energy from the lump of information), and (c) spreads in terms of amplification and organic spread factors (WHO, 2021c, p. 22).

Studying the Twitter network as "**Twitterverse**" is imperative first in order to challenge what is known in the literature about network topology and dynamics; and second, to reify any previous findings and conjectures upfront regarding the elusive complexity of Twitter. Much like a microcosm, the "Twitterverse" is a constellation of information, which expands every time new information is added and collapses due to spatiotemporality. Hence, the capacity of the "Twitterverse" to evolve is contingent to

information. From here, demystifying the phenomenon of “virality” after the spread of misinformation poses an understatement. Theorized elements (basically nodes and edges) at work do not always correlate in modeling the anticipated extraluminal (global) features of the network (e.g., characterization of node behaviors linked to trending hashtags). The “Twitterverse” has to be represented both as a network and as a system with reference to a perturbable high energy field (a dubitable, unstable dimension). Inside this field, uncertainty lurks as network entropy and field distortions increase. Much of the signals are engulfed by wavelet noise in the background of space and time. Mass (per bit of information) becomes energy in each node-to-node interaction and edge-to-edge counteraction. The detectable wave properties of misinformation may come out thereafter.

Research Questions

This study is dedicated to theorizing and modeling the COVID-19 infodemics on Twitter. To formulate analysis and conclusions, the study utilized the fundamental infodemiological queries listed below.

1. What type of tweets occurred with the topics “COVID vaccine is not safe,” “COVID19 vaccine,” and “Vaccine Rollout” from May 17, 2021 through November 26, 2021?
2. What are the types of automated Twitter accounts or Twitter bots?
3. How do network topology or pattern of connections and node synchronization differ in the bot layer, human layer, and tweet layer?

4. How does the Twitter network project energy from critical mass until the spread of COVID-19 infodemic by Schrödinger wave equations?
5. How can the network “virality” of Twitter bots be measured?
6. What is the sonification pattern of Twitter bots?

Objectives of the Study

Specifically, the objectives of this study include the following:

- To describe the type of tweets under the range of “COVID vaccine is not safe,” “COVID19 vaccine,” and “Vaccine Rollout” from May 17, 2021 through November 26, 2021;
- To classify the types of automated Twitter accounts or Twitter bots;
- To compare the pattern of connections and node synchronizations in the Twitter bot layer, human layer, and tweet layer;
- To estimate the projection of network energy from critical mass to spread of COVID-19 infodemic by Schrödinger wave equation;
- To measure the network “virality” of Twitter bots; and
- To produce the sonification pattern generated by majority of influential bots.

Scope and Limitations

This study is focused on characterization of misinformation spread via tweets labelled as “claim” using Hoaxy[®] online and bot malicious activities. Fake news typing was not performed. Twitter is not a closed system by its dynamic, permeable network boundaries. The trend of tweets may be influenced by other posts on social media platforms (Facebook, LinkedIn, Instagram, Snapchat, TikTok, Reddit, etc.). Therefore, the Twitter network became a mirror for COVID-19 infodemics worldwide with popular topics alike in other social media platforms due to cross-posting among users. The bot activities studied are specific activities by critical mass, energy decay, entanglements and node synchronization through multilayer and spectral graph visualizations, Kuramoto modeling, sonification, and wavefunction simulation. Other network activities (externalizing from Twitter) were not considered in this study.

Significance of the Study

This study will be significant to Communication Scholars (both generalist and specialist levels) for the opportunity to understand the two main causalities of an infodemic: first, misinformation spread and second, (nature of) bot activity from a cross-disciplinary inquiry regarding the quantumness of the processes that ties them leading to “virality” as expressed in mass and energy equivalence. This study is able to shed light on nonlinear network properties that make the analysis comprehensive. WHO’s public health research agenda for infodemic management is

supported by the development of a robust infodemic detection pipeline, which exposes vulnerabilities of bots to mitigation strategy by injection of counteracting bots into Twitter network according to conditions for bots' synchronization and life cycle. In addition, the techniques that were devised can be applied to climate change research, policy change analysis, computational neuroscience, cancer and genomic studies, etc. through network representations and the "bots" can be any agent, entity, or molecule of greater interest.

This study should pave the way for "infodemiology" becoming a specialization track under the Doctor of Communication (DComm) Program offered by the University of the Philippines Open University in response to future infodemics. The specialization is envisioned as "**Infodemiology for Global Communication Integrity**" involving two departments: the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies (FICS) for courses on Computer Science (covering artificial intelligence, machine learning, and quantum computing), Data Science, Network Science, and Knowledge Management; and the Faculty of Management and Development Studies (FMDS) for Global Health Surveillance and Disaster Risk Management through Informatics. Infodemiology will (a) strengthen data mining techniques for evidence, (b) promote the development of robust information systems against malicious bots and use of bots for infodemic mitigation, (c) provide insights transformable into action, and (d) provide up-to-date evidence for dissemination on social media platforms.

At the level of communication praxis, massive dissemination of scientific findings of this study can attract (a) the establishment of more social media "infodemic observatories" that will be publicly accessible, (b) a multiagency infodemic mitigation framework to be designed, and (c) research funding from global academic consortia to be led by UP Open University through a joint FICS and FMDS program on

“infodemiology” or UPOU identified as a WHO Collaborating Center to provide training and education of “Infodemiology Practitioners,” and also setting the compass for risk communication within the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) network.

Operational Definition of Terms

1. **COVID-19 infodemic** – refers to the total number of bots ($n = 562$), humans ($n = 824$), and tweets ($n = 1374$) aggregated in the core dataset (core_data.csv) based on the search topics “COVID vaccine is not safe,” “COVID19 vaccine,” and “Vaccine Rollout” that were retrieved from October 20, 2021 to November 27, 2021.
2. **Misinformation** – refers to false news, hoaxes, rumors, conspiracy theories, or satire (funny opinion) tweets that were labelled as “claim” by Hoaxy[®] or specifically, the “Number of False Tweets” in “Equation 1: Bot Mass (Kg) in the Network” determined by the number of edges ($n = 316$) in the bot layer since bots detected on Hoaxy[®] platform were associated with low-credibility tweets (i.e., all tweets from bots were considered false tweets).
3. **Twitter Bots** – refers to automated, precarious (and zombie-like in terms of littering information) Twitter accounts first detected on Hoaxy[®] and then classified using Botometer[®] at a bot score of $\geq .43$.

4. **Quantization** – refers to the calculation of the least amount of mass and (potential) energy to reproduce the phenomenon of misinformation spread and Twitter bot activity or “COVID-19 infodemic” on a quantum scale (i.e., anywhere near the oscillation range of 10^{-23} until 10^{-24}).
5. **Virality** – refers to the distortive power of Twitter bots over network information and communication (on the assumption of being weaponized by humans), which is mathematically contextualized in Equation 4, Virality of Bots in the Network.
6. **Critical Mass** – refers to the traction or pull of network elements over five dimensions (space, time, mass, energy, and wave, as depicted in Figure 22, Theorized intranodal and internodal spatiotemporal neo-dynamics) and mathematically translated using Equation 2, Quantization of Bot Energy (Joules) in the Network, which is projected from phase transition of Twitter bots (.0003 secs) until time to critical threshold (.0015 secs) over an energy of 9.61×10^6 Joules on a global network scale.
7. **Energy Decay** – refers to the energy damping phenomenon where energy (in eigenvalues or Joules) decreases (below zero) to a lower boundary potentiation in the network through bots’ modification of the energy landscape.
8. **Entanglements** – refers mainly to the (a) structural connectivity between bot, human, and tweet layers by complex graph visualizations, and alternatively, (b) the

signal convergence or wave-to-wave coherence (nonstructural interactions when nodes oscillate) between energy fields at the same energy level by spectrogram analysis.

9. **Complex Graph Visualizations** – refers to (a) undirected multilayer plots and (b) directed multiplex plots.

10. **Spectral Graph Visualizations** – refers to the results of the implemented heat mapping technique in stochastic graphs (a special type of multiplex graph) and matrix plots that indicate changes by color densities; or simply put, these are the spectrogram outputs.

11. **Synchronization** – refers to the level of spatial and/or functional configuration of nodes through “phase transition” (involves attraction to other nodes and nearby node activation) and which is measured by coupling strength using Kuramoto model simulation. This is assumed to co-occur with and to be vital in the (expression of) explosion of “critical mass” within the network.

12. **Wavefunction Simulation** – refers to the results of the (a) time-dependent Schrödinger equation or Technique 1: Finite Difference and (b) time-independent Schrödinger equation or Technique 2: Eigenstate Evolution.

13. **Sonification** – refers to the conversion of data into audio files and the application of parameter mapping as technique for making deeper sense of (the subliminal nature of) the most influential bots at the acoustic level by scoring their very erratic activities with musical tones according to crescendo, plateau, and decrescendo patterns.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Quantization of mass and energy (to their decomposition) in the analysis of complex networks (particularly for suspect anomalies during information transmission and exchange) are not explored with so much interest until recently, but these were addressed by observing inhomogeneous (regression of) densities and internal node state changes and not to detect bot behavior on social media networks such as Twitter. In this study, attention starts with the coupled encoding-decoding processes as generative, stochastic processes in the Twitter network and the spatiotemporality of oscillating interactions of nodes are supported both by formation of elaborate network connections, chaotic to random signaling, and scattering waves of energy as if it flourishes onto unbounded field. Nonetheless, complexity is topological and by exceptional regime of quantum mechanisms in the transmission and exchange of (mis)information. The ensemble of metaphors based on the phenomenon explained constitutes the “**Twitterverse**”.

Discourses on the articulation of technical limitations of contemporary approaches beckoned the need for alternatives that are plausible to reproduce and to vouch empirical and pseudo empirical data using an interdisciplinary framework (i.e., communication and new physics theories) that is fashioned using a shared lens to query the fast diffusion of misinformation (the rise of “virality”) and continual bot and human dynamics controlling the re-expressions (generation and amplification) of misinformation. Hence, there is always an intention throughout this study to provoke a “storm of thinking” among scholars and an offsetting of the classical norms in network

analysis that bend towards an irresistible curiosity in theorizing about quantum explanations.

This study opens up and navigates towards alternative, promising techniques by engaging in methodical and analytical investigations of “**misinformation**” and “**virality**” to gauge the “**COVID-19 infodemic**” found in many discourses using representations for the “quantization” of information to mass and then to energy as Vopson (2019) has attempted to prove in his experiments.

Translation of the equations proposed by Vopson (2019) into quantum states for network analysis is appealing for a number of fields: cross-disciplinary theorizing (communication and quantum mechanics); and speculation of the evidence of chaos by a distortive evolution (i.e., spatial disfiguration along time projection), which will make sense when put together from historical datasets visualized in multilayer graphs. Although the functional effect of node connectivity secondary to coupling and structural assemblage has caught the attention of network scientists (as key for novel discovery) in recent scientific literature reviewed during this study, the pure information-theoretical approaches cannot overcome the long-standing limitations in terms of tracking facts versus misinformation every Twitter data analysis and effort at capturing the obscured complexity of network dynamics are just as close to proving and disproving quantum processes as ever. Furthermore, “critical mass” is intriguingly nonspecific yet is an important factor to discern empirically.

To the knowledge of the Researcher, no literature has characterized the elements of misinformation and the sequela of cyclic network processes related to “virality” with both multi- and interdisciplinarity. Specifically, emulating quantum conditions in order to expose: (a) the formation of “critical mass” beginning from the rapid volume and spread of misinformation; (b) the spectrum of energy and wave fluctuations as markers of the dynamic network transmission of misinformation (by its
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reach and velocity), and (c) the synchronization of nodes and the entanglements at their edges allowing the co-occurrence of low-credibility tweet transmissions across multiple layers. The latter is special because it is featuring the role of oscillations and phase coupling which are needed to build and regulate nodes' behavior in hubs in terms of "gatekeeping". Gatekeeping as a valid online social network phenomenon was emphasized by Bonito (2016) in her landmark Twitter data mining of news feeds and major news sources affecting disaster risk communication during typhoon events in the Philippines.

On the other hand, offering a provisional quantum model in explaining the phenomenon of "virality" regarding low-credibility tweets and malicious bots on Twitter with the application of advanced data science techniques (e.g., data sonification for the exploration and analysis of the patterns of "COVID-19 infodemic") will be theoretically and technically exquisite for the modern scholars in the field of communication. Specifically, this is posing as a revolutionary approach in the field of network science towards infodemic management.

Demystifying the "Twitterverse" by characterization of its "quantumness" seems to be a purely hypothetical endeavor (Potters, 2015, p. 3). However, the intention is always knowledge discovery in the order of discourses of representation for the research problem and the supposed array of techniques. Both are "epistemological objects" (Potters & Leuridan, 2017, p. 3); inseparable for contemplation. The "State of the Art" multiplex network visualization reflects new frameworks and metrics (Complex Systems and Networks Lab, 2021) that justify quantization of information based on its complexity. Multiplex graphs reveal unique network properties, but spectral visualization can add a powerful leverage in the analysis of unique functions of entities and structures per layer. If complex

networks are explained with a quantum component, we can understand the complexity further. Furthermore, complex network visualization would mean "...to picture clusters of information as they move through the computer, [*imagining*] what they do [*and can*] look like (Kevin Flynn, *Tron Legacy* 2010 in Tüfekci, 2015)" and perhaps information moves on "ribbons of light" (Tüfekci, 2015) or even more spectacularly in another form—as waves and energies.

Mass and energy do not fit into network analysis to represent information transmission and exchange but these have to make sense for a powerful analysis about the "quantumness" of complex networks. Even so, these reconceptualizations will be counterintuitive to information theory scholars. In this study, the attention is placed on the coupled encoding-decoding processes. Conventionally, data is extracted from chunks of information and then interpreted. Critical mass and energy patterns have no place in the analysis of complex networks (e.g., between the information layer and node layer), which may prove to be substantial in the study of misinformation spread involving malicious bot activity.

Hence, this study ventured into the conceptualization of models and methods for explaining the viral misinformation spread using (a) multilayer and multiplex visualizations of the Twitter network consisting of aggregations of nodes and edges over misinformation while implying eccentricity (the emergent spatial and fundamental temporality) of the "Twitterverse," and (b) wavefunction simulations of the projected mass-to-energy of the misinformation transmitted. In addition, quantitative information about a node's (c) capacity to diffuse misinformation, (d) local and global network disruptions, and (e) analysis of misinformation surge pattern is endeavored. The latter embraces infodemics through networks within an information-theoretic inquiry. However, disclosure of the mechanisms behind misinformation spread by just vertices

and edges cannot be dynamic without incremental measurements (in space and time) of significant co-occurrences or simultaneous events by probabilities when “virality” (massive network diffusion) is reached from critical mass. Misinformation jumping into a viral scale across the “Twitterverse” is outside the plain information-theoretic scope.

The grand complexity of the “Twitterverse” on the discourse of representation is building up the capacity of nonproprietary information embedding, imbrication, and scaling. Deeper investigations of misinformation as part of the complexity of the “Twitterverse” required theories outside of communication. This is in consideration of the fact that the variables are (a) interdependent spatiotemporally and the (b) node states are emergent to information activation (also a limiting factor) and are not necessarily bounded at their edges to influence.

The phenomenon of “virality” could be framed using Shannon’s Information Theory, Second-order Cybernetics, Network Theory, Graph Theory, Actor-Network Theory, Spiral of Silence Theory, Critical Mass Theory, and Chaos Theory through Quantum Mechanics. The latter is postulated explicitly.

First, “**entanglement**” (a term existing in quantum mechanics is used here to describe the spectral level of interaction per state; in network science, this is used to describe the physical connection or intertwining) of vertices at their edges that form the tributary connections between network layers and exacerbate misinformation flow and control (including formation of feedback loops that are replaced by signal loops from a perspective of oscillating nodal dynamics).

Second, “**superpositioning**” (another term borrowed from quantum mechanics, but is used here to describe the momentary coupling) of vertices, which can explain the shifting convergence of hubs that feed the network with a particular misinformation, and reveals the autopoietic cycle and redundancy of misinformation. Net effects of misinformation are intercepted through

substantial reshaping of communities. The drastic topological evolution is related to “virality”. Rewiring of vertices succeeding the rapid synchronization produces disentanglements and fragmentation in the network. The aftermath engenders a “linear negative network density” by polarization (Maoz, 2011, p. 24).

Preserving complex details is a major weak point in the analysis of complex networks using classical and linear information-theoretic to explain misinformation spread and bot attacks that are historically chaotic and incessantly autopoietic (i.e., programmatically recursive and replicative). A revision in the representation of complexity such as redundancy of the information cycle under cybernetics is a disruptive move in network science for its established measures (e.g., centrality), but an attractive solution would be embedding the “Twitterverse” perspective in a quantum-oriented architecture (reemphasizing the function enabled through its geometry, in particular, due to transformation of symmetries as emphasized in the study by García-Pérez, Boguñá, and Serrano, 2018) in order to observe the extensive structuring of misinformation and then approximate the value of energy chains fueling the coupled propagation of misinformation and malicious agential activities (e.g., bots) involving a number of network properties through wavefunction simulation for the appreciation of critical mass.

Rather than rescind the ideas presented above due to the onslaught of meta-discourse in positing a quantum analytical model for complex networks in studying misinformation transmission through the quantization of its mass and energy, there should be more room for speculation ironically with an eye of optimism for a new theoretical physics in network science. This should entrench knowledge discovery. The challenges so far are the specification of quantum parameters for complex
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networks and development of a quantum model of misinformation. Merits of this study should pave the way for imbrication of available techniques with experimental approaches. It is anticipated that optimization of data analytics with machine learning should make the detection of misinformation sources and prediction of “viral events” or any infodemic more reliable.

Dependent Variables

A. COVID-19 Infodemic by Volume Spread and Frequency of Low-Credibility Tweets

The literature defines misinformation as false and misleading information either “...a result of misrepresentation or misunderstanding stemming from cognitive biases or lack of understanding or attention” (Sharma et al., 2019, p. 4) at varying degrees of falsehood and intents (Sharma et al., 2020). In contemporary literature, misinformation spreading occurs through an exchange process (Sharma et al., 2019).

A grotesque analogy for misinformation is “information pollution” related to three elements: (1) agent creating misinformation; (2) message communicated; and (3) interpreter of misinformation (Blankenship, 2020, p. 5), either human or bot, within social media networks. Propagation of (mis)information (e.g., tweets) is an “information cascade” (Yang & Leskovec, 2010 cited in Sharma et al., 2020, p. 4). Retweets are “replies of the source tweet over the time scale” (Sharma et al., 2020, p. 5). Based on the practice of communication, too much misinformation will bring “information wastage” (Flor, 2007).

The spread of COVID-19 pandemic misinformation raged like a “tsunami of information” (Kouzy et al., 2020, p. 6). News articles posted on Twitter typically lasted 2.5 days or 10 to 72 hours, but the continuous sharing prolongs their lifespan and mass exposure (Blankenship, 2020) most especially if sources are newsworthy individuals such as politicians (Donavan, 2020). In a very recent study, about 70% of misinformation on Twitter is contributed by celebrities (who were the “super-spreaders”) and organizations (Shahi et al., 2021, p. 12). Tweets containing **#covid19**, **#coronavirus**, and **#fakenews** were prolific (Shahi et al., 2021). Use of emojis supported the spread of fake news for which psycholinguistic analysis will be needed (Shahi et al., 2021).

Misinformation spreads passively because of (the nature of) the medium itself, i.e., how easily agents can take advantage of the “network media ecosystem” to share misinformation and to manipulate the media for “creation and distribution of intentionally false information [or disinformation] for political ends” (Donavan, 2020) by “media manipulation” (Harvard Kennedy School, 2021, pp. 4, 8, 22) and (distributed) “amplification” (pp. 12, 14, 15). Users patronize false information (created through manipulation campaigns) because it is outrageous while the truth is boring (Harvard Kennedy School, 2021). Information disseminated by WHO and the United Nations massively fell into misinformation. Based on the EPI-WIN campaign, an infodemic pattern emerges not because of the high volume of misinformation but rather because of the velocity of reach and relative speed (WHO, 2021d), e.g., evidence supports false tweets spread faster than partially false ones at the height of the COVID-19 pandemic based on retweet count per day propagated over a number of days (Shahi et al., 2021)

Another obvious element is how social media platforms dominate the controlling and (re)shaping of information. They have penetrated all nooks of society up to 73% (Turner, 2010). For the communication theorist Marshall McLuhan, “medium is the message” as he stated in his 1964 book, “Understanding Media: The Extensions of Man” (Wikipedia, 2021a; Massachusetts Institute of Technology, 2021, pp. 1-2, 5). In other words, the medium is the culprit. Media as “artifact of communication” (Donavan, 2020) is lifeless without a capable channel.

Maria Ressa (Filipino-American Journalist) articulated in an online discussion with Prince Harry (Duke of Sussex) and Renée DiResta on TIME100 Talks, that the spread of lies through social media is exponential: “A lie told, a million times becomes a fact.” This is spreading six times faster on Twitter and with a 70% chance to be retweeted (Langin, 2018) and because of this, information centers (news agencies) are pushed to the sides (Perrigo, 2020). In her 2021 Nobel Peace Prize lecture in Oslo, Norway, Ressa accentuated the forceful distortion of the information ecosystem (digital disinformation) on a scale likened to an “invisible atomic bomb” because of the accelerant power of social media technology (NobelPrize.org. 2022).

World Health Organization (WHO) has defined “**infodemic**” in several criteria such as (a) “overabundance of information – some accurate and some not – that occurs during an epidemic,” (b) “spreads between humans in a similar manner to an epidemic [*through*] digital and physical information systems,” (c) “propagated by the fundamentally interconnected ways that information is disseminated and consumed; through social media platforms, online and through other channels,” and (d) “exacerbated by the global scale of the [*COVID-19 pandemic*] emergency” (WHO, 2021c, p. 1).

The same agency has called for evidence-based “**infodemic management**” and framework development addressed to multi-stakeholders during the 1st Infodemiology virtual conference held from June 29 to July 21, 2020, and again in the side event of the 25th United Nations General Assembly on September 23, 2020 (WHO, 2021b). The 3rd Virtual Global Infodemic Management Conference held from October 20 until December 11, 2020 promoted mitigation of the harmful health misinformation among online and offline communities through global collaboration or collective actions, government and private sector partnership, strong social engagement, infodemic management training, lessons or experiences learned, journalism and tools for fact-checking, digital health strategies, resources or platforms for high quality information sharing, user-centric approach, media literacy, data transparency and equitable access, data science in quantifying infodemics to knowledge conversion, scientific communication, policy recommendations, future challenges and probable solutions (WHO, 20121b). These should culminate in “flattening the [*infodemic*] curve” (WHO, 2021b).

Infodemic management is listed as a priority in 2021 belonging to “**COVID-19 Response**” (along with “**Gender Equality**,” “**Climate & Biodiversity**,” “**Poverty & Inequality**,” “**Sustainable & Inclusive Recovery**,” “**Nuclear Disarmament & Non-Proliferation**,” “**Peace & Crisis Prevention**,” “**Human Rights**,” “**Digital Technologies**,” and “**21st Century Reset**”) made official by the Secretary-General of the United Nations, António Guterres (United Nations Web TV, 2021; WHO, 2021b). Early AI-supported Response with Social listening (as data mining) tool (EARS) developed by Citibeats (2020) was introduced to monitor trending topics across major social media platforms using natural language processing, but remains in the pilot testing phase (WHO, 2021b). The Epidemic Intelligence from Open Sources (EIOS)

Initiative by the World Health Organization and the Joint Research Centre of the European Commission is a lot more comprehensive.

Backed up by the Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Centre, the “Public Health Intelligence function” is the impressive information technology users of the EIOS web portal benefit from. Preparedness and response actions are achieved through a chain of (1) **monitoring, detection and verification**, (2) **risk assessment** (e.g., “INFORM Covid-19”), and (3) **risk communication** (European Commission, n. d.). EIOS tools provide visual and collaborative analysis (at multi-disciplinary level). Key to knowledge discovery is the integration of contextual information (e.g., demographics, disease profile, climate, exposure to vectors, mobilization patterns, healthcare system capacity, etc.). A very large dataset is involved, stretching the limits of cybernetics. A “complex combination of [*information*] filters” and automated classifiers must be developed (Spagnolo et al., 2020, p. 20). Sentiment analysis and anomaly detection algorithms are a few elements to be added (European Union, 2020). Taxonomies and ontologies for contextual (health) information have to be created (EU, 2020) and unified.

Epidemiology has shifted into a trans-disciplinary science grounded in risk communication called “infodemiology” (WHO, 2021a, p. 2) or “...the science of distribution and determinants of information in an electronic medium, specifically the Internet, or in a population, with the ultimate aim to inform public health and public policy (Eysenbach, 2009 cited in Mackey et al., 2022)”. Misinformation has taken a serious toll on public safety that the World Health Organization has created a page disproving all COVID-19 myths (WHO, 2020). Labels and warning messages recently became available for tweets that constitute misleading information, disputed claims, and unverified claims in order to underscore the “risks of harm” (Roth & Pickles, 2020),

but this classification could only be “somewhat effective” since the parameters (decision rules) for tagging (e.g., a severe misleading information) are not clear (Hutchinson, 2020). Lethality of misinformation to the public is the offline effect of false beliefs, e.g., fueling scapegoating and offering psychological comfort (Koyuncu, 2020).

In the case of anti-vaccination or “antivaxx” retweets on December 8, 2020 with hashtags “**DoNotComply**” and “**WeDoNotConsent**,” a snapshot of misinformation spreading from 0 to 18 minutes showed an abrupt increase reaching a plateau passing half time, after which it climbed back to a second plateau (Guynn & Bajak, 2020). This has unmasked a trend that can support prediction of events. Nonetheless, the more interesting insight to muster from data is the function of the quiescent periods. Misinformation circulation on social media increased public distrust towards COVID-19 vaccines. International anti-vaxxer activity has a lot to contribute in the decline of vaccination rates, which is “highly statistically and substantively significant,” i.e., a one-point increase on a five-point disinformation scale can cause a 2% annual average drop and a 12% drop across the decade (Reinberg, 2020).

Two types of COVID-19 vaccine disinformation were found online, namely: “**cause-and-effect**” anecdotal rumors after getting the shot; and “**big lie**” conspiracy theories regarding claimed major side effects and components that included infertility, genetic alteration (Thompson, 2021), vaccines contain “aborted human fetal tissue,” turning people into monkeys, and being tracked by a “microchip surveillance technology” (Crist, 2021). Actually, conspiracy theories were spreading in 11 themes (“**BioChina**,” “**AccChina**,” “**AccUS**,” “**Scientists**,” “**Media**,” “**Hoard**,” “**Tests**,” “**5GTech**,” “**NotReal**,” “**Gates**,” and “**WorldPop**”) and creating a “monological belief system” (Miller 2020, pp. 321-322). By demographic profile, men show a tendency to

believe conspiracy theories more than women based on a Canadian survey (Stecula et al., 2020).

COVID-19 vaccine misinformation affected the American poll results in the following way: 68% of respondents were hesitant due to long-term effects; 59% worry about serious side effects; 55% believe vaccines are unsafe; and 31% think they could be getting COVID-19 from the shot (Stecula et al., 2020). NewsGuard (2021) identified more than 411 misinformation sources, 21 top vaccine myths, and 22 top COVID-19 myths. Another study revealed 14% of users are bot accounts and 19% of misinformed users were traced to these bots. Network density is higher for misinformed groups than for informed groups about COVID-19 vaccination brought mostly by disinformation campaigns (Memon & Carley, 2020).

Globally, misinformation causes mistrust in governments, public health authorities and science (Briand, 2021), and minimizes the chance for prevention and adoption of control measures (Koyuncu, 2020). Trust level in the government was low (48%) in the UK, and much lower (42%) in the US (Vox Pop Labs, 2021). Furthermore, it may be conferred that with a 1% increase in the frequency of Twitter searches (e.g., low-credibility information) the user well-being is affected by 0.24% (Jaidka, 2022, p. 4).

Pitfalls in Misinformation Detection

Information collected in the Twitter network is valued differentially. Real-world events have their own reality matrix on social media. Veracity of information changes per instance of data transmission. Essential information is always fleeting and shrouded. So, information is expressed succinctly as a probability (Vopson, 2019) of being true or false. Each data query is linked to many events. In this study, misinformation is theoretically a byproduct of an information cascade. They were shaped by biases, misinterpretations, and malicious intentions from many sources.

On the other hand, a binary level probability cannot account for events with different outcomes at the same time. Uncertainties in the detection of misinformation cannot just be summed up. Misinformation may appear nontrivial whereas deceptive messages are not surprising. They may diffuse passively, infecting nodes in the Twitter network and changing their activities. The source of the contagion is arbitrary. Either humans or machines have equal probability of spreading misinformation. On the other hand, bots are more robust, competitive, and efficient propagators. They may penetrate subgroups making their visibility tricky with network modularity. Infected nodes could stay dormant.

Detection and mitigation of misinformation are limited to the method of classification (content-based, feedback-based, and intervention-based), and technical issues with detection (automation, low accuracy and generalizability) against complexity. With regards to structural complexity, misinformation is created and diversified at the entanglements (intersections). It is straightforward to label all possible misinformation feeds, but decoding every instance would be too repetitive and convoluted as a way to trace all variants.

According to Sharma et al. (2019, pp. 12-30), the scope of “complexity” includes: (a) having high interdependent and entangled interactions, (b) following an exhaustive process requiring intensive hand-crafted computations and time, (c) being syntactic in nature such as text length and semantic variations, (d) fact-checking or veracity is reckoned from the trade-off between crowd-sourced evidence versus actual harm, (e) scaling up the process, (f) large dataset or user responses in training artificial neural networks versus machine learning speed, (g) probability assumption versus prediction reliability between number of exposed users and the number of labelled pieces of information, (h) temporality of network topologies and information throughout the network by features or patterns versus representation or interpretability, (i) annotation of user response versus analysis of user behaviors, (j) collecting data and corrective measures occur when misinformation has propagated or before it ends, (k) process cannot automatically update when ‘states’ (conditions) have changed, and (l) assumption of information propagation versus moderation or control of the process externally.

The information-theoretic basis remains dominant and immutable as a framework in processing and detecting misinformation. However, this is more prone to crashing with big data. Non-sequential information and recurring fragments of information (meaningless syntaxes) are filtered during data pre-processing. Entropy is simply controlled by reducing noise in the data, but entropy is also a critical information that should be measured as is. Moreover, diffusion of information (a linear process) is captured in many impactful Twitter network analysis, e.g., disaster tweets by Huang and Xiao (2015) on geographical situational awareness, by Bonito (2016) on sources and gatekeepers of information, and by Ahmouda et al. (2019) on human mobility patterns in the post-hurricane setting.

On the other hand, Flor's (2007, pp. 48-54) framework on "information wastage" can be a state of a node where at some point it lacks coherence among other nodes. His theory can be modified as "information disequilibrium theory" (if the author accepts such idea) to contemporary network science for the purpose of finding what network information is deviant. Even so, this would still granularize over the course of linear information generation while the nonlinear network evolution (unpredictable divergence) will affect the transmission of information causing content distortion.

High information exchanges in the real world occur by number of links or connectedness of nodes and closeness to each other (Barroga-Jamias & Brien, 1996; Sadri et al., 2020). One key theorem has prevailed, which has methodically guided the investigation of social networks. In the decreasing (information) cascade model, a node is activated or influenced by neighboring nodes (at least $\frac{1}{2}$) in an arbitrary order until the network is saturated (Kempe et al., 2005; Goh, 2012), and the probability of spreading a contagious piece of misinformation or nodes configuring themselves as contagious wanes over time (i.e., from peaks to troughs).

Unfortunately, modeling "cascades" are elucidated using a linear, monolayer diffusion or spread of misinformation in the Twitter network is discoursed and explained using a linear transmission model between elements. Nonetheless, misinformation spread seems to be heterogeneous and irreducible to the disequilibrium of materiality. Chunks of misinformation transcend into many forms and are very random. The social media network is not selective and conservative to diffusion. Its hypothetical boundaries are indiscriminate to (mis)information flow. Detection of misinformation is simply the ratification of information organized into matrices. This involves several data mining techniques and network analyses.

On the other hand, global cascades are generalized from intercepted local patterns of interaction. Investigators have relied on Moore and Shannon's 1956 framework that takes its discourse of representation out of "network reliability" of the "communication path between a specified source node and specified target node" (Ren et al., 2016, p. 2) so that an information cascade proceeds. Obviously, measurements are replicated to deal with "...interaction [*by the*] network's structure rather than the form of the interactions" (Ren et al., p. 2).

Anomalous trends of tweets and retweets easily get the attention of researchers during data analysis. On the other hand, underlying events (subliminal) are hard to detect. Graph complexity details are either misrepresented or oversimplified during data storytelling. Fortunately, high-level (three-dimensional) visualization is stunning as a tool for exposing and measuring the intricacies of complex interactions, in particular, the entanglements and transitions via coupling among nodes and edges, e.g., if viewed in multilayers (Škrlj & Renoust, 2020; Škrlj et al., 2019; McGee et al., 2019), in which each layer shows its multiplexity by the different types of edges (Hansen et al., 2020). The entity that is the same across all layers of multiplex networks will be only nodes (Škrlj & Renoust, 2020), but these are shared across all time frames (Škrlj & Renoust, 2020). Although nodes can connect at different degrees of freedom, the multiplex graph analysis does not accept "superpositioning" to evidence higher level of synchronization.

Hoaxy[®] detects low credibility information based upon claims (online temporality) and fact-checking from dataset (dating back to 2016) and independent fact-checking organization (RAND.org, 2022) linking to bots with (supervised) machine learning rather than content feature (natural language processing) or fake news life cycle (Shu et al., 2017). State-of-the-art detection implements deep learning models

(Kaliyar et al., 2021; Dsouza & French, 2022; Mishra et al., 2022; Islam et al., 2020) or hybrid models (Nasir et al., 2021; Genfi, 2021), where increased robustness is plausible through unsupervised or generative models (Deepak, 2021) like adversarial machine learning (Cresci, 2021; Yang et al., 2019).

When detecting fake news, 'misinformation' in general would be false context (Mishra et al., 2022, p. 3). Fabricated or false information is deception and the most severe kind of fake news (Islam et al., 2020, p. 6). Long short-term memory (LSTM) and recurrent neural networks (RNN) are most effective for fake news and early rumor detection, but region-based convolutional neural networks (RCNN) can detect false information (Islam et al., 2020, p. 8). Bi-LSTM with self-attention was found to be the most accurate at 79.7% (Hajli et al., 2021).

In summary, pitfalls of content feature detection come from (1) **topic diversity**, (2) **multi-modality** and (3) **multi-linguality**, while with datasets these are early detection and the available labelled data for training purposes (Giachanou et al., 2022). Detection of machine-generated fake news, malicious actors that can perform automatic textual content looking, and code biases inside black box systems (artificial neural networks) that automate profiling of users as spreaders are issues as well (Giachanou et al., 2022).

B. COVID-19 Infodemic by Twitter Bot (Malicious) Activities: The Nature of Bots

About 9% to 15% of Twitter users are social bots that were built for “one- or many-sided communication” as intelligent “opinion machines” (generation-based output), autonomous acting (retrieval-based output) and possibly dangerous agents (Assenmacher et al., 2020). Many more social media bots operate on the Darknet (80%) or via unique protocol than on Clearnet (71%) or via public internet; however, Twitter is not largely infested (24.5%) based upon bot codes that target Twitter (Assenmacher et al., 2020). Out of 36% of the social bots about which information is publicly available, only 2% are intelligently functioning; 20% are amplifying contents by sharing and liking; and 14% are simulating social connections as fake followers (Assenmacher et al., 2020). Examples of Twitter bots’ malicious activities include (a) spreading fake news campaigns, (b) spamming, (c) user privacy violation, (d) sock-puppeting (Johansen, 2020) or tweets created under deceptive human accounts, and (e) Astroturfing or mostly political tweets “...as though it originates from and is supported by grassroots participant(s)” (Trewinnard, 2016).

Users were exposed to a lot of negative information through bots (Stella et al., 2018) about vaccines especially since 50% of circulated tweets are anti-vaccination beliefs (Tomeny et al., 2017). Such exposures may increase vaccine hesitancy (Muric et al., 2021) and delay vaccination (Broniatowski et al. 2018). Health communication including (anti)vaccination is weaponized through misinformation and disinformation (Broniatowski et al. 2018). However, online information exposure among Twitter users is affected and influenced by “hyperactive accounts” after a flood (massive diffusion) of information of questionable accuracy, and then online discussions and public opinions undergo distortions shown by topic trends and news feed rankings. Users’

exposure to misinformation and disinformation and engagement with “hyperactive accounts” constitute their vulnerabilities to manipulation. Detection is based on collective account behavior and diffusion of suspicious content (Luceri et al., 2021).

The menacing amplification of misinformation in various contexts is heightened by artificial intelligence with (1) **bots**—the malicious, automated and software-controlled accounts—and by natural intelligence with (2) **trolls**—the human-operated and often state-sponsored accounts (Luceri et al., 2021). Both are responsible for perpetuating the unnatural information cascades and nudging divergence among actors within social networks through “cliques” (factions or groups), global polarization, or unencumbered fragmentation (repulsive detachment). However, bots are more contagious (spreading information and linking nodes faster) and nebulous (indistinctive and variants do overlap). They are reproducible but behavior can be precarious.

As information repeaters, bots echo every bit of information and reshape the original bits to repurpose the feedback from misinformation. Hence, misinformation turns out digitally tolerant or friendly to many users and bots can blend well among humans. Bots evade detection by (1) deeply embedding throughout the network (Luceri et al., 2019) and (2) entangling with all other nodes (Luceri et al., 2021). Bots have been converted to “digital weapons” (Cardoso, et al., 2020 cited in Luceri, Cardoso, & Giordano, 2021). Manipulated information (disinformation) and misinformation topics span from finance to public health. The latter scope is exhibited in the “latest milestone of the misinformation age” through “COVID-19 infodemics,” but disinformation (mostly “low-credibility narratives”) has been profound in the political domain “published by a small set of hyperactive accounts” (Luceri et al., 2021).

Moreover, these accounts display suspicious behavior like automated and fake accounts (Luceri et al., 2021).

Twitter bots were “one of the main actors associated with manipulation campaigns [*through false narratives, fake accounts, low-credibility news sources, state-sponsored operators, conspiracy theories, hate and inflammatory messages that compromise the integrity of social media discussions and their dissemination*], especially in a political context” and Twitter, is a good example how social media platforms become a “persuasive tools that have been progressively weaponized to affect beliefs, spread manipulative narratives, and sow conflicts along divergent factions”. They are the renowned “tweet fabricators” broadcasting about one-third of tweets. They are “one of the most recognized threats to the integrity of social media”. (Luceri et al., 2021)

According to Maria Ressa in her Woodrow Wilson Award Lecture on the Alumni Day at Princeton University, “content moderation” was enacted by algorithms that run social media platforms (Princeton University, 2022) at the level of artificial intelligence and down to machine learning (University of Delaware, 2022). Propaganda bots were part of this.

Below are some of the important findings about human and bot (inter)activities from large Twitter datasets.

Pre-COVID-19 bots were notable on "...promoting product hashtags, retweeting political candidates, and spreading links to malicious content" (Shao et al., 2018 cited in Himelein-Wachowiak et al., 2021). Tweet rate and tweet interval both have a power-law distribution (i.e., broad or heavy-tailed) but tweet interval makes an exponential cutoff (Rezvanian & Meybodi, 2016, p. 625). A tweet typically lasts about 15 to 18 minutes (Symonds, 2021; Bray, 2012), but lifetime tweets make a type-II discrete Weibull distribution (Rezvanian & Meybodi, 2016, p. 625).

Twitter bot retweets comprised 82% of the top 50 and 62% of the top 1,000 in which 66% were bot-mediated, while 34% were solely carried out by bots giving rise to more than 100 types of misinformation surrounding health and economy, e.g., "**potential cures**," "**ending stay-at-home orders**," and "**reopening America**" in more than 200 million COVID-19 tweets collected and analyzed by Carnegie Mellon University researchers (Young, 2020).

In an infodemiological study, the specific queries related to COVID-19 vaccines myths and conspiracy beliefs were "**covid vaccine infertility**," "**does covid vaccine change dna**," "**covid vaccine microchip**," "**can I get covid from vaccine**," and "**covid vaccine 5G**". As per volume of online search on Google Trends, "**vaccine + fertility**" was the highest and next was "**vaccine + DNA**" (An et al., 2021).

The latter grabbed much attention with "conspiracy theories" and then paving the way to raging, irrational behavior (Young, 2020) among netizens, e.g., burning of 5G towers after linking them to Coronavirus spread (Parveen & Waterson, 2020). The

hashtag “**2019_ncov**” ranked the highest for misinformation while “**Corona**” had the most unverifiable content (Kouzy et al., 2020, p. 6). In addition, misinformation did not seem to differ from correct information in terms of quality of tweet as both drew on the number of likes or retweets, and this indicated that misinformation can spread and engage users as though it was the truth (Kouzy et al., 2020).

On the other hand, computer science researchers at the University of Southern California have analyzed 20.5 million tweets in English (out of 30.8 million) collected from 182 countries beginning March 1, 2020 until March 30, 2020 (University of Southern California, Melady Lab, 2020). Based on their work, misinformation can be categorized into the following types: (1) “**unreliable**” (questionable, rumor mongering, satirical); (2) “**conspiracy**” (conspiracy theories); (3) “**clickbait**” (exaggerated headlines); and (4) “**political/biased**” (propaganda). However, detection of misinformation is challenging to users even when assisted by machines as it can come in multiple types. There was a 5.58% surge of COVID-19 tweets with new user accounts from November 2019 to March 2020. The spread of misinformation was tied to healthcare and political tweets. (Sharma et al., 2020)

Recently, Twitter bots were shown to take up 20 percent of the network’s mass and the 80 percent are humans. This bot-to-human proportion was reported by recent studies (Luceri et al., 2021). They generate three times more tweets than humans and cause the flooding of high-volume tweets (Bessi & Ferrara, 2016 cited in Luceri et al., 2021). Bots mimic the human pattern (in temporal aspect) of information sharing by retweeting, which is 81 percent of the time versus 74 percent of the time by humans. Bots depend a lot on retweet action since this is simpler to automate, whereas the posting of original tweets is technically demanding at a higher level of natural language processing and cognition (Ferrara, 2019 cited in Luceri et al., 2021).

Furthermore, Twitter bots were responsible for more than 10% of content generated across social media platforms and 62% of worldwide web traffic (Powers & Kounalakis, 2017, p. 13). Malicious bots are popular to spread low-credibility information (Shao et al., 2018). About 93% are “**spambots**” including sophisticated bots tweeting malware and commercial content (Broniatowski et al. 2018) and antivaccination messages followed by “**trolls**” or human accounts with deceptive identities who promote discord (Broniatowski et al. 2018) such as “**anti-vaxxers**” (Muric et al., 2021) and political activists (Yousefinaghani et al., 2021). No wonder that one-fourth of COVID-19 health information was found to be false on Twitter (Swetland et al., 2021).

The activity of humans and bots is also positively correlated with the number of tweets, retweets, and replies shared online. Moreover, the volume of messages from bots is almost comparable to human-initiated messages. This suggests that more sophisticated bots (i.e., operating through advanced AI algorithms) have been involved together with less advanced spammer bots (Ferrara, 2019 cited in Luceri et al., 2021). Different bots (ordinary and new generation) have a diverse set of activities. Approximately 38 percent of “**hyperactive accounts**” that can be detected are bots (Luceri et al., 2021). These kinds of bots operate in a small and constant number with a steady rise in activity versus ordinary bots that peak late.

In Figure 1, human-generated content is shared more than bot-generated content through retweets from bots occurring more than once every three human retweets. Bots tend to retweet equally between the two sources of information, which poses a strategy to lure engagement with human accounts and to solicit (mis)information endorsement (Luceri et al., 2019 cited in Luceri et al., 2021). Replies are mostly from human accounts while a low percentage (12%) of replies was made

in response to bots (Bessi & Ferrara, 2016 cited in Luceri et al., 2021). On the other hand, bots can now reply to humans and to other bots opposing an earlier study finding (Luceri et al., 2019). Overall, humans are the primary targets of bots.

Although bots can initiate a conversational interaction with human users (Luceri et al., 2019 cited in Luceri et al., 2021), they are “not sufficiently sophisticated to convincingly involve humans in their discussion” (Luceri et al., 2021). The number of human replies (retweets) to a bot is lower than from bot to human. Another striking finding (not shown in Figure 1) was the capacity of advanced bots to synthesize a significant amount of original content (Luceri et al., 2021), which unlike their predecessors have always relied on retweets and interacts with humans moderately.

Two things are mimicked by bots: (1) the volume of human-generated content (narratives); and (2) the temporal patterns of publishing these contents online. Bots bolster the persuasive power of social media especially containing a political agenda. Discriminating between true and false contents falls short according to users' skill. However, the level of user awareness has been attributed to less bot interaction with humans on retweets. (Luceri et al., 2021)

Figure 1. Human and Twitter bot interactions in 2018 U.S. midterm elections.

SOURCE: Luceri et al., 2021.

The bots' capacity to shift and duplicate connections, and multiply is infallible. In Figure 2, partisan activities (the polarization role) of Twitter bots during the 2018 US midterm elections were described as either "conservative" or "liberal" (Luceri et al., 2019, p. 1011). Conservative bots retweeted 43% of the time while liberal bots retweeted 71% of the time and interfered within group interactions by 22% of their retweets. Humans tended to interact more with conservative bots (28%) than with liberal bots (16%). Labelling bots this way holds up in the establishment of clustering taxonomy, but their attributes were not yet parametrized.

Bots "attempt to induce interaction by retweeting other users at a significantly higher rate" than human users in a short period of time (Schuchard et al., 2019, p. 15; Ferrara et al., 2016) and "bot-like tweeters attract more bot-like retweeters than human-like tweeters" (Yang et al., 2020, p. 3). They "connect to each other to inflate

follower counts and to increase retweets” (Subrahmanian et al., 2016, p. 11). Hence, bots have significant high out-degree centrality and eigenvector centrality (Schuchard et al., 2019). Out-degree calculates “the number of people a user retweets from,” where a high out-degree means significant information broadcasting (Jiang et al., 2021). Bots will target the most connected human hubs containing influential nodes (at peripheral areas of the network) while humans will interact with the most connected bots, which is what the in-degree measures (Stella et al., 2018).

Figure 3 shows bot participation in three major political events. Figure 4 exhibits the capacity of bots to replicate human tweets. Specifically, Figure 5 gives out the tweet pattern between bots and humans according to trends. Bots act as relay centers for both fake news and factual information, but in a community, one is the “Fake news spreader” in Figure 6. Figure 7 and Figure 8 outline the semantic interconnection between topics: COVID-19, misinformation, COVID-19 evolution, and vaccination, which is helpful in the understanding of the hierarchical classification of subtopics.

Based on Brexit Twitter discussion, bots were “...amplifying the importance of Brexit as a topic during the general [UK 2019] election”. Bots retweet more than human users. They do this independent of other bots in their own community or “...on the periphery of one community, but focusing [*by embedding*] only on that single community with [*few users and*] a low number of retweets” on a degree-based distribution. They abet existing discussions rather than fabricate new ones and generate noise. (Bruno et al., 2022)

The strategy employed by bots is mainly to increase visibility and credibility of human users (who are original sources of misinformation) by retweeting their messages, but such activity is limited. Bot activity spikes alone do not increase the total number of tweets because each type of user either bot or human contributes “...a

nearly constant share of total messages, while the total volume of posts changes” (Bruno et al., 2022).

Bots cannot inject themselves entirely to the core of retweet networks unless there are many bots retweeting other bots. Bot-to-bot retweets is around 1% of the total retweets in the network. They end up positioned to the periphery of human users and will have the same network position over time. Bots can spread in multiple kinds of discussion by shifting attention to any topic across networks at varying proportions. They can bypass detection by hiding under noisier accounts. (Bruno et al., 2022)

Figure 2. Polarization from Twitter bot interactions in 2018 U.S. midterm elections.

SOURCE: Luceri et al., 2019.

Figure 3. Bot involvement in different political discussions.

SOURCE: Schuchard et al., 2019.

Figure 4. Human-like tweet activity of bots.

SOURCE: Stella et al., 2018.

Figure 5. Cycle of tweets between bots and humans.

SOURCE: Zhang et al., 2022.

Figure 6. Transmission of fake news versus reliable news.

SOURCE: Gallotti et al., 2020.

Figure 8. Topics associated to “The Evolution of COVID-19” including “Vaccination”.

SOURCE: World Economic Forum, 2022b.

Pitfalls in Twitter Bot Detection

Bot detection is very challenging. Every human activity pattern of information sharing is emulated well by these bots so that it looks seamless. Therefore, monitoring all user activities is ineffective in spite of longitudinal observation. For example, the bot engagement is made steady with a stationary trend at the start and then it gradually progresses to appear natural. Conversely, true human accounts do present dynamic trends (non-stationary or irregular patterns) which can be mistaken as being unnatural like bots. Such controlled or scheduled engagement is meant to be a cautious, strategic (e.g., launched to shape a forthcoming event through the spreading of political conspiracies as “actionable insights”) bot injection operation (either as programmed or bot-learned activities when creating original content, e.g., on the spur of massive political campaigns) in order to evade detection while they continue to infiltrate the network (Luceri et al., 2021). On the other hand, it can be thought that bots are learning from each human and bot engagement, and gain a collective capacity to embed deeply in the network.

C. Network Complexities

Complex networks can take the following theoretical characteristics: (1) frequently changing nearest neighbor or local rules (as consequence of triggered excitable states and state-to-state transitions) that result in huge variations in the generation and transmission of ordinary information (“butterfly effect” or “ripple effect”); (2) dramatic attraction and repulsion among agents when critical mass of (mis)information is reached; (3) complex patterning of links or edges by number of overlaps and revision of path lengths (entanglements versus path shortening equals increased transmission velocity and amplification); (4) local to global organization (compositional and topological) by coupled synchronization of node states and edges; and (5) energy cycle disequilibrium (increased periodicity of energy wave collapse).

1. *Structural Entropy and Evolution*

According to Schmitz (2018), “entropy” has its place in thermodynamics, information, statistics, disorder (chaos theory), and homogeneity (social network theory). Unfortunately, Shannon’s information theory does not account for space and time including the postulates in thermodynamics (Schmitz, 2018), e.g., expression of mass and energy from units of (mis)information (Vopson, 2019).

In this study, “entropy” pertains to the network disorder due to (a) the inflected chaos via mass of information at critical level and (b) the loss or derangement of topological homogeneity (i.e., the regularity of agents in cluster and scale of agent migration secondary to polarization). These can also be represented by geometric

asymmetries due to outliers (Soltanolkotabi & Candes, 2012) over space and time. In addition, oversimplification of network dimensionality to reduce complexity (e.g., principal component analysis or PCA in Soltanolkotabi & Candes, 2012) is also a pitfall, and displaces the two aforementioned vital network details. So, “entropy” can be approximated from the change of network size using high dimensionality analysis (e.g., 3D, 4D) based on the second tenet in Schmitz’s work (2018, p. 12), where “...entropy is proportional to the surface of the object [*geometry*]” under the graph theory.

2. *High-Dimensional Entanglements*

Entanglements are tangible measures. Renoust (2013) proposed the analysis of edge entanglements. Graph techniques were revisited and further studied by Škrlj and Renoust (2020). Entanglements occur in the following cases: first, “edge-layer co-occurrence” when at least two nodes were connected by at least one edge or “two layers overlap through edges” forming a layer interaction network; second, overlapping or redundancy of relationship between layers (layer entanglement specified by the “right eigenvector” or the maximum eigenvalue of the layer overlap frequency matrix), wherein edges have connected to nodes across layers enabling nodes to transition between layers (edge-coupled entanglement) (Škrlj & Renoust, 2020, pp. 4-6).

Intersections in the network graph are measured in degree of entanglements and add more details when detecting the main propagators of misinformation. Furthermore, detection of “chaotic entanglement” (Short & Morena, 2019, p. 6) is intriguingly a level up approach which looks at complex signals known as “cupolets”

(Short & Morena, p. 3). The energy to generate the entanglement between chaotic systems leaves a trail in the evolution of the network. The hallmark in the detection is finding peak energy when at critical mass and decay of energy going back to information granules. Furthermore, this could be thought as quantizable transitions within a protean (materialization) cycle of the “COVID-19 infodemic” on Twitter.

Another way of supposing entanglement initiation is the role of the “attractor” (Short & Morena, 2019, p. 4) that brings systems to mutually engage by reciprocating information exchanges with tweets and retweets (appearing like echoic noise within the Twitter network). This “attractor” concept makes nodes highly susceptible to misinformation cascades and bombardment by polarized systems. This is contrary, if one is to speculate, to the notion that either it is by chance that they are dragged into local communication, and are recruited immediately to infect other nodes or information pathways or the edges are more porous to directed misinformation. The “attractor” can be the misinformation itself or the node (bot or not).

Entanglement of network components within quantum mechanics is theorized with the equation $|\psi_i\rangle = \cos(\alpha_i)|0\rangle + e^{-i\theta_i}\sin(\alpha_i)|1\rangle$ that gives a probability (Biamonte et al., 2019, p. 3) while “von Neumann quantum entropy” is equivalent to Shannon’s entropy denoted by the eigenvalue (Biamonte et al., 2019, p. 5). The graph can be weighted using eigenvalues to reference energy (Gutman & Shao, 2011) and these can be the basis for clustering. The relationship of “clustering” to (energy) “coupling” is inversed (Noack, 2007, p. 457). On the other hand, increased “clustering” may suggest greater misinformation sharing like misleading news between 100 to 1000 nodes (Pierri et al., 2020b, p. 7).

3. *System Chaos and (In)Stability of Edges*

Taking it from Short and Morena's concept (2019, p. 9), nodes are sources of chaos, which are generated through interactions. This is translated in this study in terms of the shared (mass of) information and control of entropy for stabilizing connections (edges) independent of the current state of the system. It was thought that an emitted or outputted sequence of information (code) by a chaotic system towards another occurs, and is repeated to sustain interactions. In addition, "...both [*chaotic systems are*] receiving and transmitting control information via the exchange function" (Short & Morena, 2019, pp. 4-6). This control information is pinned in the communication model as the feedback mechanism under "cybernetics of systems". Thus, it is raising the relevance of second-order cybernetics in chaotic systems when answering how neighboring nodes are co-regulated through entanglements and how channeling misinformation through entanglements induces a scale-free pattern based on Broido and Clauset's definition (2019).

4. *Relational Emergence between Agents of (Mis)Information*

Misinformation generation and spread is grounded in emergence of cybernetic elements of the Twitter network and the chaotic remodeling of its information matrix. Higher scales of relationships between nodes emerge because there exists "higher effective information" (Klein & Hoel, 2020, p. 1) shared by nonrandomly connected rather than "maximally dense" or "fully connected, with self-loops" nodes (Klein & Hoel, 2020, pp. 2-3), and such relationship can flourish (i.e., carrying the vital

misinformation) even if broken into small groups. This phenomenon described as “causal emergence” (Klein & Hoel, 2020, p. 5) may be entertained as one of the many potent mechanisms allowing the viral misinformation spread according to topology or network structure like those seen with “macro nodes” (Klein & Hoel, 2020, pp. 3, 7).

Emergence is revealed by special patterns of interaction between nodes or agents at random order “which inform the behavior of the [*next generation of*] agents within the system and the behavior of the system itself” (Kaisler & Madey, 2009, p. 38). There exists a node-to-node reciprocity for connecting to each other. It is the “...iterative interactions of the system elements that count” (Ratter, 2013, p. 4). Hence, an agent-based orientation (micro-level) provides appreciation of the global (macro-level) emergent phenomenon instead of determining all actors in the system (Ratter, 2013, p. 5) since the behavior of the system (e.g., Twitter) cannot be predicted based on summation of its dynamics by nonlinear parts (Kaisler & Madey, 2009). The “Twitterverse” is a network of agents and information: agents knit (transform) information; and information entwines agents. Complexity is dealt with in terms of the encounter of state transition systems and dynamical systems (Kaisler & Madey, 2009, p. 66-68).

5. Node States

In the lecture of Sapolsky (2011), state transitions can be explored stepwise between starting state and ‘mature’ (final) state. The starting state has no predictive power of the mature state, i.e., without priori, blueprint, stereotypical patterns, or general rules (top-down control). Thus, emergence to new states (e.g., behavior) is

unpredictable. However, what is known in literature is that the more asymmetry is found at the starting state, then the more future states become profound with their dynamics, and this explains the variability of agents in view of evolution. Mature states are bifurcated: diverging either to extinction or to convergence with other agents' state (as nodes) in viable patterns or their species.

The above explanation is supported by the bifurcation theory in complex systems. Activity of nodes is coupled with (mis)information generation: underscoring the “dynamic transition between non-chaos [*starting state*] and chaos [*final state*]” (Huang et al., 2019, p. 2) in the nodes. The general picture suggests nodes will almost entirely coincide with every new chaotic state, but in a past study the individual node parameters remain unchanged after emergence of chaos (Zhang et al., 2006 cited in Huang et al., 2019, p. 2). The discourse here is also bifurcating. Either nodes can keep their cycle or become disconnected (lose the entanglement or disentangles). This cycle can still be under second-order cybernetics via mutually-stabilized feedback loops, but the chaotic processes that are asserted thereafter reveals more of a quantum phenomenon. The scope of complexity of the “Twitterverse” still relies on the “high degree of connectivity” and “criticality” triggers allowing it to undergo “phase transition” as a non-Markovian system (Rickles et al., 2007, p. 935), but due to temporal changes it will enter into a Markov state.

The non-Gaussian distribution and fluctuations of energy (i.e., similar to the oscillation of transistors) and Markov process in the nodes (because they transition between states) would characterize an energy-charged system assuring that the “Twitterverse” will work as such. In Figure 9, it is likely that there is at least one recurrent state and at least one recurrent class (Pishro-Nik, 2014). Nodes will have ‘chirality’ (convoluted degrees) due to multiplexity. The idea of “ephaptic coupling” from

neuroscience (i.e., communication without direct interaction) could be possible during “mass”-ive network dynamics since the network is highly energized.

The multiple states are vital in the dramatic course of misinformation. The notations: <1 ; 1 ; and >1 in this study are “eigenvalues” (Sayama, 2015, p. 77) and “eigenstates,” which are related to wavefunction collapse and the behavior of a chaotic system (Fiordilino, 2020, p. 11). Oscillations of a node deserve much attention. However, the oscillations of highly connected (especially the most influential) nodes are more crucial in order to think about the synchronicity of phases and energy frequency during misinformation spread, and if this is plausible to reckon, then this would mean that synchronization (e.g., node phase) is often overlooked in explaining the dynamics of mis- or disinformation hubs. Most especially, this is about decentralized information processing and cascade (virally spread). Articulations on complexity of nodes are underpinned by Kuramoto’s standard model (Pietras & Daffertshofer, 2019, p. 5).

Figure 9. Representation of the Markov process.

SOURCE: Pishro-Nik, 2014.

On the other hand, delving into system “microstates” or simply the state of interaction sites (Ren et al, 2016, p. 2) of nodes offers a breakthrough when predicting the cycle of activity since the nodes nearby will have opposite states with respect to the application of the Ising model in network dynamics, specifically, the calculation of “the system’s partition function” or “density of states.” The “joint density of states” is an exhaustive estimation of internal dynamics (Ren et al., 2016, p. 3). While microstates are neither overarching nor underplaying measures of “entropy” (i.e., the flipping order to disorder and vice versa) as information moves from source to receiver, they can give clues by indirectly suggesting the system’s dynamic condition and field it is exposed to.

The states can be quantized into energy levels (Ren et al., 2016, p. 2), where the number of energy states is proportional to the square of the number of states as

N^2 (Ren et al., 2016, p. 5) or is calculated from E_{ψ} (Polson, 2021c; 2021d). However, this was reported as being exceptional in the literature, $\sim 0.5 \times 10^6$ out of more than 10^{308} microstates using Markov chain Monte Carlo simulation on a 32 x 32 square lattice graph (Ren et al., 2016, p. 5). On the other hand, node state density can be quantized in a spectrum (Dong et al., 2019).

Examining the disarray of energy discharges could provide a footprint, and indirectly gauge the uncertainty estimate of critical mass. The predictability of a misinformation cascade is limited if purely based on Shannon's model. Whether or not microstates turn auto-labile to anisotropy (shifting synchronization), due to bots' interactivity with respect to the direction of the cascades and energy that goes along, is an additional issue to be settled throughout this study.

In epidemiological modeling, "...a 'contagion' spreads over the links of a complex network [*when at or above the percolation threshold*], altering the 'states' of the nodes as it spreads, either recoverably or otherwise" (Piraveenan et al., 2013, p. 1). The 'states' can be (1) binary, e.g., infected or not, (2) discrete, e.g., susceptible, infected, or recovered, or (3) continuous, e.g., as a proportion of infected nodes (Piraveenan et al., 2013, p. 1). In this study, the states are discrete by eigenvalues: >1 , 1 , and <1 . Influence of nodes is a function of "topological connectivity" (e.g., degree centrality) and current state (Piraveenan et al., 2013). Hence, infected nodes have very strong influence. For this purpose, measurement of centrality must not be static.

For the sake of succinctness regarding the three levels of complexity identified, first, node states seen through the lens of chaos theory were described in this study (from the interpretation of the scientific literature by Sayama, 2015, p. 84) in the following manner: if the calculated value is <1 the chaos in the network is shrinking, decreasing energy amplitude, or becoming stable; if equal to 1 , the chaos in the

network is plunging into a non-zero equilibrium or energy is conserved, there is fixed energy amplitude; and if >1 the chaos in the network is growing unstable or diverging to infinity with increasing energy amplitude.

On the second level, states when nodes become entangled (applying the work by Adesso et al., 2006) were described as follows: <1 or **Class 4** (separable into two states) wherein two counteracting nodes emerge; 1 or **Class 5** (fully separable states) wherein nodes become fully separable after entanglement and states which determine temporality of activity; and >1 for **Class 1** (fully entangled states), **Class 2** (two states entangled), and **Class 3** (only one state entangled) wherein nodes become fully inseparable tripartite entanglement or clique formation occurs.

Finally, states by node synchronized oscillations or band of frequencies (adopted from the works by Ullner et al., 2018; Lodi et al., 2021; and Teichmann, 2021). If <1 , nodes are chimeric or self-consistent partial synchrony where there is coexistence of coherent and incoherent dynamics, so nodes can either end non-phase-locked or 'partially phase-locked' (synonymous to a trickling "virality," which may be contextualized by the word "karma" or the sum of the nodes' activity in the current and past states determining their future states); if 1 , nodes are in a fully synchronous (phase-locked) state with a constant phase transition; and if >1 , nodes form a giant cluster, they undergo explosive synchronization, and are massively kept phase-locked which is the dramatization of "virality".

6. Node Synchronization

Regardless whether network complexity is natural or man-made, small-world networks self-organize to optimize communication (Latora & Marchiori, 2001 cited in Jarman et al., 2017) and oscillate to synchronize (Belykh et al., 2004; Hong, Choi, & Kim, 2002; & Wang & Chen, 2002 cited in Jarman et al., 2017).

Overall dynamics of the network is represented by phase synchronization of nodes (Pietras & Daffertshofer, 2019, p. 6). This means that there is a frequency match between coupled nodes. Coupling is strong if coupling strength $\kappa > 0$ (Pietras & Daffertshofer, 2019, p. 27) otherwise weak if $\kappa \ll 1$ (Pietras & Daffertshofer, 2019, p. 29). Node dynamics converge to a stable limit without coupling or perturbations. Weak oscillations reveal intrinsic dynamics (Pietras & Daffertshofer, 2019, p. 30). In this regard, “virality” emerges from local weak oscillations that have exceeded critical value. Phase synchronization influences the processing and transfer of information, but is perturbable, and the dynamics bifurcates (nodes evolve nonlinearly) if the critical level is reached (Pietras & Daffertshofer, 2019, p. 5). However, if the critical value is exceeded, the node state loses stability and inactivates (Pietras & Daffertshofer, 2019, p. 51). Disappearance of equilibrium is a sign of local bifurcation (Pietras & Daffertshofer, 2019, p. 16).

7. *Vulnerability to Critical Mass Formation*

The term “critical mass” originated from nuclear physics. It pertains to the amount of radioactive matter leading to fission. In the context of interactive media, “critical mass” occurs when there is 10% to 15% sustained collective action (i.e., achieved through engagement in a mutually reinforcing reciprocal behavior) among core members within a group or community. For example, in the case of subscription to Short Message Service (SMS) in the Philippines, market demands rose after 10% to 15% mobile phones users began reinforcing one another’s utilization of SMS through exchange of messages. The social phenomenon within this context takes into account the number of “early adopters” required to steer the rest of the population into a collective action. (Flor, 2005)

In social science, this “critical mass” is a scaling factor of change (Flor, 2015, p. 53) but will depend on an initial group of actors and must be big enough to accomplish this change (Oliver, 2013) through “collective action” (Oliver et al., 1985). However, “critical mass” just by volume of tweets and Twitter accounts cannot be generalized since events taking place under complex networks are relative to fast-shifting temporal dynamics. So, time to critical threshold over an energy flourish at scale (i.e., to be always determined) is a matter of preponderance for understanding its quantum basis.

Any information reaching “critical mass” perturbs the local flow of information and the affinity of nodes to each other in order to form clusters. The information influx and network (re)organization are at the expense of network-system energetics. The salient background processes are presumed to be holographic because energy waves

just pass and collide. The *priori* is the mass of (mis)information. However, critical mass formation will have to be theorized on how such mass gets consolidated so fast. Critical mass is distributed in different dimensions making centrality fluid. It can be skewed or pushed out of two or more dimensions (i.e., concentrations can be found *in situ*, but still everywhere).

8. Stochastic Information Exchanges

The exchange of information is a prerequisite for the spread of misinformation in the form of “bilateral communication,” where a Poisson process works in the agent to recognize another node (this also applies to Twitter bots) while a stochastic process drives the social network and the Markov chain represents evolution of node behaviors (e.g., beliefs, opinions) with misinformation (Acemoglu et al., 2010, p. 195).

Misinformation spreads because of a large “spectral gap” in connectivity (having many potential communication pathways), fast convergence or showing a “stationary distribution” by “large second eigenvalues” (Acemoglu et al., 2010, p. 218) versus a “uniform distribution” (Acemoglu et al., 2010, p. 204) of information resulting from the Markov chain, as “forceful agents” (very influential nodes) increase in number and are making a global impact, and “forceful bridges” or edges are made (which occurs when a single forceful link connects two disconnected components) by these agents so that they may become “information bottlenecks” (Acemoglu et al., 2010, pp. 196, 217).

It seems there is a rate limiting (stochastic) threshold value for the spread of (mis)information in relation to node convergence (Acemoglu et al., 2010, p. 202) that

can be explained using the perturbation theory (p. 203). The same theory is applicable when forging a greater “tension between information aggregation and misinformation spreading” (Acemoglu et al., 2010, p. 218).

In the case of scientific rumors (e.g., Higgs boson discovery at CERN), it was found to obey a power-law distribution (De Domenico et al., 2013, p. 4) as shown in a very large Twitter dataset (Leskovec, 2015) and in the network visualization (Rossi & Ahmed, 2015). The distribution of tweet timing shifts from Poisson to non-Poisson showing bursts of rapid events between a long inactivity (De Domenico et al., 2013, p. 4). Inter-tweet periods obey a log-normal law (rather a power-law) scaling or a random, multiplicative spreading due to the increased number of edges (De Domenico et al., 2013, p. 5). Retweets (the replies) have power-law scaling (De Domenico et al., 2013, p. 4). Unlike an epidemic spread (modeled as a contagion transmission), (mis)information does not undergo an incubation period since it is volatile (De Domenico et al., 2013, p. 5). Active nodes will have “a monotonic increasing function of time” (De Domenico et al., 2013, p. 5). Nonetheless, the likelihood of node activation increases if connected to more than 1 active node, specifically through a vertex (node) that has out-going degree to another vertex with in-going degree (De Domenico et al., 2013, p. 7).

9. *Information Tunneling*

It can be assumed that entanglements make diffusion of misinformation much faster since it can transfer to or infect neighboring nodes and then be picked-up (con)sequentially especially Twitter bots mediate communications. Spatial pseudo

“tunneling” of information flow is conceivable as a function of node entanglement at the edges. On the analytical side, meticulous visual inspection would mean scanning the constitutive layers of the network and information subways (transverse tributaries) where information can tunnel much faster.

10. Energy-to-Wave Fluxes and Decay

Information pre-exists in the network. In order to appreciate the fluxes and decay of misinformation as energy and waves through space and time, space-time projection is represented through the wavefunction dynamics. First, time corresponding to the “repetitive cycles of [*travelling*] waves” (Yee, 2022, p. 21) is basic in the analysis of evolution of energy out of (mis)information. Time passes at different rates through spaces. Transverse waves will probably give a hint about the shifting mass and energy of misinformation in finding the largest gradient that it would probably gravitate towards (collectively centralized). Swinging of eigenvalues may signify energy gains and loss in consonance with a wavefunction collapse. Investigating the wavefunction becomes worthwhile by its predictability through time evolution (Fiordilino, 2020, p. 2).

Eigenvalues provide “...the asymptotic ratio of magnitudes of the state vectors between two consecutive time points,” where: >1 suggests growing unstable or divergence to infinity with an increasing (mass-energy) amplitude; <1 suggests shrinking or decreasing amplitude and becoming stable; and 1 suggests a non-zero equilibrium point at which eigenstates are conserved or energy is conserved; thus, there is a sustained amplitude (Sayama, 2015, pp. 77, 79, 84).

Spectral density is the density of eigenvalues of the adjacency matrix, which is directly related to topology (Farkas et al., 2002, p. 30). The spectral density distribution of a scale-free graph is symmetric and converges to a triangle shape at the central part while a random graph (uncorrelated) shows a semi-circle (Farkas et al., 2002, p. 31). In terms of energy decay, it is exponential when the number of target nodes decreases (Klickstein et al., 2017, p. 2).

Independent Variables

A. “Virality” of COVID-19 Tweets

Virality usually always affirms the spread of misinformation within a network like Twitter can be inquired about by looking at the constitution of critical mass, where potential energy is assumed to be at its maximum to perturb the dynamics of such complex system: first, through distortions of communication with the likelihood of forging more latent harm (referred to as “offline” effects according to Hutchinson, 2020) to users of health information (e.g., accelerating the spread of disease exponentially and causing death, namely as the consequence of self-medication with chloroquine phosphate as prophylaxis for COVID-19 that were cited by Vigdor, 2020; and second, through fabrication of anomalous and prolifically emergent patterns of communication, and drawing more mass of misinformation, thus greater chaotic energies.

Uncertainty of a news initially lags as insidious seeding of misinformation fragments or chunks throughout digital communities (in varying states of vulnerability) until they are reconstituted and form a critical mass. Hence, the misinformation

engenders setbacks as aggregated fear or panic (Godfrey, 2020) and misconception. On a brighter side, it was found that bots (in the form of chatbots intervening for COVID-19 vaccination) can significantly increase COVID-19 vaccination: “37% increase in participants holding positive attitudes, and a 20% decrease in participants saying they would not get vaccinated” on an average of 16.38 minutes of human interaction or at least anywhere between 5 and 12 minutes, but the more time users interact, “the more they changed their minds” (Altay et al., 2021).

Beyond the network borders lies the real-world process of translating the explosion of misinformation into a disordered reckoning of misinformation and dissent, which gets back into Twitter through the user’s heavy tweets. Modelling of these outcomes (from the communicational side) in recent literature (using big epidemiological data) reveals a scale-free network: transmission is degree-based (e.g., hubs with hundreds of links) under a power-law scale versus an exponential trajectory (Singer, 2020; Manchein et al., 2020; De Domenico et al., 2013). Lingering misinformation imposes havoc disproportionately, and steers the information-based dynamics into a “nonlinear pattern,” which is the hallmark of chaos (Sayama, 2015, p. 131).

There are no concrete mechanisms articulated in the literature about how misinformation builds (or can generate) inside the “Twitterverse” although it is always teeming with massive information. Therefore, theoretically it is sound to declare that true information and false information do not differ significantly (technically both can be viral), but network theory can draw the line of dissimilarities in terms of the creation of information pathways and composition of clusters. The “virality” jargon refers to the invasiveness of (mis)information brought to critical mass by (hyperactive) nodes within a short period of time. It emerges at the peaks of energy in the network above local

threshold (as galaxies would, according to Bardeen et al., 1986, cited in Kerscher, 2000, p. 5). Plateaus on the course to “virality” may suggest an “interrupted point process” (a concept from Stoyan et al., 1995 cited in Kerscher, 2000, p. 5). Furthermore, it may be close to a rectilinear energy wave pattern.

Another explanation is that “self-organized criticality” based on the “intrinsic properties of the system, as opposed to the particularities of a meme [*or fake news*], are driving virality”. So, it “...is the pattern of connections” that will “...promote the spread being fast (with super spreaders or if nodes are highly connected) and others will inhibit the spread”, clustering, and frequency of sharing (e.g., retweets) becoming a “social reinforcement”. However, network representation shows “connections [*that*] are randomly distributed among nodes on the network” (Mukerjee, 2017).

Former discourse about fake news virality was based on “information overload”. Moreover, “...bots can effectively suppress the entire ecosystem's information quality by infiltrating only a small fraction of the network” and they “...can also accelerate the formation of echo chambers by suggesting other inauthentic accounts to be followed,” known as “follow trains” (Menczer & Hills, 2020).

B. “Virality” of Twitter Bots

The discourse here is “virality” goes out of usual (i.e., controlled) dynamics. The expanse of “virality” is tied bot and human activities over tweets.

Another major culprit in the real world is due to the fact that “...the spread of disinformation can thus be attributed to human action” (Buchanan, 2020) and “...that people often share misinformation because their attention is focused on factors other

than accuracy” (Pennycook et al., 2021). The “...users mostly tend to select and share content related to a specific narrative and to ignore the rest” whereas “...social homogeneity is the primary driver of content diffusion, and one frequent result is the formation of homogeneous, polarized clusters”—**echo chambers** (Del Vicario et al., 2016). In addition, “...users who shared both questionable and conspiracy-related content were clustered more closely in the network than others, supporting the hypothesis that echo chambers can contribute to the spread of health misinfodemics” (Chen et al., 2022).

At least two factors have been established: (1) velocity of reach and (2) relative speed (WHO, 2021d). Additional possible mechanisms considered in this study about the nature of bots were (3) the Twitter bots’ artificial intelligence capacity to create content; (4) ‘resilience of bots’ (capacity to evade network detection—bot scores not definitive and are tweet topic adaptive); and (5) bots’ usage of energy in network to diffuse faster globally.

Description of Available Techniques for Network Investigation

A. Multilayer Graphs

In multilayer visualization, the relationship across layers is the “interdependence of interaction” occurring on the following levels: (1) microscopic level, where “links between the same pairs of nodes co-occur in two different layers;” and (2) mesoscopic level, where the “group to which each node belongs is similar across layers”. Edge visualization is an important challenge in multilayer graphs so “edge bundling” techniques were presented in the literature. However, clustering by edge density is worth exploring (McGee et al., 2019., pp. 136, 138).

B. Multiplex Graphs

Multiplex visualization should engender robustness in the graphical analysis. Dynamics is subsumed by notable changes in vertices, edges, and flow of misinformation. The representation of complexity as “multiplexities” should help with the theoretical arguments about the branching disruptions from COVID-19 misinformation, the future of network analysis, and “infodemiology”. Fruchterman-Reingold layout algorithm in Gephi works well to see the grouping per layer of the multiplex graph (Garcia et al., 2015, p. 7).

C. Important Network Analysis

Generally, use of “quantum statistics” (Wang et al., 2019) would be ideal, but has not yet been standardized.

Figure 10. Influential node detection using basic network measures.

SOURCE: Farahani et al., 2019, pp.10-11.

Shortest path lengths produce “six degrees of separation” in small-world networks (Himmelboim et al., 2017, p. 2) based on human-patterned social connections “...through a short sequence of acquaintances” (Kleinberg, 2001 cited in Hexmoor, 2014). Cliques or clusters interconnect via five to six nodes (Telesford et al., 2011; Goldbeck, 2013). High density local clusters are formed by these interconnecting nodes from large and sparse networks (Himmelboim et al., 2017). Hence, efficient network diffusion rests on the number of intermediaries so that even with a minimum of two nodes (Ch’ng, 2015) information could spread rapidly. On the other hand, closeness centrality is significant to the spreading capacity (tweeting) of nodes (Sadri et al., 2020, p. 8).

Small-world networks are real-world networks (Ch’ng, 2015), but not absolutely ubiquitous by their network properties at the level of classical information processing (Telesford et al., 2011) and fundamental organization, where distance (L) or steps between two randomly selected nodes are increased proportional to the logarithm of the number (N) of nodes or $L \propto \log N$ (Wikipedia, 2022a; Austin, 2012). This is because they are complex networks moving between order and disorder (Schneider & Kay, 1995; Mitchell, 2009 cited in Ch’ng, 2015) and between random networks with short path lengths (Telesford et al., 2011) and regular lattice networks or non-random networks with high clustering and rewiring probability (Telesford et al., 2011) via four degrees of connection, i.e., “each node is linked to all of its four nearest neighbors” (Graham, 2013).

Network diffusion (e.g., information transfer) dictates the network’s evolution thus materializing complex network structures by way of adaptive rewiring. Generally, this occurs by “randomly rewiring a certain proportion of edges of an initially regular network” so that “the network largely maintains the regular clustering”. The vertices or

edges to use are mobilized under a progressive topological adaptation (measured in degree as $1-p$). Explicitly, the goal is about “creating short-cuts where network diffusion is intensive while annihilating underused connections”. In effect, the network shifts from decentralization (i.e., towards high modularity or subgrouping and low centrality nodes distribution) to centralization (i.e., towards low modularity or regional conglomeration and high centrality nodes distribution) of information flow. Modularity and centrality do not coincide, but can come close at a small probability ($p=.52$). The rate of network diffusion regulates (like a feedback loop for) global adaptation (Jarman et al., 2017).

Connectivity is measured commonly by degree centrality. High levels of assortativity suggest redundancy, but also low clustering (Muller & Peres, 2019). High degrees (≥ 70) correspond to a truncated log-normal distribution of vertices that emerged in the network. A small number of vertices (nodes) in a hub are connected to many peripheral vertices. In addition, emergent structures in the network do not form central vertices but instead are more distributed. It is like saying their centrality turns off so vertices can form anywhere especially at the periphery of the network. (Jarman et al., 2017)

PageRank, degree, assortativity (similarity), and coreness (basically k -core) are the critical measures in small-world network analysis especially for those as dynamic as human neural networks and social media networks. Among them, PageRank is more informative. PageRank centrality is a version of eigenvector centrality, but the algorithm implements a Markov process from a stationary distribution in order to instantiate equal probability distribution of events as time progresses. PageRank reflects the global communication patterns through longer path lengths and convergence and divergence patterns, which could not be shown by

closeness centrality and betweenness centrality. It has been found that with at least one vertex or node, the probability (p) of traversal communication (interlayer) is increased by a deviation from the mean of the PageRank vector ($1/n$) (Jarman et al., 2017).

In a related study, the likelihood of transitioning to an adjacent vertex was estimated at .85 (Rubinov & Sporns, 2010 cited in Jarman et al., 2017), but with normalization, it is .15 by a random chance (Jarman et al., 2017). PageRank also leads to a presumption of node teleportation represented with a transition matrix, for which β is a damping factor set at .85 and the probability is calculated as $(1-\beta)/n$ (Amine, 2020).

Coreness (e.g., maximized coreness statistic c) value near 1 stipulates non-overlapping nodes into core and peripheral while values close to zero construe a partitioning that is defined poorly or relative (Jarman et al., 2017) since information transfers in the network are highly entangled among nodes. On the other hand, analysis of node interactions and centrality within its network has been done with k -core decomposition (Luceri et al., 2021). This centrality is assumed by the degree of node “embeddedness” in a subgraph of the network or k -core. The k -core decomposition exposes “...the set of nodes deeply embedded in a graph by recursively pruning nodes with degrees less than k ” (Luceri et al., 2021). The higher the k -core, the more the node is embedded.

Luceri et al. (2021) found that the hyperactive bots (the advanced human-like bots) increase with k undergoing k -core decomposition, but ordinary accounts (either less advanced bots or human accounts) work the other way. These hyperactive bot accounts take a high central position within the retweet network while the centrality

of their human counterparts is related to bot accounts. Ordinary bots are deeply embedded within the retweet network based on the number of connections or edges. It was proven that when k increases, the percentage of human accounts plunges, but the bot population remains steadfast. The centrality of hyperactive bots indicates the capacity to infiltrate online discussions aggressively and to beckon users' trust by fabricating a pseudo-credible activity as humans in a short time.

It has been found recently that as randomness in network structure increases, the capacity of complex contagions to spread globally (in reference to k -core distribution) falls off sharply due to the disruption of a vital fraction of "reinforcing ties" or "wide bridges," and it is also possible that nodes with low degree centrality and low betweenness centrality are most influential by initiating the spread of contagions from neighboring nodes, thereby becoming adopters (Guilbeault & Centola, 2021). Based on inference, amplification of contagions is not from primary spreaders, but by their followers. So, followers will falsely acquire a high degree centrality and high betweenness centrality. Degree versus entanglement can be brought into this picture.

Average shortest path length (also known as average node-to-node distance) and clustering coefficient are topologically-independent measures that have been established for the study of small-world networks (Karyotis & Khouzani, 2016). Path length alludes to "distributed processing" of information among nodes while clustering coefficient mirrors the "regional specialization" (Telesford et al., 2011). Unfortunately, average shortest path length is not very useful if contagion spreading is complex since network connectedness and node centrality create misleading information (Guilbeault & Centola, 2021). Classical metrics can be optimized, for example to "complex path length" and "complex centrality" calculations, but the scalability of such kind of implementation still needs reckoning (Guilbeault & Centola, 2021).

Degree centrality, betweenness centrality, and percolation are all topologically-oriented network measures and are accessible too. With percolation, input values (before percolation) and output values (after percolation) all constitute structural information (Ghavasieh et al., 2020, p. 7).

Node clustering based on density in the network is measured by the number of links of a core node in its neighborhood (following the rule of *k-nearest neighbor*). Outside the core node's reach are "noise nodes" (Chen, 2020, pp. 115-116). The number of unknown sources (e.g., misinformation) can be determined using node selection and clustering techniques (Chen, 2020, p. 120). The impression that nodes behave the same way whenever structurally entangled is answered by measuring "transitivity" by a clustering coefficient. Richters and Peixoto (2011) found transitivity analysis (in the context of trust propagation) with the community-centered approach insightful.

Percolation centrality can account the state changes of individual nodes before and after the "virality". Percolation can answer "how and why a networked system loses its functionality" (Ghavasieh et al., 2020, p. 3). Here a network (G) and its nodes (N) can be laid out in an adjacency matrix A , where: $A_{ij} = 1$ if *node i* and *node j* are connected or else equals 0 if not connected. Statistical (e.g., correlations) and geometrical (e.g., size of largest connected elements, size distribution of disconnected clusters) analyses are based on the effect of random or sequential (i.e., in order to find the most influential) node removal from original network to functionality (Ghavasieh et al., 2020, pp. 3, 6). Theoretically, network activity persists when the remaining nodes reassemble to stay intact.

Moreover, percolation techniques have been used in bioinformatics to study mutation and duplication rates (Kim et al., 2002 cited in Ghavasieh et al., 2020, p. 7).

In the same perspective, the variance of misinformation linked to influential and influenced nodes is due to a 'mutation' as a network anomaly, and can be posited as being either related to induced topological alterations or sequelae of enhanced dynamics (e.g., entropy, energy).

If network activity is chaotic, perturbation of a node state leads to another chaotic cycle. On the other hand, if the network is robust owing to its heterogeneity, the effect of perturbation resolves by spatial adaptation. Dynamics transition from chaotic to robust is a function of (1) connectivity or topological architecture (e.g., at $k = 20$ or a moderate connectivity results to 5% robustness, R) and (2) probability (p) of node activation after an interaction in the basic equation: $2p(1-p)k = 1$ either with Poissonian or Gaussian distribution. Chaos is imminent when $2p(1-p)k > 1$ while the network stabilizes at value of ≤ 1 for an arbitrary scale-free exponent ($\gamma > 2.5$ at any value of p) (Aldana & Cluzel, 2003).

Pitfalls in Conventional Network Analysis

Clustering with modularity is dependent on the number of internal links, l_s (at least $2l_R^{\min}$ or equal to the order square root of the total number of links in the network, $\sqrt{2L}$) per module or cluster inclusive of cliques and its interconnections to other modules, which implies that at maximum modularity optimization or the resolution limit, community detection may be a combination of smaller communities (Fortunato & Barthelemy, 2007). This only ascertains that modularity is ineffective with overlapping communities (Mascolo, 2011, p. 15) that are churning (mis)information

covertly back and forth. While the alternative is a clique percolation method, retweets between groups, which account for weak ties and also carry (mis)information (Mascolo, 2011, p. 29), may not be dismembered into subgroups, and are consequently discounted.

Moreover, community detection becomes impractical since the number of partitions overruns the network size quickly and exponentially (Samay et al., 2014). On the other hand, centrality measures could be useful to pick up on the load or flow of (mis)information each node accepts, but the heterogenous structure of complex networks would pose arbitrary determination of values (either resulting in over- or underestimation) due to the following: (a) uncertainty of 'localization' or position of nodes (e.g., nodes may belong in the same k -core number); (b) dynamic changes in distances between nodes (e.g., shortest path length changes with the logarithm of the number of nodes) may reflect a false level of closeness centrality even though nodes have different roles in (mis)information propagation; (c) cumbersome computations for large networks (e.g., betweenness centrality); (d) importance of the node (with the viral misinformation) by weights of the eigenvector may centralize in a small number of nodes, or comes close to zero, thus making them invisible in large networks while Hashimoto non-backtracking (i.e., going back to a previously visited node after at least two occasions) matrix B offers a solution for the problem of node localization, e.g., undirected networks. In this method each undirected link is replaced with a pair of directed links, and then spectral clustering is performed for community detection based on centrality of a node (in eigenvalue) by the sum of its contributions for all neighboring nodes following Ihara-Bass theorem.

However, limitations arise when eigenvalues cannot be differentiated, as is the case when "homophily" (i.e., nodes are more connected in the same community than

between communities) is vague and no algorithm can work better (at this detectability threshold) than labelling nodes by chance including subgraphs, which cannot be backtracked since they have tree-like connections and they are discarded along with the information about the network structure. Moreover, while the algorithm can be manipulated like the flow matrix (Newman, 2013 cited in Rodrigues, 2019), the process takes a lot of computations; and (e) determination of connected nodes on the assumption of uniform probability versus their individual importance (e.g., PageRank), in which each node represents a periodic or recurrent state or event in a Markov chain (a stochastic process), its discovery being dependent on the number of steps or transitions (i.e., such probability is expressed by the exponential of the Shannon entropy equation), and accessibility of the nodes following random walks or visits in the network, but which should be the shortest in order to receive more weight (Rodrigues, 2019, pp. 179-188).

On the other hand, centrality measures are still very helpful, particularly in studying the influence of central nodes on the evolution of dynamical processes in the network (Rodrigues, 2019, p. 188). The susceptible-infected-recovered or SIR model is widely applied to explain the phenomenon of misinformation transmission through state-to-state transition of nodes according to contagion theory. Under stochastic processes, each infected node transmits the “contagion” (misinformation) to all nodes nearby, and then recovers (reverts to its susceptible state) with a fixed probability. Although the model has upgraded with new variables and pathways (e.g., the susceptible-exposed-infected-skeptical or SEIZ model), it is limited to the adoption of misinformation (Jin et al., 2014) and detection of misinformation is derived here (e.g., exposed ratio or RSI, where: >1 = news stories; <1 = rumors in Mathur & Gupta, 2017, p. 583) even when two different groups are involved (Isea & Lonngren, 2017).

The critical threshold of spreading depends on network structure or organization (Isea & Lonngren, 2017). However, centrality of nodes (influence) plays a significant role in contagion propagation, e.g., as proposed by de Arruda et al. (2014 cited in Rodrigues, 2019), by random walks accessibility measured in spatial networks, and Kitsak et al. (2010 cited in Rodrigues, 2019) by *k*-core and eigenvector centrality in scale-free networks (Isea & Lonngren, 2017). Identification of the most influential spreaders remains a problem in complex networks.

D. Network Density Calculation

One bit of information weighs 3.19×10^{-38} Kg at 300 Kelvin, which is room temperature (Vopson, 2019, p. 3). Thus, in order to appreciate mass in the network, standard equation for network density calculation is fundamental (NetworkX codes by Sayama, 2015, pp. 318-320).

However, Dong et al. (2019) have crafted the landmark for the ingenious analysis of network density. Their approach is more rigorous when it comes to spectral density or “density of states,” owing to the “overall distribution of eigenvalues” (Dong et al., 2019, p. 1152). Comparing dynamics between a natural and an artificial (bot-mediated) phenomenon can be conducted with spectral density using von Neumann’s equation (De Domenico & Biamonte, 2016, pp. 2-3).

The Python codes by Schreiber (2020) underscore the worth of density operators. Based on simulation, von Neumann entropy (the quantum equivalent of Shannon entropy) will increase to evolve over time (i.e., from pure state into mixed state) passing an “intermediate point,” which can be the best time to measure density

or to inquire about the uncertainty of the system in terms of its quantum state and the amount of (mis)information.

E. Modeling of the State-to-State Transition of Nodes

Network states over time (i.e., producing divergence or bifurcations) could be simulated using the Python codes by Sayama (2015) based on “local bifurcations” (pp. 130-132) to look into the threshold point before shifting between stable (nonviral) and unstable (viral). In addition, the Lyapunov exponent (Sayama, 2015, pp. 139-141) is useful to visualize the “stretching” and Lorenz equations (Sayama, 2015, pp. 142-146) to reveal the “folding” of entangled systems.

The “symmetric mixed states,” specifically “three-mode Gaussian states” (Adesso et al., 2006, pp. 13-14) make more sense in terms of “quasi-probability” (Adesso et al., 2006, p. 2). They are continuous variables and can be known by a “covariance matrix” (Adesso et al., 2006, p. 2). There are five classes of states identified as follows: **Class 1**, fully entangled states; **Class 2**, two states entangled; **Class 3**, only one state entangled; **Class 4**, separable into two states; and **Class 5**, fully separable states (Adesso et al., 2006, p. 5). These states will uphold a period of “synchronization” and are interpreted by eigenvalues. A fully inseparable tripartite entanglement (or a clique) has a value >1 (under Class 1 through Class 3) while fully separable (Class 5) has a value equal to 1 (Adesso et al., 2006, p. 15). On the other hand, <1 is assumed Class 4. The most important aspect about entanglements is the “promiscuous sharing of information” (Adesso et al., 2006, p. 15) due to the mediation of Twitter bots. The Wigner function simulates this phenomenon in wave propagation,

but the conjecture is that the states are Gaussian (Quesada, 2019; Marchildon, 2018; Weinbub & Ferry, 2018) from the following variables: $N = \text{number of nodes}$;

$$\sigma = \frac{2^N}{6}; \text{ and } \mu = 2^{(N-1)} \text{ minus } .50 \text{ to } 1.0 \text{ (Alam, 2018).}$$

Generally, parameterization is taken in “partly deterministic, partly stochastic models...” (Kerscher, 2000, p. 5). This is the way to obtain a theorized spatial distribution of what counts as entities. The (energy) “flux” as indicator of emergence is limited to homogenous events (Kerscher, 2000, p. 6). Therefore, wavelengths should be studied in multiplex to finely discriminate events cloaked by the background noise. This puts the Fourier transform equation into good use (Kerscher, 2000, p. 8). In the case of nodes within a vast space, point existence (and their distances) is by the speed of light. Energy scintillations within a “Twitter network-system” can be approximated in a calorimetric (temperature) spectrum or heat map. Second-order statistics (for probability density of states) such as Minkowski functionals and J -function (Kerscher, 2000) will be appropriate if energy variance is at a very large scale or high energy.

F. Modeling of the Distribution of Mass and Energy

Calculation of Fisher information (FI) can be used to determine the probability distributions of mass and energy. The methodology formulated by Ahmad et al. (2016, pp. 2-6) is desirable and can be implemented using the codes by Complex and Sustainable Urban Networks Lab (2018), where change in network density and energy over time (Δy_i) is simply determined by the equation $y_i(t_j) - y_i(t_k)$; binned (values

grouped); and plotted separately. FI equation by Karunanithi et al. (2008 cited in Ahmad et al., 2016, p. 2) gives a probability distribution, $p(s)$ for the binned value of interest whereas the equation (P_i) by Mayer, Pawlowski, and Cabezas (2006 cited in Ahmad et al., 2016, p. 4), expressed as the number of points in state divided by the number of points will reveal the amplitude of the probability distribution, $q(s)$ derived from $(q_i = \sqrt{p_i})$. FI is interpreted as follows: nonzero trend, non-chaotic dynamics; steady decrease, impending chaos; steady increase, becoming organized; and sharp decrease, chaotic system (Ahmad et al., 2016, p. 6). Artificial neural networks (e.g., codes for machine learning by Charnock, 2018) will do great in predicting events that are nonlinear following the principle of FI (Charnock et al., 2018).

G. Modeling of the Spatial Evolution of Network Elements

The workflow for quantification of network topology by Donner (2018, p. 14) involves empirical orthogonal function (EOF) analysis with time series plots and statistical similarity measurements (e.g., Pearson correlation). This is applicable for studying linear decomposition of mass and energy in time series and functional network analysis for studying dynamic variations, which entails “binarization” (a non-linear transformation) of data through “thresholding.”

The method introduced by Mathews et al. (2020, p. 16340) applies Gaussian mixture models (GMMs) for examining network topology in terms of “edge-based joint distribution” with scatter plots and then introduces a comparison of adjacent distribution with distances to reduce large data (omit redundancy) and to re-visualize

the network while inferring from a dynamical perspective. The codes can be accessed from Mathews (2020). Since edges only meet end-to-end, distance measurements between nodes, which are indirect connections, have been estimated by the shortest path length. The shortest path length is relevant to network density equation (Rosenblatt, 2013) and the Euclidean spaces in the network (Demiryurek & Shahabi, 2012). So, such topological features (particularly spatial details) can also be represented by Voronoi diagrams. In addition, they can be used to find node location with Delaunay triangulation using minimum spanning tree (Gallier, 2011).

The Twitter network is nonetheless a huge constellation of points like the universe, hence labeled: "Twitterverse". Minimum spanning tree is about the "local clustering properties of a distribution of points" (Cybulski et al., 2014, p. 3570). The large-scale structure (LSS) mapping algorithm by Cybulski (2017) makes sense if network size is extremely complex. Hujsak's (2018) machine learning codes will work for feature extraction of the LSS map after some modifications. Implementation of stochastic models will support the elucidation of mass into energy and finally, the emergence of "virality." The Poisson model is common (Kerscher, 2000, p. 5). In the Poisson model, the mean local number of nodes and edges (comprising the "galaxy" in the original concept) inside a (network) region is directly proportional to the total mass it has.

Saganowski (2017, pp. 20-21) proposed the group evolution discovery (GED) method to track changes in the formation of a social network by sequences of events. The main objective is to capture the "temporality" of information about node position by timeframes, which can reveal how the network is forming, growing, splitting, shrinking, continuing, merging, and dissolving. The algorithm serves to partition or section continuous events into time intervals (Saganowski, 2017, pp. 23-24). The

information at different levels of perturbations is quantified in order to find concurrent dynamics through a collection of events that are either opposing or in conjunction.

Two-dimensional visualization will linearize the evolving components while important details are reduced. Here node activity is represented by a fixed (disentangled) data point. The underlying elements are flattened. Node activity can only be represented one at a time. Subgroups shrinking and merging or forming and dissolving are accounted for independently. The resolve taken by Saganowski (2017, pp. 22-23) entailed both measurement of community overlaps and inclusions of the node: first in quantity, the portion shared among identical communities; and second in quality, its vital contribution in the network. However, assigning the events represented per timeframe is not only tedious for large quantities of information (big datasets), but (maybe) also misleading. Therefore, machine learning is employed.

Network information embedding techniques, for example, data representation inside the Hilbert space (Adams, 2020; Altay, 2021) allows feature mapping of density estimates from eigenvalues (Sriperumbudur et al., 2010, p. 1522). The process is more effective with a support vector machine algorithm (Schuld & Killoran, 2018, p. 2). Power space theorem is behind spatial embedding. The power-law distribution in space is a function of the adjacency matrix of the eigenvalues (Benowitz, 2018, p. 1). After eigenvalues become a space filling curve (SFC) bit sequence, they give point locations in space or as vectors (Guan et al., 2018).

H. Modeling of the Classical Network Dynamics

Dynamics representation with the Kuramoto model works on coupling strength, which is inversely proportional to the number of connections or by the inverse of the square root of connectivity. Instead of examining for oscillation stationarity in asynchronous dynamics, investigations shifted to the ubiquitous phenomenon of massive coupling: "collective irregular dynamics" or CID using biological neurons as an example. CID supports the emergence of large macroscopic fluctuations by the increase in the number of connections or degree (k) than network size (N) in relation to the spike trends (fibrillatory). At the thermodynamic limit (also coupling limit), the large frequency diverges into high and low (indicating microscopic chaotic dynamics) by spectral density and node convergence (by synchronization) decreases. Ironically, stochasticity takes place in spite of the fact that CID is a deterministic process, which has been shown to contribute in the evolution of the network (even beyond the coupling limit) (Ullner et al., 2018).

Nodes, as (classical) harmonic oscillators, are represented by this equation: $\left[(K/2) (\textit{amplitude})^2 \right]$ (Morin, 2008b). In this study, K touches on the Boltzmann constant equal to 1.380649×10^{-23} joule per Kelvin (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2018). This is proportional to the logarithm of the number of microstates of the system (Marinescu & Marinescu, 2012) in a thermodynamic perspective under the Second Law of Thermodynamics, where the increase of energy is towards the maximum (Gao et al., 2019). Such phenomenon is the inflection to critical mass and declines due to energy transformation (e.g., heat) as node activity and information diffusion wanes. The Boltzmann constant offers: first, an ideal measure of disorder or

information both statistically and spatially; and second a bridge between spatial patterns (e.g., topological features of the Twitter network) and thermodynamic interpretations (e.g., heat maps for adjacency matrix, modularity, spectral decomposition, etc.) (Gao et al., 2019). Oscillations are no longer limited to a one-dimensional phase. Networks can exhibit (a) chimera states or self-consistent partial synchrony (not all phases or frequencies are equal), (b) fully synchronous state under a constant phase shift or any (c) clustered states (Ullner et al., 2018; Teichmann, 2021).

Equally spaced nodes (these are the nodes rotating apart on a reference frame) throughout the interval $[0, 2\pi]$ during Kuramoto simulation are a sign of no synchronization, for example, $\theta_k(t) = 1$ wherein zero is a critical point (Moler, 2019b). Spacing is denoted by beta, β where from .24 to .23 nodes are locked into a single phase and cannot synchronize (Moler, 2019b). On the other hand, evolution of node states is measured in $\theta_j - t$, $(\theta_j - t) - \theta_k(t)$, which will show the rate of change in oscillation (Moler, 2019b). The number of lines clumping in the graph correspond to nodes differentiating into fast, medium, and slow frequencies that are stable (Moler, 2019b) unless percolated.

When the entropy threshold is exceeded (at critical mass), continuous transition is replaced by discontinuous transition. Roughly stipulating the (mis)information churned out in every transition not only makes the contagion diffusive (in communicational sense) rather altering the native rules in transmitting the contagion. With the higher-order Kuramoto framework, visualization of the multiplex interrelationship of vertices through edges (based on neuronal models) exposes the following: (1) pairwise coupling between phases (states) in one layer; and (2)

modulation by the local dynamics of individual nodes in the other layer (Millán et al., 2020, p. 4). This modulation *per se* has to be studied to establish whether it is explicit or quasi so that quantum instances can be described in terms of the pattern acted out by bots or fictitious accounts.

The fate of nodes in response to the information contagion under a chaotic space over (lag) time is determined by the bifurcation parameter, ($L > 2\pi$) based on the “shape of the normalized (time-averaged) power spectrum,” where it follows a non-Gaussian distribution (Encyclopedia of Mathematics, 2011). The Twitter network is a complex system principally due to the elaborate “structuring” (organization of the sender-information-receiver) more than or additive to the pre-existing structure there is from the amount of information pictured out using Fisher’s equation, $FI \approx 4 \sum_i = 1m[q_i - q_{i+1}]^2$ by Karunanithi et al. (2008 cited in Ahmad et al., 2016, p. 2). Misinformation spreads by higher-order interactions of simplicial complexes. This challenges the standard Kuramoto model of synchronization, i.e. “In the absence of links between the nodes each oscillator obeys its own dynamics and is unaffected by its neighbors. However, when the interaction among neighbor nodes switches to above a given [critical] value, the [harmonic] oscillators start to beat at the same frequency” (University of London, 2020).

I. Modeling of the Quantum Network Dynamics

A wave is made up of a correlated collection of oscillations and its harmonic motion is sinusoidal with reference to time. Energy moves back and forth between kinetic (when it collapses) and potential (at maximum limits). (Morin, 2008b)

However, on the basis of (the number of) quantum states, the k has another face as von Neumann entropy (Marinescu & Marinescu, 2012) which Shannon entropy cannot plainly quantify with the (in)variability of distribution of (mis)information in the network *vis-à-vis* evolution of energy states through time.

In this study, virality of a complex system (e.g., “Twitterverse”) is portrayed as (1) relativistic (i.e., information behaves as a particle and the kinetic energy is a result of its mass at the speed of light) with Vopson’s (2019) equation theorized from Einstein's equation, where mass is relativistic (Umul, 2007, p. 4); and (2) nonrelativistic (i.e., energy equivalent of information in both kinetic and potential propagates through waves, but less than the speed of light) with the time dependent Schrödinger equation. Eigenvalues (denoting energy values) are calculated with time-independent or $1-D$ Schrödinger equation (Nave, 2000). Any change of wavefunction is a sign of perturbation of a stationary state in nonrelativistic systems that rapidly propagates (at a finite rather than infinite speed due to time delay to reach distant regions) with an inconceivable nonlocality, wherein quantum states do not depend on local hidden variables (including feedback mechanisms) and particles (for example, nodes and misinformation) just appear (Shnaid, 2013).

System state is measured in time (e.g., time-dependent Schrödinger equation) and position in space (x), which is reported as eigenstate, $\varphi(\vec{r})$ in a linear combination (array) or not. However, eigenstate ($<1, 1, >1$) flips or remains stationary

independent of time. Phase transition of nodes (i.e., from linear to nonlinear dynamics represented by wave generation patterns) is time-dependent in view of synchronization through this complex exponential factor, $e^{i\theta}$ (Tokmakoff, 2020).

Energy in the system has a Gaussian distribution. Time-dependent wavefunction oscillates and collapses (damps-out) evenly according to the Schrödinger equation (Figure 11). This only describes a dissipative system—energy decays as a function of time projection. There is coherence if waves have a Gaussian spread. On the other hand, decoherence suggests anomalous realities. In Figure 12, underdamping (at 1.0) has a gradual decay until below zero but recovers quickly above the equilibrium point with oscillations while in overdamping (at .30), return to equilibrium (from above zero) is slow without oscillations. Critical damping (at .60) has an energy drop close to zero and can get back fast to equilibrium in a non-oscillating manner. The damping ratio is interpreted in the following: $\zeta < 1$, underdamped; $\zeta > 1$, overdamped; and $\zeta = 1$, critically-damped (MathWorks, 2022a). For theory consistency, <1 is a stable state, >1 is unstable, and 1 is at equilibrium (Sayama, 2015, pp. 77, 79, 84).

Positive eigenvalues suggest an unbound system while negative (or below zero) eigenvalues occur in a bound system. Whenever both positive and negative eigenvalues are generated, variable (unbound) oscillations occur. Thus, energy is interpreted with dynamic invariance (Um, Yeon, & George, 2002).

Normalization does not apply to unbounded systems (except with linear combinations) while quantization of eigenvalues is unacceptable since they vary continuously (Schroeder, 2022, p. 38). Energies grow faster, for example from linear to exponential (Gelfreich & Turaev, 2008) although not necessarily to infinity. This

growth drives virality to a spree. However, the potential well shapes the wavefunction collapse (Figure 18).

Figure 11. Resonance produced from Schrödinger equation.

SOURCE: Modified from Information Philosopher, 2022.

Figure 12. Energy damping trajectories.

SOURCE: Um et al., 2002, p. 160.

Figure 13. Gaussian distribution per energy level increase.

SOURCE: MikeRun, 2021.

In Figure 14, unbounded phase oscillations abide to the symmetry of energy sinking into the system. It will rise at high velocity with a narrow leading-edge wavelength and will disperse at low velocity by (1) widening the trailing-edge wavelength and (2) decreasing the peak amplitude to conserve energy (Schroeder, 2022, p. 86). Oscillations will decrease momentum over a linear ramp potential energy ahead until they stop at the boundary of the field and then reverse direction, but the shape will be irregular as the spread recurs (Schroeder, 2022, pp. 92-93). So, stochasticity (i.e., predictability of patterns) and randomness (i.e., emergence of

patterns) depend on the (1) potential energy inside the potential well and (2) the back-and-forth movement of the wavefunction across three physical regions (Figure 15). Waves oscillate freely in Region I and Region III but will move according to the potential in Region II, and will start an exponential decay here (Ling et al., 2019).

From the energetics and wave phenomena standpoint, viral misinformation spread has predictable and variable peak energy cycles. However, wave collapse can offer more valuable information about “localization” (the perturbations within the network) or multicenter (rather than an epicenter) of the potential energy well.

Figure 14. Dispersion of energy through wave packets.

SOURCE: Schroeder, 2022, p. 86.

Energy amplitudes (as probability densities) among eigenstates are coherent or in superposition if there are well-defined relationships between waves or they are equal to 1 (Young, 2020), which indicates a strong correlational value.

Figure 15. Patterns of oscillation.

SOURCE: Ling et al., 2019.

For small values, energy eigenvalues are discrete quantities, but they turn to continuous quantities at higher levels. The system can no longer stay as a bound state. It must become unbound to dissipate energy and find equilibrium. Energy eigenvalues get closer and closer until they reach a maximum level. Distances between energy levels inside the potential energy well that are equal to the lowest levels of potential energy or lowest vibrational transitions make them good estimates of mass of influential nodes on a spectrum. Just like particles, nodes will oscillate at very low frequencies even at ground state, where: $n = 0$ or “zero-point vibration” (Nave, 2000).

Explosive synchronization and entangled processes take place at the moment chaos aggravates in the network throughout the transformation of critical mass (from Tweets) into perturbing energy levels in wave fluxes. Perturbation of nodes maximizes system entropy and proceeds to random disorder. Movement from nonequilibrium to equilibrium is shown as a leftward shift ($t = 0$) of the Gaussian well (Figure 16). Further oscillations ($t > 0$) will move the system

to equilibrium. The system requires more dampening to spread out the energy and to become stable ($t < 0$). The time from nonequilibrium to equilibrium provides an opportunity to approximate the bot cycle. In Figure 17, “...bound-state wavefunctions oscillate within the classically allowed regions and decrease exponentially in the classically forbidden regions” (Schroeder, 2022, p. 65) until equilibrium.

SOURCE: Hsueh et al., 2020, p. 3.

Figure 17. Wavefunction oscillations in a bound state.

SOURCE: Schroeder, 2022, p. 65.

The discourse on measurement of mass and energy corresponding to information is not far from the rigorous determination of the breadth of the extensive properties, particularly entropy and entanglement (Bera et al., 2019, pp. 1851, 1854). Statistically, this makes sense in the analysis of dispersion. The mean and standard deviation are not useful if results are skewed. Moreover, they cannot give "...the best representative value of the distribution" (Bera et al., 2019, p. 1854) based on the nature of the distribution, e.g., differential entropy values diverge (Bera et al., 2019, p. 1853). However, in order to study nonlinear systems, skewness is an important representation.

The critical value denotes "...the ordering of quantum states with respect to their distance from the minimum uncertainty state" (Bera et al., 2019, p. 1854). Specifically, this is drawn out of a probability distribution bounded by the first and third quartiles. The semi-interquartile range is a valid reference for the "position and momentum distributions of all quantum states" (Bera et al., 2019, p. 1851). The median (second quartile) is suitable as quantifier of dispersion (Bera et al., 2019, p. 1852). On the other hand, entropy of the wave has a nondecreasing slope or concave function by its logarithm (Gzyl, 2021, p. 1). However, if the median is reported in finding critical thresholds, the very high and very low values are discounted (Salgado, 2017) as outliers, which in turn, defeats the effect of the anomalies in the distribution.

Examination of *p-value* distribution could support the assumption of "coupling" of recruited nodes in the context of "polarization" (Interian & Ribeiro, 2018, p. 657). Having *p-value* less than the significance level α per node implies a large number of cases. While on a global scale, a greater distribution is indicative of massive polarity. However, with any network polarization index, data has to be "symmetrized" (Maoz, 2006, p. 398).

J. Signal Processing and Data Sonification

For signal processing, analysis of energy waves (the emitted signals of the observed network) can give the location of nodes and energy strength (Chen, 2020, p. 107), which is theorized to define “virality”. Influential nodes vary in threshold depending on the phase. So, determination of critical thresholds has to be made. The caveat is that with a big threshold, lower energy nodes may be ignored. Most influential nodes (active seeders) are those that have bigger energy readings than neighboring nodes. However, due to the effect of adjacency, measuring the high energy readings of individual nodes close to each other in the same dense network distribution makes no significant difference. Noise (entropy) in the network will affect the energy readings of nodes. Therefore, influential nodes must be studied more quantitatively (Chen, 2020, p. 113).

Sonification is an extra step in the analysis of the energy spectrum especially highlighting these events using sounds: (1) time estimation of critical mass; (2) the immediate post-critical mass (dematerialization); (3) the manifestation of (explosive) kinetic energy (transmission velocity with increasing pitch and shifting tones); and (4) energy loss (dissipation with decreasing pitch). It continues to be endeavored for rediscovering insights with old and continuous datasets like the search for dark matter (Vasilakos et al., 2020) or for better understanding of highly convoluted datasets in the case of the spike proteins sequence of the COVID-19 virus (Buehler, 2020).

Data sonification represent a move from information designs that are limited to dashboards to data-driven storytelling for the public. Audio data have been available about COVID-19 in the United States since January 2020 until October 2020 based on reported cases and geospatial data, greenhouse gas emissions in USA based on

nitrogen oxides in the air from 1990 to 2018, and social vulnerability index in New York City based on percentage of population infected of COVID-19 and percentage of population living in poverty. Therefore, cross disciplinary conversations occur with broader reach or expanse, convergence, and inclusiveness. Scientific data has a better chance to be understood and data scientists and multimedia designers may be able to get insights from journalists, audio content creators, blind or visually impaired community, and older persons can engage as well. Key benefits of this technique are (1) lay understanding, (2) equal accessibility, and (3) faster distribution over audio-first and screenless devices (McGrory, 2020).

Sonification offers accessibility for the visually impaired scholars to interpret and explore datasets (Emsley & Roure, 2017, p. 11). Such endeavor was successfully instrumentalized by Dr. Wanda Diaz Merced who is visually impaired but a leading scientist in the field of astronomy. In her doctoral thesis, sonification is an adjunct to data visualization for improving sensitivity to detect events when there is low signal-to-noise ratio, thus the (2D) visual data presentation is ambiguous (Diaz Merced, 2013, p. 10).

Furthermore, sonification of the influential nodes' bleeping energy band, first, into something as raw as collective noise; and secondly, polishing (filtering by frequency windowing) the audio stream in order to discern the harmonic signature, has initiated the ingenious implementation of a "quantizer" in the concept of a meaningful, real-time particle detection from the ATLAS experiment at CERN (Hill et al., 2017) when heavy ions collide in the LHC (ATLAS Experiment, 2018), but with the intention of advocating a multimodal bot detection (visual or graphical, statistical, spectroscopic, and sonic).

Sonification dates back to the early 1990s for use in data exploration (Ballora et al., 2012). A clear advantage of sonification in social network analysis is the study of temporal patterns (Jamieson & Boase, 2016) through the following: conversion of Twitter hashtags and keywords into a soundscape using Tweetscaples (Hermann et al., 2012); conversion of arousal-valence scores among Twitter followers to trending artists (Ash, 2012); mapping data to its sonic parameters as followers evolve over time using granular synthesis and sound modulation (Vogt et al., 2012); detection of anomalous Twitter events with ascending set of pitch sequences and louder timbre (Ballora et al., 2012); data-driven melodic representation of the Twitter’s network structure (Jones & Gregson, 2014); real-time musical scoring or soundtrack composition based on tweet inputs and sentiment analysis that reveal “the meaning of the natural language of the tweets” and mood on Twitter respectively (Drymonitis & Chatzopoulou, 2021).

This unique approach has been adopted by physicists at CERN for big data exploration, where the elucidation of datasets is according to: (1) **meaning/content** from ‘phenomenological’ representation or data modeling (disclosure of tangible states is entirely a product of numerical acquisition) to ‘metaphoric’ representation or sound modeling (i.e., nominal or non-trivial and nonnominal or trivial properties are differentiated by magnitude comparison and estimation, e.g., increasing particle mass correlates with decreasing pitch given the appropriate method of amplification or equalization in terms of scaling (windowing) or audio file (and format) manipulation to achieve a match—although neither always exacting nor intuitive since there is semantic coding bias—between data fragments and tones; (2) **structure** by mapping patterns or sequences, amplitude or pitch, and symmetry in reference to time and space; and (3) **elements**, for example, by the range of acoustic units displayed (pitch

in decibels, dB is graphed) that are interpreted directly and “gestalt units” or the smallest perceivable (psycho-acoustical) characteristics (i.e., nominality is the relative weighing) of the sound reaching the listener ear about its composition (synthesis) and frequency band distortions per modulation (Vogt, 2010, pp. 73-91).

The bifurcation of sound elements either making sonification artistic as entertainment or empirical (Neuhoff, 2019, pp. 328-329) puts up the discourse of representation and hence, a limitation. Although data before and after sonification do not necessarily have to be structurally identical (Hermann, 2008, p. 4), they must tell the same information.

In Figure 18, a wider range of confidence or even incontrovertible evidence is plausible in the interest of cybersecurity (Axon et al., 2016, p. 256) and comprehensive qualification of bot attackers with “sound footprints” added to “Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS)”. Later, it has been shown to raise levels of situational awareness since operators are able to understand the network’s behavior (Debashi & Vickers, 2018) seen against the multiple sources of incoming information (Ballora et al., 2012) plus it lowers their workload demands (Debashi & Vickers, 2018).

Figure 18. Sonification in network monitoring.

SOURCE: Axon et al., 2016, p. 256.

Chapter III

FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

Ontology and Theoretical Constructs

The main constructs, namely: “**COVID-19 Infodemic**” and “**Network Complexities**” would best describe (and sum up) the overarching events and the unfolding of network elements that make up the grand phenomenon of “**Virality**” inside the “**Twitterverse**” by tweet dataset, which has been theorized with “quantumness” in this study. These are linked together to explain the misinformation spread about COVID-19 vaccination and the configuration of agents (humans and bots). Analysis of complex networks has revealed how it is intriguingly creating knowledge, while cybernetics has established its frontiers in terms of process control in the sense that “...without the assumption of a definite causal order between the parties” (Guérin & Brukner, 2018, p. 2), a node’s temporal connectivity and disconnectivity to other nodes (relying on energy streams and fluctuations) can control the scale of misinformation. Disproportionate aggregations of nodes can still lead to the emergence of “critical mass”—even outside of their local topology—through quantum processes.

Conceptual Framework

Characterization of misinformation spread and Twitter bot activity takes into account critical mass, energy decay, entanglements, as well as node synchronization using multilayer and spectral graph visualizations, Kuramoto modeling, sonification, and wavefunction simulation.

Figure 19.1. Conceptualization of the cause-and-effect model for the main variables.

$$Virality_{Tweets} = Virality_{Bots}$$

In this study, the target measurement is the **"Virality" of Twitter Bots**, which is calculated using the **"Global Equation 4: Virality of Bots in the Network."** This same equation served as the grand equation in explaining the main phenomenon.

On the other hand, “**Virality**” of **COVID-19 Tweets** is investigated using the time-dependent Schrödinger equation and time-independent Schrödinger equation and then analyzed in “**Table 37. Comparison of outcomes based on number of tweets.**”

Research Propositions

1. COVID-19 vaccine ‘infodemic’ (misinformation spread) has linear and nonlinear mechanisms. This phenomenon was captured by implementation of various (statistical) network measurements.
 - 1.1. The linear pathway is simply an information cascade shown by contagion models (Jin et al., 2014) via social networks where nodes transmit and acquire infection because of the connection proximity rule (closer distance means faster spread) in the network (spatiality) and nature of ‘exposure’ (temporality cycle and influence, power, or virulence of infected nodes). These validated mechanisms obey the Information Theory by Shannon and Weaver (1949) and Moore and Shannon (1956) (Sharma et al., 2020). Same will be assumed to be true when it comes to the explanation of misinformation spread and impact of bots on social media. The birth of Information Theory formulated in the seminal papers by Shannon and Weaver (1949), and Moore and Shannon (1956) laid the basic foundation for the Information Age to flourish and for Communication Scholars to valorize the study of the Internet under “infodemiology,” in particular, a science by itself (Eysenbach, 2009 cited

in Mackey et al., 2022) that is inextricably linked to the investigation of an “infodemic”. Path linearity is best expressed in order of events: (a) misinformation (co)generation by humans and Twitter bots; (b) misinformation amplification by Twitter bots; (c) neighbor node recruitment (convergence on misinformation); and (d) massive and accelerated misinformation diffusion. The synopsis is oversimplified by making it appear that mitigation is straightforward by severing occurrence of prior events.

- 1.2. The nonlinear mechanisms start in a linear (exponential) manner and proceed into diverging, co-occurring or overlapping events: (a) ‘**periodic**’ (continuous) inflation of the degree of connections between nodes to a critical threshold or critical point by percolation theory (also described as passing from steady energy state fluxes to explosive energy dissipation) or it can be denoted as the time to critical mass (suggesting Twitter bots can make abrupt internal (node) state changes or system dynamics that prevent their deexcitation by (overpowering) external feedback versus biological nodes (based on human tweet generation) that normally is impossible to suddenly change according to Palsson (2011, cited in Haiman et al., 2021) and (b) ‘**nonperiodic**’ (discontinuous or stepwise) phase transition, i.e., after each emergence of plateau to a critical phase of node activity inflections. At either criticality for infodemic detection, the anomaly patterns have equifinality to (a nonzero) decay considering the Twitter network is an open system. Kinetic energy damping or decomposition is anticipated to become negative potential energy (i.e., back to a bound state where nodes will again fabricate new connections

and attract even more neighbor nodes while tweets reflood the network to a critical mass including all activated nodes).

2. The “Twitterverse” is perturbable (easily affected internally and externally) as any open system and pliable as any social media network. This phenomenon was captured by the Fast Incremental von Neumann Graph Entropy (FINGER) algorithm.

2.1. The Twitter network is complex in many (disarrayed) properties when seen through the lens of chaos theory. First, the constellation of information is held together spatially by edges in different planes of configurations (multilayer and multiplex) especially with regard to entanglements in topology. Second, its expansion is skewed by temporality of the (fluid-like) distribution of information—when it is added and removed. The question of “what” to “where” is the uncertainty side that depends on probability. Localization is arbitrary rather than unfixed to data points; only entropy is certain—at higher entropy levels, anomaly patterns are noisier and become serially aimless with plain graphs.

2.2. The network can neither resist the information flow nor change the fundamental physics of information flow. However, it can ‘dematerialize’ (convert) the mass of information, have it amplified into equivalent measurable energy (Vopson, 2019), and exchange it as energy output (Palsson, 2011, cited in Haiman et al., 2021) or revert it to mass and input the energy to reactivate the same system (Katz & Kahn, 1966, cited in Mele, 2010, p. 128) or another one coming from node interactions. The Twitterverse is an energy dense quantum field that is landscaped by unstable dynamics.

3. Twitter bots are key players with the same agency as human accounts but are much more prolific spreaders (super spreaders). Twitter bots, however, are designed amplifiers of information whether factual or not (dis- or misinformation). This was visualized by multilayer and spectral (multiplex) graphs.
 - 3.1. Visualization of the arrangement of edges between vertices is an expositional endeavor in the study of networks both for “global cascades” (i.e., network activation by a small group of nodes as the primary active seeders of information) and cascade condition (Brummitt et al., 2012, pp. 1-2). Single-layer global cascades fall between continuous transition after “the emergence of the giant connected component” and discontinuous transition or when global cascades disappear (Brummitt et al., 2012, p. 2). Hence, a contagion (malicious Tweet) is signified by a mass of nodes and edges around it.
4. Critical mass corresponds to the (kinetic) energy peak. This was visualized by spectrogram analysis.
 - 4.1. Determination of critical mass in network analysis is not about the ‘how’ but rather about the ‘where’ and ‘when’. Thus, speculation regarding its incidence is first about the atypical concentration of mass and then how such mass outgrows the local limits into a phenomenon of virality in social media networks. Ripples of energy waves are equally important in the propagation of misinformation, especially as bots target hubs and take control.
5. Entanglements correspond to the interlayer or any anomalous and/or alternate connections between nodes and the frequencies at the same energy level

(nonstructural entanglement) allowing signals to “quantum jump” overcoming spatiotemporality limitations during unbound states of nodes in the field. This was visualized after calculating entanglement across bot, human, and tweet layer and ‘entanglement per node’ (entropy of entanglement). Frequency interfaces were visualized intuitively in a spectrogram.

- 5.1. A case of “entanglement” happens when a hub (in one layer) acts as hub in another layer (Goh, 2012, p. 15). Basically, “cascades” in multiplex graphs are portrayed from tree (network) to root (node) spread according to the Erdős–Rényi model giving statistical probabilities of entanglement (Goh, 2012, p. 2) from an adjacency list (Hagberg et al., 2018), but random graphs can only mimic partial entangled states (Perseguers, 2010, p. 65) in spite of exhibiting change in properties completely at a critical point under the laws of quantum physics. Moreover, they cannot be scale-free like the real-world is (Perseguers et al., 2013, p. 45).
- 5.2. Entanglement is also indicated by a giant connected component (at least 80% of final clustering value) after merging network layers (Cardillo et al., 2013, p. 3). On the other hand, a recent study discourages the costly analysis of “coupling” by structure to study entanglement and instead advocates the evaluation of function (dynamics) “by maximizing the deviation of a system’s entropy from the limit of free and noninteracting layers” (Ghavasieh & de Domenico, 2020, p. 1).
- 5.3. Although not yet proven, the process that attempts to determine the functional architecture of hubs thriving on misinformation using both topological and spectral analysis of the visualized multilayers could suggest that entanglement is not always a structure-dependent process

(e.g., hierarchical overlaying, nesting a power-law rule), but is generated through an elaborate ‘quantumness’ (coupling of the states of network components) and cascading flourish of (1) information, (2) mass, and (3) energy.

6. The von Neuman entropy corresponds to network evolution, at least with regard to edge formation. This was calculated using the von Neuman Graph entropy algorithm.
7. Node synchronization corresponds to the fundamental force (i.e., by coupling strength) in network dynamics. This was simulated using the Kuramoto model.

7.1. Node dynamics can be analyzed based on the Kuramoto model in this

equation: $\dot{\theta}_k = \omega_k + \frac{K}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n \sin(\theta_j - \theta_k), k = 1, \dots, n$, so that if the coupling

strength or $k = 0$ nodes are linear and independently oscillating, if $k = .50$ nodes move at a common frequency, and if $k = .12$ nodes approach their threshold value and go through a nonlinear synchronization (Moler, 2019a). Over the critical point, node dynamics will get to a common limit (Moler, 2019a). In addition, the Kuramoto model accounts for time evolution of nodes and their oscillations are by “...the gradient of a potential [energy] function” (Moler, 2019b) according

to this equation: $v(t) = \frac{4}{n^2} \sum_k \sum_{j>k} \sin^2 \frac{\theta_j(t) - \theta_k(t)}{2}$ and this potential

normalizes by $4/n^2$ (Moler, 2019b).

- 7.2. The internal frequencies of oscillating nodes whenever information is seeping allows them to attract and to affix links with adjacent nodes connected, but this depends on the coupling constant labeled “coupling

strength". In the literature, dramatic events (explosive synchronization) start showing at any point between $k = 1$ and $k = 2$ (Millán et al., 2020) and then spiking steadily at $k > 2$. This could translate into a node state of >1 . On the other hand, phase transition happens above the lower critical dimension, $dl = 4$ (Hong et al., 2005, cited in Ódor & Kelling, 2019) or lower system threshold.

8. Distribution of critical mass into energy corresponds to wave peaks. This was simulated using two wavefunction equations (Method 1 and Method 2). Specifically, Python codes by Polson (2021c; 2021d) were implemented for the time-dependent Schrödinger equation or "**Technique 1: Finite Difference**" and time-independent Schrödinger equation or "**Technique 2: Eigenstate Evolution**".
 - 8.1. The "spookiness" of the quantum phenomena theorized inside the Twitter network starts from the transmutation of the volume of information into a diffusible mass and then energy into a wavefunction. The ripples of waves when they collapse may depend on the richness of the entangled intricacies.
 - 8.2. The differential wave-like noise (from the transduction of mass and energy) between information and misinformation flows in the network corresponds to the wavefunction anomaly suggesting a quantum phenomenon which can be harnessed for detection of significant events.
 - 8.3. The representation of theoretical mass of misinformation and its energy equivalent distribution within the Twitter network by wavefunction simulation is based on Schrödinger wave equations.

9. The Twitter bots' audio footprint corresponds to their level of "virality" or brute effects. This was performed by sonification of data pertaining to the most influential Twitter bots.
10. The "virality" of Twitter bots corresponds to the quantized network energy measured through Twitter bots' activity on top of human activity (their dynamic expanse is over tweets exchanged). This was globally calculated and interpreted as an index score.

Developing a novel method of comprehensive data-driven analytics

Equations were made to calculate mass and energy. Schematic diagrams were conceptualized to describe the dynamics between bots, humans, and tweets inside the "Twitterverse". To achieve the goal of this research, the study went through three phases. The illustrations of the three phases are (1) "**Conceptualization of the Twitterverse**," (2) "**Twitter Data Mining**," and (3) "**Post Tweet Mining**". The latter two phases are outlined in **Chapter 3: Methodology**.

Phase 1 (Figure 19.2) is where postulation of models out of communication and physics theories takes place. In this study, information is elucidated as a state of matter, in which finite mass can be theoretically "quantized" (reduced) per bit of information (Figure 20) thermodynamically at 3.19×10^{-38} Kg (Vopson, 2019). Mass of information was originally assumed from stored information (Kish & Granqvist, 2013). Information inside the "Twitterverse" dematerializes to energy and materializes to mass back and forth nonlinearly.

Figure 19.2. Conceptualization of the methodical approach from theories (Phase 1).

Legend: Solid lines, direct; broken lines, indirect or via chain of postulated throughput

Important insights from communication theories

Information theory is used to explain the chain of misinformation transmission while second-order cybernetics examines the feedback loop among humans and bots and between them to support the redundancy (trail) of misinformation. From the network theory, the following insights were accepted (based on Glanz et al., 2015 cited in Struweg, 2020, p. 122): first, network topology and characteristics have influence on system performance (i.e., flow of information and communication); second, actors'

network position (bot versus human) affects their activities; and, third, actors' activity configure with their network environment (i.e., more perturbed, more chaotic). When these are brought under graph theory, the bots, humans, and tweets will 'entangle' (intertwine), and then will converge to several hubs across layers where they seemingly superimpose functionally.

On the other hand, Actor-Network Theory (ANT) supports the claim that humans and Twitter bots assume same agency (as capable source of dis- or misinformation) at "The Third Age of Artificial Intelligence" (Mialhe & Hodes, 2017) since they (can) act synonymously in Twitter network by joint actions. Critical Mass Theory draws from ANT in the way it views synchronized activities. However, only when a sufficient number of users (i.e., 10% to 15%) were engaged to interact according to the literature or when the synchronized nodes can steer other nodes into a "collective action" (Flor, 2005), thereby reaching a massive scale (Flor, 2015, p. 53). This constitutes a momentary but repetitive event in the Twitter network. The Spiral of Silence Theory highlights the quiescence of nodes before and also immediately after "critical mass" that makes them vulnerable to either receiving another contagion and re-clustering into a bigger mass or to breaking into small clusters.

Theory-hold for the conceptualization of equivalence and quantum phenomenon

Vopson's (2022, p. 5) conjectures that (a) "...information transcends into mass or energy" and (b) "...elementary particles [*do*] store a fixed and quantifiable value of information about themselves" would support the hypothesis that "information" is theoretically a fifth form of matter. Increase in validity of such claim can only be proven experimentally.

From early experiments, information equivalence to mass was based on the space occupied by data after saving on an empty disk while the equivalence to energy was with heat released whenever data is erased and stored back (Vopson, 2019). Later experiments showed gamma photons and low energy photons are produced from information erasure during the positron–electron annihilation process (Vopson, 2022, p. 3).

So, this study locks onto the opportunity of moving forward from rudimentary proofs at least via representations from empirical data. Theories of communication are brought into this study to shed light on Vopson's (2022; 2019) fundamental assertions that "information" should be considered as matter by its own state and by being quantizable to mass and energy. In relation to size, a bit of information is 25×10^{-9} m, compared to an atom which is $\sim 10^{-10}$ m (Vopson, 2020, p. 1), showing that by such a scale the information bits can virtually be particles with mass accounted from its storage density.

For providing an alternative lens in quantitative research, new physics can be emancipated from the frigid classical context of information transmission and the basic, original physics can be revisited so as to provide explanations for the

related online social network phenomena. The latter requires acknowledging “quantumness” as unaccounted mystery behind the “virality” seen in the “COVID-19 infodemic” plus the intrinsic “complexities” of online social media networks such as Twitter.

Figure 20. The mass, energy, and information equivalence.

SOURCE: Vopson, 2019, p. 3.

Epistemology

The re-conceptualization of Shannon’s information theory to explain contagion transmission will surpass the frontier in modeling misinformation inside a social network such as Twitter. The ontological departure starts from the proposition of the existence of convoluting dimensions (as theorized in Figure 22), namely: (1) information and its transmission at critical mass (i.e., at the moment of instigating

network chaos to randomness, thus higher complexity); (2) topological entropy and energetics over time (i.e., a comprehensive definition of network evolution) by unstable frequencies and energy levels; (3) node state synchronization; and (4) connectivity by entanglements and dysconnectivity by abrupt disentanglements. The ground work puts up a multilayer (stacked layers) and multiplex (individual layer) visualizations and extended scope of network analytics.

The work by Brummitt et al. (2012, pp. 3-4) is intuitive as a good exemplar to frame the classical sender-receiver reference systems behind network theory, and to derive the thought of asymmetric structuring of internodal communications (coupling and entanglements) while considering mass displacement and energy decay that spans the Twitter network as (mis)information flows.

According to Nikola Tesla (1942 cited in Hunt & Schooler, 2019) "...to find the secrets of the Universe, [*we have to*] think in terms of energy, frequency and vibration". The research problems entail harder scientific rigor that is beckoning for empirical justification versus keeping an illusion of plausibility, most especially as it finds a way into the controversial quantum mechanics.

Although it does seem counterproductive to argue plausibility without extensive mustering of evidence from literature for stipulating quantum mechanisms behind misinformation spread on social media, no consensus has ever been achieved to explain this phenomenon in a crystal cleared manner or to dismiss any quantum basis.

There is no commonplace expression of "misinformation". Each generation of misinformation is consolidated to a virality energy potential by a spillover of mass and energy from reference systems (of nodes) at different states. Theorizing such phenomenon can be remarkably discursive and technically skeptical.

Social network analysis still constitutes a gray area much in need of further inquiry. Empirical knowledge is generated from demystification of virality of the COVID-19 tweets and bot activity using social network analysis from a quantum perspective with plausible simulation scales.

The conceptualizations came from (1) Shannon's Information Theory, (2) Cybernetics (second-order), (3) Network Theory (visualized by Graph Theory), (4) Critical Mass Theory, (5) Actor-Network Theory, (6) Spiral of Silence Theory, and (7) Quantum Mechanics (Chaos Theory was subsumed).

The approach implemented in this study lifts the veil of opportunities for deep(er) infodemiology research beginning with quantum suppositions and ending with pseudo empirical proofs by complex computer simulations.

Formulaic Representations

The equations below were formulated to translate Vopson's (2019) work into more neutral than pseudo empirical proofs obtained from the collected Twitter datasets. These equations also pose as major discourses but should not be seen as a derogatory presentation intended to abandon outright or point out drawbacks in scholarship as they are meant to be rigorous in quantitative expressions among mathematicians and (theoretical) physicists. These formulated equations represent the attempts made by the Researcher to make sense of the theorized (logic of) relationships among variables and their values to quantize.

While one might argue that perfect equivalence between solutions has not been achieved by relying on what is largely a pseudo-empirical approach (mathematical

modeling and data simulations), this should not be a reason to dismiss the representations entirely. What should be considered is that all knowledge limitations encountered have required adjustments to postulate other network phenomena involved and to show tangibility. Thus, the Researcher proposes that rigor has to be further investigated through a follow-up inquiry while presumption of the Researcher's best knowledge about this study should be considered unequivocal.

The work of Shahi et al. (2021, p. 13) demonstrated a very comprehensive Twitter network analysis. Although the results were impressive, they do not pan out to answer questions regarding: (1) locality of misinformation; (2) parallel processes involved; and (3) detection thresholds. So, the only other way to find answers will be the assumption of quantum processes. Quantum entanglement (inside complex networks) has been theorized using mathematical equations (Adesso et al., 2006). However, this study traces the phenomenon from the hard-fast rule of network analysis while adding the ingrained complexities that brings forth "quantumness".

The equations below are called upon to produce global measurements (**Equation 1 through Equation 4**) and 'local' (per node) measurements (**Equation 5 through Equation 9**) of mass and energy.

Global Equation 1: Bot Mass (Kg) in the Network

$$= \frac{\text{Number of Bot and Human Interactions} \times \text{Number of False Tweets}}{\text{Network Density}} \times 3.19 \times 10^{-38} \text{ Kg}$$

Global Equation 2: Quantization of Bot Energy (Joules) in the Network

$$= [\text{Bot Mass} \times (\text{Coupling Strength} \times \text{Matrix Power of Eigendecomposition})] \times 8.98755179 \times 10^{16} \text{ m}^2 / \text{s}^2$$

Global Equation 3: Quantization of Energy in Network (Joules)

$$= \frac{\text{von Neumann Graph Entropy Evolution}}{\text{Schrödinger Eigenstates Evolution}} \times (1.38064 \times 10^{-23} \text{ J/K} \times 300 \text{ K}) \times 0.69314718055995$$

Global Equation 4: Virality of Bots in the Network

$$= \text{Average Bot Energy} \quad (\text{Average Energy in Network})$$

Local Equation 5: Critical Threshold per Node before Node Virality

$$= \frac{\text{Energy Equivalent} \times \text{Average of Before and After Percolation Centrality}}{\text{Energy in the Network}} \times \text{Energy in the Network}$$

Local Equation 6: Critical Threshold per Node after Node Virality

$$= \frac{\text{Energy Equivalent} \times \text{Average of Before and After Percolation Centrality}}{\text{Energy in the Network}} \times \text{Virality of Bots} \times \text{Energy in the Network}$$

Local Equation 7: Mass Equivalent (Kg) per Node

$$= \frac{\text{Degree}}{\text{Network Density}} \times 3.19 \times 10^{-38} \text{ Kg}$$

Local Equation 8: Energy Equivalent (Joules) per Node

$$= \text{Mass Equivalent (Kg)} \times 8.98755179 \times 10^{16} \text{ m}^2 / \text{s}^2 \times \text{Average Energy in Network}$$

Local Equation 9: Phase Factor (adapted from Staples et al., 2011, p. 5)

$$\beta = \sqrt{\frac{2T}{mc^2}}$$

$$\beta = \sqrt{\frac{2(\text{Average Energy in Network})}{\text{Mass Equivalent (Kg) per Node} \times 8.98755179 \times 10^{16} \text{ m}^2 / \text{s}^2}}$$

Schematic Representations

The subprocesses illustrated below are accounted for in **Equation 2** and **Equation 9**.

Figure 21. Theorized node synchronization and quantum network dynamics.

The classical model proposed by Shannon-Weaver in 1949 (Al-Fedaghi, 2012) is respected for its point-to-point transmission of information in network analysis. The drawbacks, if one is to adopt the constructs faithfully, are unidirectionality of flow rather than indirect and static and linear representation of node relationships (e.g., 2D graphs) with bimodal activity (encoder and decoder). Expected through this study, the introduction of provisional models (Figure 21 through Figure 24) will overturn the long-held assumption of information transmission. Furthermore, laminating Shannon and Weaver's seminal works that founded the contemporary understanding of the constructs of communication within a quantum philosophy would be a bold stroke, albeit contestable. It is a choice not to inherit its limitations.

Information processing (message to signals and reversibility) is remarkable in the Shannon-Weaver model, although entirely dependent to the structural capacity of reference systems. So, the reconciliation consists of taking the investigation of organization (topology), processes and conditions (dynamics) into the domain of quantum mechanics. Within this scientific framework, "superpositioning" and "entanglement" are *bona fide* anomalies. Signaling is patronized and exaggerated to oscillations, but is grounded in the changes of (eigen)state and energy with eigenvalues. Node states are analogous to quantum states. Therefore, realities (the outcomes) are mixed instead of performing a split function: encoder and decoder are joined as a complex.

Proving "quantum coupling" is compelling in the picture conceptualized. Information transmission is through synchronization of signals (Figure 21) by non-Gaussian fluctuations between nodes (e.g., intermittent jumps, anomalous diffusion). Doing so yields better understanding as to why the distribution of density decay has a heavy tail (Zheng et al., 2021), and how equilibrium is reached at "minimum-

uncertainty states.” The latter is the time that the (mass and energy) distributions become Gaussian (Bera et al., 2019, p. 1853). The chaotic co-entanglement of nodes is either direct or indirect. Numerous signals collide at this time while cascading (mis)information. States that arise from a Gaussian distribution are resonated in harmonic wave packets (Bera et al., 2019 p. 1851), but oscillations vary from time to time. Future patterns emerge and evolve in a probabilistic turnover of events. Therefore, variabilities are the result of the Markovian process (Gzyl, 2021). Oscillations are an emergent property of adaptive systems without the need for periodicity in a regulatory process (Cheong & Levchenko, 2010). A chain of events happens every time nodes are brought to an energy spectrum inflected by the mass of information presented to them.

Oscillations carry high information content based on the application of Fourier transform shown in sine waves (Pythontic.com, 2020) and can breach spaces (Cheong & Levchenko, 2010, pp. 667-668). Thereby, “ephaptic coupling” is brought into context despite the fact that it has initially been proposed in biological systems drawn on the FitzHugh-Nagumo model of neuron excitation (Doulcier, 2019). System complexity is remarkable due to process redundancies (Faghieh et al., 2010.). Interactions of nodes have been thought to occur between their nearest neighbors, but could actually happen in the shared space. Although it has been observed that oscillations are grounded in the Poisson process on time intervals, decoherence pattern should be factored in (Sheheitli & Jirsa, 2020, pp. 600-606).

A unique feature of complex systems is synchronization. Here, nodes can be thought of as “self-sustained oscillators that interact [*with one another*]” (Rodrigues, 2019, p. 191) in which its purpose is arguably for energy waves detection or an energy footprint during state transitions. This is seen as initial entry point for pulling out a

discourse on the representation of complex networks by (af)fixing a novel, integrative framework to compliment the picture of the “mass-energy-information equivalence” introduced by Vopson (2019, p. 3) into the plausibility of seizing more explanations about how misinformation (aside from what construes after information genesis) jumps into virality with reference to the state-to-state transition of nodes (i.e. situating the diffusion curve, critical mass, and polarization within their network), and supersedes the order of information flow with quantum and network theories through quantization of (as opposed to largely denominating) spatio-temporal events, e.g., the metamorphosis of “COVID-19 infodemic” on Twitter.

Node oscillations are autoconfigured to the interaction with their direct neighbors during synchronization (Pikovsky et al., 2003 cited in Rodrigues, 2019). Within this theoretical construct, hubs form due to synchronization of the resonated natural (native) frequencies as oscillators. Nodes connect “...by the sine of their phase differences” (Rodrigues, 2019, p. 15).

Based on the Kuramoto model, evolution of nodes takes place in the phases of oscillation (Rodrigues et al., 2016 cited in Rodrigues, 2019). Phase transition to synchronization is either in first-order or second-order. The former occurs in scale-free networks, where hub oscillations are much faster compared to adjacent nodes, but natural frequency and number of connections are correlated (e.g., homogenous recruitments), while the latter occurs if nodes oscillate independently without regard for network structure.

The above would suggest rogue agents interplaying (e.g., internodal rewiring by bots) or targeted attacks. The presence of central nodes is a factor (i.e., centrality dictates the fate of synchronization and connectivity thereafter), but this is actually a concern for the “critical coupling strength” especially between homogenous nodes.

However, the Twitter network is heterogeneous rather than homogeneous and yet nodes still synchronize at a surprising magnitude. A key dramatic feature of virality starts at “explosive synchronization” (Rodrigues et al., 2016, pp. 17-18) of nodes.

Communication within a complex network, in accordance with Kuramoto simulation in Python (Damicelli, 2021), is theorized on coupled oscillations of nodes (Millán et al., 2020, p. 1) or clock-like synchronization. Proof of this concept are the “topological dynamical signals” (Barbarossa & Sardellitti, 2019 cited in Millán et al., 2020, p. 1) or flux generated during their interactions. However, an alternative consideration for looking into topological dynamics (signaling at the juncture of nodes) has been proposed receiving increasing attention among network scientists. Collectively, the investigation of dynamical processes relies on a higher-order Kuramoto framework. This is representing “simplicial complexes” (2 or more nodes interacting) using profound dimensionality (Millán et al., 2020, p. 2).

Moreover, “adaptive coupling” has been considered here, and is consequential to the projected dynamics on the nodes and triangles from their links. Indeed, synchronization is inducible (the same is true on the other end, desynchronization). In explosive synchronization, “simultaneous discontinuous transition” of dynamics occurs from coupling while in simple synchronization, there are “continuous phase transitions” (Millán et al., 2020, pp. 2, 5). The insights that can be drawn are the *bona fide* discourses for the hallmark features of synchronization from the emergence (and dissipation) of energy wavelengths (e.g., harmonic, sine), and periodicity of entanglement corresponding to viral misinformation spread.

Entanglements can randomly emerge or be fabricated (e.g., bot mediation) in the information layer and where entropy accentuates and misinformation can be repurposed, lost, or iterated. Aggressive (rogue as opposed to plain egocentric) nodes

are capable of recruiting naive nodes regardless of locality and convert them into brewing hubs of misinformation. These nodes are autopoietic, meaning they can recover per cycle with almost perpetual redundancy under state transitions ($<1, 1, >1$). Moreover, uncertainty (variability) of node states in churning out misinformation and their entanglements in the “Twitterverse” depends largely on the extent of chaos induced by the flooding of misinformation until threshold is overcome and critical mass is achieved. Nodes pick up the spillover of misinformation at vulnerable intra- and inter-phases.

Figure 22. Theorized intranodal and internodal spatiotemporal neo-dynamics.

The complexities shown above are milled out into pseudo empirical measures of node dynamics inside the Twitter network through the Kuramoto model of synchronization and the wave phenomenon and eigenstates according to Schrödinger equation. Figure 22 is investigated using two formulaic representations: **Equation 1** and **Equation 3**. It is assumed that the course of local disorder changes (sub)network topology by the contagion message from infected communities and entanglements grow scale-free with much bifurcated complexity to neighboring communities or periphery.

In Figure 22, the functional feature of classical entanglement ensues from the coupling of layers and the non-additive interactions that arise (Brummitt et al., 2012, p. 1). The cascade condition answers the query “how multiplexity facilitates cascades” (Brummitt et al., 2012, pp. 2-3) in two branching processes: along the layer, “ignoring activations by multiple active neighbors” but by single active node; and across the layer by the “off-diagonals” or “additional activation channel,” which maximizes the cascade regions, particular to feedback routes. The “coupling” of nodes between layers increases their susceptibility (Brummitt et al., 2012, p. 4) to cooperate over the misinformation despite a non-random distribution (Goh, 2012, p. 15).

The value of (mis)information expressed in time is contingent to direction of flow. Every bit of information proceeds and is retrieved with time. Moreover, there is no master clock for the “Twitterverse.” It is notoriously punctuated by the expanding and incompressible space that information builds and collapses. Thus, time is ‘non-periodic’ (continuous) discord of finite events, and should be measured within the span of the opening and closing of spaces (e.g., snipping the irregular localization of information at its peak). However, this occurs at the brink demanding analytics to run

after both information (mass) and state (energy) fluctuations. To the knowledge of the investigator, such conjecture has never been introduced for network analysis.

We can obtain insights from “A Large Ion Collider Experiment” (ALICE) at the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN) in Geneva, Switzerland regarding the physics of particle detection using the Time Projection Chamber (TPC) for describing the nature of information as a state of matter, specifically depicted by the flow velocity of electrons. Specifically, ALICE-TPC tracks the density effects of moving particles in a field of energy waves. Bits of information behave as expected of particles. They move against the forces of the digital spaces of the “Twitterverse” existing in duality: possessing mass and expressing waves of energy (Farina, 2017). The latter property is quantized using the nonrelativistic Schrödinger equation (Sudiarta & Geldart, 2007) and characterized further using Born’s probability amplitude (measured by the square of the magnitude of the wavefunction, ψ^2 cited in Farina, 2017).

Figure 23. Theorized misinformation processing and recodification.

Misinformation can be claimed according to the novelty in principal components when compared with any former information. Critical mass is accountable under the theoretical conversion of information bytes and is arbitrary on threshold. The 'gating mechanism' for the uptake and transmission of information is controlled or de-escalated and will be theorized by features of nodal oscillation and co-entanglements of the following: (1) local critical mass and energy flux in the spatiotemporal network, (2) misinformation pooling (interspaced with time to chaos and time to randomness) and energy dissipation.

Moreover, Figure 23 has been conceptualized based on Information Theory, Second-order Cybernetics, Actor-Network Theory, Critical Mass Theory, and Spiral of Silence Theory (for the quiescence of nodes until critical mass); measurements by **Equation 3, Equation 7, Equation 8.**

Since bots and humans on Twitter have symmetry of agency as autonomous objects behind misinformation spread and virality, Actor-Network Theory or ANT is applicable. The social theory materializes from individual agent relationships (human actors are “actants” and nonhuman analogues are nonindividual entities powered by algorithms and software) within networks by distribution, homogeneity, and proximity (Hajli et al., 2021) or centrality. ANT examines the actors, interactions, meanings, and actions inside social media networks. More importantly, ANT allows deeper inquiring, first about the relationship between actors and second, the tweet (hyper)production by socially intelligent bots on Twitter from machine and deep learning.

There is always cooperation between bots and humans: spammers and hackers manipulate other bots “to appeal to current profiles” and to produce exaggerated effects that are severe like panic and anxiety about COVID-19 (Chakraborty et al., 2020; Shi et al., 2020 cited in Hajli et al., 2021). Moreover, personal account creation is hard to automate for bots so that it will require a human user to interact with a Web-based interface and to confirm being human, e.g., with CAPTCHAs and/or verifications via email and SMS (Wang, Angarita, & Renna, 2018). Therefore, bots are fully autonomous if they can: (a) automatically create accounts on social media platforms; (b) adapt to comply with changes in the social media platforms; and (c) detect and understand content for their objectives (Wang, Angarita, & Renna, 2018). These limitations are overcome by human actions and the introduction of misinformation and disinformation in the network begins through them with bots.

Although the material study of Twitter bots beckons at the language level within an ANT scope (Mattozzi, 2019 cited in Hajli et al., 2021), their capabilities are not limited to transmission of content (where meanings are preserved) rather they can initiate or auto transform the content at the action level (AI-driven) and further content

uncertainty is resonated (collective abstract to concrete replication or multiplex of actants to multiplicity of actors versus the direct abstract to concrete or actants to actors) at the interaction level. Arguably, this is not Latour's (2005 cited in Hajli et al., 2021) conception of the intermediary role of ANT between agents, i.e., meanings transported without transformation.

A network is simply a collection of human and non-human objects behaving interdependently affecting each other through social media technology. Twitter bots, by artificial intelligence, are superorganisms capable of (a) generating and posting content that refabricates reality into many possible meanings (visual and linguistic) linked to objects within networks, (b) interacting with humans like "actants," (c) altering the behavior of those actants (even other bot entities), and (d) evolving from programmed activity by learning from every encounter with actants. In addition, ANT does capture "**semiotic relationality**" where actants and entities define and shape one another through tweets, "**heterogeneity**" by type of bot and human user communities, and "**materiality**" of actants by characteristics embedded into their networks defining the properties (Hajli et al., 2021).

Hence, detection of bots can be made using ANT according to basic characteristics of bots that set them apart from humans by their malicious activity pattern. In fact, ANT is a "theory and methodology combined" (Walsham, 1997 in Hajli et al., 2021). Actions of agents are the result content dissemination (tweet patterns), deliberation of content (decoding in the user which is attributed to intelligence for information processing), and manipulation (disinformation rather than misinformation) which should be unique among bots (Hajli et al., 2021) based on the scale of contents generated over a short period of time. Content manipulation defines malicious agents, but such detection heavily relies on available databases to run fact-checking.

In this study, tweets were not scrutinized as to whether they generate further misinformation or disinformation. Attention was on low-credibility tweet diffusion and characterization of bots because bots are primary sources and disseminators of misinformation (e.g., fake news) and disinformation (Hajli et al., 2021) and each is a “who,” as opposed to “it,” assumes a capable human agency (existing behind a Twitter account) on information generation and transmission under ANT.

However, humans surpass bots’ level of credibility, but bots have a significant impact when shaping public opinion on social media, for example, they can make an opinion from a genuine source appear false and cut-off disagreeing users (Ross et al., 2019 cited in Hajli et al., 2021) and even blackmail them. Bots nudge users to concerted actions thus ending the ‘spiral of silence’ too soon. ANT gives credit to AI powering these agent-entities who become key player actors in the Twitter network “...who are linked by associations of heterogeneous networks of aligned interests” (Walsham, 1997 cited in Hajli et al., 2021). The capability of bots to find and to form connections with intelligent users (regardless of whether they are humans or bots) and to remain ubiquitous at times is an advantage over humans.

The sophistication of bots is described in their scientifically advanced capacity—the imitation of human online behavior on the activity level (e.g., production of original content for a specific topic by retweets of existing content or tweets about articles or websites elicited from predefined keywords out of crawling the internet, answering to comments in a reasonable manner, discussing topics with other users) rather than on the frequency of interaction with users as the communication pattern of interest (Assenmacher et al., 2020). These bots can work in groups (bot nets) and spread spam, political (disinformation) campaigns or “dystopian media narratives”, etc. directed by a “herder” (Assenmacher et al., 2020). Bots interact with each other (form

clusters) to make convincing human-like dynamics via the “Responder” bot (Assenmacher et al., 2020).

Misinformation processing is not just uniquely unconventional but also rather enigmatic (not fully understood in the literature). It has classical representations of information transmission (e.g., either in the form of undirected or directed graph), but intrinsic processes are fuzzy (e.g., eigenstates) that require a quantum representation.

First-order and second-order cybernetics may be overridden (dysregulated) by the fluidized mass of information (central tendencies are relative). Critical mass and the mutation of content are beyond the capacity of the feedback mechanisms between nodes. Bots collectively move the mass of information to and from human users. Since mass quantizes into energy, the uncertainty does not come solely from information processing and recoding, but also from the energy propagated during communication.

Cybernetics applied to misinformation spread through influential nodes is agency-determined in terms of its capacity to have (a period of) “stability” and “uncertainty reduction” (Yolles, 2021) when making a connection. The former refers to the horizontal process (e.g., clique formation) while the latter is the vertical process (e.g., from stochastic to a deterministic contagion spreader). Unfortunately, without energy perturbations (which cause instability and uncertainty), these processes cannot continue. Calculation of the von Neumann entropy will underscore the quantum states for nonlinearity of system components (Wu et al., 2019) and processes with the collapse of the wavefunction in **Equation 3**. However, misinformation is the substrate and product of the dynamics. So, **Equation 7** and **Equation 8** will measure the capacity of a node in the following order: assuming its mass through misinformation (materialization); oscillating with the transmission of misinformation at a certain energy

level (dematerialization) and aspatial (skewed) distribution; and salvaging energy back to mass condensed at a new location (centrality shifts).

Entanglements and superpositioning are products of a myriad of (co)incidental (temporal) relationships that are nevertheless moving towards being purposely structured (the spatial aspect of visualization using graph theory) in the lens of ANT. While functionality is supposedly inherent as programmed (*a priori*), it is a regulated cause and effect of dynamics within a structural loop (through cybernetics) or field (through quantum mechanics). Instead of loosening definitions and moving out of context, the phenomenon of misinformation spread and virality by actors (humans and bots) would have lenses condensing by inter definitions which are articulating a grasp of dimensions between quantum mechanics and theories relevant to understanding complex networks.

Figure 24. Theorized sequence of events leading to virality.

Based on literature, misinformation spreads in the following sequence of events: first, the network (targeted) is exposed to misinformation from an external source and is considered infected if a node shares it; second, internal exposure happens at a burst; third, nodes relay misinformation to other nodes proceeding to an

internal infection; and fourth, the contagion (misinformation) grows as external and internal exposures continue (Wang et al., 2018). On the other hand, this study challenges the stated causality.

It can be queried that the time series simulation of wave collapse is more on the conversion of one state to another (Polson, 2021a, 2021b). Multiplicity of wave ascents and descents showcase the theorized mass into energy. Rossegger's (2009, p. 8) explication of Enrico Fermi's equation about velocity as the culprit behind energy loss in the system, which can create more intense disruptive effects in a series of dramatic changes (Rossegger, 2009, p. 80), seems to be consistent with real world findings by WHO (2021d) about the viral propagation including amplification of misinformation via mainstream media. The space charge deviation model in Rossegger's (2009, p. 80) can be modified as shown in Figure 24. **Equation 4** through **Equation 6** assert the energy influx and outflux and the occurrence of "virality".

The particle and wave metaphor about the activity of nodes suits the uncertainty of their states if entangled and the randomness of such uncertainty—the regal spookiness of quantum states. The mass equivalence of information converts into energy at the speed of light (Vopson, 2019). Energy loss by decay is due to velocity instead of the mass according to Rossegger (2009, p. 8), where the Lorentz force drives the movement of particles (inside a vacuum) with respect to mass (Rossegger, 2009, p. 15) and direction by its angle due to drift velocity (Rossegger, 2009, p. 23). Velocity is achieved from information transmission (Figure 24). On the other hand, it is hard to contest this using the model by Vopson (2019) because the formulaic representations were drawn from different experiments.

The "bra-ket notation" for the wavefunction vectors of misinformation in Hilbert space, which represent the projection or length (Hossenfelder, 2020a) of spread of the

base energy of nodes and edges raised to their complex number conjugates (*), is represented as:

$$\langle mis | information \rangle = node_1 edge_1^* + node_2 edge_2^* + node_3 edge_3^* + \dots n^{th}$$

According to Born's rule, the probability of energy wave collapse (decay) when nodes are highly seeding (most influential) across the network graph can be represented as:

$$\begin{aligned} \langle layer | energy \rangle^2 &= node_1 node_1^* + node_2 node_2^* + node_3 node_3^* + \dots n^{th} \\ &= 1 \text{ (base state)} \end{aligned}$$

Theoretical superpositioning of nodes (measured by energy states) assumes coherence (Hossenfelder, 2020b) because they are correlated. The correlated nodes between clusters are raised to the phase of oscillation (θ) of the other pair. This can be represented as:

$$\begin{aligned} |energy \rangle &= node_1 |eigenvalue_1 \rangle + node_2 |eigenvalue_2 \rangle \\ &= \sqrt{1/2} |eigenvalue_1 \rangle + \sqrt{1/2} e^{i\theta} |eigenvalue_2 \rangle \end{aligned}$$

The density matrix of the above will be:

$$\rho = |energy\rangle\langle energy| = \begin{bmatrix} eigenvalue_1 eigenvalue_1^* & eigenvalue_1 eigenvalue_2^* \\ eigenvalue_2 eigenvalue_1^* & eigenvalue_2 eigenvalue_2^* \end{bmatrix}$$

Issues in Visual and Sonic Representations

Detection of false positive Twitter bots or false negative genuine human accounts with Botometer[®] is a well-known limitation. However, bot characteristics agreed with the most recent literature (Bruno et al., 2022).

The number of overlapping edges is a known problem in complex visualizations of multiplex graphs resulting in incomprehensible layouts and a lot of time spent in resolving issues. These issues are intra-layer overdrawing and inter-layer overdrawing. The former is solved by increasing edge transparency based on density and thresholding. The latter requires redistribution of edges and manual configuration of individual arc heights. Cognitive load, the interpretation and understanding of network complexity, is overwhelming to deal with in terms of domain, data, and visual complexity. There is a chance that details will be overlooked. When embedding and projecting the dynamic features of vertices and edges in the graph layout (or to a point at which it is necessary to reduce the graph into manageable vector space/dimensions), many topological properties (mostly key parts) are lost. (Škrlj et al., 2019)

Investigator bias (cultural and contextual) in mining, annotation, sampling, and classifying tweets constitutes a limitation (Shahi et al., 2021) considering that Twitter datasets have multilingual corpus on various topics (Memon & Carley, 2020). This may be overcome by studying the mass and energy equivalent of misinformation.

Twitter datasets are easily skewed and the skewing (Pfeffer et al., 2019) is caused by biases (e.g., built into the characteristics of the platform) and manipulation or tampering data on the platform including the analysis (Pfeffer et al., 2018). Bots (5-9%) and spammers have a large impact on the quality of sampled tweets collected by APIs (Morstatter et al., 2016). These agents are “content polluters” (Liu et al., 2016, p. 139) in consideration of the Pareto Principle: 80% of information is generated by 20% of the users, yet there is not much data to analyze (big-data paradox) about them (Liu et al., 2016).

A lot of data noises and limitations exist due to the fact that sampling techniques used were deterministic: search API (by tweets available in the past 7 days raising a problem of data attrition); sampled stream (by hashtags); filtered stream (by keywords); and graphs and cascades (Wu et al., 2020). In addition, there are missing social data, e.g., data from sampled graphs were shown with decreased edge weights or have disappeared while topological and contextual distortions are common from sampled cascades (Wu et al., p. 716). Representativeness is another issue (Ahmed, 2015).

Although selection bias is subjective, deleted tweets were unreported in datasets. Data cleaning and statistical significance are technical in nature, but are still biases. There is this black box selection bias either committed from non-disclosure of the process of organizing the dataset or the way algorithms were run to obtain the dataset on Twitter and how they can be replicated. (Potting, 2016, pp.18-26)

Data sonification undergoes many distortions mainly by (1) fundamental perception of visualized data versus its audition and (2) subjectivity in audition, noise during “cross talks,” musical affinities of coders as source of biases, and meaning uncertainty due to interdisciplinary interpretations: artistic and scientific (Neuhoff, 2019, p. 327).

Chapter IV

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Simulation and modeling were largely utilized together with descriptive (during data exploration), correlational (relationships between bots, humans, and tweets were studied with models and actual data), and inferential (i.e., based on trends) analyses of results.

Methods

To answer the research questions, comprehensive data representation and analytics were implemented. They go by (1) **Network Analysis**, which included: (a) Network Centralities, (b) Community Detection, and (c) Quantization by Energy and Mass Equations based on Vopson's (2019) Model, (2) **Network Visualization**, (3) **Dynamic Node Synchronizations by Kuramoto Model Simulation**, (4) **Critical Mass and Energy Distributions by Wavefunction Simulation**, and (5) **Data Sonification**.

Procedures

The data processing pipeline (Figure 25) was written in [Python 3.9.0](#), an open-source programming language, and was implemented in [Jupyter Notebook](#) locally using a laptop computer and then archived on GitHub as “[COVID-19 infodemics](#)” under “[jphernandezrn](#)” (Hernandez, 2021). Working with **Git files** and making the GitHub repository were implemented according to online video tutorials by Markham (2014). Any later code editing was performed in [Microsoft Visual Studio Code 1.67.0](#).

Datasets were (1) aggregated, (2) visualized, (3) fed into simulations, (4) converted into sound, and (5) analyzed logically. Theoretical equations were codified and GitHub source codes from publicly shared repositories are ‘forked’ (copied). These codes were repurposed to perform automated, data-driven analytics rather than hard-coding for every function outputs. Machine learning algorithms were integrated in the pipeline. Thus, fetching values manually would not have been suitable. Moreover, with data-driven code implementations, calculations are not bounded with any data cap. So, adding more data is not a problem. The pipeline is designed to handle big data.

The installation package for 64-bit Windows was downloaded from Python Software Foundation (2020) using the tutorial by Parisi (2020) on YouTube. A number of [dependencies](#) were required, namely: (1) **Jupyter Notebook**, (2) **Requests** (HTTP library), (3) **Pandas**, (4) **NumPy**, (5) **Matplotlib**, (6) **NetworkX**, (7) **Nxviz**, (8) **Python-Louvain**, (9) **Py3plex**, (10) **Kuramoto**, (11) **Seaborn**, (12) **Sklearn**, (13) **SciPy**, (14) **Numba**, (15) **July**, (16) **Moment**, and (17) **Miditime**. Microsoft C++ 14.0 (for graph build tools on Windows) was also installed.

The raw datasets were collected from [Hoaxy[®] Beta](#) (Observatory on Social Media, 2022), after obtaining the ‘**Twitter API Keys**’ (consumer key, consumer secret key) and ‘**Authentication Tokens**’ (access token, access token secret) according to the steps shown by Shakarami (2021) on YouTube.

Twitter datasets were exported from Hoaxy[®] website using the target phrases “**COVID vaccine is not safe**,” “**COVID19 vaccine**,” and “**Vaccine Rollout**”. These were according to trending hashtags in 2021 at Symplur.com. Twitter dataset covered tweets created from May 17, 2021 until November 26, 2021 from two data collection points: October 20, 2021 and November 27, 2021. However, data visualization was targeted until December 30, 2021, which means arbitrary values were generated automatically by the heatmap library after November 27, 2021. This may be construed (roughly) as a forecast.

The **csv files** were preprocessed for aggregation into one file as raw data in the GitHub subdirectory “[./raw_data](#)” of “**COVID-19_infodemics**” using “**correlate-data.py**”. The final dataset can be found on the “[./dataset directory](#)” and is named: “**core_data.csv**”.

Figure 25. Automated Data Acquisition Pipeline (Phase 2).

Phase 2 presents data mining for bots generating misinformation with tweets through Hoaxy® and bot classification through Botometer® implemented via algorithms in Python language, i.e., [correlate-data.py](#). Phase 2 also presents the number of low-credibility tweets (misinformation). Specifically, tweet mining and bot detection are performed through Hoaxy® beta (Observatory on Social Media, 2022), an online fact-

checking and network visualization tool developed by Shao et al. (2016) at Indiana University.

Network graphs were visualized using [NetworkX](#). Although [Py3plex](#) (Škrlić, 2021) is better since it has full functionality most especially visualization of network decomposition and aggregation up to >10 layers with $\geq 10,000$ nodes as compared to other tools (Škrlić et al., 2019, pp. 5-7, 9), still “NetworkX provides many generator functions and facilities to read and write graphs in many formats” (Georgiev, 2014, p. 13) and the network graphs in this study do not contain “100M/1B edges” (Georgiev, 2014, p. 8).

Network dynamics on the basis of excitation (induced) is instrumental in the following: (1) uncovering the broad natural or resonant frequencies (Beebe & Moss, 2021) by peaks and their shape by direction of peaks (Siemens Digital Industries Software, 2020b); and (2) tracing where they materialize. Bringing nodes to an excited state was accomplished in this study by implementing the Kuramoto model for estimating the coupling strength of node during synchronization (Damicelli, 2021); measuring centralities (especially after percolation), demonstrating the wavefunction collapse or “reduction of the wave packet” (Information Philosopher, 2022) to a single eigenstate (Wikipedia, 2022c) using the Schrödinger equation, and further interpretations of energy projection from sonification spectrograms.

Sonification of the activity of influential nodes (i.e., by degree of connections) was considered to give a deeper perspective by exploiting “...the auditory system’s sensitivities to periodicities, to dynamic changes, and to patterns” and to allow situational awareness (Ballora et al., 2012, p. 1) on the interpretation of sound deviations. The richness of Twitter as data source is not only because of the sizable, structured data it has, but also for the expressive data (Jones & Gregson, 2014).

Figure 26. Post Tweet Mining Pipeline (Phase 3).

Phase 3 refers to the development and implementation of the analytics algorithm in Jupyter Notebook ([Paper Implementation.ipynb](#)), namely: (1) network analysis; (2) network visualization; (3) simulation of network dynamics and energy distribution from data; and (4) data sonification after signal processing. The implementation of the comprehensive analytics verified super spreaders and provided an opportunity to forecast spread of misinformation.

Instrumentation

Tweet mining and bot detection were performed through Hoaxy[®] Beta (Observatory on Social Media, 2022), an online fact-checking and network visualization tool developed by Shao et al. (2016) at Indiana University. The PhET interactive simulator: "[Quantum Tunneling and Wave Packets](#)" (University of Colorado, 2022) was used to reproduce the oscillations and to confirm such behavior. Two statistical instruments were used, namely correlations and ANOVA to test the difference of the variables. On the other hand, [DAW Pro Tools HD 12](#) (third-party plugins include [Celemony Melodyne 4](#), [Kontakt 5 Player](#), and [Air Music Tech Xpand!2](#)) and [Audacity[®] 3.1.3](#) were required for sonification (parameter mapping) and analysis respectively. Parameter mapping involved scoring all bot activities with musical tones according to crescendo, plateau, and decrescendo patterns.

Analyses

Descriptive, correlational, and inferential analyses of data were performed separately. Post-Python statistical tests were done in Microsoft[®] Excel[®] 2019 and reported using the 7th edition of The American Psychological Association (APA) style and all other formatting (Bhandari, 2022; American Psychological Association, 2020). The level of significance is .05 alpha. Extrapolations were derived from graphs, equations, and wavefunction simulations.

Hoaxy[®] and Botometer[®] provided the bot scores to differentiate Twitter bots from humans. There is no consensus about the best cut-off for Twitter bot detection in the scientific literature. Threshold scores selected were either .30, .43, .50, .70, .75, or .80 on a caveat that they influence directly the number of bots to find (Martini et al., 2021). However, a confidence threshold of .75 is more acceptable (Memon & Carley, 2020, p. 4), but this is very tight. Bot detection algorithms are not perfectly accurate (Cresci et al. 2017 cited in Yang et al., 2020).

With BotometerLite[®], .50 is a reasonable threshold (Yang et al., 2020). Although Hoaxy[®] was the detection tool in this study, Botometer[®] still performed the bot score calculations (Observatory on Social Media, 2022) and has been used in previous studies (Chang et al., 2021; Broniatowski et al. 2018; Wojcik et al., 2018). Threshold was set at .43 and the rules set were “if **from_user_botscore** $\geq$.43 then **from_user_screen_name** is bot” and “if **to_user_screen_name** $\geq$.43 then **to_user_id** is bot. Thus, the expected bot detection through Botometer[®] is between 92% to 93% (Bruno et al., 2022).

[Botometer[®] version 4 API](#) "english" with a complete automation probability (CAP) at .80 was used to classify bots (Yang, 2020). CAP works according to Bayes' theorem, where an estimate is made on the overall prevalence of bots in order to balance false positives with false negatives (Observatory on Social Media, 2022).

The following are the types of bots: (1) “**Astroturf**” are “political bots and accounts involved in follow trains that systematically delete content” (Observatory on Social Media, 2022) often as propaganda bots (Powers & Kounalakis, 2017, p. 16) or bots in an echo-chamber which can aid network polarization (Gorodnichenko et al., 2021); (2) “**fake follower**” or “bots purchased to increase follower counts” (Observatory on Social Media, 2022); (3) “**financial**” or “bots that post using cashtags”

(Observatory on Social Media, 2022); (4) **“other”** or “miscellaneous other bots obtained from manual annotation, user feedback, etc.” (Observatory on Social Media, 2022); (5) **“self-declared”** or “bots [*categorized*] from botwiki.org,” and (6) **“spammer”** or “accounts labeled as spambots” (Observatory on Social Media, 2022) with bot scores .00, 4.1, 1.5, 4.7, 3.2, and 2.8 respectively (Yang, 2020). Account is a **“private account”** when no information is extractable because they are protected Twitter accounts. Bot scores ranging from .485 to .988 would suggest **hybrid bots**—these are “...partially automated and partially controlled by humans” (Chang et al., 2021, p. 11).

Chapter V

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Some new literatures were cited here to support the results and discussions.

Research Question 1: What type of tweets occurred with the topics: “**COVID vaccine is not safe,**” “**COVID19 vaccine,**” and “**Vaccine Rollout**” from May 17, 2021 through November 26, 2021?

For the knowledge of the Communication Scholars and the intended dissemination of this study, let it be known that misinformation spreads through replies than retweets. The cycle breaks off about every 3 months. Twitter bots were continually active. However, bots that burst in activity had a shorter period which, more importantly, confirmed the findings by Yang et al. (2020). The ‘core dataset’ (tweets based on “**COVID vaccine is not safe,**” “**COVID19 vaccine,**” and “**Vaccine Rollout**”) were only 1381.

Table 1. Codes for aggregating and classifying data (correlate-data.py).

```
1. import pandas as pd
2. import json
3. import os
4. import botometer
5.
6.
7.
8.
```

```

9. raw_dataset_dir = "./raw_data/"
10. output_dir = "./dataset/"
11.
12.
13.
14.
15. # utils
16.
17.
18. def writeToFile(file_data, file_name):
19.     print("File written successfully!")
20.     with open(file_name, 'w') as outfile:
21.         data = json.dumps(file_data, separators=(',', ':'))
22.         outfile.write(data)
23.
24.
25. def classifyBot(botometer_data):
26.     classification = "blank"
27.     baseline_score = 0;
28.     classifications =
["astroturf", "fake_follower", "financial", "other", "self_declared", "spammer"]
29.
30.     if "display_scores" in botometer_data:
31.
32.
33.         for bot_type in classifications:
34.             bx = botometer_data["display_scores"]["english"][bot_type]
35.             if baseline_score < bx:
36.                 classification = bot_type
37.
38.     return classification
39.
40.
41. # botometer API
42.
43.
44. rapidapi_key =
"d9fa466601msh8b4786e05eda027p1d321bjsnef6f552e3278"
45. twitter_app_auth = {
46.     'consumer_key': '8d2J3nLhNpWyBlizFtidvoQyB',
47.     'consumer_secret':
'i3diRmOQVT74wWSPeRatDvEoijnTfNeRrjOUOXmNWl8T6815SY',
48.     'access_token': '1418799546583429122-
83GskPvSAyL6y676F23nnedvoAl0jd',
49.     'access_token_secret':
'gx9ssHgKhi34P5PTCEGa2uworOs0DU2ZkZ2fT4aO5ugpZ'
50. }
51.
52.
53. bom = botometer.Botometer(wait_on_ratelimit=True,

```

```

54.         rapidapi_key=rapidapi_key,
55.         **twitter_app_auth)
56.
57.
58.
59.
60. # dataset files
61.
62.
63. raw_data = os.listdir(raw_dataset_dir)
64.
65.
66. # full data
67. full_data = pd.DataFrame()
68.
69.
70.
71.
72. print("=====")
73. print("Correlating Hoaxy CSV Data data...")
74. print("=====")
75.
76.
77. # merge all data
78.
79.
80. for datafile in raw_data:
81.     print("Processing ==> ",datafile)
82.     csv_to_df = pd.read_csv(raw_dataset_dir+datafile)
83.     full_data = pd.concat([full_data,csv_to_df])
84.
85.
86.
87.
88. # begin preprocessing
89.
90.
91.
92.
93. # remove empty columns
94. full_data = full_data.dropna(how='all' , axis=1, inplace=False)
95. # remove duplicate rows
96. full_data = full_data.drop_duplicates(subset=["from_user_id","to_user_id"])
97.
98.
99. # data botometer type columns
100.     full_data.insert(0, "from_user_bot_type", "", False)
101.     full_data.insert(0, "to_user_bot_type", "", False)
102.
103.

```

```

104.         # add columns for user types
105.         full_data.insert(0,"from_user_type","human", False)
106.         full_data.insert(0,"to_user_type","human", False)
107.
108.
109.
110.
111.         # TODO: classify which are bots and which are not bots & bot type
with botometer
112.
113.
114.         all_bots = {}
115.
116.
117.         for index, row in full_data.iterrows():
118.
119.             if row["from_user_botscore"] >= 0.43:
120.                 full_data.at[index,"from_user_type"] = "bot"
121.
122.                 if "@"+row["from_user_screen_name"] not in all_bots:
123.                     all_bots["@"+row["from_user_screen_name"]] = "blank"
124.
125.
126.
127.
128.             if row["to_user_botscore"] >= 0.43:
129.                 full_data.at[index,"to_user_type"] = "bot"
130.                 if "@"+row["to_user_screen_name"] not in all_bots:
131.                     all_bots["@"+row["to_user_screen_name"]] = "blank"
132.
133.
134.
135.         # loop through all bots for botometer classification
136.
137.
138.         for i,bot in enumerate(all_bots):
139.
140.
141.             try:
142.                 result = bom.check_account(bot)
143.                 bc = classifyBot(result)
144.                 all_bots[bot] = bc
145.                 print(bot,"==>",bc)
146.                 print(i,"/",len(all_bots))
147.             except:
148.                 print("Protected tweeter account, skipping:", bot)
149.                 all_bots[bot] = "private_account"
150.
151.
152.         writeToFile(all_bots,"bots_data.json")

```

```

153.
154.
155.     for index, row in full_data.iterrows():
156.
157.
158.         to_user_name = "@"+row["to_user_screen_name"]
159.         from_user_name = "@"+row["from_user_screen_name"]
160.
161.
162.         if from_user_name in all_bots:
163.             full_data.at[index,"from_user_bot_type"] =
all_bots[from_user_name]
164.
165.
166.         if to_user_name in all_bots:
167.             full_data.at[index,"to_user_bot_type"] =
all_bots[to_user_name]
168.
169.
170.
171.
172.
173.
174.
175.
176.
177.
178.     # output correlated data
179.     print(full_data)
180.     print("=====")
181.     print("Data preprocessing complete!")
182.     full_data.to_csv(output_dir+"core_data.csv")

```

After importing the processed datasets, each dataset is displayed as a Pandas Data frame. On this data frame, tweets and bots are classified as follows: “**from_user_type**” determines if an origin user account is bot or human; “**to_user_type**” determines if the destination user account is bot or human; “**from_user_bot_type**” specifies the type of bot account sending tweets; “**to_user_bot_type**” specifies the type of bot receiving tweets.

Bots were classified in the following manner: “**fake follower**” if bot increases follower counts (Observatory on Social Media, 2022); “**self-declared**” if bot matches any bots from botwiki.org (Observatory on Social Media, 2022); “**Astroturf**” if it is a political bot which typically “starts the follower train and encourages other users to comment, like, retweet, and follow each other” (Pope, 2019) and “systematically delete content” (Observatory on Social Media, 2022); “**spammer**” if the Twitter account was labeled as spambots from several datasets (Observatory on Social Media, 2022); “**financial**” if bot posts are using cashtags (Observatory on Social Media, 2022); “**other**” if bot does not fall into any former types; and “**private account**” if Twitter account had protected settings and timeline cannot be accessed.

Tweets were most of the time in the form of replies than of retweets (Figure 27). Generally, human users spread and amplify versus create misinformation on social media by reposting, retweeting, and replying (Vosoughi et al., 2018 cited in Tully et al., 2020). They are not likely to reply to misinformation. Instead, they tend to provide corrections after seeing other users’ corrections (Tully et al., 2020). However, human users may also have contributed to the spread of COVID-19 misinformation unknowingly (Himelein-Wachowiak et al., 2021).

A recent study found that 33% of top content sharers (the most influential nodes) from low-credibility sources were bots (Himelein-Wachowiak et al., 2021). Early in 2020, 45% of COVID-19–related tweets came from bots (Allyn, 2020 cited in Himelein-Wachowiak et al., 2021). Bots that are weaponized to spread vaccine misinformation have been known even before the COVID-19 pandemic (Broniatowski et al., 2018 cited in Himelein-Wachowiak et al., 2021). Almost 17% of bots were found to be most influential.

Between 53% and 66% of bots actively tweeted with hashtags such as “**coronavirus**,” “**covid19**,” and “**socialdistancing**” (Himelein-Wachowiak et al., 2021). Based on evidence of tweet production over 234 days (from January 1, 2020 to August 21, 2020), a population of 3953 bots have made 3.03 million tweets, which on average was 768.9 ($SD=1145.4$) per bot (Himelein-Wachowiak et al., 2021). However, in spite of the aforementioned statistics, bots contributed to the spread of misinformation with “**anti-vaxxer**” tweets disproportionately represented (Yuan et al., 2019 cited in Himelein-Wachowiak et al., 2021). There were about 41% bots detected in this study.

Replies were frequently created by bots in this study (Figure 27), which supports the notion that bots are now “convincingly human,” for example, social bots that are advanced to possibly configure their behavior and a hybrid type of human and bot or cyborgs (Himelein-Wachowiak et al., 2021). These bots are even smarter as content polluters unlike traditional spammer bots (Himelein-Wachowiak et al., 2021).

Table 2. Codes for importing the processed data.

```
1. import numpy as np
2. import pandas as pd
3. import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
4.
5.
6. # processed dataset generated by correlate-data.py
7. input_data = pd.read_csv("./dataset/core_data.csv")
```

Table 3. Codes for plotting the tabulated data.

```
1. print("Data Overview:")
2. fig, axes = plt.subplots(nrows=2, ncols=2, figsize=(23,7))
3. plt.subplots_adjust(wspace=0.2, hspace=0.5)
4. input_data["from_user_bot_score"].plot(ax=axes[0, 0]);
5. axes[0, 0].set_title("From user bot score");
6. input_data["to_user_bot_score"].plot(ax=axes[0, 1]);
7. axes[0, 1].set_title("To user bot score");
8. pd.value_counts(input_data["to_user_bot_type"]).plot.bar(ax=axes[1, 0]);
9. axes[1, 0].set_title("To user bot types");
10. pd.value_counts(input_data["tweet_type"]).plot.bar(ax=axes[1, 1]);
11. axes[1, 1].set_title("Tweet types");
12. fig.suptitle("Core Dataset Overview: (core_data.csv)", fontsize=20)
13. plt.savefig("./figures/dataset-overview.png")
```

Figure 27. Distribution of COVID-19 tweets.

Bots and humans form communities to exchange information in which humans are exposed to a large bot-generated content by retweets. In fact, retweeting is the main mechanism in the wider spread of misinformation (especially from media accounts behaving like bots) and it gives a direct measure of the broadcasting potential of different accounts over the same topic. Although bots retweet and interact more with other users than with humans, there is no significant bot centrality increase because connections are concentrated among verified human accounts or retweets

take place between human accounts most of the time. Furthermore, bots could not engage in a reciprocal communication for the sake of increasing their network visibility. This puts unverified accounts, for example bots, at a lower level of centrality than humans even if bots attract more attention. Combined activities of bots and humans on Twitter are responsible for the massive spread of misinformation. (González-Bailón & De Domenico, 2021)

Data analysis has shown users created more replies than retweets which can have two explanations: (1) humans dominate the spread of misinformation; and (2) bots are far more sophisticated nowadays to generate human content (Himelein-Wachowiak et al., 2021). Bots have capabilities to search and to retrieve non-curated (unverified) information on the web, and to propagate it using trending topics and hashtags (Center for Information Technology and Society, 2022). They amplify such information during its early spreading before hitting virality (Shao et al., 2018).

Table 4. Coding for visualizing the spread of misinformation.

```
1. import numpy as np
2. import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
3. import july
4. from july.utils import date_range
5. import moment
6.
7.
8.
9. network_timeseries = {}
10. network_node_classifications = {}
11.
12. # create network timeseries data
13.
14. for index, row in input_data[range_start:range_end].iterrows():
15.     tweet_date = moment.date(row["tweet_created_at"]).format("YYYY-MM-DD")
16.
17.     if tweet_date not in network_timeseries:
```

```

18.     network_timeseries[tweet_date] = 5
19. else:
20.     network_timeseries[tweet_date] += 1
21.
22.     bot_type = ""
23.
24.     if row["from_user_type"] == "bot":
25.         network_timeseries[tweet_date] += 1
26.         bot_type = row["from_user_bot_type"]
27.     else:
28.         bot_type = "false (human account)"
29.
30.
31.
32.     node_item = {
33.         "id": index,
34.         "username": row["from_user_screen_name"],
35.         "bot_type": bot_type,
36.         "user_type": row["from_user_type"],
37.         "origin_tweet_date": tweet_date,
38.         "degree": network_timeseries[tweet_date],
39.         "tweet_url": row["tweet_url"]
40.     }
41.
42.     if row["from_user_screen_name"] not in network_node_classifications:
43.         network_node_classifications[row["from_user_screen_name"]] =
            node_item
44.     else:
45.         network_node_classifications[row["from_user_screen_name"]]["degree"]
            += network_timeseries[tweet_date]
46.
47.
48. # sort entries
49. sorted(network_timeseries.keys())
50.
51.
52. # print(network_timeseries)
53.
54. tsl = list(network_timeseries.keys())
55.
56. start_date = tsl[0]
57. end_year = moment.date(tsl[len(tsl)-1]).format("YYYY")
58.
59. dates = date_range(start_date, f"{end_year}-12-30")
60. data = np.random.randint(0, 1, len(dates))
61.
62. timeframe_data = {}
63.
64. for date in dates:
65.     dx = moment.date(date).format("YYYY-MM-DD")

```

```
66. timeframe_data[dx] = 180
67.
68. for dx in list(network_timeseries.keys()):
69.     timeframe_data[dx] = network_timeseries[dx]
70.
71.
72. july.heatmap(dates, list(timeframe_data.values()), title='Misinformation Spread
    Heatmap', colorbar=True, cmap="Blues", fontsize=12)
73. plt.savefig("./figures/misinformation_heatmap.png")
74.
```

In Figure 28, misinformation breaks off every three months which is similar to a very recent study showing that “...social bots [*activity on COVID-19 vaccination*] remained active over three periods” (Zhang et al., 2022, p. 1). Furthermore, it takes a single instance (cell in dark blue) of tweeting a contagious content to perpetuate it up to eight months. The heatmap shows the intensity of the propagation. Bot tweets are ‘discontinuous with a decreasing monotonic sequence’—based on King’s (2013) explanation of monotonic increasing versus monotonic decreasing—after critical mass that is bounded above by only one dark blue cell on May 18, 2021 and below by empty cells indicating no new tweets were created rather than saying the network is devoid of tweets. However, if activity continues then it is monotonic increasing according to De Domenico et al. (2013). Indeed, the spread of information is an inconsistent phenomenon within an asymmetric information environment (Lee, 2021).

Figure 28. Actual spread of misinformation.

Based on literature about content generation, traditional bots retweet the tweets of other users (either humans or bots) more often, but intermittently rather than composing original and credible tweets which human users would do. Moreover, human users configure their behavior every online session accordingly. The number of new tweets created by humans diminishes throughout the session which is the opposite among bots (Himelein-Wachowiak et al., 2021).

Social bots achieve virality by “...excessive posting, early and frequent retweeting of emerging news, and tagging or mentioning influential figures”. They can retweet articles within seconds after the first post.

Evidence is now available about bot squads or “groups of bots that follow and retweet the same group of hubs,” which are shared by a group of human-operated accounts. These human-operated accounts are actually the strongest hubs and bots operate through them. Some bot followers have the same political influence as humans and attract bot followers too. Hubs’ messages are amplified via retweets (Caldarelli et al., 2020 pp. 1-2).

Breaks periods in tweets also reveal that there were more bots continually active (in light blue cells) and bots that burst in activity (from blue to faded cells) were on a short-term basis (Yang et al., 2020).

Research Question 2: What are the types of automated Twitter accounts or Twitter bots?

For the knowledge of the Communication Scholars and the intended dissemination of this study, let it be known that bot tweets comprised about 46% (of the mass of the Twitter network) during the study period. This is way over the findings by Luceri et al. (2021) about 20%. The “**false human accounts**” were greater than (67%) “**traditional bots**” (33%), in particular, “**spammers**” (27%) or spam bots. Twitter bots produced more out-going communications by broadcasting misinformation in the form of tweets (Jiang et al., 2021) to other nodes, which is equivalent to saying a “high out-degree centrality” (Schuchard et al., 2019) took place than these bots were active with in-coming communications from other nodes.

Figure 29. Frequency of connection from a bot with bot score $\geq .43$.

Figure 30. Frequency of connection to a bot with bot score $\geq .43$.

The results above will support the understanding of in-degree (Figure 29) and out-degree (Figure 30) transmission of misinformation. Indeed, bots get significant high out-degree centrality (Schuchard et al., 2019) or misinformation originates from them going to a connected node. It is true that spread of misinformation is done by broadcasting (Jiang et al., 2021). The graphs may translate into wave spectra and thus provide an insight about signal generation for network communication.

Figure 31. Distribution of Twitter bot species.

This confirmed that spammers or spambots (traditional) were prolific and the most detectable (Himelein-Wachowiak et al., 2021) since in literature they comprised about 93% of bot population (Broniatowski et al. 2018). Political bots were not present which means COVID-19 vaccine misinformation and related topics have not spread as “computational propaganda” or in any of the following semantics: “**information warfare**,” “**online astroturfing**,” “**cyberturfing**,” etc. (Woolley, 2020). Nevertheless, bots can post “filler content” to hide a political agenda (Herring-Margaret & Delwiche, 2018).

Research Question 3: How do network topology or pattern of connections and node synchronization differ in the bot layer, human layer, and tweet layer?

For the knowledge of the Communication Scholars and the intended dissemination of this study, let it be known that Twitter bots form single focal group and conform around human user groups forging to intermediate within their dynamics. They create interlayer connections profoundly and cause the faster diffusion of misinformation. Bots that burst in activity had a shorter period thus confirming the findings by Yang et al., (2020). Generally, bots synchronize around 400 seconds (6.67 minutes); peak dynamics reached 200 seconds (3.33 minutes) at most. The most influential (very active) bots oscillate in many small, low degree clusters.

Based on first network analysis, Twitter bots showed high betweenness and eigenvector centralities. Random walk score and PageRank score were useful in detecting false human account super spreaders (e.g., **bev768**). Number of cliques rise inconsistently in the bot layer; decreased in human layer. Intralayer entanglements mostly by “other” (e.g., **ronnoconiv**), “self-declared” (e.g., **NFL**), and “spammers” (e.g., **dansiddiqui**, **StefanLazar10**, **santa_tzu**). The von Neumann Graph Entropy (FINGER) score was 3.2549 versus 2.1320 over .0109 sec. or 2.69345 (averaged) edge created per .011 seconds; information divergence increases from bot layer to human layer. Significant entropy was produced by spambots (e.g., **Left_of_You** and **Daniel2510G**) and false human accounts (e.g., **CobyJayJr42** and **babibelle33**) during entanglement. Entanglements were more frequent from bots (intensity at .4161) than from humans (.0038) causing low entanglement homogeneity (<1).

Based on second network analysis, Twitter bots have mixed but temporal states (activity every .0687 sec) by negative entanglement. Certainly, they work in proximity

by closeness centrality >1 . Intermediating spammers were few by betweenness centrality <1 . Multiple edges validated by random walk and PageRank scores <1 . The critical bot threshold after virality lowers due to fall of critical mass. After percolation, central spreaders (mostly false human accounts) increased in percolation centrality, random walk and PageRank scores. Peripheral spreaders (mostly spammers) decreased. No change in percolation centrality was due to indirect connections of nodes (mostly spammers) but scattered in the network.

Based on Kuramoto modeling, there was no bot synchronization and phase-locking if coupling strength, $K_c \leq .20$ or if active bots reduced by 15% reduction. Twitter bots have split (simultaneous synchronization and desynchronization), one-way track dynamics based on missing natural frequency values, which is also a trademark of artificial intelligence. Two equilibrium or plateau periods were shown during their phase transition. This suggests multi stability which allows them to adapt to communication and become resilient to deactivation.

Multiplex Visualization

The core csv dataset was converted into graph data using NetworkX. Two methods of visualizations were performed: multiplex (within layer connections) and multilayer (between layer connections). The layers were named bot layer, human layer, and tweet layer (composed of bots and human interactions).

Table 5. Codes for generating multiplex graphs.

```
1. from mpl_toolkits.mplot3d import Axes3D
2. import networkx as nx
3. import matplotlib.path_effects as path_effects
4. from mpl_toolkits.mplot3d.art3d import Line3DCollection
5. %matplotlib inline
6.
7. # let's start with the important stuff. pick your colors.
8. cols = ['steelblue', 'mediumseagreen', 'darksalmon']
9. np.random.seed(1)
10.
11. # Create a set of graph layers
12. layer_names = ["Tweet Layer", "Human Layer", "Bot Layer"]
13. node_colors = {"bot": "red", "human": "green"}
14. mention_edge_color = "blue"
15. def_edge_color = "grey"
16.
17.
18. tweets_layer = nx.Graph()
19. human_layer = nx.Graph()
20. bot_layer = nx.Graph()
21.
22. # create data for bot layer
23.
24. all_bots = {}
25. all_humans = {}
26. all_tweets = {}
27.
28. range_start = 0
29. range_end = 1380
30. layout_iterations = 100
31.
32. def createUserNetworkLayers(delimiter, outputData, outputNetwork):
```

```

33. # get all the delimiter from input_data
34. for index, row in input_data[range_start:range_end].iterrows():
35.
36.     from_username = row["from_user_screen_name"]
37.     to_username = row["to_user_screen_name"]
38.     is_mention = row["is_mention"]
39.
40.     # process all data based on delimiters
41.     if row["to_user_type"] == delimiter and to_username not in outputData:
42.         outputData[to_username] = {"username": to_username, "bot_type":
row["to_user_bot_type"], "to": [], "mentions": [], "type": delimiter}
43.
44.
45.     if row["from_user_type"] == delimiter and from_username not in
outputData:
46.         data = {"username": from_username, "bot_type":
row["from_user_bot_type"], "to": [], "mentions": [], "type": delimiter}
47.         if row["to_user_type"] == delimiter:
48.             data["to"].append(to_username)
49.             data["mentions"].append(is_mention)
50.
51.         outputData[from_username] = data
52.
53.     if row["from_user_type"] == delimiter and from_username in outputData:
54.         if row["to_user_type"] == delimiter and to_username not in
outputData[from_username]["to"]:
55.             outputData[from_username]["to"].append(to_username)
56.             outputData[from_username]["mentions"].append(is_mention)
57.
58.     # create nodes
59.     for ix, item, in enumerate(outputData):
60.         user_node_color = cols[2] if outputData[item]["type"] == "bot" else cols[1]
61.
        outputNetwork.add_nodes_from([(ix, outputData[item]), weight=len(outputData
[item]["to"]), color=user_node_color)
62.
63.     # create edges
64.     for ix, item in enumerate(outputData):
65.         if len(outputData[item]["to"]) > 0:
66.             for y, conn in enumerate(outputData[item]["to"]):
67.                 edge_color = mention_edge_color if outputData[item]["mentions"][y]
== True else def_edge_color
68.
        outputNetwork.add_edge(ix, list(outputData.keys()).index(outputData[item]["to"
][y]), color=edge_color)
69.
70.
71. def createTweetsData(inputLayer):
72.     for node in inputLayer:
73.         all_tweets[node] = inputLayer[node]

```

```

74.
75.
76. def createTweetsNetworkLayer(data):
77.     for ix, item, in enumerate(data):
78.         user_node_color = cols[2] if data[item]["type"] == "bot" else cols[1]
79.         tweets_layer.add_nodes_from([(ix,data[item])],color=user_node_color)
80.
81.     for ix, item in enumerate(data):
82.         if len(data[item]["to"]) > 0:
83.             for y, conn in enumerate(data[item]["to"]):
84.                 edge_color = mention_edge_color if data[item]["mentions"][y] ==
True else def_edge_color
85.                 tweets_layer.add_edge(ix,list(data.keys()).index(data[item]["to"][y]),
color=edge_color)
86.
87. raw_layer_data = [all_tweets, all_humans, all_bots]
88.
89.
90. # Create connections between layers, by getting the nodes with most
connections for each layer
91. # Only return the nodes with connections
92. def createLayerConnections(layer_data):
93.     c_data = []
94.     conns = []
95.     for ix, x in enumerate(layer_data):
96.         c_data.append({
97.             "node_id": ix,
98.             "connections": len(layer_data[x]["to"])
99.         })
100.
101.     c_data = sorted(c_data, key = lambda i: i['connections'],reverse=True)
102.
103.     for ix, x in enumerate(c_data):
104.         if x["connections"] > 0:
105.             conns.append(x["node_id"])
106.
107.     return conns
108.
109. # this function will create custom with of connections between layers of the
multi layer network chart
110. def fetchConnectionDensity(layer_data):
111.     c_data = []
112.     conns = []
113.     conns_density = []
114.     for ix, x in enumerate(layer_data):
115.         c_data.append({
116.             "node_id": ix,
117.             "connections": len(layer_data[x]["to"])
118.         })
119.

```

```

120. c_data = sorted(c_data, key = lambda i: i['connections'],reverse=True)
121.
122. # get number of connections for the connected nodes
123. for ix, x in enumerate(c_data):
124.     if x["connections"] > 0:
125.         conns.append(x["connections"])
126.
127. # calculate connection density by normalizing the number of connections
    between layers
128. for ix, cn in enumerate(conns):
129.     max_density = max(conns)
130.     min_density = min(conns)
131.     c_density = ((cn-min_density) / (max_density - min_density)) +1
132.     conns_density.append(c_density)
133.
134. return conns_density
135.
136.
137.
138.
139. graphs = [tweets_layer, human_layer, bot_layer]
140.
141. createUserNetworkLayers("bot",all_bots,bot_layer)
142. createUserNetworkLayers("human",all_humans,human_layer)
143. createTweetsData(all_bots)
144. createTweetsData(all_humans)
145. createTweetsNetworkLayer(all_tweets)
146.
147. print(createLayerConnections(all_bots))
148. print(fetchConnectionDensity(all_bots))
149.
150.
151. pos = nx.kamada_kawai_layout(tweets_layer) # assuming common node
    location
152.
153. # prepare subplots
154.
155. fig, all_axes = plt.subplots(1, 3, figsize=(23,7))
156. ax = all_axes.flat
157.
158. for i, gr in enumerate(graphs):
159.     ax[i].set_title(layer_names[i], fontsize=20)
160.     nx.draw(gr,pos, node_size=60, ax=ax[i], node_color=cols[i])
161.
162. plt.savefig("./figures/per-layer-visualization.png")
163.
164.
165. print("Generating bot layer graph..")
166. print("No. of Bot Nodes:",len(all_bots))
167. print("No. of Human Nodes:",len(all_humans))

```

```
168. print("Total Tweets",len(all_tweets))
```

Figure 32. Multiplex visualization of bot, human, and tweet vertices and their edges.

Results showed bots form a single focal group while humans have multiple groups. Tweet layers undergo human-like clustering and bots conform (graft) around them.

Multilayer Visualization

Table 6. Codes for plotting the multilayer graph.

```
1. # Set height and width of figure
2. w = 8
3. h = 7
4.
5.
6. def blayerEdgeColors(cd):
7.     cxm = []
8.
9.     for cxs in cd:
10.        if(cxs > 1.45):
11.            cxm.append("blue")
12.        else:
13.            cxm.append("grey")
14.     return cxm
15.
16. fig, ax = plt.subplots(1, 1, figsize=(w,h), dpi=200,
17.                        subplot_kw={'projection':'3d'})
18. for gi, G in enumerate(graphs):
19.     # node positions
20.     xs = list(list(zip(*list(pos.values())))[0])
21.     ys = list(list(zip(*list(pos.values())))[1])
22.     zs = [gi]*len(xs) # set a common z-position of the nodes
23.
24.     # node colors
25.     cs = [cols[gi]]*len(xs)
26.
27.     # if you want to have between-layer connections
28.     if gi > 0:
29.         thru_nodes = createLayerConnections(raw_layer_data[gi])
30.         lines3d_between = [(list(pos[i])+[gi-1],list(pos[i])+[gi]) for i in thru_nodes]
31.         between_lines = Line3DCollection(lines3d_between, zorder=gi,
32.                                           color=blayerEdgeColors(fetchConnectionDensity(raw_layer_data[gi])),
33.                                           alpha=0.6, linestyle='--',
34.                                           linewidth=fetchConnectionDensity(raw_layer_data[gi]))
35.         ax.add_collection3d(between_lines)
36.
37.     # add within-layer edges
38.     lines3d = [(list(pos[i])+[gi],list(pos[j])+[gi]) for i,j in G.edges()]
39.     line_collection = Line3DCollection(lines3d, zorder=gi, color=cols[gi],
40.                                       alpha=0.5, linewidth=0.7)
41.     ax.add_collection3d(line_collection)
```

```

39.
40. # now add nodes
41. ax.scatter(xs, ys, zs, c=cs, s=5, edgecolors='.2', marker='o', alpha=0.6,
zorder=gi+1)
42.
43. # add a plane to designate the layer
44. xdiff = max(xs)-min(xs)
45. ydiff = max(ys)-min(ys)
46. ymin = min(ys)-ydiff*0.1
47. ymax = max(ys)+ydiff*0.1
48. xmin = min(xs)-xdiff*0.1 * (w/h)
49. xmax = max(xs)+xdiff*0.1 * (w/h)
50. xx, yy = np.meshgrid([xmin, xmax],[ymin, ymax])
51. zz = np.zeros(xx.shape)+gi
52. ax.plot_surface(xx, yy, zz, color=cols[gi], alpha=0.1, zorder=gi)
53.
54. # add label
55. layertext = ax.text(0.0, 1.2, gi*0.95+0.5, layer_names[gi],
56. color=cols[gi], fontsize='small', zorder=1e5, ha='left',
va='center')
57.
58. # set them all at the same x,y,zlims
59. ax.set_ylim(min(ys)-ydiff*0.1,max(ys)+ydiff*0.1)
60. ax.set_xlim(min(xs)-xdiff*0.1,max(xs)+xdiff*0.1)
61. ax.set_zlim(-0.3, len(graphs) - 2 + 0.1)
62.
63. # select viewing angle
64. angle = 30
65. height_angle = 21
66. ax.view_init(height_angle, angle)
67.
68. # how much do you want to zoom into the fig
69. ax.dist = 13.5
70.
71. ax.set_axis_off()
72.
73. plt.savefig("./figures/multiplex-network.png")

```

SOURCE: Adapted from Klein, 2021.

Figure 33. Multilayer visualization.

Table 7. Codes for fetching the graph network information.

```

1. graph_network_info = []
2.
3. layer_info = {
4.
5. }
6. print("Nodes and Edges per layer")
7. for i, gr in enumerate(graphs):
8.     print(layer_names[i])
9.     print("Number of nodes:",gr.number_of_nodes())
10.    print("Number of edges:",gr.number_of_edges())
11.
12. print("")
13.
14. between_layer_names = ["-", "Human Layer to Tweets Layer", "Bot Layer to
    Human Layer"]
15.
16. print("Between Layer Edges:")
17. for i, gr in enumerate(graphs):
18.     if i > 0:
19.         print(between_layer_names[i])
20.         print("No. of Beetween Layer
    Edges",len(createLayerConnections(raw_layer_data[i])))

```

Bot layer contains 562 vertices with 316 edges. Human layer contains 824 vertices with 533 edges. Tweet layer contains 1374 vertices with 693 edges. There are 24 edges between bot layer and human layer while 61 edges are between human layer and tweet layer. A total of 139 vertices are connected across three layers, for example, “**VanderluciaSch1**” (other; **user id:** 545 and 1347) is among the most influential bots with a high degree (710).

If each intralayer edge will correspond to a tweet, bots are responsible for $45.60\% \left(\frac{316}{693} \times 100 \right)$ while the majority are from humans at $76.91\% \left(\frac{533}{693} \times 100 \right)$. The study results are not far from those found in the literature (Himelein-Wachowiak et al., 2021; Luceri et al., 2019). Ironically, the presence of more interconnections between

layers means less epidemic capacity (spreading of misinformation) because of the distribution of interconnection and the large (out-degree) difference produced between inter and intra neighbors (Basaras et al. 2017, p. 12). Therefore, bots can spread misinformation faster than humans via interlayer edges.

By investigation of Twitter network using the (undirected) multilayer approach, "...[*global*] topological features of multi-layer diffusion networks might be effectively exploited to detect online disinformation" (Pierri et al., 2020a, p. 15). For example, *k-core* may be used to find the most influential users while "the average distance between all pairs of nodes in a cascade tree" (Pierri et al., 2020a, p. 7) can be a metric for structural virality (sort of edges hyper capacity).

Interlayer edges permit diffusion of information across layers. Information theory is operationalized in the representation of (mis)information diffusion per layer having a "pure top-down broadcast" where cascades merge in a common node via Twitter interactions (e.g., mentions, replies, etc.) and mono-directionality is overcome through a loop, which can be measured using the size of the largest strongly connected component (Pierri et al., 2020a, pp. 7-8).

Network statistics performed in each layer were standard metrics. Inter-layer connections are analyzed as entanglements. The main culprit for the viral spread of misinformation is the agent (Blankenship, 2020, p. 5) either mediated by bots or with humans.

Table 8. Codes for generating edge list per layer.

```
1. layers_edgelist = []
2.
3. mx_layers = ["tweets_layer", "human_layer", "bot_layer"]
4.
5. # generate a custom edgelist and combinem them for all layers
6. for i, g in enumerate(graphs):
7.     networkedgelist = nx.generate_edgelist(g, data=False)
8.     print(f"Generating Edgelist for {mx_layers[i]}")
9.     for ix, x in enumerate(networkedgelist):
10.        e = x.replace(" ", f" {mx_layers[i]} ")
11.        edge_line = f"{e} {mx_layers[i]} 1"
12.        layers_edgelist.append(edge_line)
13.
14. # write edgelist to file "mxlist.txt"
15. with open('./dataset/mxlist.txt', 'w') as f:
16.     for item in layers_edgelist:
17.         f.write("%s\n" % item)
18.
19. print("=====")
20. print("Custom data generation Completed!")
```

File is saved as "[mxlist.txt](#)". Connected (entangled) vertices via edges by at least two layers are **superpositioning**—exhibiting the same function or behavior in the network.

The values in Table 10 are data driven and change along with the input dataset. Influential nodes table is based on degree mapping per layer. A seeded value of 5 was added in for visualization purposes.

Table 9. Codes for classifying the most influential nodes.

```
1. # preprocess node network classifications
2. network_node_classifications = list(network_node_classifications.values())
3. # sort by degree descending order
4. network_node_classifications = sorted(network_node_classifications, key =
    lambda i: i["degree"],reverse=True)
5.
6. mib_table = pd.DataFrame(network_node_classifications)
7. display(mib_table)
8. mib_table.to_csv("./dataset/most_influential_users.csv")
```

In this study, the primary measure is “degree”. It dictates the spread of misinformation whenever the number of connections is large. The rules were: (1) each node had an initial value of 5; (2) +1 was added to 5 for every connection to a node; and (3) the value incremented once more by 1 if a connection is from a Twitter bot or fake user. No deletion or mutation of nodes ever happened throughout the implementation.

Mass of bots depends on “degree”. The “...high degree nodes attract disproportionately much weight” and “...relatively much of the weight seems to concentrate between high degree nodes” (Traag et al., 2016, p. 81). This means that “high degree nodes connect relatively stronger to other high degree nodes” and, in turn, explains their “assortativity” (Traag et al., 2016, p. 86).

A node may be considered massive if degree is >200 (Traag et al., 2016, p. 86). It can be inferred from here that high degree (most influential) nodes do “...reinforce existing co-occurrences [*of tweets connecting between nodes*]” (Traag et al., 2016, p. 81) by building entanglements (complex connections) through and with other high centrality nodes.

The influential nodes table shows nominally classified nodes (humans and bots), degree (bots > humans), and other network measures. Nodes without significant connections to other nodes in the network have been filtered out.

Nodes connected between each layer are identified using the influential nodes table. Nodes are sorted by degree matching their type. Tweet layer combines human and bot accounts in the exchange of information.

Individual node degree refers to the number of node connections and the number of nodes connections to bots. Under the assumption that bots are unreliable sources of information, they are more often than not considered malicious. Hence, a node with more connections to bots will get the highest degree to spread misinformation. Degree is calculated independently of network structuring due to information flow (e.g., divided or polarized, unified, fragmented, clustered, and inward and outward hub-and-spoke by Himelboim et al., 2017) and structural entanglement.

Table 10. List of most influential nodes by degree ($n = 95$).

No.	ID	Username	Bot type	User type	Tweet date	Degree
0	978	newsmax	spammer	bot	5/26/2021	34672
1	434	JonPort79449036	false (human account)	human	10/9/2021	15721
2	308	nickisnest	false (human account)	human	8/13/2021	2881
3	591	CobyJay41	false (human account)	human	8/11/2021	2473
4	155	bev768	false (human account)	human	10/7/2021	2285
5	6	danny086756661	spammer	bot	8/11/2021	2281
6	1155	robert_traurig	spammer	bot	5/26/2021	1516
7	791	Simone_Voice	spammer	bot	7/19/2021	715
8	1347	VanderluciaSch1	other	bot	8/30/2021	710
9	100	Daniel2510G	spammer	bot	9/8/2021	630
10	928	ella03787321	false (human account)	human	7/18/2021	609
11	759	SpiritYah	false (human account)	human	7/20/2021	508
12	906	Learningpods1	false (human account)	human	5/26/2021	446
13	1330	BrandonLesco1	false (human account)	human	11/9/2021	439
14	701	kawarren818	false (human account)	human	8/9/2021	427
15	766	haber_okuyorum1	false (human account)	human	7/20/2021	416
16	1166	santa_tzu	spammer	bot	5/26/2021	388
17	1160	Yaocyou	spammer	bot	5/26/2021	386
18	1159	JaneDoe89034155	spammer	bot	5/26/2021	384

19	129	CobyJayJr42	false (human account)	human	10/5/2021	383
20	1154	mimosa_9th_	spammer	bot	5/26/2021	374
21	778	DutchDL	false (human account)	human	7/21/2021	370
22	869	107devorah	false (human account)	human	7/17/2021	345
23	804	fuzzyface	false (human account)	human	7/19/2021	330
24	943	LoveTahoe1	false (human account)	human	7/27/2021	309
25	753	deltazebedee1	false (human account)	human	7/21/2021	306
26	970	DDonP3	private_account	bot	7/24/2021	304
27	940	takapirulainen	spammer	bot	7/18/2021	297
28	742	sfbtears	spammer	bot	10/16/2021	265
29	974	NoSurrender200	other	bot	7/24/2021	249
30	967	texaspatriette	false (human account)	human	7/24/2021	210
31	819	ninskiberry	false (human account)	human	7/19/2021	196
32	836	moonbeam696	false (human account)	human	7/21/2021	195
33	834	AndersonPolaris	false (human account)	human	7/21/2021	191
34	938	Rac_helz	false (human account)	human	7/18/2021	189
35	1310	CobyJayJr43	spammer	bot	11/16/2021	186
36	936	Max65752957	false (human account)	human	7/18/2021	185
37	712	babibelle33	false (human account)	human	8/25/2021	180
38	924	Caring_Canuck	false (human account)	human	7/18/2021	161
39	782	PantsClock	false (human account)	human	7/19/2021	153
40	581	VanderleydeSo14	private_account	bot	8/30/2021	150
41	963	tvegaw	false (human account)	human	7/23/2021	150
42	816	justletmebeme1	false (human account)	human	7/18/2021	149
43	849	DixieGenX	false (human account)	human	5/24/2021	136
44	574	sir_lars	false (human account)	human	10/7/2021	133
45	831	elofan1276	false (human account)	human	7/22/2021	133
46	749	Jaye1222	false (human account)	human	7/21/2021	125
47	689	1SweetSoldier	false (human account)	human	8/15/2021	124
48	891	laureenrobinso1	false (human account)	human	5/23/2021	110
49	827	JackJackedMe	other	bot	7/23/2021	99
50	838	BaringMyClaws	false (human account)	human	7/21/2021	99
51	825	KyleJayBonnell	false (human account)	human	7/22/2021	95
52	747	j_windsong	spammer	bot	10/17/2021	92
53	935	Vicmot	false (human account)	human	7/18/2021	91
54	839	momJenRodriguez	other	bot	5/25/2021	90
55	927	mattlargey	false (human account)	human	7/18/2021	83
56	926	Andreopeeneilan	false (human account)	human	7/18/2021	82
57	723	globalism_no	spammer	bot	8/27/2021	80
58	909	val_ic	false (human account)	human	7/18/2021	79
59	814	mynameisnotkim1	private_account	bot	7/19/2021	78
60	738	Voyeur80370397	false (human account)	human	10/17/2021	72
61	959	Sayyestolifeno1	false (human account)	human	8/5/2021	69
62	0	Left_of_You	spammer	bot	5/17/2021	66
63	734	RockinTrump	self_declared	bot	8/21/2021	64
64	961	zoogirl121	false (human account)	human	7/26/2021	57
65	775	maatуска_t	false (human account)	human	7/20/2021	55
66	830	YatesSaunders	false (human account)	human	7/22/2021	49
67	903	bilks	false (human account)	human	5/26/2021	48
68	824	QWarrior18	false (human account)	human	7/19/2021	46
69	823	MSkuggsida	false (human account)	human	7/19/2021	45
70	822	loveiswhereits2	false (human account)	human	7/19/2021	44

71	818	BBCNews	spammer	bot	7/19/2021	42
72	698	BeverlyDHolmes	false (human account)	human	8/6/2021	41
73	912	pinopire43	false (human account)	human	5/18/2021	38
74	919	AllieLucas1971	false (human account)	human	5/20/2021	35
75	910	AlfaBravo005	false (human account)	human	5/22/2021	31
76	731	raroberts2010	spammer	bot	8/19/2021	30
77	1165	HetrickBarry	spammer	bot	5/25/2021	28
78	889	Laban471	false (human account)	human	5/26/2021	27
79	1342	NH_2_NC	false (human account)	human	11/5/2021	27
80	1164	NYLockdown	spammer	bot	5/25/2021	26
81	1163	l11432	spammer	bot	5/25/2021	24
82	1162	drmassee	spammer	bot	5/25/2021	22
83	1161	EdwinRankin	spammer	bot	5/25/2021	20
84	977	EynoufElizabeth	spammer	bot	5/25/2021	18
85	918	IBelieveMothers	false (human account)	human	5/22/2021	17
86	1344	ussuricat1	false (human account)	human	9/2/2021	13
87	868	PatriotDany	false (human account)	human	5/26/2021	12
88	916	LoFaSho24	false (human account)	human	5/18/2021	12
89	697	CBmdnc	false (human account)	human	8/7/2021	11
90	867	Sbartol3	false (human account)	human	5/26/2021	11
91	887	SmithMEGA007	false (human account)	human	7/15/2021	10
92	733	sgibbsters	false (human account)	human	8/16/2021	9
93	917	CrashingJustice	false (human account)	human	5/23/2021	9
94	848	DonnaOw66990971	false (human account)	human	5/24/2021	5

Based on features of bot accounts in the literature (Himelein-Wachowiak et al., 2021), they have been created more recently and have longer usernames. Moreover, human accounts show stronger positive sentiments compared with bots. However, these features were not all helpful for their characterizations. In particular, bots do not always have long usernames as shown in the results.

Profiling of Twitter bots has to be extensive because spambots have been designed to appear as genuine as human accounts (Cresci et al., 2017a; Cresci et al., 2017b). The devised degree calculation was fundamental in the first round of network analysis. From the listed most influential accounts, the number of assumed deceptive accounts or false human accounts was high at 67% ($n = 64$) while only 33% ($n = 31$) are traditional bots, in particular, 24% ($n = 23$) were “**spambots**”. On the other hand,

out of the total cases ($N=1374$) which comprised the tweet layer, “spambots” detected were around 27% ($n=375$).

The section below covers the global network measurements.

Visualization of Network Communities

Graph-based method of detection works according to homophily: “malicious users will have similar [behavioral] patterns” (Collins et al., 2021, p. 259).

Table 11. Coding for Circos plot visualization.

```
1. import nxviz as nv
2. # plot each circos using nxviz
3.
4.
5. for i,g in enumerate(graphs):
6.     nv.CircosPlot(g)
7.     ax = plt.gca()
8.     ax.set_title(f"{layer_names[i]} (n={g.number_of_nodes()},
9.     e={g.number_of_edges()})", fontsize=15, y=1.02)
10.    plt.savefig(f"./figures/{layer_names[i]} - Circos plot.png")
```

Figure 34. Comparison by Circos plot.

Circos plots are used commonly in genomic studies to show variations or alterations in sequence structure (Krzywinski et al., 2009). Using a similar approach, structural variations provide clues about bot involvement. Bot footprints are detectable by their dense, traversing, and conflating edges that form a stretched triangular shape. This is apparent in the bot layer and tweet layer.

Visualization of the Adjacency Matrix

Table 12. Codes for visualization of adjacency matrix.

```
1. fig, axs = plt.subplots(1, 3, figsize=(23, 5))
2.
3. # Plot adjacency Matrix for each layer
4. for i,g in enumerate(graphs):
5.     g = nx.k_shell(g)
6.     # covert network data to adjacency matrix array
7.     ajD = nx.adjacency_matrix(g).toarray()
8.     # limit array size, for uniformity
9.     axs[i].imshow(ajD, interpolation="bilinear")
10.    axs[i].set_title(f"{layer_names[i]} (n={g.number_of_nodes()},
    e={g.number_of_edges()})", fontsize=15, y=1.02)
11.
12. fig.suptitle('Adjacency Matrix for each Network Layer', fontsize=17, y=1.08 )
13. plt.savefig("./figures/per-layer-adj-matrix.png")
```

This visualization was done using [imshow](#) from [Matplotlib](#) and a function from NetworkX converted the network graph data into an adjacency matrix array. The algorithm [nx.k_shell](#), a decomposition function, was used to filter disconnected parts of the graph data. For the x and y labels of the adjacency matrix, it will cover all the nodes of the network represented in numbers.

Figure 35. Comparison by adjacency matrix (structural connectivity).

Plots do not show homogeneity of structure, i.e., by distribution of cells towards the main diagonal (Vathakkattil & Pakrashi, 2020). Increasing structural distances from the main diagonal would allow for the formation of (1) opposing clusters (at 180°) with contradicting dynamics or “anti-phase synchronization” (Vathakkattil & Pakrashi, 2020) and (2) polarization.

On the other hand, structural heterogeneity has minimal effect on stability of interactions but is controlled by (a) **coupling strength**, (b) **dynamical heterogeneity**, and (c) **mean network degree** (Skardal & Arenas, 2015).

Bots will pan out more connected into small groups compared to humans. On the other hand, polarized clusters are observed in the human layer by concentration of nodes from the diagonal of the matrix (Shore et al., 2016, p. 857), which are joined by a large central structure intermediating as gatekeepers and as information repeaters of the echo chamber. The visualized polarization resembles a previous study (Figure 36).

Hybrid bots could be suspected (encircled in red) providing ties between the groups and central structure. The two bots at the corner of the central structure will provide new attachments and possibly moderate the echo chamber. Tweet layer interspaces and segregates into small groups which may indicate bot infiltration.

Figure 36. Polarization in Twitter network using contour plots by a study comparison.

Source: Cota et al., 2019, p. 5.

Differentiating between bot and human can follow the rules of homophily: humans are inclined to follow or connect with other humans and bots go with other bots. But because bots have become more sophisticated, this approach is less effective. In fact, bots can build social networks like humans. Hence, machine learning (ML) algorithms are needed to boost the predictive accuracy of detection, but if ML models were trained on highly curated bot data sets (e.g., on certain hashtags or spamming identities), these may fail to detect bots in other contexts. In addition, detection biases with ML models deter reliability (Himelein-Wachowiak et al., 2021).

Visualization of the Assortativity Matrix

Table 13. Codes for visualization of assortativity degree mixing matrix.

```
1. print(f"Degree Assortativity Coefficient")
2. for i, g in enumerate(graphs):
3.     print(f"{layer_names[i]}: {nx.degree_assortativity_coefficient(g)}")
4.
5. print(" ")
6.
7. print(f"Assortativity Degree Mixing Matrix")
8.
9. fig, axs = plt.subplots(1, 3, figsize=(23, 5))
10.
11. # Plot adjacency Matrix for each layer
12. for i, g in enumerate(graphs):
13.     # covert network data to adjacency matrix array
14.     ajD = nx.degree_mixing_matrix(g)
15.     # limit array size, for uniformity
16.     axs[i].imshow(ajD, interpolation="bilinear", cmap="plasma")
17.     axs[i].set_title(f"{layer_names[i]} (n={g.number_of_nodes()},
18.         e={g.number_of_edges()})", fontsize=15, y=1.02)
19.
20.
21. assortativity_node_degrees = []
22.
23. print(f"Assortativity Node Degree")
24. for i, g in enumerate(graphs):
25.     #TODO: save dataset of node degree
26.     nDeg = nx.node_degree_xy(g)
27.     print(f"{layer_names[i]}: {len(list(nDeg))}")
28.
29. plt.savefig("./figures/degree-mixing-assortativity.png")
```

Figure 37. Comparison by assortativity degree mixing.

Bots work in proximity with each other (equidistant) but stay distinct. They absorb more energy as shown by the scintillated radiance of colors.

Assortativity is "...a network analogue of correlation used to describe how the presence and absence of edges covaries with the properties of nodes" (Peel et al., 2018, p. 4057) or to put it simple, this is "the tendency of nodes to attach to others with similar characteristics" (Pelechrinis & Wei, 2016, p. 1). Since degree assortativity or homophily is negative for all layers, the results are interpreted in terms of 'disassortativity' (Gera, 2017) or heterogeneity. These may be due to the (1) negative covariance (Gera, 2017) and (2) multilayering. Bot layer is more heterogenous (-0.64) than human layer (-0.50). Disassortativity of the tweet layer (-0.51) is more human-related than bots.

Disassortative mixing (degree-based) are common for biological and information networks versus social media networks (Gera, 2017; Mutlu & Garibay, 2022). The way 'degree' was calculated could be a factor. However, recent evidence has found that consensus formation causes disassortativity and agents have a heterogeneous distribution in the network (Mutlu & Garibay, 2022). Bots get into a consensus easily through synchronicity of organization and programmed behavior to

attack nodes. Moreover, the disproportionality of the types of bots in the network affects distribution and hence more disassortativity.

Visualization of Network Modularity

Table 14. Codes for network modularity.

```
1. import community as community_louvain
2. import matplotlib.cm as cm
3.
4.
5. fig, all_axes = plt.subplots(1, 3, figsize=(23,5))
6. ax = all_axes.flat
7. fig.suptitle("Network Modularity",y=1.02, fontsize=20)
8.
9. for i, g in enumerate(graphs):
10.    G = g
11.    # color maps
12.    cmaps = ["viridis","summer","autumn"]
13.    # compute the best partition
14.    partition = community_louvain.best_partition(G)
15.    # draw the graph
16.    pos = nx.kamada_kawai_layout(G)
17.    # color the nodes according to their partition
18.    cmap = cm.get_cmap(cmaps[i], max(partition.values()) + 1)
19.    ax[i].set_title(f"Louvain Communities ({layer_names[i]})", fontsize=14)
20.
21.    network_modularity = community_louvain.modularity(partition, G)
22.    sm = plt.cm.ScalarMappable(cmap=cmap, norm=plt.Normalize(vmin=-1,
    vmax=network_modularity))
23.    sm.set_array([])
24.    cbar = plt.colorbar(sm, ax=ax[i])
25.    nx.draw_networkx_nodes(G, pos, partition.keys(), node_size=40, ax=ax[i],
    cmap=cmap, node_color=list(partition.values()))
26.    nx.draw_networkx_edges(G, pos, alpha=0.2)
27.
28. plt.savefig("./figures/network-modularity.png")
```

The algorithm returns the modularity of the given partition of the graph, and network layers using the Louvain community detection method for optimizing modularity (Bruno et al., 2022).

Modularity measures both the number of edges within the community and the number of edges going outside the community. Values are between -1 and $+1$. A score of $+1$ indicates all the edges are connecting the nodes within the community. A score of 0 indicates only half of the edges are connecting the nodes within the same community while the other half are connecting outside the community. A score of -1 indicates that there are no edges connecting the nodes within the community instead all nodes are connecting outside the community (Stuart, 2020). In terms of information flow, high modularity (i.e., towards $+1$) contain divided information while it is unified in low modularity (Himmelboim et al., 2017, p. 5).

The Louvain algorithm optimizes community detection by “local moving” (nodes are moved between communities until modularity no longer increases or modularity gain ceases) and then by “aggregation” (summation of all edge weights of nodes between communities into a single weighted edge and merging the communities down to one). The process is iterative and time consuming, i.e., 95% of the time is spent for “local moving” (Stuart, 2020).

Figure 38. Comparison by Louvain modularity.

All communities are attracted to the center. Bots aggregate and form a small number of communities, but these are more connected among each other. Humans form larger aggregations, but are connected to the outside than to the core (values between -1 and 0). There are more communities in the tweet layer and hubs emerge (values between 0 and $+1$). Bots in the tweet layer are responsible for a number of connections to and from hubs.

Visualization of Network Decomposition

Table 15. Codes for network decomposition (k -core).

```

1. import matplotlib.cm as cm
2.
3. fig, all_axes = plt.subplots(1, 3, figsize=(23,5))
4. ax = all_axes.flat
5. fig.suptitle("Network Decomposition",y=1.02, fontsize=20)
6.
7. for i, g in enumerate(graphs):
8.     # convert graph to network decomposition subgraph
9.     G = nx.k_core(g)
10.    core_number = nx.core_number(G)
11.    cmaps = ["viridis", "summer", "plasma"]
12.    pos = nx.kamada_kawai_layout(G)
13.    cmap = cm.get_cmap(cmaps[i], max(core_number.values()) + 1)
14.    ax[i].set_title(f"({layer_names[i]}) k-core algo | n={G.number_of_nodes()},
    e={G.number_of_edges()}", fontsize=14)
15.    sm = plt.cm.ScalarMappable(cmap=cmap, norm=plt.Normalize(vmin=1,
    vmax=2))
16.    sm.set_array([])
17.    cbar = plt.colorbar(sm, ax=ax[i])
18.    nx.draw_networkx_nodes(G, pos, core_number.keys(), node_size=90,
    ax=ax[i], cmap=cmap, node_color=list(core_number.values()))
19.    nx.draw_networkx_edges(G, pos, alpha=0.5)
20.
21. plt.savefig("./figures/network-decomposition.png")

```

Figure 39. Comparison by network decomposition.

Network decomposition per layer is based on a NetworkX's *k-core* decomposition algorithm. Core bots (most influential) seem to arrange themselves in a special geometry—a nonagon to become structurally and functionally integrated as a unit. Interestingly, there are two bots inside and outside the nonagon that interlude the chain of communication, which may be “Responder” bots (Assenmacher et al., 2020), gatekeepers, coupled scavenger node, buffer nodes (Chen et al., 2019), or just hubs for attracting neighbor nodes when building spatial connections and transforming these connections of nodes into a rudimentary ‘connectome’ or neural network (Figure 39).

In addition, by neural network topology, the ‘connectome’ likely assumes a Markov chain neural network (Tch, 2017) where looping of communication is by second-order cybernetics. It can also be noted that the shape observed assumes the pattern of “formation dynamics” (Chen et al., 2019) of bots coupled with proximity to each other and the elaboration of spatial complexity depends on their synchronization. Nodes become sparse in the human layer as they go to the periphery while nodes in the tweet layer could form small groups if distributed far outward (Figure 39). Obviously, the discourse of representation here is losing much details about the complex connectivity of nodes especially the overlaps among important nodes since the *k-core* algorithm employs a pruning process (Basaras et al., 2017, p. 13).

This section covers the local network measurements.

Visualization of Stochastic Graphs and Network Statistics

For stochastic graph modeling, the undirected multiplex graphs are converted to directed graphs before visualization. Stochastic graph models are implemented to visualize the outcomes of (and possible) vertex interactions due to randomness. These data-supported models are useful "...to discover or understand the (latent) structure of a network, as well as for clustering purposes" (Lee & Wilkinson, 2019, p. 1).

More importantly, online social media networks (e.g., Twitter, Facebook) are intrinsically non-deterministic, unpredictable, and uncertain because "structural and behavioral parameters are time varying parameters" which deterministic graphs cannot show instead these are restricted by fixed weights (Rezvanian & Meybodi, 2016, p. 621). Weights of the edges are random variables proceeding to exponential distributions (Rezvanian & Meybodi, 2016, pp. 636-638).

Node size increase shows evolution by a superimposed node that grows eccentrically. On the other hand, nodes overlapped by another large node (like a superstructure) indicate dominance and become functionally singular.

Table 16. Codes for local network statistics and plots.

```
1. network_stats_dataframe = []
2.
3. def fetchNetworkStats(gx, i):
4.     print(f"Network Layer: {layer_names[i]}")
5.     is_connected = nx.is_connected(gx)
6.     netstat = {
7.         "layer_name": layer_names[i],
8.         "no_of_nodes": gx.number_of_nodes(),
9.         "node_connectedness": is_connected,
10.        "diameter": False,
```

```

11.     "average_path_length": False,
12.     "density": nx.density(gx),
13.     "transitivity": nx.transitivity(gx),
14.     "clustering_coefficient": nx.average_clustering(gx),
15.     "average_degree": np.mean([i[1] for i in gx.degree()]),
16.     "neighborhood": len((list(nx.all_neighbors(gx, 0)))),
17.     "vertice_connectedness": nx.has_path(gx, 0, 1),
18.     "clustering_coeficient_vertices": nx.clustering(gx, 0),
19.     "degree_adjacent_vertices": gx.degree(0)
20. }
21.
22. # check connection dependent statistic algos
23. if is_connected == True:
24.     netstat["diameter"] = nx.diameter(gx)
25.     netstat["average_path_length"] = nx.average_shortest_path_length(x)
26.
27.
28. network_stats_dataframe.append(netstat)
29.
30. figx = (10,4)
31. lw = 2
32.
33. # plot degree distribution via histogram
34. degs = [i[1] for i in gx.degree()]
35. fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=figx)
36. ax.get_xaxis().tick_bottom()
37. ax.get_yaxis().tick_left()
38.
39. ax.plot(degs, color="#3F5D7D", linewidth=lw);
40. fig.suptitle(f"{layer_names[i]} - Degree Distribution")
41. plt.savefig(f"./figures/{layer_names[i]} - Degree Distribution.png")
42.
43.
44. # eigen centralities
45. eigen_centralities = nx.eigenvector_centrality(gx, max_iter=600).values()
46.
47. fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=figx)
48. ax.get_xaxis().tick_bottom()
49. ax.get_yaxis().tick_left()
50. ax.set_title(f"{layer_names[i]} - Eigenvector centrality")
51.
52. ax.plot(eigen_centralities, color="#3F5D7D", linewidth=lw);
53.
54. # plot betweenness centrality
55. between_centralities = nx.betweenness_centrality(gx).values()
56.
57. fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=figx)
58. ax.spines["top"].set_visible(False)
59. ax.spines["right"].set_visible(False)
60. ax.set_title(f"{layer_names[i]} - Betweenness centrality")

```

```

61. plt.savefig(f"./figures/{layer_names[i]} - Betweenness centrality.png")
62.
63.
64. ax.plot(between_centralities, color="#3F5D7D", linewidth=lw);
65.
66. # display unified centrality plot for the Network Layer
67. fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=figx)
68. ax.spines["top"].set_visible(False)
69. ax.spines["right"].set_visible(False)
70. ax.set_title(f"{layer_names[i]} - Centrality Plot")
71. ax.plot(between_centralities, color="green", linewidth=lw,
        label="Betweenness Centralities");
72. ax.plot(eigen_centralities, color="blue", linewidth=lw, label="Eigenvector
        Centralities");
73. ax.legend()
74. plt.savefig(f"./figures/{layer_names[i]} - Centrality Plot.png")
75.
76.
77. # display Stochastic Graph Model
78. # convert to stochastic_graph
79. sDigx = nx.stochastic_graph((gx.to_directed()))
80. node_colors = list(nx.get_node_attributes(sDigx,'color').values())
81. edge_colors = list(nx.get_edge_attributes(sDigx,'color').values())
82.
83. fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 9))
84. nx.draw(sDigx,
85.         pos=nx.kamada_kawai_layout(sDigx),
86.         # with_labels=True,
87.         ax=ax,
88.         node_size=[i[1]*10 for i in sDigx.degree()],
89.         node_color=node_colors,
90.         edge_color=edge_colors,
91.         width=1.0,
92.         font_size=10.0,
93.         font_color="#002966",
94.         alpha=0.75)
95. ax.set_title(f"{layer_names[i]} - Stochastic Graph Model")
96. ax.plot([0],[0],color="darksalmon",label="Bot layer", linewidth=10)
97. ax.plot([0],[0],color="darkgreen",label="Human Layer", linewidth=10)
98. ax.plot([0],[0],color="grey",label="Tweet", linewidth=2)
99. ax.plot([0],[0],color="blue",label="Tweet (Mention)", linewidth=2)
100. ax.legend(frameon=False)
101.
102. plt.savefig(f"./figures/{layer_names[i]} - Stochastic Graph Model.png")
103.
104.
105. # display plots per layer
106. for i, g in enumerate(graphs):
107.     fetchNetworkStats(g, i)
108.

```

```

109. # print table
110. netstatTable = pd.DataFrame(network_stats_dataframe)
111. display(netstatTable)
112.
113. #create csv file
114. netstatTable.to_csv("per_layer_network_stats.csv")

```

Table 17. Summary of Digraph statistics.

	<i>Bot Layer</i>	<i>Human Layer</i>	<i>Tweet Layer</i>
Number of Nodes	562	824	1374
Node Connectedness	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
Diameter (Maximum Eccentricity)	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
Average Path Length (Shortest Path Between Two Nodes)	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
Density	0.0020	0.0016	0.0007
Transitivity	0	0	0
Clustering Coefficient (Nodes)	0	0	0
Average Degree Connectivity (Average Nearest Neighbor Degree of Nodes)	1.1246	1.2937	1.0087
Neighborhood (Common Neighbors)	3	0	1
Vertex Connectedness (Common Pathway)	TRUE	FALSE	TRUE
Clustering Coefficient (Nodes)	0	0	0
Degree of Vertices (Adjacency)	3	0	1

Node connectivity pertains to the “minimum number of nodes that must be removed to disconnect G [graph] or render it trivial” or rather “the number of node independent paths (paths that share no nodes other than source and target)” by Menger’s theorem (Hagberg et al., 2022, p. 161).

For a directed graph (Digraph), if “**TRUE**,” nodes are strongly connected otherwise “**FALSE**” if weakly connected since ties do not stay long (temporal connectivity).

Diameter and average path length are “**FALSE**” suggesting not all nodes have bidirectional relationships (Baeldung, 2020). Vertex connectedness is “**TRUE**” if common ties exist allowing the spread of (mis)information and “**FALSE**” if there are none.

Bot density is greater than humans and tweets. Bots have more adjacent edges by degree of vertices compared with tweets while humans have none, but humans are more connected locally to bots and tweets.

Centrality describes either **structural** (node position according to distribution which is altered by the normalization of ties) or **non-structural** (functional) network properties. Moreover, structural position influences power and control of resources, in particular, information based on interactions (e.g., tweets). However, information can diffuse without hierarchy through communities.

Highly central nodes are gatekeepers. It means they have a powerful position to filter information and to restrict its access, and to moderate communities. Connected nodes have greater access to quality information since they are also more connected to other highly connected nodes (Santana, 2022).

In theory, uncertainty (entropy) is higher among peripheral nodes than centralized nodes due to the quality of information received outside the core of the network and so ‘transitivity’ (refers to transitive ties which connect nodes into cliques) emerges (Santana, 2022). However, as is clearly seen in the results (Table 17), transitivity and clustering coefficient are zero either because (a) nodes have no true connections (in the presence of many self-loops) or (b) each layer is actually dense as a “complete bipartite graph with equal sized partitions” (Schank & Wagner, 2005, p. 8) wherein vertices of the first set are connected to the vertices of the second set (Wikipedia, 2021b).

Another factor to be considered is that multigraphs have parallel or multiple edges between the same nodes (Medium, 2020). However, self-loops are allowed in a Digraph but not multiple (parallel) edges instead edges traverse the graph via neighbors or adjacent nodes (NetworkX, 2022). DiGraphs discount entanglements. Unfortunately, some details are lost. Besides, transformation of a multilayer network into a simple graph is inadvertent because current algorithms (e.g., NetworkX) require it to measure centralities (Mukunda, 2021, p. 18).

Figure 40. Plots for bot layer.

Figure 41. Plots for human layer.

Figure 42. Plots for tweet layer.

Bot centrality distribution (Figure 40) is more fluid (i.e., betweenness and eigenvector do not conform) than that of humans (Figure 41). The tweet layer (Figure 42) is disrupted by bots and then humans are nudged (unknowingly) to amplify misinformation throughout the network.

Generally, a bot pattern has abrupt increments towards the central hub while a human pattern wanes linearly with tweets away from the central hub. Moreover, spikes in the graphs that stand for the outstanding and low-key centralities will assert the cluster of nodes having the same process of communication (functional connectivity).

The unique operation of each node (a multimodal perspective) is segregated within the cluster. Communication between nodes by diffusion of (mis)information per layer or module occurs on multiple scales. By an intuitive interpretation of centrality measurements (Figure 40 through Figure 42), the level of complexity is likened to the (modularly coupled) connectivity of neural networks in the human brain (Bazinet et al., 2021).

“Eigenvector centrality is a more sophisticated view of centrality” (Hansen et al., 2020). It is highly correlated to in-degree under a symmetrized network (Valente et al., 2008, p. 11). For directed graphs, it gets high values among nodes with more in-coming links from high in-degree nodes (Meghanathan, 2015). Sophisticated bots emulate humans via in-degree connections.

Figure 43. Misinformation transmission among bots.

Bots do not have the large central hub instead they disperse exponentially into small but highly-linked homogenous clusters. There are four in the graph. An increase in the size of vertices will mean centrality rise and hub emergence (Farahani et al., 2019).

Figure 44. Misinformation transmission among humans.

Misinformation spread among human users is centrality dictated. The central hub passes the misinformation to intermediate hubs. This provides a hierarchy in gatekeeping misinformation that bots target and hijack. Human layer has more hubs than clusters compared to bots.

Moreover, vertices tend to depart (shift) from random to power-law connectivity, i.e., "...their structure being dominated by a number of 'satellite' nodes each with a small number of [*inhomogeneous*] connections, and a few 'hub' nodes with very large degrees of connectivity."

On the other hand, a linear relationship develops over a very broad range of connectivity between the frequencies of nodes with connectivity when distribution is measured on a logarithmic scale. Thus, the network evolves scale-free. Such is true

about social networks and contagion (misinformation) transmission. (Pagel et al., 2007, p. 2)

Figure 45. Misinformation transmission between bots and humans.

Bots attack the central human hub indirectly through individual and small clusters of human users at the periphery of the network. Important nodes have the tendency to overlap with each other (Guo et al., 2020, p. 3).

Visualization of Cliques

Table 18. Codes for visualizing cliques.

```
1. def runCliqueAlgos(gx, i):
2.
3.     print(f"Layer: {layer_names[i]}")
4.     cq_data = {
5.         "graph_clique_number": nx.graph_clique_number(gx),
6.         "graph_number_of_cliques": nx.graph_number_of_cliques(gx),
7.         "max_weight_clique": nx.max_weight_clique(gx, weight=None)
8.     }
9.
10.    display(cq_data)
11.
12.    enumerate_all_cliques = list(nx.enumerate_all_cliques(gx))
13.    ecn = []
14.    for ec in enumerate_all_cliques:
15.        for ex in ec:
16.            ecn.append(ex)
17.
18.    LinePlot(ecn, 2, f"{layer_names[i]} - Enumerate All Cliques")
19.
20.    find_cliques = list(nx.find_cliques(gx))
21.    ecn = []
22.    for ec in find_cliques:
23.        for ex in ec:
24.            ecn.append(ex)
25.
26.    LinePlot(ecn, 2, f"{layer_names[i]} - Find Cliques")
27.
28.    G = nx.make_clique_bipartite(gx)
29.    cliques = [v for v in G.nodes() if G.nodes[v]["bipartite"] == 0]
30.    G = nx.bipartite.project(G, cliques)
31.    G = nx.relabel_nodes(G, {-v: v - 1 for v in G})
32.
33.    sDigx = gx
34.
35.    node_colors = list(nx.get_node_attributes(sDigx, 'color').values())
36.    edge_colors = list(nx.get_edge_attributes(sDigx, 'color').values())
37.
38.    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 9))
39.    nx.draw(sDigx,
40.           pos=nx.kamada_kawai_layout(sDigx),
41.           # with_labels=True,
42.           ax=ax,
43.           node_size=70,
44.           node_color=node_colors,
```

```

45.     edge_color=edge_colors,
46.     width=1.0,
47.     font_size=10.0,
48.     font_color="#002966",
49.     alpha=0.75)
50. ax.set_title(f"{layer_names[i]} - Make Clique Bipartite & Make Max Clique
Graph")
51. ax.plot([0],[0],color="darksalmon",label="Bot layer", linewidth=10)
52. ax.plot([0],[0],color="darkgreen",label="Human Layer", linewidth=10)
53. ax.plot([0],[0],color="grey",label="Tweet", linewidth=2)
54. ax.plot([0],[0],color="blue",label="Tweet (Mention)", linewidth=2)
55. ax.legend(frameon=False)
56. plt.savefig(f"./figures/{layer_names[i]} - Make Clique Bipartite & Make Max
Clique Graph.png")
57.
58.
59.
60.
61. node_clique_number = nx.node_clique_number(gx)
62. ecn = []
63. for ec in list(node_clique_number.values()):
64.     ecn.append(ec)
65.
66. LinePlot(ecn, 2, f"{layer_names[i]} - Node Number of Cliques")
67.
68. number_of_cliques = nx.number_of_cliques(gx)
69. ecn = []
70. for ec in list(number_of_cliques.values()):
71.     ecn.append(ec)
72.
73. LinePlot(ecn, 2, f"{layer_names[i]} - Number of Cliques")
74.
75. xc = nx.cliques_containing_node(gx)
76. ecn = []
77. for ec in list(xc.values()):
78.     for ex in ec:
79.         ecn.append(len(ex))
80.
81. LinePlot(ecn, 2, f"{layer_names[i]} - Cliques Containing Node")
82.
83.
84.
85. # run all clique algos for all layers
86. for i, g in enumerate(graphs):
87.     runCliqueAlgos(g,i)

```

Cliques are co-entanglements. Largest clique (**graph_clique_number**) in all graphs is 2. Tweet layer is immense by maximal cliques (**graph_number_of_cliques**) formed up to id number 1325 (username: **DonCryptoDraper**; spammer) contrary to human layer until at 784 (**NathalieDecuyp2**; human) and bot layer until at 558 (**LaliWety**; other). Same vertices have maximum weight of cliques (**max_weight_clique**). The tweet layer owes this on a wider inclusion of vertices from 545 (**VanderluciaSch1**; other) to 1373 (**lissandro_dp**; human) followed by human layer from 809 (**cat_bair**; human) to 823 (**ArmywifeDi**; spammer) and then bot layer from 545 (**VanderluciaSch1**) to 558 (**LaliWety**). Surprisingly, these are not the most influential in the network. However, they could be contemplated as “common retweeters” (Bruno et al., 2022, p. 15) for the most influential nodes. Vertex id 545 (**VanderluciaSch1**) is superpositioning across three layers.

The graph “Enumerate All Cliques” (Figure 43 through Figure 45) shows the reported vertices above with highest peaks. The complete vertex list is in the file “**2nd_network_analysis_raw_data.csv**”.

Generally, the number of cliques escalates inconsistently in the bot layer (Figure 46) but diminishes in the human layer (Figure 47). Tweet layer bifurcates into contrasting trends (Figure 48).

Bots do not bud off from their central hub (Figure 49). Peripherally-oriented clusters are held together by a central hub in the human layer (Figure 50). Bot clusters graft themselves to the central hub of human vertices in the tweet layer by intersecting at the edges (Figure 51).

Figure 46. Clique distribution in bot layer.

Figure 47. Clique distribution in human layer.

Figure 48. Clique distribution in tweet layer.

Figure 49. Clique formation by bots.

Bot Layer - Make Clique Bipartite & Make Max Clique Graph

Figure 50. Clique formation by humans.

Human Layer - Make Clique Bipartite & Make Max Clique Graph

Figure 51. Clique formation between bots and humans.

Measurement and Visualization of Centralities per Node

Table 19. Codes for measuring centralities of each influential node.

```
1. import random
2. import operator
3.
4. # get target graph network
5. tnx = graphs[0]
6.
7. pagerank = nx.pagerank(tnx, max_iter=100)
8. bc_tnx = nx.betweenness_centrality(tnx)
9. evc_tnx = nx.eigenvector_centrality(tnx, max_iter=600)
10. ncn_tnx = nx.node_clique_number(tnx)
11. cfcc_tnx = nx.closeness_centrality(tnx)
12.
13. pagerank_dx = {}
14. bc_tnx_dx = {}
15. evc_tnx_dx = {}
16. ne_dx = {}
17. pc_dx = {}
18. ncn_dx = {}
19. cfcc_dx = {}
20.
21.
22. # parse centrality values to fit format for tabulation
23.
24. for i,x in enumerate(pagerank.values()):
25.     pagerank_dx[i] = {"page_rank":x}
26.
27. for i,x in enumerate(bc_tnx.values()):
28.     bc_tnx_dx[i] = {"betweenness_centrality":x}
29.
30. for i,x in enumerate(evc_tnx.values()):
31.     evc_tnx_dx[i] = {"eigenvector_centrality":x}
32.
33. for i,x in enumerate(NE_mid.values()):
34.     ne_dx[i] = {"node_entanglement":x}
35.
36. for i,x in enumerate(ncn_tnx.values()):
37.     ncn_dx[i] = {"clique_number":x}
38.
39. for i,x in enumerate(cfcc_tnx.values()):
40.     cfcc_dx[i] = {"closeness_centrality":x}
41.
42.
43. # set algorithm results as node attribute for tabulation
44. nx.set_node_attributes(tnx, pagerank_dx)
```

```

45.nx.set_node_attributes(tnx, bc_tnx_dx)
46.nx.set_node_attributes(tnx, evc_tnx_dx)
47.nx.set_node_attributes(tnx, ne_dx)
48.nx.set_node_attributes(tnx, ncn_dx)
49.nx.set_node_attributes(tnx, cfcc_dx)
50.
51.
52.percolation_cx = nx.percolation_centrality(tnx, attribute="page_rank")
53.
54.# parse percolation values
55.
56.for i,x in enumerate(percolation_cx.values()):
57.    pc_dx[i] = {"percolation_centrality":x}
58.
59.nx.set_node_attributes(tnx, pc_dx)

```

Correlations were performed between network measures. Significant values start at .50 (Jaadi, 2019).

Table 20. Correlation between network measures.

	<i>D</i>	<i>NE</i>	<i>NC</i>	<i>EC</i>	<i>BC</i>	<i>CC</i>	<i>BPC</i>	<i>APC</i>	<i>RW</i>	<i>PR</i>
Degree (D)	1.00									
Node Entanglement (NE)	0.02	1.00								
Number of Cliques (NC)	0.07	0.09	1.00							
Eigenvector Centrality (EC)	0.09	0.02	0.05	1.00						
Betweenness Centrality (BC)	0.26	-0.03	0.09	0.85	1.00					
Closeness Centrality (CC)	0.39	0.02	0.24	0.47	0.67	1.00				
Before Percolation Centrality (BPC)	0.26	-0.03	0.09	0.85	1.00	0.67	1.00			
After Percolation Centrality (APC)	0.23	-0.03	0.09	0.88	1.00	0.65	1.00	1.00		
Random Walk (RW)	0.68	-0.03	0.17	0.58	0.84	0.68	0.84	0.81	1.00	
PageRank (PR)	0.68	-0.03	0.17	0.58	0.84	0.68	0.84	0.81	1.00	1.00

Degree centrality, betweenness centrality, closeness centrality, and eigenvector centrality are widely used measures of individually important nodes, e.g., by (a) power and (b) frequent exchange of communication (Santana, 2022) but not sets of important nodes (Lewis, 2020, p. 78). Specifically, the various roles of edges in the process of information transmission are measured using closeness centrality and betweenness centrality (Wang et al., 2022).

The values below were also generated after running codes in Table 54.

Across all nodes ($n=1374$), “**ronnoconiv**” (other type of bots, node id 60), “**NFL**” (self-declared, node 165), “**dansiddiqui**” (spammer, node id 251), and “**StefanLazar10**” (spammer, node id 354) were distinctive by entanglement scores of .42, .37, .35, and .27 respectively. Nodes traverse either between human layer and bot layer or between human layer and tweets layer. However, since determination of most influential nodes ($n=95$) follow a degree-based (≥ 5) rule in this study, they were not included in Table 10 instead “**santa_tzu**” (spammer, node id 436) was the only one with a leading entanglement score. Intriguingly, despite a very low score of .01, “**santa_tzu**” was detected in all three layers.

Node entanglement and degree were not correlated. None of the centrality measures showed relationship to node entanglement. Therefore, it is an independent measure.

“**bev768**” (false human account, node id 155 and 620) had the highest eigenvector centrality at .70 and moves between human layer and tweets layer. Just as for node entanglement, the score does not correlate to any local measures.

Eigenvector centrality is also an independent measure. It is nonoverlapping to other network centralities.

“**bev768**” had the highest betweenness centrality score at .07. The score correlates to eigenvector centrality ($r = .85$).

“**bev768**” had the highest closeness centrality at .11. The score correlates to betweenness centrality ($r = .67$).

“**bev768**” had the highest before percolation centrality at .07, after percolation centrality at .10, and random walk and PageRank scores which are both at .06. Unfortunately, the calculated PageRank was too low (i.e., for a transition probability of the node) in reference to literature at a (normalized) minimum value of .15 (Jarman et al., 2017). The scores correlate to betweenness centrality ($r = .84$), before percolation centrality ($r = .84$), after percolation centrality ($r = .81$), closeness centrality ($r = .68$), and degree ($r = .68$), and eigenvector centrality ($r = .58$).

The high percolation centrality and betweenness centrality of “**bev768**” makes it the most important non-percolated node as target for infodemic mitigation because the node is directly at the path where the contagion spreads (Piraveenan et al., 2013). This bot is a verified super spreader.

Table 21. Codes for the calculation and visualization of percolation centrality.

```

1. def customizeNodesize(value):
2.     def_size = 80
3.     if value > 0.01:
4.         def_size = value*2000 + 580
5.     return def_size
6.
7.
8. sDigx = nx.stochastic_graph((tnx.to_directed()))
9. node_colors = list(nx.get_node_attributes(sDigx,'color').values())
10. edge_colors = list(nx.get_edge_attributes(sDigx,'color').values())
11.
12. node_colors =
13.     list(nx.get_node_attributes(sDigx,'percolation_centrality').values())
14.
15. cmap=plt.cm.rainbow
16. vmin = min(node_colors)
17. vmax = max(node_colors)
18.
19. fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 9))
20. nx.draw(sDigx,
21.         pos=nx.kamada_kawai_layout(sDigx),
22.         # with_labels=True,
23.         ax=ax,
24.         node_size=[customizeNodesize(i) for i in percolation_cx.values()],
25.         node_color=node_colors,
26.         edge_color=edge_colors,
27.         width=1.0,
28.         font_size=10.0,
29.         font_color="#002966",
30.         cmap=cmap,
31.         vmin=vmin,
32.         vmax=vmax,
33.         alpha=0.75)
34. ax.set_title(f"Percolation Centrality Stochastic Graph Model")
35. ax.plot([0],[0],color="grey",label="Tweet", linewidth=2)
36. ax.plot([0],[0],color="blue",label="Tweet (Mention)", linewidth=2)
37.
38. sm = plt.cm.ScalarMappable(cmap=cmap, norm=plt.Normalize(vmin = vmin,
39.                                                         vmax=vmax))
40. sm._A = []
41. plt.colorbar(sm)
42. ax.legend(frameon=False)
43.
44. plt.savefig(f"./figures/Percolation Centrality Stochastic Graph Model.png")

```

Figure 52. Spectrographic visualization of percolation centrality (tweet layer).

The central hub (human) is percolated by neighbors. Specifically, the entirety of the Markov process (percolation) is by human actions through bot influence (encircled in the graph): an explicit show of actor-network theory. The semi-circle node formation stipulates uncorrelated densities (Farkas et al., 2002) due to the dynamic topology.

Table 22. Codes for the calculation and visualization of betweenness centrality.

```

1. sDigx = nx.stochastic_graph((tnx.to_directed()))
2. node_colors = list(nx.get_node_attributes(sDigx,'color').values())
3. edge_colors = list(nx.get_edge_attributes(sDigx,'color').values())
4.
5. node_colors =
   list(nx.get_node_attributes(sDigx,'betweenness centrality').values())
6.
7. cmap=plt.cm.turbo
8. vmin = min(node_colors)
9. vmax = max(node_colors)
10.
11.fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 9))
12.nx.draw(sDigx,
13.     pos=nx.kamada_kawai_layout(sDigx),
14.     ax=ax,
15.     node_size=[customizeNodesize(i) for i in bc_tnx.values()],
16.     node_color=node_colors,
17.     edge_color=edge_colors,
18.     width=1.0,
19.     font_size=10.0,
20.     font_color="#002966",
21.     cmap=cmap,
22.     vmin=vmin,
23.     vmax=vmax,
24.     alpha=0.75)
25.ax.set_title(f"Betweenness Centrality Stochastic Graph Model")
26.ax.plot([0],[0],color="grey",label="Tweet", linewidth=2)
27.ax.plot([0],[0],color="blue",label="Tweet (Mention)", linewidth=2)
28.
29.sm = plt.cm.ScalarMappable(cmap=cmap, norm=plt.Normalize(vmin = vmin,
   vmax=vmax))
30.sm._A = []
31.plt.colorbar(sm)
32.ax.legend(frameon=False)
33.
34.plt.savefig(f"./figures/Betweenness Centrality Stochastic Graph Model.png")

```

Figure 53. Spectrographic visualization of betweenness centrality (tweet layer).

The pattern of betweenness centrality in the Digraph is similar to percolation centrality (Figure 52).

Table 23. Codes for betweenness and percolation centrality plots.

```
1. fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(15,4))
2. ax.spines["top"].set_visible(False)
3. ax.spines["right"].set_visible(False)
4. ax.set_title(f"Betweenness - Percolation Centralities")
5. ax.plot(list(nx.get_node_attributes(tnx,'percolation_centrality').values()),
        color="blue", linewidth=5, label="Percolation Centrality");
6. ax.plot(list(nx.get_node_attributes(tnx,'betweenness_centrality').values()),
        color="red", linewidth=5, label="Betweenness Centrality");
7.
8. ax.legend()
9. plt.savefig(f"./figures/Betweenness and Percolation - Centralities Plot.png")
```

Figure 54. Comparative distribution of betweenness and percolation centralities.

Percolation centrality works on betweenness centrality by calculation. The larger their gap, the more (mis)information flows through particular nodes (Piraveenan et al., 2013).

Table 24. Codes for the calculation and visualization of the PageRank.

```
1. sDigx = nx.stochastic_graph((tnx.to_directed()))
2. node_colors = list(nx.get_node_attributes(sDigx,'color').values())
3. edge_colors = list(nx.get_edge_attributes(sDigx,'color').values())
4.
5. node_colors = list(nx.get_node_attributes(sDigx,'page_rank').values())
6.
7. cmap=plt.cm.RdYIBu
8. vmin = min(node_colors)
9. vmax = max(node_colors)
10.
11. fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 9))
12. nx.draw(sDigx,
13.         pos=nx.kamada_kawai_layout(sDigx),
14.         ax=ax,
15.         node_size=[customizeNodesize(i) for i in pagerank.values()],
16.         node_color=node_colors,
17.         edge_color=edge_colors,
18.         width=1.0,
19.         font_size=10.0,
20.         font_color="#002966",
21.         cmap=cmap,
22.         vmin=vmin,
23.         vmax=vmax,
24.         alpha=0.75)
25. ax.set_title(f"Page Rank Stochastic Graph Model")
26. ax.plot([0],[0],color="grey",label="Tweet",linewidth=2)
27. ax.plot([0],[0],color="blue",label="Tweet (Mention)",linewidth=2)
28.
29. sm = plt.cm.ScalarMappable(cmap=cmap, norm=plt.Normalize(vmin = vmin,
    vmax=vmax))
30. sm._A = []
31. plt.colorbar(sm)
32. ax.legend(frameon=False)
33.
34. plt.savefig(f"./figures/Page Rank Stochastic Graph Model.png")
```

Figure 55. Spectrographic visualization of the PageRank results (tweet layer).

PageRank values are low. The calculation is defined by (1) number of inbound links and (2) weighting of the linking page (Ryte.com, 2021), which are the nodes in the graph. There are more outbound links by spammers than inbound links based on the results contrary to sophisticated bots. Nodes are broadcasting (seeding) tweets.

Although nodes will stay active if more neighbors are active by tweets, submodularity condition can be factored in, i.e., “the marginal effect of each neighbor is decreasing when the set of active neighbors increases” (Mossel & Roch, 2010). Node activity is cancelled by other similarly active nodes. Weighting of node influence is spread out globally. The limitation of the PageRank algorithm is another factor. It does not account for the linking patterns on a temporal basis (Mariani et al., 2015).

Table 25. Codes for the calculation and visualization of Random Walks.

```

1. Graph = tnx
2.
3.
4. # random_node is the start node selected randomly
5. random_node = random.choice([i for i in range(Graph.number_of_nodes())])
6. dict_counter = {} #initialise the value for all nodes as 0
7. for i in range(Graph.number_of_nodes()):
8.     dict_counter[i] = 0
9. # increment by traversing through all neighbors nodes
10. dict_counter[random_node] = dict_counter[random_node]+1
11.
12. #Traversing through the neighbors of start node
13. for i in range(100):
14.     list_for_nodes = list(Graph.neighbors(random_node))
15.     if len(list_for_nodes)==0:# if random_node having no outgoing edges
16.         random_node = random.choice([i for i in
            range(Graph.number_of_nodes())])
17.         dict_counter[random_node] = dict_counter[random_node]+1
18.
19.     else:
20.         random_node = random.choice(list_for_nodes) #choose a node
            randomly from neighbors
21.         dict_counter[random_node] = dict_counter[random_node]+1
22.
23. # using pagerank() method to provide ranks for the nodes
24. rank_node = nx.pagerank(Graph)
25.
26. #sorting the values of rank and random walk of respective nodes
27. sorted_rank = sorted(rank_node.items(), key=operator.itemgetter(1))
28. sorted_random_walk = sorted(dict_counter.items(),
            key=operator.itemgetter(1))
29. # print(sorted_rank)
30. # print(sorted_random_walk)
31.
32. # parse random walk with the rest of the network analysis attributes
33.
34. rw_dx = {}
35.
36. for i,x in enumerate(rank_node.items()):
37.     rw_dx[i] = {"random_walk":x[1]}
38.
39. nx.set_node_attributes(tnx, rw_dx)
40.
41. # visualiza network with random walk
42.
43. sDigx = nx.stochastic_graph((tnx.to_directed()))
44. node_colors = list(nx.get_node_attributes(sDigx,'color').values())
45. edge_colors = list(nx.get_edge_attributes(sDigx,'color').values())

```

```

46.
47. node_colors = list(nx.get_node_attributes(sDigx,'random_walk').values())
48.
49. cmap=plt.cm.PiYG
50. vmin = min(node_colors)
51. vmax = max(node_colors)
52.
53. fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 9))
54. nx.draw(sDigx,
55.         pos=nx.kamada_kawai_layout(sDigx),
56.         ax=ax,
57.         node_size=[customizeNodesize(i) for i in
58.                   nx.get_node_attributes(sDigx,'random_walk').values()],
59.         node_color=node_colors,
60.         edge_color=edge_colors,
61.         width=1.0,
62.         font_size=10.0,
63.         font_color="#002966",
64.         cmap=cmap,
65.         vmin=vmin,
66.         vmax=vmax,
67.         alpha=0.75)
68. ax.set_title(f"Random Walk Stochastic Graph Model")
69. ax.plot([0],[0],color="grey",label="Tweet", linewidth=2)
70. ax.plot([0],[0],color="blue",label="Tweet (Mention)", linewidth=2)
71. sm = plt.cm.ScalarMappable(cmap=cmap, norm=plt.Normalize(vmin = vmin,
72.                                                         vmax=vmax))
73. sm._A = []
74. plt.colorbar(sm)
75. ax.legend(frameon=False)
76. plt.savefig(f"./figures/Random Walk Stochastic Graph Model.png")
77.
78. # nodes_dx contains the processed networkx graph data
79. nodes_dx = list(tnx.nodes(data=True))

```

SOURCE: Gulshan, 2020.

Figure 56. Spectrographic visualization of the Random Walks (tweet layer).

Results showed no difference to PageRank. Unfortunately, random walk values are low. Overall, there is a low probability of returning to the same path because the network is heterogenous (Collins et al., 2021, p. 259).

Table 26. Codes for visualization of random walk distribution.

```
1. random_walk_values = nx.get_node_attributes(tnx,'random_walk').values()
2.
3. figx = (15,4)
4. fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=figx)
5. ax.spines["top"].set_visible(False)
6. ax.spines["right"].set_visible(False)
7. ax.set_title(f"Random Walk Node values")
8.
9. ax.plot(random_walk_values, color="green", linewidth=5.0);
10. plt.savefig(f"./figures/Random Walk Values.png")
```

Figure 57. Random walk distribution.

Random walk is periodic instead of the expected aperiodic (Kriener et al., 2012, p. 3) notably by having a large gap approximately between node id 250 (username: **KJP46**; spammer) and 610 (username: **margbrennan**; human). Based on structure, not all paths from every node connect to every other node in the Digraph representation.

The von Neumann Graph Entropy

Table 27. Codes for the evolution of von Neumann graph entropy/VNGE.

```
1. import time
2. from scipy.sparse.linalg.eigen.arpack import eigsh
3.
4.
5. def normalized_laplacian(adj_matrix):
6.     nodes_degree = np.sum(adj_matrix, axis=1)
7.     nodes_degree_sqrt = 1/np.sqrt(nodes_degree)
8.     degree_matrix = np.diag(nodes_degree_sqrt)
9.     eye_matrix = np.eye(adj_matrix.shape[0])
10.    return eye_matrix - degree_matrix * adj_matrix * degree_matrix
11.
12.
13. def unnormalized_laplacian(adj_matrix):
14.     nodes_degree = np.sum(adj_matrix, axis=1)
15.     degree_matrix = np.diag(nodes_degree)
16.     return degree_matrix - adj_matrix
17.
18.
19.
20. def VNGE_exact(adj_matrix):
21.     start = time.time()
22.     nodes_degree = np.sum(adj_matrix, axis=1)
23.     c = 1.0 / np.sum(nodes_degree)
24.     laplacian_matrix = c * unnormalized_laplacian(adj_matrix)
25.     eigenvalues, _ = np.linalg.eig(laplacian_matrix)
26.     eigenvalues[eigenvalues < 0] = 0
27.     pos = eigenvalues > 0
28.     H_vn = - np.sum(eigenvalues[pos] * np.log2(eigenvalues[pos]))
29.     return H_vn
30.
31.
32. def VNGE_FINGER(adj_matrix):
33.     start = time.time()
34.     nodes_degree = np.sum(adj_matrix, axis=1)
35.     c = 1.0 / np.sum(nodes_degree)
36.     edge_weights = 1.0 * adj_matrix[np.nonzero(adj_matrix)]
37.     approx = 1.0 - np.square(c) * (np.sum(np.square(nodes_degree)) +
38.     np.sum(np.square(edge_weights)))
39.     laplacian_matrix = unnormalized_laplacian(adj_matrix)
40.     ""
41.     eigenvalues, _ = np.linalg.eig(laplacian_matrix) # the biggest reduction
42.     eig_max = c * max(eigenvalues)
43.     ""
```

```

43. eig_max, _ = eigsh(laplacian_matrix, 1, which='LM')
44. eig_max = eig_max[0] * c
45. H_vn = - approx * np.log2(eig_max)
46. print('H_vn approx:', H_vn)
47. print('Time:', time.time() - start)
48.
49.
50. Nmx = Nmx.astype(float)
51.
52. # evolution of von neumann graph entropy
53. envge = VNGE_exact(Nmx)
54. print("Von Neumann Graph Entropy Exact: ", envge)
55. VNGE_FINGER(Nmx)

```

SOURCE: Tsui, 2021.

Spreading (diffusion) capacity of nodes is explained by information entropy (Guo et al., 2020, p. 3). The von Neumann graph entropy (VNGE) facilitates measurement of (1) information divergence and (2) distance between (undirected) graphs such that $G = (V, E, A)$. Specifically, A denotes the symmetric weight matrix (degree matrix) or $D = \text{diag}(d_1, \dots, d_n)$. The Laplacian matrix (normalized graph) is simply $L = D - A$. The Laplacian spectrum (of the multi-scale graph structure) is shown

in eigenvalues, λ_i . VNGE equation is put together as: $H_{vn}(G) = -\sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{\lambda_i}{\text{vol}(G)} \log \frac{\lambda_i}{\text{vol}(G)} \right)$

, where volume of graph or $\text{vol}(G) = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_i = \text{trace}(L)$. Time complexity is calculated as

$O(n^3)$. (Tsui, 2021)

The VNGE approximate is calculated using the Fast Incremental von Neumann Graph Entropy (FINGER) algorithm (Tsui, 2021), which reduces the computation of VNGE from cubic complexity to linear complexity and makes online computation possible and efficient (Chen et al. 2019).

Furthermore, VNGE discloses (1) the quantum states (especially as a mixture of pure states) whenever there are changes in the density matrix, (2) graph centralization, and (3) the maximum amount of extractable classical information (Minello et al., 2019, pp. 2, 4). Obviously, global structural information is measured by the VNGE equation whereas the Shannon entropy equation calculates graph complexity based on local (histographical) distribution of network graph structures (Liu et al., 2021). However, use of spectral representation (e.g., decomposition) solves this problem (Liu et al., 2021), which was implemented.

The exact VNGE is 3.2549 and the approximated value is 2.1320. Time complexity is at .0109. This can mean that the Twitter network evolves spatiotemporally every .011 seconds. Entropy changes as new edges are added to the graph (Minello et al., 2019, p. 27). By the average of approximated and exact VNGEs, it is deduced that 2.69345 edges are added each .011 seconds.

VNGE decreases as the average degree increases according to Laplacian spectrum observations (correlation is due to majorization), but is less sensitive to change of graph size (Liu et al., 2021). In a straightforward calculation, this is

$$\text{Average Degree} = \frac{\text{Total Edges}}{\text{Total Nodes}} = \frac{m}{n} \text{ (Lizardo \& Jilbert, 2020). So, when compared per layer: } \text{bots} = \frac{316}{562} = .5623; \text{ humans} = \frac{533}{824} = .6468; \text{ and } \text{tweets} = \frac{693}{1374} = .5044,$$

it is claimed here that the center of entropy (information divergence) is the human layer but is crossing to and from the bot layer (exchanged a lot) than tweet layer with respect to value difference of .0845 (human and bot layers) versus .1424 (human and tweet layers). This is depicted in Figure 23 whenever content transformation is cycle milled.

Hub centrality is calculated for the purpose of knowing which layer has the most influence in the network and once more comparing the entropies intuitively. This

equation was used: $Hub\ Centrality = \frac{Total\ Edges\ x\ 2}{Total\ Nodes}$ (Mukunda, 2021, p. 11). The layer

is a hub if value is above or equal to average centrality value. The calculations are

expressed in the following: $bots = \frac{316 \times 2}{562} = 1.1246 (> .5623)$;

$humans = \frac{533 \times 2}{824} = 1.2937 (> .6468)$; and $tweets = \frac{693 \times 2}{1374} = 1.0087 (> .5044)$. The human

layer is most influential, but entropy flows into this hub from the bot layer. Entropy in the tweet layer will always be the highest. Entropy increases in the tweet layer every time misinformation floods the network. Misinformation is cogenerated by bots and humans.

Majorization was contemplated in the visualization of subgraphs to preserve the relationship between 'degree' (sequence of structural information) and 'spectrum' (pattern decomposition of structural information, e.g., energy) representation of quantum states (Liu et al., 2021). Hence, stochastic subgraphs were used.

Entropy of Entanglement

Table 28. Codes for calculating entropy of entanglement.

```
1. from __future__ import division
2. import numpy as np
3. import networkx as nx
4. import time
5. import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
6. import warnings; warnings.simplefilter('ignore')
7. import operator
8. from progressbar import ProgressBar
9. from random import seed, random
10. import scipy as sci
11. import sklearn
```

```

12. import seaborn as sns
13. from sklearn import metrics
14. import os
15.
16. #utility for line plotting
17. def LinePlot(data, lw, title):
18.     figx = (10,4)
19.     fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=figx)
20.     ax.spines["top"].set_visible(False)
21.     ax.spines["right"].set_visible(False)
22.     ax.set_title(f"{title}")
23.
24.     ax.plot(data, color="orange", linewidth=lw);
25.     plt.savefig(f"./figures/{title}.png")
26.
27.
28.
29.
30. def entropy(G,beta):
31.     ### Calculates the entropy of network G at beta as diffusion time, defined
    at https://doi.org/10.1038/s42005-021-00633-0
32.     Ls = np.sort(nx.laplacian_spectrum(G))
33.     Z = np.sum(np.exp(-beta*Ls))
34.     p = np.exp(-beta*Ls)/Z
35.     p=np.delete(p,np.where(p<10**-20))
36.     #p=np.delete(p,np.where(p<10**-8))
37.     S = np.sum( -p * np.log2(p) )
38.     return S
39.
40. def entropy_diff_time_small(G):
41.     ### Calculates the entropy of network G at small diffusion time, defined at
    https://doi.org/10.1038/s42005-021-00633-0
42.     Ls = np.sort(nx.laplacian_spectrum(G))
43.     diff_time = Ls[np.where(Ls>10**-12)[0]][0]
44.     k_ = len(G.edges())/len(G.nodes())
45.     beta = -np.log(.9)/diff_time
46.     print('beta = ',beta)
47.     sp = np.exp(-beta*Ls)
48.     Z = np.sum(sp)
49.     p = np.exp(-beta*Ls)/Z
50.     p=np.delete(p,np.where(p<10**-20))
51.     S = np.sum( -p * np.log2(p) )
52.     return S,beta
53.
54. def entropy_diff_time_mid(G):
55.     ### Calculates the entropy of network G at middle diffusion time, defined at
    https://doi.org/10.1038/s42005-021-00633-0
56.     Ls = np.sort(nx.laplacian_spectrum(G))
57.     diff_time = Ls[np.where(Ls>10**-12)[0]][0]
58.     k_ = len(G.edges())/len(G.nodes())

```

```

59. beta = -np.log(.33)/diff_time
60. print('beta = ',beta)
61. sp = np.exp(-beta*Ls)
62. Z = np.sum(sp)
63. p = np.exp(-beta*Ls)/Z
64. p=np.delete(p,np.where(p<10**-20))
65. S = np.sum( -p * np.log2(p) )
66. return S,beta
67.
68. def entropy_diff_time_large(G):
69.     ### Calculates the entropy of network G at large diffusion time, defined at
       https://doi.org/10.1038/s42005-021-00633-0
70.     Ls = np.sort(nx.laplacian_spectrum(G))
71.     diff_time = Ls[np.where(Ls>10**-12)[0]][0]
72.     k_ = len(G.edges())/len(G.nodes())
73.     beta = -np.log(.01)/diff_time
74.     print('beta = ',beta)
75.     sp = np.exp(-beta*Ls)
76.     Z = np.sum(sp)
77.     p = np.exp(-beta*Ls)/Z
78.     p=np.delete(p,np.where(p<10**-20))
79.     S = np.sum( -p * np.log2(p) )
80.     return S,beta
81.
82. def entanglement_small(G):
83.     ### Calculates network entanglement of all nodes of network G at small
       diffusion time, defined at https://doi.org/10.1038/s42005-021-00633-0
84.     pbar = ProgressBar()
85.     S_1,beta = entropy_diff_time_small(G)
86.     ent = {}
87.     nodes = list(G.nodes())
88.     for i in pbar(range(len(nodes))):
89.         G_i=G.copy()
90.         k = G_i.degree[nodes[i]]
91.         G_i.remove_node(nodes[i])
92.         S_2 = entropy(G_i,beta)
93.         G_star = nx.star_graph(k+1)
94.         S_star = entropy(G_star,beta)
95.         S_2 = S_2 + S_star
96.         ent[nodes[i]]=S_2 - S_1
97.     return ent
98.
99. def entanglement_mid(G):
100.    ### Calculates network entanglement of all nodes of network G at middle
       diffusion time defined at https://doi.org/10.1038/s42005-021-00633-0
101.    pbar = ProgressBar()
102.    S_1,beta = entropy_diff_time_mid(G)
103.    ent = {}
104.    nodes = list(G.nodes())
105.    for i in pbar(range(len(nodes))):

```

```

106.     G_i=G.copy()
107.     k = G_i.degree[nodes[i]]
108.     G_i.remove_node(nodes[i])
109.     S_2 = entropy(G_i,beta)
110.     G_star = nx.star_graph(k+1)
111.     S_star = entropy(G_star,beta)
112.     S_2 = S_2 + S_star
113.     ent[nodes[i]]=S_2 - S_1
114.     return ent
115.
116. def entanglement_large(G):
117.     ### Calculates network entanglement of all nodes of network G at large
diffusion time defined at https://doi.org/10.1038/s42005-021-00633-0
118.     pbar = ProgressBar()
119.     S_1,beta = entropy_diff_time_large(G)
120.     ent = {}
121.     nodes = list(G.nodes())
122.     for i in pbar(range(len(nodes))):
123.         G_i=G.copy()
124.         k = G_i.degree[nodes[i]]
125.         G_i.remove_node(nodes[i])
126.         S_2 = entropy(G_i,beta)
127.         G_star = nx.star_graph(k+1)
128.         S_star = entropy(G_star,beta)
129.         S_2 = S_2 + S_star
130.         ent[nodes[i]]=S_2 - S_1
131.     return ent
132.
133. G = graphs[1]
134. # NE_small=entanglement_small(G) # calculates the entanglement at
short-range interactions
135. NE_mid=entanglement_mid(G) # calculates the entanglement at middle-
range interactions
136. # NE_large=entanglement_large(G) # calculates the entanglement at
large-range interactions
137. LinePlot(list(NE_mid.values()),2,f"Node Entanglement Values")

```

SOURCE: Ghavasieh et al., 2021.

Another source of entropy is node entanglement in the network. It measures the dynamic process of node entanglement at their edges while the network evolves as misinformation diffuses continuously (Ghavasieh et al., 2021). The result is greater than 1 ($\beta = 1.69$) which suggests that the process occurs during an unstable state. This

also means that nodes were entangled by 169%, but result may be considered typical for large systems (Bianchi & Dona, 2019).

In addition, entropy will remain nonzero because of entanglements (Bianchi & Dona, 2019). Large entanglements were shown between node id 0 to node 400 containing the most influential nodes. Specifically, node id 0 (username: **Left_of_You**) through 100 (**Daniel2510G**) are spambots. They not only rose and set off a contagion in the network but become ubiquitous by creating multiple links.

On the other hand, node id 129 (**CobyJayJr42**) through 712 (**babibelle33**) are false human accounts and are good in reproducing the pattern of human connectivity through cascading entanglements (power-law distribution). Succeeding node types alternate between spammer and false human accounts interspersed with other bots and private accounts. Gaps may imply disentanglements to rewire in the network.

Figure 58. Distribution of node entanglements (Laplacian range, 0.0 to 0.5).

Multilayer Entanglement

Table 29. Codes for calculating network entanglement.

```
1. from py3plex.core import multinet
2. from py3plex.algorithms.multilayer_algorithms.entanglement import
   compute_entanglement_analysis
3.
4. # visualization from a simple file
5. multilayer_network = multinet.multi_layer_network().load_network(
6.     "./dataset/mxlist.txt", directed=True, input_type="multiedgelist")
7. multilayer_network.basic_stats()
8.
9. analysis = compute_entanglement_analysis(multilayer_network)
10.
11. print("%d connected components of layers" % len(analysis))
12. for i, b in enumerate(analysis):
13.     print('--- block %d' % i)
14.     layer_labels = b['Layer entanglement'].keys()
15.     print('Covering layers: %s' % layer_labels)
16.
17.     print('Entanglement intensity: %f' % b['Entanglement intensity'])
18.     print('Layer entanglement: %s' % b['Layer entanglement'])
19.     print('Entanglement homogeneity: %f' % b['Entanglement homogeneity'])
20.     print('Normalized homogeneity: %f' % b['Normalized homogeneity'])
```

SOURCE: Škrlj, 2021.

There are 1635 nodes (256 are atypical) and 1542 links. Overall, entanglement intensity is .2444. Bot layer has .4161, human layer has .0038, and tweet layer has .9093. Entanglement homogeneity is lower than 1 at .7674 (normalized, .5569). Bot layer entanglement intensity is much higher than human layer because bots were programmed to elicit multiple connections through human users. Tweet layer is expected to collect dense entanglements because misinformation is actively spread here.

Low intensity indicates a less coupled or sparse network. Intensity is directly correlated with 'edge dropout' (i.e., the emergence of layered patterns of intensity

following and affecting the network's generative process) as opposed to number of layers, which is uniformly distributed with regard to homogeneity. Nodes agglomerate based on the phenomenon of homophily or similarity, but entanglement homogeneity is low (<1) in the network which means there are many cross-links between bots and humans. On the other hand, layer interaction of similar nodes leads to clique formation in low dropout areas. (Škrlj & Renoust, 2019)

The section below covers dynamical node measurements.

Node Synchronization

Table 30. Codes for simulating Kuramoto's node synchronization.

```
1. import seaborn as sns
2. from kuramoto import Kuramoto
3.
4. kuramoto_results = {}
5.
6. def runKuramotoModel(gx, i):
7.     sns.set_style("whitegrid")
8.     sns.set_context("notebook", font_scale=1.6)
9.
10.    network_layer = layer_names[i]
11.
12.    # Instantiate a random graph and transform into an adjacency matrix
13.    graph_nx = nx.k_core(gx)
14.    graph = nx.to_numpy_array(graph_nx)
15.
16.    # Instantiate model with parameters
17.    model = Kuramoto(coupling=3, dt=0.01, T=10, n_nodes=len(graph))
18.
19.    # Run simulation - output is time series for all nodes (node vs time)
20.    act_mat = model.run(adj_mat=graph)
21.
22.    # Plot all the time series
23.    plt.figure(figsize=(12, 4))
24.    plt.plot(np.sin(act_mat.T))
```

```

25. plt.xlabel('time', fontsize=25)
26. plt.ylabel(r'$\sin(\theta)$', fontsize=25)
27. plt.suptitle(f'{network_layer} - Network Transformation Time Series',y=1.02,
    fontsize=15)
28. plt.savefig(f'./figures/{network_layer} - Network Transformation Time
    Series.png')
29.
30. # Step 2
31. # Plot evolution of global order parameter R_t
32. plt.figure(figsize=(12, 4))
33. plt.plot(
34.     [Kuramoto.phase_coherence(vec)
35.      for vec in act_mat.T],
36.     'o'
37. )
38. plt.ylabel(f'order parameter', fontsize=25)
39. plt.xlabel('time', fontsize=25)
40. plt.ylim((-0.01, 1))
41. plt.suptitle(f'{network_layer} - Global order parameter',y=1.02, fontsize=15)
42. plt.savefig(f'./figures/{network_layer} - Global order parameter (k).png')
43.
44.
45.
46. # Step 3
47. # Plot oscillators in complex plane at times t = 0, 250, 500
48. fig, axes = plt.subplots(ncols=3, nrows=1, figsize=(18, 5),
49.                          subplot_kw={
50.                              "ylim": (-1.1, 1.1),
51.                              "xlim": (-1.1, 1.1),
52.                              "xlabel": r'$\cos(\theta)$',
53.                              "ylabel": r'$\sin(\theta)$',
54.                          })
55.
56. times = [0, 200, 500]
57. for ax, time in zip(axes, times):
58.     ax.plot(np.cos(act_mat[:, time]),
59.            np.sin(act_mat[:, time]),
60.            'o',
61.            markersize=10)
62.     ax.set_title(f'Time = {time}')
63.
64. plt.suptitle(f'{network_layer} - Oscillators in complex plane',y=1.02,
    fontsize=15)
65. plt.savefig(f'./figures/{network_layer} - Oscillators in complex plane.png')
66.
67.
68.
69. #Step 4
70.
71. # Run model with different coupling (K) parameters

```

```

72. coupling_vals = np.linspace(0, 0.6, 100)
73. runs = []
74. for coupling in coupling_vals:
75.     model = Kuramoto(coupling=coupling, dt=0.1, T=500,
n_nodes=graph_nx.number_of_nodes())
76.     model.natfreqs = np.random.normal(1, 0.1,
size=graph_nx.number_of_nodes()) # reset natural frequencies
77.     act_mat = model.run(adj_mat=graph)
78.     runs.append(act_mat)
79.
80. # Check that natural frequencies are correct (we need them for prediction
of Kc)
81. plt.figure()
82. plt.hist(model.natfreqs)
83. plt.xlabel('natural frequency')
84. plt.ylabel('count')
85. plt.suptitle(f"{network_layer} - Natural Frequency",y=1.02, fontsize=15)
86. plt.savefig(f"./figures/{network_layer} - Natural Frequency.png")
87.
88.
89.
90. # step 5
91. # Plot all time series for all coupling values (color coded)
92. runs_array = np.array(runs)
93.
94. plt.figure()
95. for i, coupling in enumerate(coupling_vals):
96.     plt.plot(
97.         [model.phase_coherence(vec)
98.          for vec in runs_array[i, :].T],
99.         c=str(1-coupling), # higher -> darker
100.        )
101.     plt.ylabel(r'order parameter ( $R_t$ )')
102.     plt.xlabel('time')
103.     plt.suptitle(f"{network_layer} - Coupling values time series",y=1.02,
fontsize=15)
104.     plt.savefig(f"./figures/{network_layer} - Coupling values time series.png")
105.
106.
107.
108. #Step 6
109.
110. # Plot final Rt for each coupling value
111. plt.figure()
112. for i, coupling in enumerate(coupling_vals):
113.     r_mean = np.mean([model.phase_coherence(vec)
114.                       for vec in runs_array[i, :, -1000:].T]) # mean over last 1000
steps
115.     plt.scatter(coupling, r_mean, c='steelblue', s=20, alpha=0.7)
116.

```

```

117. # Predicted Kc – analytical result (from paper)
118. Kc = np.sqrt(8 / np.pi) * np.std(model.natfreqs) # analytical result (from
    paper)
119.
120. # Save Network Kc data
121. kuramoto_results[network_layer] = Kc
122.
123. plt.vlines(Kc, 0, 1, linestyle='--', color='orange', label='analytical
    prediction')
124.
125. plt.legend()
126. plt.grid(linestyle='--', alpha=0.8)
127. plt.ylabel('order parameter (R)')
128. plt.xlabel('coupling (K)')
129. sns.despine()
130. plt.suptitle(f'{network_layer} - Final coupling (Kc)', y=1.02, fontsize=15)
131. plt.savefig(f'./figures/{network_layer} - Final coupling (Kc).png')
132.
133.
134.
135.
136.
137. # loop through network layers
138. for i, g in enumerate(graphs):
139.     runKuramotoModel(g,i)
140.
141. # print kuramoto Kc Coupling Results:
142. print(kuramoto_results)

```

SOURCE: Damicelli, 2021.

The Kuramoto model exposes “coupled group dynamics” (Petkoski et al., 2018)

based on this equation: $\frac{d\theta_i}{dt} = \omega_i + \frac{K}{M_i} \sum_j A_{ij} \sin(\theta_j - \theta_i)$, where K is the coupling

parameter and M_i is the number of oscillators or nodes (N) interacting with oscillator

i , and A is the adjacency matrix of node interactions (commonly binary and

undirected or gaussian-like symmetric function) that if *node i* interacts with *node j*,

$A_{ij} = 1$, or else 0 (Damicelli, 2021).

Basically, the node moving ahead (*node i*) is stimulated to slow down while the node running behind (*node j*) to accelerate. Each node as an oscillator has its own natural frequency ω or a constant angular velocity. A random initial (angular) position θ_i is given to each oscillator (Damicelli, 2021).

As coupling strength increases from 0 to 1, the system is seen to transition from a nonsynchronous to a bistable state and then to a synchronous state where explosive synchronization of nodes occurs. Nodes within the same frequency range will cluster, but once other nodes (oscillating on a different frequency) join the cluster, it results to an explosive synchronization from the clash of frequency mismatch. This is proportional to the coupling strength generated. Partial synchronization is not shown because nodes will have the same critical coupling strength to reach synchronization. When coupling strength exceeds 1, the system becomes a mixed state which will be replaced by a continuous transition. Negative coupling occurs when frequency mismatch is very large between nodes thereby increasing the order parameter (number of transitions, e.g., -1, -0.5, 0.8, 1.0, 1.1, 1.7) to increase synchronous nodes or decrease nonsynchronous nodes compared to positive coupling. Buffer nodes work in between synchronous and nonsynchronous nodes, but suppress the latter whenever coupling strength increments during partial synchronization and synchronized nodes. The moment nonsynchronous nodes decrease, buffer nodes compete with synchronous nodes. The fate of buffer nodes can either become nonsynchronous or synchronous (Chen et al., 2019).

From an adjacency matrix of nodes per layer, the relative 'strength of interaction' (critical coupling) among bots were higher ($K_c = .21$) than humans ($K_c = .11$) and tweets ($K_c = .14$) based on Damicelli's (2021) initial parameters:

$coupling = 3$, $dt = .01$, $T = 10$. Predicted coupling strengths were too small (weak) for explosive synchronization to show up according to literature which is a value above 1 (Millán et al., 2020; Rodrigues et al., 2016, pp. 17-18; Dörfler & Bullo, 2011).

In an old experiment with 500 oscillators at a low coupling constant of $K = .20$, "...the system can still achieve some level of synchronization. However, it clearly takes the system longer to establish the partially synchronized state" while strong fluctuations were observed in these levels and "...the coupling is weak enough to permit the formation of an unsynchronized component. The fluctuations caused by this component grow as the coupling constant is reduced further, until all synchronization vanishes" (English, 2007, p. 148).

The sharp network transformation into phase-locking (as a function of coupling strength based on time of convergence) is shown throughout the evolution of oscillator phases. On the other hand, the order parameter R_t calculates the global synchronization at time (t), which is the normalized length of the sum of all vectors or nodes oscillating in the complex plane (Damicelli, 2021).

In Figure 59, bots converged or were synchronized around 400 seconds (6.67 minutes) and the sharp transition was observed before reaching 200 seconds (3.33 minutes). At 500 seconds, bots synchronize tighter.

Nodes are completely unable to synchronize for very low coupling strength ($K < .15$) and the same is true beyond the critical coupling. However, what happens beyond critical coupling is first, they are "...suddenly able to form a broad cluster that 'travels' together on the unit circle [*hence more globally connected*]," e.g., $K = .80$, $N = 250$ and second, synchronization happens (English, 2007, pp. 146, 148). It only shows that the 'degree of synchronization' (cluster size) depends sensitively on

the coupling strength and the N , for example, the outcomes in Figure 59 ($n = 562$) versus Figure 61 ($n = 478$). At $K_c = .15$, there is no bot synchronization and phase-locking.

Ultimately, node oscillations will converge to an equilibrium. It is important to address that synchronization weakens when the order parameter is increased (Filatrella et al., 2007, p. 9). Nodes break up whenever K is weak (e.g., $K/N = 1$) but will go on relatively synchronous if K is strong (e.g., $K/N = 12$). A large cluster of synchronous oscillators (like bot aggregation) are observable with an intermediate coupling (e.g., $K/N = 6$). However, nodes are not locked to this cluster if natural frequencies are at the tails of the distribution. The understanding of this phenomenon is that the interaction functions will overcome the dissipation of natural frequencies as K increases. Thus, the result is a transition from incoherence to partial and then full synchronization (Breakspear et al., 2010).

By "...principle of [*node*] organization: those oscillators in the synchronized cluster that have an intrinsic frequency above the mean will lead in phase, and those with lower than [*the*] average intrinsic frequencies will trail," implies that "...the only thing holding the fast oscillators back is the combined pull of the slower ones, and vice versa" (English, 2007, p. 146).

In this study, low coupling strength is $K \leq .20$ while $K = .40$ is high (English, 2007, p. 147). Nodes with $K_c \geq .12$ (bots and tweets) is believed to synchronize in two states, which will merge into one if $K_c = .25$ via discontinuous transition (Lei et al., 2021). The two states can be observed as "...the synchronized cluster and the unsynchronized background" (English, 2007, p. 146). Bots were more actively engaged and can easily organize based on results (Figure 59).

Since phase-locking was observed to be partial (Breakspear et al., 2010, p. 3), the bot state is also partially 'entrained' or "...the order parameter is [*partially*] bounded from above and below" (Bronski & Wang, 2021, p. 16), this actually gives a "...sufficiently strong coupling when the natural frequencies of the individual oscillators are independent identically distributed random variables, as well as upper and lower bounds on the size of the largest cluster of partially entrained oscillators" (Bronski & Wang, 2021, p. 1).

Partial phase-locking involves nodes (the oscillators) that could potentially become phase locked while the rest are a 'perturbation' (an attractor to converge asymptotically) to the former (Bronski & Wang, 2021, pp. 6-7). This gives bots an advantage to synchronize among themselves and pull other nodes within their radius.

In the evolution of phases, positive and negative sine values may also denote inhibitory (kinetic energy to dissipate energy) and excitatory (lower potentials to displace equilibrium) transitions respectively. Bots operate in favor of a more negative potential compared to humans. However, the latter have more energy that needed to be dissipated.

Figure 59. Bot layer synchronization ($n = 562$).

Figure 60. Natural frequency, phase transition, and coupling strength estimation.

The missing natural frequency values suggest bots have split dynamics, specifically the possibility of chimera states: “coexistence of coherent and incoherent dynamics” (Lodi et al., 2021, p. 9) or some bots were synchronized and others were desynchronized independently at the same time like brain neurons, which correspond to artificial intelligence. Plateaus before and after the frequency distribution were interrupted which also suggests multi stability (having two equilibrium periods) at a certain number of (a) bots ($n = 562$) particularly in Figure 59, (b) combinations or variants, and (c) interactions of these variants. The significant proportion of variants diluting the relationships among other nodes and timing of their interactions will need another investigation.

The fact that bots displayed natural or rather intrinsic frequency relating to synchronization (even though discontinuous) affirms the network phenomenon of synchronization among nodes, regardless of whether they are natural or synthetically made (Lodi et al., 2021, p. 1). Node clusters synchronize at the moment of stability (Lodi et al., 2021, p. 3).

Nodes (in clusters) synchronize interdependently in complex networks. Here node edges intertwine (entangle structurally) to communicate mostly via one-way

rather than by bidirectional propagation of information (or its counterpart energy) using preferred paths. Furthermore, synchronization of nodes (bots) is one-way dependent on other nodes (Lodi et al., 2021, p. 2).

Figure 61. Bot layer synchronization ($n = 478$).

Bots attempted to lock into a synchronized phase by attracting more of each other (Figure 61), but it showed that a reduction (14.95%) of bots from 562 to 478 has prevented synchronization. Although chaos could have favored the migration of bots and their aggregation, it did not favor the increase and retention to a stable coupling strength. Raising the notion of ‘anisotropy’ could explain how bots meddle their internal states (Ren et al., 2016) to at least pseudo synchronize which in turn attracts more potential.

Figure 62. Natural frequency, phase transition, and coupling strength estimation.

The Twitter network operates like an electric circuit too. For the sake of clarity, natural frequency does not equal to oscillating frequency. Oscillators (nodes) start undriven (not triggered) and undamped unless displaced from equilibrium. Damping (decay) is caused by resistance to the flow of information or kinetic energy. At the time of equilibrium displacement, oscillations decay back to equilibrium (e.g., critical damping commences) and kinetic energy is converted into heat according to thermodynamics. So, the natural frequency does not equal the damped oscillation frequency (Cadence, 2019). Bots alter the natural frequencies of other nodes and can

increase the local resistance (hence giving rise to premature damping) to information flow.

When damping rate (natural logarithm of energy decay rate) equals to or surpasses the natural frequency of oscillators, the time to return energy to equilibrium is lengthened. This makes transient oscillation not possible. However, oscillators will only resonate a frequency at the repetition rate of the driving signal (1) when driven by a periodic signal (e.g., sinusoidal) versus repeating analog waveforms (e.g., sawtooth wave, frequency modulated signal, stream of clock pulses) and (2) when the natural frequency is greater than the damping rate (Cadence, 2019). Bots are signal drivers using a sinusoidal waveform.

Figure 63. Human layer synchronization.

Figure 64. Natural frequency, phase transition, and coupling strength estimation.

Based on order parameter visualized in the bot layer with few bots ($n = 478$), human layer (Figure 60 through Figure 61), and tweet layer (Figure 62 through Figure 63), the pattern and level of damping (shown by amplitude drops) is significant for the nodes to resonate and sustain a synchronizing frequency. Energy dissipates due to resistance at the edges and, possibly, from nonlinear frequencies emitted (e.g., background noise, counter signaling) through very discursive communications by other nodes (bots) especially in the human layer and tweet layer.

On the other hand, if nodes behave as quantum harmonic oscillators, then total energy is conserved and gets distributed evenly at equilibrium instead of being dissipated to heat which happens to bots represented as classical damped (spring-like) harmonic oscillators (Hsueh et al., 2020). In this study, bots may transition between classical and quantum harmonic oscillators as energy lowers and becomes quantized. This is postulated based on the gaps in the natural frequency.

Again, from literature, the “main frequency of the oscillations in the turbulent state is determined by a large number of small locally coherent groups...” (Frolov & Hramov, 2021, p. 7) and the “local coherence in the turbulent state before the transition to coherence is higher in the ‘core’ ensemble than in ‘influential’ [nodes]” (Frolov & Hramov, 2021, p. 7). Hence, detection of anomaly is by “an abrupt increase of the

main frequency at the beginning of synchronization and its decrease throughout the event” (Frolov & Hramov, 2021, p. 8). Bots resonate well in many small clusters, but main activity is represented by core bot synchronization and not by all influential bots.

Figure 65. Tweet layer synchronization.

Figure 66. Natural frequency, phase transition, and coupling strength estimation.

Coupling strength between nodes is correlated with the characteristics of nodes (Wu et al., 2018). Bots will not have discourses among themselves to distort and filter out connections resulting to polarization unlike what humans do. The lack of uniform frequency distribution (Wu et al., 2018) can be a reason for the failure of an explosive, full synchronization (i.e., the very rapid, steep rise, and sustained node activity) in any of the simulations. Time to and between onset of node activity (time delay) will shape the projection of synchronization only if coupling strength increases (Wu et al., 2018).

A jump-like node transition between excited and nonexcited is described in literature as “hysteresis” (Frolov & Hramov, 2021) or simply the critical coupling threshold (this separates the synchronized nodes above and non-synchronized below) at the onset of synchronization (e.g., hub and its peripheral nodes) and is affected by (phase) locking between the nodes of interest and their attractivity (Zou et al., 2014). The oscillations will not die because connections between low degree nodes (humans or bots) of large human hubs give small perturbations (Zou et al., 2014) or kick.

When compared to biological neurons, unlike the dynamics of bots, human dynamics is “non-stationary” by intermittent (two mounts in Figure 63) but transient synchronization (Petkoski et al., 2018). A nonmonotonic pattern validates the “anti-phase synchronization” (Vathakkattil & Pakrashi, 2020) of coupled human clusters.

Research Question 4: How does the Twitter network project energy from critical mass until the spread of COVID-19 infodemic by Schrödinger wave equations?

For the knowledge of the Communication Scholars and the intended dissemination of this study, let it be known that by results of “Equation 9: Phase Factor”, spambots (e.g., **newsmax**) and false human account bots (e.g., **JonPort79449036**) make faster tunneling (crossing) time between dimensions (multilayers). This may confirm the plausibility of a (brief) **non-structural entanglement** between nodes with “energy ties” instead of a relationship with tweets and ‘**teleportation**’ (energy transfer) rather than depending solely on the information cascade to reach other nodes.

On the other hand, by wavefunction simulation, a 29.45% network energy inflation by a 13.55% tweet increase led to “virality” following the “COVID-19 infodemic” spread equivalent to 9.61×10^6 J (energy overspill). The time to critical threshold (mass becomes massive) was at .0015 seconds. Twitter bots increased Twitter network’s potential energy by 50 J favoring diffusion of low-credibility tweets to adjacent nodes in .26 seconds versus .29 seconds by active human users. This proved the catalytic effect of Twitter bots on network dynamics and spread of misinformation. Two energy plateaus were underscored for any malicious bots to remain active and resilient. Energy conservation occurs during the 1.12 to 1.34 seconds gap. Bots’ phase transition (i.e., activation by tweets or nodes) was about .0003 seconds.

The space and time discourse in quantum representations

Since “quantization” is undertaken, neither space nor time becomes a parameter or a fixed point. Instead, they represent certain dimensions of complexity of the “Twitterverse”. In particular, time refers to “...an infinite manifold of transition rates for discontinuous quantum transitions,” where “...each change in nature corresponds an integer number of quanta of action [*by values of h as symbolized in the Schrödinger Equation*]”. Physical quantities change by discrete steps or “quantum jumps” [*which were shown through bizarre inflation and crush of wave amplitudes*]. (Capellmann, 2021, p. 1)

Moreover, ‘in between transitions’ (changes in wave pattern) were all probabilities but to make the communication of the study results tangible they were laid against the dimension of (1) time as a projection of the COVID-19 infodemic (*y-axis*) and (2) space as a projection of the energy level equivalent to the phenomenon (*x-axis*). Such pragmatic tenacity may be questioned in future scientific reviews or by discourse(s) among scholars and may be unforgivable but we can’t deny “...the general conviction, that Quantum Theory retains Newtonian space-time notions [*which means*], physical processes occurring continuously in space-time”. So, any wave function collapse can be represented by Max Born’s statistical interpretation as they were observed facts or events in the physical world with discrete values. (Capellmann, 2021, p. 32)

Two methods are compared in the wavefunction simulation, namely: **finite difference (Method 1)** through time-dependent Schrödinger equation; and **eigenstate evolution (Method 2)** through time-independent Schrödinger equation.

Implementation of The Time-Dependent Schrödinger Equation

The time-dependent Schrödinger equation:

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \psi(x, t) = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \psi(x, t) + V(x)\psi(x, t) \quad \psi(0, t) = \psi(L, t) = 0$$

can be simulated by

multiplying both sides by mL^2 or written as: $imL^2\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \psi = -\frac{1}{2}\hbar^2 L^2 \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \psi + mL^2 V(x)\psi$. The

final equation is: $i \frac{\partial}{\partial t'} \psi = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x'^2} \psi + V'(x)\psi$ (Polson, 2021c; 2021d).

Method 1: Finite Difference Equation

Finite difference is calculated with the discretized equation:

$$i \frac{\psi_j^{m+1} - \psi_j^m}{\Delta t} = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\psi_{j+1}^m - 2\psi_j^m + \psi_{j-1}^m}{\Delta x^2} + V(x)\psi_j^m,$$

which is rewritten as:

$$\psi_j^{m+1} = \psi_j^m + \frac{i}{2} \frac{\Delta t}{\Delta x^2} (\psi_{j+1}^m - 2\psi_j^m + \psi_{j-1}^m) - i\Delta t V(x)\psi_j^m$$

(Polson, 2021c; 2021d). On the other

hand, eigenstate evolution is calculated with a quantizing equation:

$$-\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} \psi + V(x)\psi = E\psi,$$

and then rewritten as:

$$\psi(x, t) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} c_j \psi_j(x) e^{-iE_j t} \quad c_j = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \psi(x, 0) \psi_j^*(x) dx$$

(Polson, 2021c; 2021d).

Technically, the eigenvalue of energy (E) is extracted from the eigenfunction of system's state (described by its wave, ψ) using an operator to represent a "pure-state eigenfunction" (Zúñiga-Segundo et al., 2016, p. 1) expressed as $\hat{H}\psi = E\psi$, where: $\hat{H}$ signifies a Hamiltonian operator, and the resulting Schrödinger wave

amplitude (ψ) is normalized to a constant equal to 1 (Cremer Jr., 2012). The equation is quadratic (Um et al., 2002). In addition, the operator pertains to all interactions between nodes as particles and network as energy field. The source codes are replicated except if $Nx = \text{number of nodes}$. The dt/dx^2 is .1885 or <1 and will have an underdamped wave collapse.

Table 31. Codes for calculating the normal energy curve of the network.

```

1. # Network Calculation
2. Nx = graphs[0].number_of_nodes()
3.
4. Nt = 100000
5. dx = 1/(Nx-1)
6. dt=1e-7
7. x = np.linspace(0, 1, Nx)
8.
9. # step 2
10.
11. Nt = 100000
12. dx = 1/(Nx-1)
13. dt=1e-7
14. x = np.linspace(0, 1, Nx)
15. psi0 = np.sqrt(2)*np.sin(np.pi*x)
16. mu, sigma = 1/2, 1/20
17. V = -1e4*np.exp(-(x-mu)**2/(2*sigma**2))

```

SOURCE: Modified from Polson, 2021c.

A dimensionless potential (i.e., normal energy curve) is calculated with the equation: $V(x) = -10^4 \exp\left(\frac{-(x-L/2)^2}{2(L/20)^2}\right)$ or $V(x) = -n(x, \mu = L/2, \sigma = L/20)$ in simplified form (Polson, 2021c; 2021d). These are coded as shown in the next table. The energy curve is depicted in Figure 67. Potential energy well increases in width as energy transitions to higher levels in Figure 68 (MikeRun, 2021).

Table 32. Codes for visualizing the normal energy curve.

```
1. plt.figure(figsize=(8,3))
2. plt.plot(x,V)
3. plt.xlabel('$x$')
4. plt.ylabel('$V(x)$')
5. plt.savefig("figures/Network Dimensionless potential.png")
```

SOURCE: Polson, 2021c.

Figure 67. Lowest possible energy of the potential well in the Twitter network.

The initial wave function is visualized from the finite difference equation using the same source codes (Polson, 2021c; 2021d). Position is on the x -axis while potential energy (PE) is on the y -axis. Change of position and PE amplitude indicates the time-independent harmonic potential (Bohm et al., 2019) of oscillating nodes. The more the potential is negative there is greater attraction or “energy pull” of bots to other nodes and in the Twitter network.

Table 33. Codes for simulating the (re)distribution of potential energy.

```

1. psi = np.zeros([Nt,Nx])
2. psi[0] = psi0
3.
4. @numba.jit("c16[:,:](c16[:,:])", nopython=True, nogil=True)
5. def compute_psi(psi):
6.     for t in range(0, Nt-1):
7.         for i in range(1, Nx-1):
8.             psi[t+1][i] = psi[t][i] + 1j/2 * dt/dx**2 * (psi[t][i+1] - 2*psi[t][i] + psi[t][i-1]) -
1j*dt*V[i]*psi[t][i]
9.
10.    normal = np.sum(np.absolute(psi[t+1])**2)*dx
11.    for i in range(1, Nx-1):
12.        psi[t+1][i] = psi[t+1][i]/normal
13.
14.    return psi
15.
16. psi_m1 = compute_psi(psi.astype(complex))
17.
18. print(psi_m1)
19.
20. plt.plot(x, np.absolute(psi_m1[5000])**2)
21. plt.savefig("figures/Network potential.png")
22.
23. #np.sum(np.absolute(psi_m1[10000])**2)*dx

```

SOURCE: Polson, 2021c.

Figure 68. Non-Gaussian energy spikes due to bots and misinformation spread.

The energy spreads asymmetrically, which may eventually cause it to decay with a log-normal distribution due to the nature of the random variables and the system entropy (The Physicist, 2010). Normally, peaks of wavefunctions (highest probability density) concentrate towards a geometric center with a narrow width since there is very small uncertainty in the position or localization of energy from nodes (Adams, 2013, p. 1). The energy level collapses from the same position and moves towards an area of least potential. In the graph, the wavefunction goes outside of the well's barrier to the right side.

The phenomenon that was simulated revealed that bots produce 'unnatural perturbations' (energy is added synthetically but unequally) inside the Twitter network. On the other hand, it does appear in the graph that multiple Gaussian wells have emerged, which is plausible when potential energy in the network increases and wavefunction moves "...in quasi-continuous bands, each consisting of a very large number of closely spaced energies" thereafter (Schroeder, 2022, p. 77).

The tunneling time (i.e., in and out of the potential well) is half the oscillation period or $\frac{T}{2}$ (Schroeder, 2022, p. 75), which will indirectly describe the diffusion time of influential nodes. The wavefunction is sinusoidal inside the Gaussian well but exponential outside of it because the potential well allows part of the wavefunction to spill-out beyond the edges so the wavelength inside gets longer for the same number of bumps (Schroeder, 2022, p. 54). However, if the system's energy level (in eigenvalue) is $E > 50$ the wavefunction will become sinusoidal outside the well based on the time-independent Schrödinger equation (Schroeder, 2022, p. 54).

Evolution of kurtosis in the plot is attributed to the "phases" (de Freitas & Dodonov, 2021, p. 361) of each node from linear to nonlinear dynamics. They undergo different phases to stay active by (1) increasing connections in the network and (2)

oscillations to communicate (with frequencies related to energy bursts) and to synchronize themselves. In this study, the number of phases coincide with the number of dense critical points on the graph that also assume a spectral parameter by Fourier transform for power from at least a two-dimensional random energy field depending on the Fourier components (Feldbrugge et al., 2019, pp. 6, 8, 10).

In addition, the topological structure of a field (i.e., Twitter network) is intimately connected to the character and distribution of (energy source) points in that field (Feldbrugge et al., 2019, p. 9). Obviously, the plot shows a “highly local non-Gaussian [*instead of smooth and continuous*] random field” (Feldbrugge et al., 2019, pp. 6, 30) since symmetry is broken (Feldbrugge et al., 2019, p. 11) and connectivity with surrounding structures (e.g., degree) and boundaries (e.g., number of communities) is just uncertain (because of structural redundancies or overlaps) with increasing heterogeneity (i.e., low assortativity) instead of a homologous organization (Feldbrugge et al., 2019, p. 13).

Another perspective on this is that non-normality is due to dealing with a product (or geometric mean) of (essentially independent) random variables rather than a sum of them; we should expect that the resulting distribution will be approximately log-normal rather than normal.

Implementation of The Time-Independent Schrödinger Equation

Method 2: Eigenstate Evolution

Table 34. Codes for calculating and plotting eigenvalues.

```
1. dx = 1/(Nx-1)
2. x = np.linspace(0, 1, Nx)
3. psi0 = np.sqrt(2)*np.sin(np.pi*x)
4.
5. def V(x):
6.     mu, sigma = 1/2, 1/20
7.     return -1e4*np.exp(-(x-1/2)**2/(2*(1/20)**2))
8.
9. d = 1/dx**2 + V(x)[1:-1]
10. e = -1/(2*dx**2) * np.ones(len(d)-1)
11. w, v = eigh_tridiagonal(d, e)
12.
13.
14. # step
15.
16. E_js = w[0:70]
17. psi_js = np.pad(v.T[0:70], [(0, 0), (1, 1)], mode='constant')
18. cs = np.dot(psi_js, psi0)
19. def psi_m2(t):
20.     return psi_js.T@(cs*np.exp(-1j*E_js*t))
21.
22. plt.figure(figsize=(8,3))
23. plt.plot(x, psi0**2)
24. plt.plot(x, np.absolute(psi_m2(10000*dt))**2)
25. plt.savefig(f"./figures/Compute Eigen states - t2.png")
26.
27. exgs = np.absolute(psi_m2(10000*dt))**2
28. print(exgs)
```

SOURCE: Polson, 2021c.

Figure 69. The Gaussian distribution of Method 1 and Method 2.

The graph (Figure 69) also represents a Gaussian pulse and its linear decay goes by a pulse train. For signal processing, this is close to **sinc function** or “the continuous inverse Fourier transform of a rectangular pulse” (MathWorks, 2022b).

However, representation of wave function’s phase in space can be more informative with wavelet transformation (Zúñiga-Segundo et al., 2016) if this study would need to be replicated.

Table 35. Codes for fetching the animation frames and eigenvalues.

```
1. from matplotlib import animation
2. from matplotlib.animation import PillowWriter
3. import numba
4. from numba import jit
5. from scipy.linalg import eigh_tridiagonal
```

Table 36. Codes for wavefunction simulation.

```

1. def animate(i):
2.     ln1.set_data(x, np.absolute(psi_m1[100*i])**2)
3.     ln2.set_data(x, np.absolute(psi_m2(100*i*dt])**2)
4.     time_text.set_text('${10^4 mL^2}^{-1}t=${:.1f}'.format(100*i*dt*1e4))
5.     plt.savefig(f"./figures/method_comparison/{i+1}.png")
6.
7. fig, ax = plt.subplots(1,1, figsize=(8,4))
8. #ax.grid()
9. ln1, = plt.plot([], [], 'r-', lw=2, markersize=8, label='Method 1')
10. ln2, = plt.plot([], [], 'b--', lw=3, markersize=8, label='Method 2')
11. time_text = ax.text(0.65, 16, "", fontsize=15,
12.     bbox=dict(facecolor='white', edgecolor='black'))
13. ax.set_ylim(-1, 20)
14. ax.set_xlim(0, 1)
15. ax.set_ylabel('$|\psi(x)|^2$', fontsize=20)
16. ax.set_xlabel('$x/L$', fontsize=20)
17. ax.legend(loc='upper left')
18. ax.set_title('$(\text{mL}^2)\text{V}(x) = -10^4 \cdot n(x, \mu=L/2, \sigma=L/20)$')
19. plt.tight_layout()
20. ani = animation.FuncAnimation(fig, animate, frames=1000, interval=50)
21. ani.save('./figures/method-comp-anim.gif', writer='pillow', fps=50, dpi=100)

```

SOURCE: Polson, 2021c.

Wavefunction Simulation

Figure 70. Projected misinformation spread by wavefunction simulation.

In Figure 70, there is dissociation or decoherence between the two methods indicating disruptive shifts in energy potential due to alterations of mass concentration (i.e., nodes activity in the tweet layer). The discontinuous behavior of bots produces a quasi-disentangled phase: (1) at the left and (2) at the right of the potential well (where **Method 2** localizes). Movement of wave packets along the x -axis can determine critical mass occurrence in space and time. So, at the highest energy level that can be splurged ($J^{-2}s^{-2} = 99.9$) the probability of the “virality” of misinformation (i.e., significant bot activity) is until eight months, which supports the actual misinformation spread (Figure 28).

The peaks generated through **Method 1** roughly estimates the quantizable but evolving magnitude of cybernetics in action (a Markov process) by a probability density calculated using the Schrödinger equation (Ash, 2022), in this case, putting the infinitesimal dynamics together in the Twitter network and knowing its locality on a fuzzy point with a time scale. Wavefunction collapses stochastically according to Sabine Hossenfelder (Ash, 2022). Moreover, it sets off interference patterns (alternating constructive interference or high amplitude and destructive interference or low amplitude) that (will) predict the whereabouts of most influential bots as the probability amplitude moves into three physical regions (I through III) involving different wave behavior (Ling et al., 2019).

Region I and III will allow bots to: (1) increase their number of connections; (2) form entanglements and cliques; and (3) harmonically resonate from a chunk of (mis)information and amplify entropy (from what is already complex as far as organization and dynamics are concerned) in the Twitter network. Oscillations are reduced every time they 'pass' (tunnel into) the potential well (Region II) and this is where the uptake of energy (in the network) and critical mass betide. Every rise and fall of waves can coincide with the opening and closing of network spaces while wave tunneling through the potential well can mean the movement of bots and misinformation inside the network.

Influential nodes are believed to induce local excitation using narrow impulses over other nodes that resonate across a field of (background) energy capacitating the network. At the collapse of wave function from a Gaussian distribution, neither messages nor signals can be sent. Instead, any prior information can only change into new information (Information Philosopher, 2022) and the uncertainty diminishes as other probabilities disappear right away. Viral (mis)information from influential nodes

will have a peculiar, asymmetric wave packet as it spreads out in the network to decay.

The simultaneous flickers of energies from node state changes are dampened quickly. Influential nodes start with relatively higher potential energy (at the cost of the inherent network potential out of the conserved theoretical mass and energy) than passive nodes to bring information into “virality”. (Mis)information, mass, and energy regenerate after passing their criticality levels, but in a skewing manner.

In Table 37, it was demonstrated that the number of nodes is an important factor for the movement of mass, energy variation, and behavior of oscillation across three physical regions. Increasing vertices has the following effects: (a) it garners more chaotic activity and become immense; (b) it smolders the precipitous decrescence of misinformation (Region III or on the right of the potential well), i.e., once transmitted with significant mass (?) and energy (?); and (c) it lets the asymmetrical sinking of energy in the potential well thereby avoiding same equilibrium level. The cut-off energy potential can be declared at $1.68 \times 10^{-1} J^{-2} s^{-2}$ from the average of two initial energy

parameters $\left(\frac{1.46 \times 10^{-1} + 1.89 \times 10^{-1}}{2} \right)$ expressed in the ordinary differential equation,

dt / dx^2 . Intensity is high by seven months (long diffusion) with total tweets of 1374. On the other hand, intensity is high before one month and will regress over seven months (short diffusion) with total tweets of 1210 because of early decay. The phenomenon is assumed if there is 13.55% increase in tweets and with a 29.45% energy step up using

the rate of change equation by Chen (2021): $\left(\frac{1374}{1210} - 1 \right) \times 100$ and

$\left(\frac{1.89 \times 10^{-1}}{1.46 \times 10^{-1}} - 1 \right) \times 100$ respectively.

Table 37. Comparison of outcomes based on number of tweets.

Total Tweets: 1210	Total Tweets: 1374
Oscillation behavior if $dt/dx^2 = 1.46 \times 10^{-1}$	Oscillation behavior if $dt/dx^2 = 1.89 \times 10^{-1}$
Late Decoherence (More Turbulent)	Early Decoherence (More Immense)
<p>$(mL^2)V(x) = -10^4 \cdot n(x, \mu = L/2, \sigma = L/20)$ $(10^4 mL^2)^{-1} t = 0.6$</p>	
Late Potential Well Climb (Method 2)	Late Potential Well Climb (Method 2)
<p>$(mL^2)V(x) = -10^4 \cdot n(x, \mu = L/2, \sigma = L/20)$ $(10^4 mL^2)^{-1} t = 79.0$</p>	
Early Decay (Method 2)	Late Decay (Method 2)
<p>$(mL^2)V(x) = -10^4 \cdot n(x, \mu = L/2, \sigma = L/20)$ $(10^4 mL^2)^{-1} t = 89.6$</p>	
Shorter Diffusion (Method 1)	Longer Diffusion (Method 1)
<p>$(mL^2)V(x) = -10^4 \cdot n(x, \mu = L/2, \sigma = L/20)$ $(10^4 mL^2)^{-1} t = 99.9$</p>	
Full-Length Simulation (1 of 2)	Full-Length Simulation (2 of 2)

Graphs on the right column of Table 37 were excerpts from the wavefunction simulation. Graphs on the left panel were generated from a previous code implementation. QR codes at the bottom of Table 37 provide access for a full-length visualization and file download.

Simultaneous events are also shown above such as emergence and collapse of network structures. Perhaps, this is the only representation in this study that allows back and forth observations (more like a time machine) of the possible but very temporal evolutions of the network.

Table 38. Codes for visualizing the eigenstate network potential.

```
1. from scipy.linalg import eigh_tridiagonal
2.
3. # step 1
4. N = Nx
5. dy = 1/N
6. y = np.linspace(0, 1, N+1)
7.
8. #step 2
9. def mL2V(y):
10.     return 1000*np.sin(20*y) * y**4
11. d = 1/dy**2 + mL2V(y)[1:-1]
12. e = -1/(2*dy**2) * np.ones(len(d)-1)
13. w, v = eigh_tridiagonal(d, e)
14.
15. plt.figure(figsize=(10,5))
16. plt.plot(y, mL2V(y), lw=2)
17. plt.title('Potential', fontsize=30)
18. plt.ylabel('$V/V_0$', fontsize=25)
19. plt.xlabel('$x/L$', fontsize=25)
20. plt.grid()
21. plt.savefig('./figures/eigenstates potential.png', dpi=200)
```

SOURCE: Polson, 2021b.

Figure 71. Eigenstate potential of tweets ($n = 1374$).

Based on projected energy, the course alternates with >1 and <1 . This implies alternating states (unstable and stable) of varying intensity (Sayama, 2015, pp. 77, 79, 84).

Table 39. Codes for visualizing all eigenstates.

```
1. plt.figure(figsize=(10,5))
2. plt.plot(y[1:-1], v.T[0])
3. plt.plot(y[1:-1], v.T[1])
4. plt.plot(y[1:-1], v.T[2])
5. plt.plot(y[1:-1], v.T[3])
6. plt.title('Eigenstates', fontsize=30)
7. plt.ylabel('\psi', fontsize=25)
8. plt.xlabel('x/L', fontsize=25)
9. plt.grid()
10. plt.savefig('./figures/eigenstates plot.png', dpi=200)
```

SOURCE: Polson, 2021b.

Figure 72. Quantization of potential by eigenstates.

The potential well (in blue) appeared late in the process due to broad (tsunami-like) oscillations on the left of Region II. These represent the cascade of critical mass (in chunks of misinformation through redundancy) per state leaving the ground state (at 0). On the other hand, it can be conceived that about 70% of the time of network activity is spent at Region I (the pre-critical period) and energy from misinformation exhibits scattering after each (energized) spew of events against the potential ramp or immediate boundary of the well. Chaotic events taking place are unbounded, but unless it can display a strong impulse (i.e., with a potential a lot greater than the pull of the ground state) the eigenstate cannot emerge.

There are three eigenstates in the picture. The yellow line graph is a natural phenomenon while the green line (biphasic) graph and red line (triphasic) graphs were actuated synthetically by bots. The green line graph can be interpreted as a forerunner

of the red line graph. Moreover, the red line graph more likely represented the fusion of bot energy (significantly by the most influential population) and network energy. The mid-plateau in this red line graph is a non-zero equilibrium which conserves energy (delaying its earliest decay or sudden plunge) and permits a steady movement (rather boosting) towards a steep ascend at higher energy grade (i.e., as high as possible to overcome attenuation through and inside the potential well).

Table 40. Codes for converting line plots into a bar graph.

```
1. plt.bar(np.arange(0, 10, 1), w[0:10])
2. plt.ylabel('$mL^2 E/\hbar^2$')
3. plt.savefig('./figures/eigenstates bar plot.png', dpi=200)
```

SOURCE: Polson, 2021b.

Figure 73. Visualization of eigenstates and energy.

In Figure 73, the negative potential is the damped portion of the energy spectrum. It would account for the theoretical energy gradient between bots and network. Bots rapidly sink into the potential well in order to steal energy. They contribute to global energy by amending the incrementation exponentially (after the long plateau in the graph).

Table 41. Codes for plotting the quantized potential.

```
1. x = np.linspace(0, 1, 1000)
2. y = np.sin(20*x) * x**4
3.
4. plt.plot(x, y)
5. plt.xlabel('$x/L$')
6. plt.ylabel('Potential')
7. plt.savefig('./figures/eigenstates-potential.png', dpi=200)
```

SOURCE: Polson, 2021b.

Figure 74. Visualization of bot potential (recalibrated from network).

Bot potential (Figure 74) is scaled-down from the network due to the fact that they follow the energy landscape of the network. Damping of waveforms is a manifestation of energy dissipation when a system undergoes cyclic stress (Siemens Digital Industries Software, 2020a). The translation of ‘stress’ as something affecting dynamics in the Twitter network is instancial, but synthetically ordered when bots infiltrate the information flow: first, massive hyperactivity provocation of nodes occurs and second, consequential massive, local energy disequilibrium. The latter generates coarser frequencies. Thus, it brings about the “critical phenomena” or “phase transition,” where they change discontinuously (Duminil-Copin, 2019) at some kind of pseudo-threshold and become more connected (i.e., the probability or p increased from 0 to 1 with the opening of vertices) as a “giant component [or cluster]” (Novozhilov, 2022) assumed by plots of peaked global convergence during synchronization, and then information, mass, and energy spread out faster.

Based on percolation theory, a large n or network size produces a sharp threshold (a steep increment) in Erdős and Rényi networks. But these are “...uncorrelated networks with homogeneous degree distribution” (Biamonte et al., 2019, p. 2). The threshold is calculated this way: $p_n = \frac{\log n}{n}$ (Duminil-Copin, 2019), for example, when p reaches .60, percolation is at medium and up to .80, it is high (Sedgewick & Wayne, 2019). The process is discontinuous involving connection between two node clusters at any given time, but is “half restricted” (denoted as $n/2$) for every “phase transition” in which “...a constant fraction of the vertices is accumulated into a single giant component within a sublinear [or random] number of steps,” thus it is called “explosive percolation” (Panagiotou et al., 2011).

Using Erdős and Rényi's mathematical representation, time difference between node phase (inactive to active) is approximately .0003 seconds. Using the data in Table 42, energy percolation of the network yields

$$p_n = \frac{\log(1175)}{1175} = \frac{3.07003786661}{1175} = .0026 \text{ versus bots having few more seconds}$$

$$p_n = \frac{\log(1023)}{1023} = \frac{3.00987563371}{1023} = .0029 \text{ since } n \text{ is smaller. By half restriction } (n/2),$$

the network energy is concentrated over a matrix size of $n=588$ while bots take less space, $n=512$ in order to achieve their energy potential and to build (more effective) connections. However, when bots impregnate the network, time to threshold is a lot

$$\text{quicker: } p_n = \frac{\log(2198)}{2198} = \frac{3.34202768809}{2198} = .0015.$$

The maximum energy gained (potential and kinetic) may not be coincidental with the summation of energy in the network and from bots rather it is (re)extracted from low energy fluctuations in the network, and since the nadir does not drop to zero and bots can take advantage of it to a steady, granular fluctuations until an “**explosive percolation**” (activity bursts) is launched from a sharp threshold at .26 seconds (Figure 76). As energy level increases, bots cluster. Even outside of Erdős and Rényi's equation, in Figure 75 and Figure 76, the plots confirm the effect of bots. Threshold of the network took .29 seconds to climb to a maximum energy (70000 Joules), but through multiple potentiating steps or resonating energies which is exhaustive. Time had decreased to .26 seconds to achieve a new equilibrium at a potential energy of 50 Joules with bots (Figure 76).

Figure 75. Underdamped energy fluctuations inside Twitter (over .29 sec).

Figure 76. Overdamped energy spread after injection of bots (over .80 sec).

In theory, “good bots” can counteract bots and misinformation (Flores-Vivar, 2019). They can counteract malicious bots from reaching a critical energy level (50 J at .26 sec) for unleashing destructive chaos in the network, e.g., deploying a “Misinformation fighting bot” (Sun, 2021) and influencing other users (at equal or exceeding amount of energy) until they can be cognizant (to break the attention) massively about the spreading misinformation or disinformation wherein such user

behavior is linked to the Spiral of Silence Theory by Neumann (1974 cited in Sun, 2021).

Furthermore, the difference was statistically significant by one-way ANOVA. The average energy needed to spread (mis)information without bots is higher ($M = 1.88 \times 10^2$, $SD = 2.81 \times 10^3$) than with bots ($M = 1.01 \times 10^2$, $SD = 2.05 \times 10^3$), ($F(1, 2195) = 4.2375$, $p = .0397$) with skewness increased, which shows a very large or disproportionate, erratic energy respectively: 21.87 ($SE = 81.90$) versus 29.92 ($SE = 43.80$) in Table 42 through Table 44. It is energy intensive and a less efficient spread if lacking the (most) influential bots.

Kurtosis and skewness of energy distribution are noteworthy to discourse based on the volatile jumps and flow of energy when assuming the matrices are behaving fluidic and diffusion of energy is facilitated with the hike of low-credibility information (Yang et al., 2020) during “phase transition”. The latter are also induced and reintroduced by hyperactive bots as they make and amplify posts of low-credibility information and links to such information are especially routed to key hubs while echoing mostly the “politicization of the pandemic” (Yang et al., 2020, p. 1). Because energy is equivalent to information (Vopson, 2019), the skewed energy landscape follows the uneven distribution of tweet creation (Petersen & Gerken, 2021; Malik & Pfeffer, 2016). On the other hand, energy lowers with the fall of tweets trend and bot activity over these tweets.

Reporting an irregular energy landscape with an oversight of entropy (basically due to consumption of energy in classical thermodynamics) is a mediocre endeavor. However, “negentropy” or the energy opposing the decay (Isa & Dumas, 2020) of node activities and connectedness is often overlooked. So, a novel explanation would be that a maximum energy level drops as a result of “negentropy”

and shifts the direction of energy diffusion. The new equilibrium may also fit the description of a “punctuated equilibrium” in the light of macro evolution secondary to “mutations” (Wikipedia. 2022b) of messages and their information processing (interpretations among nodes) after the network is first infected. Hence, variants are omnipresent in the network.

The advantage of a step-up equilibrium is that it can sustain “virality” on a longer decay from “overdamping” since (integrations of) node dynamics were nudged by bots through synchronized activities (using harmonic signaling from concerted impulses) and retuning of local energy consumption. Energy overflows by 9.61×10^6 or >1 between mean energy of the network and mean energy of most influential nodes. On the other hand, with lone intrinsic energy cycling of the network, faster steep rise and fall produces underdamping (energy loss).

Table 42. Energy profile before percolation by influential nodes.

	<i>(Base) Energy in Network</i>	<i>Energy of Influential Nodes</i>
Count (<i>n</i>)	1175.00	1023.00
Mean (<i>M</i>)	1.88×10^2	1.95×10^{-32}
Median	5.38	5.18×10^{-33}
Standard Deviation (<i>SD</i>)	2.81×10^3	1.05×10^{-31}
Standard Error of the Mean (<i>SEM</i>)	8.19×10^1	3.27×10^{-33}
Confidence Level (95%)	1.61×10^2	6.41×10^{-33}
Kurtosis	501.24	422.92
Skewness	21.87	18.65
Range	6.55×10^4	2.65×10^{-30}
Minimum	4.88×10^{-1}	2.59×10^{-33}
Maximum	6.55×10^4	2.65×10^{-30}

Table 43. Energy profile after percolation by influential nodes.

	<i>(Base) Energy in Network</i>	<i>Energy Fusion in Network</i>
Count (<i>n</i>)	1175.00	2198.00
Mean (<i>M</i>)	1.88×10^2	1.01×10^2
Median	5.38	7.94×10^{-1}
Standard Deviation (<i>SD</i>)	2.81×10^3	2.05×10^3
Standard Error of the Mean (<i>SEM</i>)	8.19×10^1	4.38×10^1
Confidence Level (95%)	1.61×10^2	8.59×10^1
Kurtosis	501.24	939.35
Skewness	21.87	29.92
Range	6.55×10^4	6.55×10^4
Minimum	4.88×10^{-1}	2.59×10^{-33}
Maximum	6.55×10^4	6.55×10^4

Table 44. Analysis of variance for the energy trends.

SUMMARY				
<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
Energy in Network	1.17×10^3	1.56×10^5	1.33×10^2	4.24×10^6
Energy of Influential Nodes	1.02×10^3	1.99×10^{-29}	1.95×10^{-32}	1.09×10^{-62}

ANOVA (Single Factor)						
<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	9.61×10^6	1	9.61×10^6	4.2375	.0397	3.8457
Within Groups	4.98×10^9	2195	2.27×10^6			
Total	4.99×10^9	2196				

The skewness describes a non-Gaussian energy dispersion in the Twitter network by base energy and influential nodes' energy (Table 42), and fused energies (Table 43). Skewness is >1 , therefore high positive (5E Analytics, 2016) because "...the distribution is depleted of values below the mean" or in spectrographic (ab)normality, there is "...more power above the mean (at higher dispersion distance) when compared to a Gaussian" (Davis, 2000) as energy falls to decay while kurtosis

is also positive because the "...distribution is more peaked than a Gaussian" (Davis, 2000) or leptokurtic, i.e., >3 (5E Analytics, 2016).

Despite asymmetry having been confirmed, the significant result of the one-way ANOVA remains valid because it "...can tolerate data that is non-normal (skewed or kurtotic distributions) with only a small effect on the Type I error rate" unless if platy kurtosis was shown and group sizes are small (Laerd.com, 2018). Moreover, the *F-test* component of ANOVA makes it robust against Type I error (Blanca Mena et al., 2017).

To challenge the skewness and kurtosis of the data, Monte Carlo methods may be a robust alternative and comparison of the energy profiles will be based on "contrast sensitivity function" between "linear sine-wave gratings" of spatial frequencies, for example, "0.2 to 20 cycles per degree" (Almeida et al., 2019).

Using the slope-intercept equation: $y = mx + b$, sloping of the energy depends on the value of b . If large, the slope is shallow (Schroeder, 2022, p. 100). In this study, this is elucidated in the following: y is the predicted energy level in the network; b is in the value of β or the phase factor (**Equation 9**); m is the critical threshold after node virality minus critical threshold before node virality; and x is $(10^4 mL^2)^{-1}t$ from the time-dependent Schrödinger equation. The y is divided by 2 to get the tunneling time in seconds. Figure 77 showed that with low β , the energy rises faster. This is the case, for example, when a wavefunction (dimensionless) value of 79.2 is given. In addition, it was demonstrated computationally that y is just equal to the value of β regardless of the wavefunction value.

Figure 77. Energy and trend reconstruction from wavefunction histogram.

Also, with much lower β (fast-phasing) the tunneling time is even shorter among the two most influential nodes: “**newsmax**” (user id: 978; spammer bot) and “**JonPort79449036**” (user id: 434; false human account). These nodes can either imbibe greater potential energy from the potential well or burrow multiple potential wells theoretically and then shift between energy levels quickly. The following are inferred about the capacity of fast-phasing nodes: (a) they easily infect other nodes; (b) they meddle between nodes and within groups recurrently and gain intractable influence since they engage more frequently than other nodes; (c) they are replenished by local changes in energy with which they are also involved; (d) they fill space stochastically; (e) they pull nodes into clusters; and (f) they mobilize the infected nodes to repossess disentangled edges from the periphery.

The frequency of binned values registering on the y -axis of the histogram will be equivalent to predicted energy (Bister et al., 2021, pp. 3, 5). From Figure 76, at .26 seconds the energy threshold is 50 Joules. In Figure 77, this is 32 Joules between .24 to .46 seconds. The difference of 18 Joules (36%) implies an energy loss during the initial jolt of energy due to entropy. Energy conserved to mass is very minimal while the rest of the energy is lost to heat (i.e., the thermodynamic aspect of systems) throughout the digital infrastructure ecosystem. Thus, a streaming mass of misinformation is required. In a study about complex quantum systems, the energy cost of entanglement extraction ($T_{\text{ent}}^{\Lambda} = \Delta E / \Delta S$) is represented as heat loss (T) when entanglement entropy increases (ΔS) that will average at 30% or 50% per increment (Bény et al., 2018). Furthermore, the projected energy loss is exponential (Bény et al., 2018).

Overall, energy is intensified (.02 to .24 sec) and scattered (.46 to 1.12 sec), and then discretized to smaller mass (1.34 to 1.56 sec). Energy will decay exponentially to the right of the step potential barrier because kinetic energy is less than the potential energy or $E < V_0$ (Wikipedia, 2022d), but intriguingly, there is an energy gap before energy is cut down. The energy level arising after the gap represents a conserved mass (perchance a fully discoursed misinformation). Bots will go along with the diffusion of misinformation by a Markov process (Kriener et al., 2012) but they can contour the flow of misinformation resulting to an 'overdamp' (saturation) of mass within the radius of their degree of node connections. However, they also lose energy quickly (Figure 79).

Bots will cluster near the potential well (where there are highly connected nodes) to draw energy. Bots (under a quantum condition) are bounded in the potential

well—value of $V(x) < 0$ and “[have] V amount of energy less than of what it would need to become free” (Taskin, 2016), which means they are excited faster to a redundancy and hang onto stability (having plateaus) than (uninfected) neighboring nodes. Moreover, course, non-Gaussian spikes (noisy background during sonification) could be attributed to bots’ flourishing energy sequestered through an energy gap from 1.12 to 1.34 seconds (based on Figure 77) in the network. This gap is a changeover into unbound state. Bots will use this period to aggregate (like a swarm) and launch massive attacks later on. Figure 78 shows the wave function oscillations after hitting the step potential (at 5 nm) and underpins the insights in Figure 77 except about the energy gap.

Figure 78. Comparison using PhET simulator.

SOURCE: University of Colorado, 2022.

The array of eigenvalues from the adjacency matrix (or the eigenvectors) was transposed manually into a vertical series in an Excel spreadsheet. These values were plotted from largest to smallest as shown in Figure 79. It uncovered the occurrence of two plateaus along a steep (controlled) descent which will prevent the total inactivation of bots and allow recovery of energy potential. The results affirm the pattern in Guynn and Bajak (2020). Quantum oscillations happen between 10^{-23} and 10^{-24} in reference to the sensitivity of laser interferometers for gravitational wave detection (Tse, 2019; Waldman, 2011).

Figure 79. Lower boundary potentiation in the bots by eigen decomposition.

No manipulation of the order of values was made in Figure 80 that shows the pattern of impulses. Bots are energized with a large impulse (by Twitter network or other nodes) and this is followed by sequential pulses with narrowing intervals (Figure

80) until energy drops (Figure 79). Below “Plateau 2” is theorized as the energy drain which signifies return to a potential well. On the other hand, this trajectory may actually support the phenomenon of phase-locking in order to synchronize (Breakspear et al., 2010, p. 6) bots. Such pattern could tell the conversion from in-coming signals (Figure 29) to out-going signals (Figure 30). Energy-to-signals were matched by approximation.

Figure 80. Impulse production and intensification.

Information is fed to bots by other nodes (bots and humans). Information gets remixed and filtered (hence local entropy increases). Bots will output signals that amplify the information with redundancy. The signals are sinusoidal. The fluctuations imply a Poisson to non-Poisson trend described by De Domenico et al. (2013) where a log-normal law (rather a power-law) between signals would apply.

Fourier Transformation of Signals and Spectrogram Analysis

Table 45. Coding for node influence simulation in time series on a spectrogram.

```

1. import numpy as np
2. from numpy.fft import fft, fftfreq
3. import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
4. %matplotlib inline
5. from pylab import specgram
6. from scipy.io.wavfile import write
7.
8.
9. dt = 0.001
10. t = np.arange(0.0, 4.0, dt)
11. s1 = np.sin(2*np.pi*20*t)
12. s2 = 3*np.sin(1.2*np.pi*20*t)
13. mask = np.where(np.logical_and(t>1, t<2), 2.0, 0.0)
14. s2 = s2 * mask
15. nse = 0.004*np.random.randn(len(t))
16.
17. for i,x in enumerate(s1):
18.     s1[i] = 0.00
19. x = nse
20.
21.
22. for i, xt in enumerate(network_node_classifications):
23.     if(xt["degree"] > 0):
24.         x += 2*np.sin((xt["degree"]*0.01)*np.pi*20*t) *
           np.where(np.logical_and(t>1, t<2), 0.5, 0.03)
25.     else:
26.         x += 1*np.sin((i*0.0004)*np.pi*20*t)
27.
28. NFFT = 256 # the length of the windowing segments
29. Fs = int(2.0/dt) # the sampling frequency

```

```

30.
31. # Generate Audio File from Signal
32.
33. data = x
34. data.astype(int)
35. print(data)
36. scaled = np.int16(data/np.max(np.abs(data)) * 1152767)
37. write('./dataset/spectrogram_audio.wav', len(data), scaled)
38.
39.
40.
41. plt.figure(figsize=(29,9))
42. plt.subplot(211)
43. plt.plot(t, x)
44. plt.suptitle("Node Influence Line Plot & Spectrogram (Simulated Signal)",
    fontsize=20)
45. ax1 = plt.subplot(212)
46. Pxx, freqs, bins, im = plt.specgram(x, NFFT=NFFT, Fs=Fs, noverlap=255,
    cmap="jet")
47. ax1.set_ylim((0,600))
48. plt.colorbar()
49. plt.savefig("./figures/node_influence_spectrogram.png")

```

Numerical values in **Line 13**: “mask = np.where(np.logical_and(t>1, t<2), 2.0, 0.0),” **Line 24**: “x += 2*np.sin((xt["degree"]*0.01)*np.pi*20*t) * np.where(np.logical_and(t>1, t<2), 0.5, 0.03),” and **Line 26**: “x += 1*np.sin((i*0.0004)*np.pi*20*t)” are logical parameters. These are required by numpy function to ‘mask’ (map) values between mixed signals.

In **Line 15**: “nse = 0.004*np.random.randn(len(t)),” the seed value is needed for signal generation since the simulation implementation does not fall into any standard signal processing, but the output is data-driven. The spectrogram will depend on the random (input) data, and is not absolute. Therefore, values cannot be fetched precisely. The array of values is generated each time codes are run. Noise and timeline values create the signal plot.

The spectrogram of the degree of nodes and influential degree share the same thought of “degree” quantitatively. However, they have different implementations. The ‘**spectrogram degree**’ has some added frequency values for visualization while for the influential nodes, the ‘**individual degree**’ for each node is not averaged. It does not take into account all the other degree of the other nodes, but is calculated by the number and type of connection.

Figure 81. Simulated frequency pattern of most influential nodes.

In Figure 81, the encircled trend has some similarity with Figure 5 based on frequency surges (Zhang et al., 2022). Bots mimic their human counterparts through duplication of their tweet frequency. Noise can be attributed to spambots.

The patterns displayed above may be likened to multiple “Type 3” radio emissions, which are fast-drifting energy bursts consisting of narrowband signals cycling from high to low frequencies (Arnold, 2020, p. 212). It conveys a scattered, accelerated propagation in a non-ballistic pathway of “density inhomogeneities” (Reid, 2020, p. 11) when there are massive and energetic states. Moreover, it can be inferred

that energy exchange is possible through waves due to a “wave-wave process” (Reid, 2020, p. 12). This is based on the four levels of frequency entanglements (yellow and red areas that are indicated by black arrows) between peaks around .50 seconds and 1.00 seconds in the spectrogram.

Entangled energies (of node microstates) traverse space through (micro)radiation and such phenomenon creates a mixed state (Balasubramanian et al., 2021) of: (a) nodes and (b) information (entropy level), where they pulse and impulse simultaneously. Nodes manifest a complex, more of a fabricated agency—part human state and part bots state and the information about and around them is warped. Bot activity and (mis)information transmission have both quantum (nonlinear physics, e.g., the von Neumann entropy) and classical (linear physics in accordance to the second law of thermodynamics—entropy, i.e., fundamental to information theory by Shannon) mechanisms.

Visualization of noise and entanglement of signals rely on three variables: (1) **seed value** coded in **Line 15**: `nse = _____*np.random.randn(len(t))`; (2) **logical value** coded in **Line 24**: `x += 2*np.sin((xt["degree"]*_____) * np.pi*20*t) * np.where(np.logical_and(t>1, t<2), 0.5, 0.03)`; and (3) **degree of nodes**. A comparison is shown in Figure 79. High seed value and low logical value are ideal for simulating “chaotic entanglement” in the appearance of noisy signals with the increase in degree (number of connections). High entropy is obvious in the presence of noise. Co-entanglement is pointed out to having both (1) **structural/topological entanglement or (hyper)spatial connectivity (geometrical domain)** such as a “tripartite entanglement” (Adesso et al., 2006) or a clique when >1 (in this case, referring to an averaged “degree” of most influential bots) and (2) **entanglement at the energy level**

(quantum domain), whereby chaos is an inductor. Moreover, >1 indicates an unstable state, <1 is stable, and 1 is equilibrium (Sayama, 2015).

On the other hand, the randomness (of sub-conditions) is responsible to variation of patterns thereafter. If the value of the parameters in the coding are standardized, the degree of nodes changes the entire picture. Changes in the initial simulation conditions are magnified significantly because of chaos which then goes into random fluctuations. However, the unfolding of (probable) energies through these random fluctuations is left to quantum mechanics by erudition. Bots add chaos, but disguise it as a sparky frequency somewhat holographic that of human interactions. Bots are engulfed in this frequency once randomness proceeds where: (a) they oscillate capably (between 1.0 to 2.0 seconds) and (b) they quantum mechanically thrive relativistic to critical mass.

Figure 82. Effect of seed value, logical value, and node degree to spectrogram.

Research Question 5: How can the network “virality” of Twitter bots be measured?

For the knowledge of the Communication Scholars and the intended dissemination of this study, let it be known that based on result of “Equation 4: Virality of Bots in the Network,” 70% of inflated node dynamics appeared bot-mediated. Twitter bot clusters increase with increase energy in the network—bots are energy hungry in order to proliferate.

A bot mass of 9.51×10^{-30} converts to 1.58×10^{-13} J of energy per 2.14×10^{-18} J energy increment in the network. This will cause the energy in network to rise exponentially to about 70000 J.

Mass equivalent (**Equation 7**), energy equivalent (**Equation 8**), critical threshold before node virality (**Equation 5**) and critical threshold after node virality (**Equation 6**) have very high positive correlation to degree and between each other, but have moderate positive correlation to Random Walk and PageRank. This only underscored a degree-directed bot activity.

By the quantum metrics above, **newsmax** (user id: 978, spammer) is most significant by mass equivalent (3.39×10^{-12}), energy equivalent (6.51×10^{-13}), critical threshold before virality (1.69×10^{-16}), and critical threshold after virality (1.19×10^{-16}). Thus, **newsmax** is notoriously disruptive than **bev768**. It may be supposed the two bots compete for influence in the network: the former spatially, the latter temporally.

Global Network Calculations (Equation 1 through Equation 4)

Table 46. Codes for implementing Equation 1 through Equation 4.

```
1. from numpy.linalg import matrix_power
2.
3. # Equation 1: Bot Mass
4. interactions = graphs[0].number_of_edges()
5. false_tweets = graphs[2].number_of_edges()
6. network_density = nx.density(graphs[0])
7. cmtx = 3.19*10**-38
8.
9. print("Calculating Bot Mass:")
10. print("Number of Interactions bet bots and human users:", interactions)
11. print("Number of False Tweets:", false_tweets)
12. print("Network Density:", network_density)
13. print("Constant:", cmtx)
14.
15. bm = ((interactions*false_tweets)/network_density)*cmtx
16.
17. print(" ")
18.
19. # Equation 2: Bot Energy
20. kcp = kuramoto_results["Tweet Layer"]
21. matrix_power_ev = matrix_power(eigenDecomposition, 3)
22. speed_of_light_squared = 8.98755179*10**16
23.
24.
25. be = bm*(kcp*matrix_power_ev)*speed_of_light_squared
26. be = be.real
27. np.savetxt('bot_energy.txt', be, delimiter=',')
28.
29. print("Calculating Bot Energy:")
30. print("Bot Mass:", bm)
31. print("Kuramoto Coupling:", kcp)
32. print("Matrix_power:", (np.matrix.flatten(be)[0:1]), "...")
33. print("Speed of light squared:", speed_of_light_squared)
34.
35. print(" ")
36.
37.
38. print("Calculating Energy in Network:")
39. # Equation 3: Energy fluctuations
40. evolution_vnge = envge
41. evolution_eigenstates = exgs.real
42. constant_kb = (1.38064*10**-23)*(300)
43. constant_ln2 = 0.69314718055995
44.
```

```

45. print("von Neumann Graph Entropy:", evolution_vnge)
46. print("Evolution of Eigenstates:", evolution_eigenstates)
47. print("kb constant:", constant_kb)
48. print("ln2 constant:", constant_ln2)
49.
50. efx = (envge / exgs)*constant_kb*constant_ln2
51. # set infinite values to zero
52. efx[efx >= 1E308] = 0
53. efx[np.isnan(efx)] = 0
54. efx = efx.real
55.
56. print(" ")
57.
58. # Equation 4: Virality of Bots
59. print("Calculating Virality of Bots:")
60.
61. print("Bot Energy", type(be), "...")
62. print("Energy in Network", efx, "...")
63.
64.
65. vob = be**(np.average(efx))
66. vob[np.isnan(vob)] = 0
67. vob = np.average(vob)
68.
69.
70.
71. print(" ")
72. print(" ")
73. print("=====  

=====")
74. print("Results:")
75.
76. # show results
77. print("Bot mass: ", bm)
78. print("Bot Energy (Averaged Value): ", np.average(np.matrix.flatten(be)))
79. print("Energy In Network (Averaged Value): ", np.average(efx))
80. print("Virality of Bots: ", vob)
81.
82. # matrix visualizations
83. fig, all_axes = plt.subplots(1, 2, figsize=(23,5))
84. ax = all_axes.flat
85. fig.suptitle("Equation result visualizations", y=1.1, fontsize=20)
86.
87. # compute the best partition
88. ax[0].set_title(f"Bot Energy Matrix", fontsize=14)
89. ax[0].imshow(be, cmap="jet", interpolation="bilinear")
90.
91. ax[1].set_title(f"Energy In Network", fontsize=14)
92. ax[1].plot(efx)
93.

```

```

94.
95.
96. plt.savefig("./figures/matrix_visualizations.png")

```

Equation 1: Bot Mass (Kg) in the Network

$$= \frac{\text{Number of Bot and Human Interactions} \times \text{Number of False Tweets}}{\text{Network Density}} \times 3.19 \times 10^{-38} \text{ Kg}$$

Number of interactions between bots and human users: 693

Number of false tweets: 316

Network density: 0.000734693098655607

Constant: $3.1899999999999996 \times 10^{-38}$

Bot mass: **$9.508347380399999 \times 10^{-30}$**

Equation 2: Quantization of Bot Energy (Joules) in the Network

$$= [\text{Bot Mass} \times (\text{Coupling Strength} \times \text{Matrix Power of Eigendecomposition})] \times 8.98755179 \times 10^{16} \text{ m}^2 / \text{s}^2$$

Bot mass: $9.508347380399999 \times 10^{-30}$

Kuramoto coupling strength: 0.13913487992949353

Matrix power of eigendecomposition: $[8.58975203 \times 10^{-28}] \dots$

Speed of light squared: $8.98755179 \times 10^{16}$

Quantization of Bot energy: **$1.5759548722984758 \times 10^{-13}$**

Equation 3: Quantization of Energy in Network (Joules)

$$= \frac{\text{von Neumann Graph Entropy Evolution}}{\text{Schrödinger Eigenstates Evolution}} \times (1.38064 \times 10^{-23} \text{ J/K} \times 300 \text{ K}) \times 0.69314718055995$$

von Neumann Graph Entropy: 3.254892110851875

Evolution of eigenstates: $\begin{bmatrix} 0.00000000 & 1.04709940 \times 10^{-5} & 4.18837569 \times 10^{-5} & \dots \\ 4.18837569 \times 10^{-5} & 1.04709940 \times 10^{-5} & 0.00000000 & \dots \end{bmatrix}$

Boltzmann constant, kB: 4.14192×10^{-21}

ln2 constant: 0.69314718055995

Quantization of Energy in network: **$2.138477456637343 \times 10^{-18}$**

Equation 4: Virality of Bots in the Network

= Average Bot Energy *(Average Energy in Network)*

Bot energy (average): `<class 'numpy.ndarray'> ...`

Energy in network (average): $\begin{bmatrix} 0.00000000 & 8.92433475 \times 10^{-16} & 2.23109537 \times 10^{-16} & \dots \\ 2.23109537 \times 10^{-16} & 8.92433475 \times 10^{-16} & 0.00000000 & \dots \end{bmatrix} \dots$

Virality of bots: **0.7041420118343193**

By equation models (in quantized amounts), a littlest bot mass of 9.51×10^{-30} will equal to 1.58×10^{-13} J of potential energy and the same amount is for the kinetic energy required. **Energy in the network is augmented by Twitter bots to 2.14×10^{-18} J per bit of misinformation.** Virality index has been devised (Table 47). Since .70 falls between .81 to 1.00, the interpretation is “High” with COVID-19 vaccine misinformation. This also means 70% of dynamics is bot-mediated.

Table 47. Index of bot virality.

Virality of bots	Interpretation
.81 to 1.00	Very high
.61 to .80	High
.41 to .60	Moderate
.21 to .40	Low
.00 to .20	Very low

Figure 83. Visualization of energy calculations in Python.

In Figure 83, bots merge as energy level increases (0 through 12). They also replicate the energy spectrum to diffuse symmetrically (0 through 10). Also, energy in a network takes place linearly, but logarithmically it is not actually a smooth phase transition. It is too noisy and wavy in the middle part in reference to Figure 75 and bots use this opportunity to maintain activity. The total number of nodes ($n=1374$) represented by the Tweet layer can correspond to the number of steps to transfer energy. If node count is made equal to time, it will take 1374 seconds or 23.33 minutes.

Energy in a network (Figure 83) resembles the equilibrium momentum distributions of a system containing quantum harmonic oscillators with random disorder based on Figure 81 (Hsueh et al., 2020). Furthermore, this supports the claim that vertices operate by quantum oscillations throughout their dynamics (Figure 84).

Figure 84. Distribution of equilibrium momentum.

SOURCE: Hsueh et al., 2020, p. 5.

The section below covers the calculations per node.

Local Calculations (Equation 5 through Equation 9 and Other Metrics)

Table 48. Codes for calculation of mass, energy, and threshold per influential node.

```

1. def mass_equivalent(degree):
2.     result = (degree/nx.density(tnx)) * (3.19**-38)
3.     return result
4.
5. def energy_equivalent(me):
6.     result = me * speed_of_light_squared * np.average(efx)
7.     return result
8.
9. def critical_threshold_of_node_before_node_virality(ee):
10.    result = ((ee*np.average(np.concatenate((list(bc_tnx.values()),
11.    list(percolation_cx.values()))))) / np.average(efx)) * np.average(efx)
12.
13. def critical_threshold_of_node_after_node_virality(ee):

```

```

14. result = ((ee*np.average(np.concatenate((list(bc_tnx.values()),
      list(percolation_cx.values())))) * vob) / np.average(efx)) * np.average(efx)
15. return result

```

Table 49. Codes for tabulating results per influential node.

```

1. network_timeseries = {}
2. network_node_classifications = {}
3.
4. # create network timeseries data
5.
6. for index, row in input_data[range_start:range_end].iterrows():
7.     tweet_date = moment.date(row["tweet_created_at"]).format("YYYY-MM-
      DD")
8.
9.     if tweet_date not in network_timeseries:
10.         network_timeseries[tweet_date] = 5
11.     else:
12.         network_timeseries[tweet_date] += 1
13.
14.     bot_type = ""
15.
16.     if row["from_user_type"] == "bot":
17.         network_timeseries[tweet_date] += 1
18.         bot_type = row["from_user_bot_type"]
19.     else:
20.         bot_type = "false (human account)"
21.
22.
23.
24.     node_item = {
25.         "id": index,
26.         "username": row["from_user_screen_name"],
27.         "bot_type": bot_type,
28.         "user_type": row["from_user_type"],
29.         "origin_tweet_date": tweet_date,
30.         "tweet_url": row["tweet_url"],
31.         "degree": network_timeseries[tweet_date],
32.         "node_entanglement": 0,
33.         "eigenvector_centrality": 0,
34.         "betweenness_centrality": 0,
35.         "clique_number": 0,
36.         "before_percolation": 0,
37.         "after_percolation": 0,
38.         "page_rank": 0,
39.         "mass_equivalent": 0,

```

```

40.     "energy_equivalent": 0,
41.     "critical_threshold_before_node_virality": 0,
42.     "critical_threshold_after_node_virality": 0,
43. }
44.
45. if row["from_user_screen_name"] not in network_node_classifications:
46.     network_node_classifications[row["from_user_screen_name"]] =
        node_item
47. else:
48.     network_node_classifications[row["from_user_screen_name"]]["degree"]
        += network_timeseries[tweet_date]
49.
50.
51. # sort entries
52. sorted(network_timeseries.keys())
53.
54.
55. # print(network_timeseries)
56.
57. tsl = list(network_timeseries.keys())
58.
59. start_date = tsl[0]
60. end_year = moment.date(tsl[len(tsl)-1]).format("YYYY")
61.
62. dates = date_range(start_date, f"{end_year}-12-30")
63. data = np.random.randint(0, 1, len(dates))
64.
65. timeframe_data = {}
66.
67. for date in dates:
68.     dx = moment.date(date).format("YYYY-MM-DD")
69.     timeframe_data[dx] = 180
70.
71. for dx in list(network_timeseries.keys()):
72.     timeframe_data[dx] = network_timeseries[dx]
73.
74. # preprocess node network classifications
75. network_node_classifications = list(network_node_classifications.values())
76. # sort by degree descending order
77. network_node_classifications = sorted(network_node_classifications, key =
        lambda i: i["degree"], reverse=True)
78.
79. # create dictionary for the network dataset
80.
81. htx = dict(nodes_dx)
82.
83. # correlate datasets
84.
85. for i, ix in enumerate(network_node_classifications):
86.     current_node = ix["username"]

```

```

87. match = next(item for item in htx.values() if item["username"] ==
    current_node)
88. if match:
89.     network_node_classifications[i]["node_entanglement"] =
    match.get("node_entanglement", 0)
90.     network_node_classifications[i]["eigenvector_centrality"] =
    match.get("eigenvector_centrality", 0)
91.     network_node_classifications[i]["betweenness_centrality"] =
    match.get("betweenness_centrality", 0)
92.     network_node_classifications[i]["closeness_centrality"] =
    match.get("closeness_centrality", 0)
93.     network_node_classifications[i]["clique_number"] =
    match.get("clique_number", 0)
94.     network_node_classifications[i]["before_percolation"] =
    match.get("betweenness_centrality", 0)
95.     network_node_classifications[i]["after_percolation"] =
    match.get("percolation_centrality", 0)
96.     network_node_classifications[i]["page_rank"] = match.get("page_rank", 0)
97.     network_node_classifications[i]["random_walk"] =
    match.get("random_walk", 0)
98.     network_node_classifications[i]["mass_equivalent"] =
    mass_equivalent(ix["degree"])
99.     network_node_classifications[i]["energy_equivalent"] =
    energy_equivalent(mass_equivalent(ix["degree"]))
100.    network_node_classifications[i]["critical_threshold_before_node_virality"]
    =
    critical_threshold_of_node_before_node_virality(energy_equivalent(mass_eq
    uivalent(ix["degree"])))
101.    network_node_classifications[i]["critical_threshold_after_node_virality"]
    =
    critical_threshold_of_node_after_node_virality(energy_equivalent(mass_eq
    uivalent(ix["degree"])))
102.
103.
104. mx_table = pd.DataFrame(network_node_classifications)
105.
106. print("Complete Table - Sorted by Degree")
107. display(mx_table)
108. mx_table.to_csv("./dataset/influential_nodes_and_network_analysis.csv")

```

Code outputs are tabulated on the GitHub repository. In the interest of determining relationships between individual measurements, a simple correlation was performed in Microsoft® Excel® 2019. Mass equivalent, energy equivalent, critical

threshold before node virality and critical threshold after node virality have very high positive correlation to degree ($r=1$) and between each other, but have moderate positive correlation to Random Walk ($r=.68$) and PageRank ($r=.68$).

The spambot “**newsmax**” (user id: 978) has the largest mass equivalent (3.39×10^{-12}), energy equivalent (6.51×10^{-13}), critical threshold before virality (1.69×10^{-16}), and critical threshold after virality (1.19×10^{-16}).

Table 50. Codes for calculating means and standard deviations per influential node.

```

1. nstats_total = {
2.   "value": "Total",
3.   "degree": np.sum(mx_table["degree"].tolist()),
4.   "node_entanglement": np.sum(mx_table["node_entanglement"].tolist()),
5.   "eigenvector_centrality": np.sum(mx_table["eigenvector_centrality"].tolist()),
6.   "betweenness_centrality":
   np.sum(mx_table["betweenness_centrality"].tolist()),
7.   "closeness_centrality": np.sum(mx_table["closeness_centrality"].tolist()),
8.   "clique_number": np.sum(mx_table["clique_number"].tolist()),
9.   "before_percolation": np.sum(mx_table["before_percolation"].tolist()),
10.  "after_percolation": np.sum(mx_table["after_percolation"].tolist()),
11.  "page_rank": np.sum(mx_table["page_rank"].tolist()),
12.  "random_walk": np.sum(mx_table["random_walk"].tolist()),
13.  "mass_equivalent": np.sum(mx_table["mass_equivalent"].tolist()),
14.  "energy_equivalent": np.sum(mx_table["energy_equivalent"].tolist()),
15.  "critical_threshold_before_node_virality":
   np.sum(mx_table["critical_threshold_before_node_virality"].tolist()),
16.  "critical_threshold_after_node_virality":
   np.sum(mx_table["critical_threshold_after_node_virality"].tolist()),
17.}
18.
19.nstats_mean = {
20.  "value": "Mean",
21.  "degree": np.mean(mx_table["degree"].tolist()),
22.  "node_entanglement": np.mean(mx_table["node_entanglement"].tolist()),
23.  "eigenvector_centrality":
   np.mean(mx_table["eigenvector_centrality"].tolist()),
24.  "betweenness_centrality":
   np.mean(mx_table["betweenness_centrality"].tolist()),
25.  "closeness_centrality": np.sum(mx_table["closeness_centrality"].tolist()),
26.  "clique_number": np.mean(mx_table["clique_number"].tolist()),

```

```

27. "before_percolation": np.mean(mx_table["before_percolation"].tolist()),
28. "after_percolation": np.mean(mx_table["after_percolation"].tolist()),
29. "page_rank": np.mean(mx_table["page_rank"].tolist()),
30. "random_walk": np.mean(mx_table["random_walk"].tolist()),
31. "mass_equivalent": np.mean(mx_table["mass_equivalent"].tolist()),
32. "energy_equivalent": np.mean(mx_table["energy_equivalent"].tolist()),
33. "critical_threshold_before_node_virality":
    np.mean(mx_table["critical_threshold_before_node_virality"].tolist()),
34. "critical_threshold_after_node_virality":
    np.mean(mx_table["critical_threshold_after_node_virality"].tolist()),
35. }
36.
37. nstats_std = {
38.     "value": "Standard Deviation",
39.     "degree": np.std(mx_table["degree"].tolist()),
40.     "node_entanglement": np.std(mx_table["node_entanglement"].tolist()),
41.     "eigenvector_centrality": np.std(mx_table["eigenvector_centrality"].tolist()),
42.     "betweenness_centrality":
        np.std(mx_table["betweenness_centrality"].tolist()),
43.     "closeness_centrality": np.sum(mx_table["closeness_centrality"].tolist()),
44.     "clique_number": np.std(mx_table["clique_number"].tolist()),
45.     "before_percolation": np.std(mx_table["before_percolation"].tolist()),
46.     "after_percolation": np.std(mx_table["after_percolation"].tolist()),
47.     "page_rank": np.std(mx_table["page_rank"].tolist()),
48.     "random_walk": np.std(mx_table["random_walk"].tolist()),
49.     "mass_equivalent": np.std(mx_table["mass_equivalent"].tolist()),
50.     "energy_equivalent": np.std(mx_table["energy_equivalent"].tolist()),
51.     "critical_threshold_before_node_virality":
        np.std(mx_table["critical_threshold_before_node_virality"].tolist()),
52.     "critical_threshold_after_node_virality":
        np.std(mx_table["critical_threshold_after_node_virality"].tolist()),
53. }
54.
55.
56. nstats = [nstats_total, nstats_mean, nstats_std]
57.
58.
59. ns_table = pd.DataFrame(nstats)
60.
61. print("Network Statistics Table")
62. display(ns_table)
63. ns_table.to_csv("./dataset/network_statistics_per_column.csv")

```

Table 51. Network statistics of most influential nodes ($n=95$).

	<i>Total</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
Degree	76576.00	806.06	3865.83
Node Entanglement	-0.0539	-0.0006	0.0023
Eigenvector Centrality	0.8893	0.0094	0.0719
Betweenness Centrality	0.1863	0.0020	0.0087
Closeness Centrality	1.3620	1.3620	1.3620
Clique Number	176.00	1.8526	0.3545
Before Percolation Centrality	0.1863	0.0020	0.0087
After Percolation Centrality	0.2550	0.0027	0.0124
Centrality Change (connected to disconnected) as time evolution (sec)	0.0687	0.0007	0.0037
Random Walk	0.4254	0.0045	0.0107
PageRank	0.4254	0.0045	0.0107
Mass Equivalent (Kg)	7.48×10^{-12}	7.87×10^{-14}	3.78×10^{-13}
Energy Equivalent (J)	1.44×10^{-12}	1.51×10^{-14}	7.26×10^{-14}
Energy Transmitted to Network (J)	6.04×10^{-12}	6.36×10^{-14}	3.05×10^{-13}
Critical Threshold before Virality (J)	3.73×10^{-16}	3.93×10^{-18}	1.88×10^{-17}
Critical Threshold after Virality (J)	2.63×10^{-16}	2.77×10^{-18}	1.33×10^{-17}
Theoretical Critical Value (J) per Node	1.10×10^{-16}	1.16×10^{-18}	5.57×10^{-18}

Negative entanglement, in the context of quantum entanglement, describes bots having a mixed state and are separable (easily disentangle) depending on the network initial state (Yu & Eberly, 2007, p. 2) like amount of misinformation, energy, active network components, etc.

Total eigenvector centrality confirms that these bots are most influential on a range of 0 to 1. On the other hand, total closeness centrality is greater than 1 which confirms the bots work in proximity among themselves involving 1 to 2 large cliques by clique number. A low betweenness centrality (<1) makes intermediating bots infrequent within clusters or communities. Random walk and PageRank are low (<1) as well which will be interpreted as bots competing for their importance and will probably not direct human users to other bots except to themselves, plus multiple edges are present. Another explanation could be that node influence overlaps and it

translates into a collective global influence (summed effect of multisource spreaders) by cooperation among nodes (Teng et al., 2016) through synchronization.

For random walks, specifically the mean first-passage time (mean recurrence time) is inversely proportional to node's degree but the steady state of nodes is degree-dependent (Speidel et al., 2015), i.e., an increasing degree of connectivity means becoming more stable.

Before percolation centrality and after percolation centrality correspond to transition of nodes with the influx of (mis)information. The change in centrality from connected or functional network to disconnected or nonfunctional network reveals "network reliability" (Li et al., 2015, p. 556) and may also describe a spectral gap in centrality rankings (Benzi & Klymko, 2013).

This study looks at centrality gap as the temporality of connections with respect to time evolution under the roof of quantum mechanics where the internal excited state (eigenstate) of bots changes fast (a total of .0687 seconds for the most influential). It shows that bot nodes terminate connectivity or fail due to operational limits meaning critical thresholds (before and after virality) are surpassed and energy will decay differently over time (Figure 85).

When individual nodes are cut off from a giant component, they form clusters of connected nodes and then fragments into terminal clusters (Li et al., 2015, p. 557). Critical threshold of bots after virality will be lower. They will also require less energy in the immediate post virality to reactivate since some of the energy is conserved. On the other hand, should node potential fall below the operational value (difference between high and low thresholds or theoretical critical value), small isolated clusters are produced and will mark their lifetime (Li et al., 2015, p. 557) after contributing to virality (Table 51).

The mass of bots is quantizable to energy but much of their energy is radiated to the network. Theoretically, it sinks into the potential well and will fuel a larger disequilibrium and negentropy to maintain the network.

Figure 85. Connectivity distribution and patterns of decomposition by literature.

SOURCE: (A, B) Gonçalves, 2021; (C) Pagel, Meade, & Scott, 2007, p. 3; (D)

Speidel et al. 2015, p. 7.

Table 52. Codes for generating sub tables from network analysis.

```

1. print("Percolation Centrality Table (Before and after comparison)")
2.
3. def bp Centrality_change(row):
4.     if row["betweenness Centrality"] > row["percolation Centrality"]:
5.         return "decrease"
6.     if row["betweenness Centrality"] < row["percolation Centrality"]:
7.         return "increase"
8.     if row["betweenness Centrality"] == row["percolation Centrality"]:
9.         return "no change"
10.
11. # parse degree influence to network data
12. for i, x in enumerate(htx.values()):
13.     htx[i]["degree"] = 0
14.
15.
16. pct = pd.DataFrame.from_dict(htx.values())
17. prt = pd.DataFrame.from_dict(htx.values())
18. rwt = pd.DataFrame.from_dict(htx.values())
19.
20.
21. # update degree values
22. for i, x in enumerate(network_node_classifications):
23.     pct.loc[pct["username"] == x["username"], ["degree"]] = x["degree"]
24.     prt.loc[prt["username"] == x["username"], ["degree"]] = x["degree"]
25.     rwt.loc[rwt["username"] == x["username"], ["degree"]] = x["degree"]
26.
27.
28.
29. pct = pct[["username", "betweenness Centrality",
30.            "percolation Centrality", "degree"]]
31. pct["change"] = pct.apply(lambda row: bp Centrality_change(row), axis=1)
32. pct = pct.rename({"betweenness Centrality": "before_percolation",
33.                  "percolation Centrality": "after_percolation"}, axis=1)
34. pct = pct.sort_values(by=["degree"], ascending=False)
35. display(pct)
36. pct.to_csv("./dataset/percolation_before_and_after.csv")
37.
38. print("Page Rank Table")
39. prt = prt[["username", "page_rank", "degree"]]
40. prt = prt.sort_values(by=["degree"], ascending=False)
41. display(prt)
42. prt.to_csv("./dataset/page_rank_nodes.csv")
43.
44. print("Random Walk Table")
45. rwt = rwt[["username", "random_walk", "degree"]]
46. rwt = rwt.sort_values(by=["degree"], ascending=False)
47. display(rwt)
48. rwt.to_csv("./dataset/random_walk_nodes.csv")

```

The sub tables (**percolation_before_and_after.csv**, **random_walk_nodes.csv**, and **page_rank_nodes.csv**) are accessible under 'dataset' of **COVID-19_infodemics**. Every vertex ($n=1374$) is measured for value (a) increase, (b) decrease or (c) no change after percolation using the NetworkX codes by Lee (2021). The number of vertices was the same across three calculations.

Percolation centrality, Random walk, and PageRank decreased in "**newsmax**" (spammer, **user id**: 247) from 5.25×10^{-3} to 5.06×10^{-3} , "**VanderluciaSch1**" (other, **user id**: 545 and 1347) from 5.84×10^{-5} to 5.62×10^{-5} , "**kawarren818**" (human, **user id**: 984) from 3.82×10^{-5} to 3.73×10^{-5} , "**haber_okuyorum1**" (human, **user id**: 1033) from 2.97×10^{-5} to 2.93×10^{-5} , "**fuzzyface**" (human, **user id**: 1065) from 2.97×10^{-5} to 2.93×10^{-5} , "**PantsClock**" (human, **user id**: 1048) from 2.23×10^{-5} to 2.23×10^{-5} , and "**sir_lars**" (human, **user id**: 895) from 2.23×10^{-5} to 2.23×10^{-5} . These were fully percolated by critical mass (were initial spreaders) and have moved from a central position to peripheral (Piraveenan et al., 2013) and even to another layer (e.g., **VanderluciaSch1**).

Nodes without any change after percolation (i.e., zero) have no direct link to percolated nodes (Piraveenan et al., 2013) but spread misinformation independently via links they form like "**ronnoconiv**" (other; **user id**: 60), "**NFL**" (self-declared; **user id**: 165), "**KJP46**" (spammer; **user id**: 250), "**dansiddiqui**" (spammer; **user id**: 251), "**StefanLazar10**" (spammer; **user id**: 354), "**santa_tzu**" (spammer; **user id**: 436), "**LaliWety**" (other; **user id**: 558), "**margbrennan**" (human; **user id**: 610), "**NathalieDecuyp2**" (human; **user id**: 784), "**cat_bair**" (human; **user id**: 809), "**ArmywifeDi**" (spammer; **user id**: 823), "**DonCryptoDraper**" (spammer; **user id**: 1325), and "**lissandro_dp**" (human; **user id**: 1373). They fill spaces between center and periphery of the network.

Nodes that showed an increase were central spreaders (Piraveenan et al., 2013) like “bev768” (false human account; **user id:** 620) from 6.79×10^{-2} to 1.01×10^{-1} , “nickisnest” (false human account; **user id:** 725) from 3.23×10^{-2} to 4.14×10^{-2} , “CobyJay41” (false human account; **user id:** 913) from 2.89×10^{-2} to 3.95×10^{-2} , “JonPort79449036” (false human account; **user id:** 189) from 3.07×10^{-2} to 3.93×10^{-2} , “CobyJayJr42” (false human account; **user id:** 85) from 4.86×10^{-3} to 7.22×10^{-3} , “Daniel2510G” (spammer; **user id:** 67) from 5.80×10^{-4} to 5.97×10^{-4} , “Left_of_You” (spammer; **user id:** 1) from 1.34×10^{-4} to 1.73×10^{-4} , and “babibelle33” (false human account; **user id:** 994) from 6.37×10^{-6} to 6.87×10^{-6} . False human accounts tend to dominate centrally while spammers work peripherally which the literature supports (Stella et al., 2018).

Table 53. Summary of results.

	<i>Percolation Centrality</i>	<i>Random Walk</i>	<i>PageRank</i>
Decrease	7	7	7
Increase	60	60	60
No Change	1307	1307	1307
Total (<i>N</i>)	1374	1374	1374

Table 54. Codes for manually tracing all nodes (unfiltered by degree).

```

1. network_tracing_table = pd.DataFrame(htx.values())
2. nxt_table = pd.DataFrame(network_tracing_table)
3. nxt_table = nxt_table[["username", "bot_type", "node_entanglement",
   "eigenvector_centrality", "betweenness_centrality", "closeness_centrality",
   "clique_number", "page_rank", "random_walk"]]
4. display(nxt_table)
5.
6. nxt_table.to_csv("./dataset/2nd_network_analysis_raw_data.csv")

```

The codes above were implemented to analyze nodes below a degree cut-off of 5 but have valuable network metrics. The table is comprehensive and is located on the GitHub repository under dataset: “[2nd network analysis raw data.csv](#)”.

Research Question 6: What is the sonification pattern of Twitter bots?

For the knowledge of the Communication Scholars and the intended dissemination of this study, let it be known that Twitter bots oscillate from <25 *dB* then dropping to a brief equilibrium and finally surging to 94.12 *dB* at 2090.91 *Hz* roughly over 2.0 seconds. Signal anomalies indicate malicious bot activities. These were detectable from .006 seconds until .048 seconds. A sudden frequency change of .00025 seconds may be considered the period of reaching critical mass, which is followed by a signal burst from bots' virality. Translation of this network phenomenon to a real-world (perceptible) scale is equivalent to the energy released from a chest x-ray. Twitter bots communicate like signal drivers (generating sinusoidal waveform) going non-uniform or asymptotic (nonlinear).

In this study, sonification is more helpful in the analysis of energy burst (i.e., the catalytic driver to "virality" from the network's energy threshold and the echoic signals within Twitter's digital microcosm) through "quasi-musical sequences" (Kafala, 2019, p. 129) of chaotic frequencies found in the decomposition of harmonic structures. Sonification converts impulses into harmonics.

Sonification of simulated data points in the spectrogram signifies (a) characterization of energy emission (burst) in timing of the highest pitch, (b) "virality" of misinformation with its cascading intensity, and (c) "virulence" of the spreaders (most influential nodes) based on rapidity and repetitiveness of tones (periodicity). Sonification of the raw data is simply "audification". The process is a straightforward conversion and done with minor (technical) enhancements (Dubus & Bresin, 2013) to increase clarity.

In this study, the degree of influential node connections that are simulated over four seconds code for binary signals. Basically, time-series data is reproducible in acoustic waveforms (de Campo, 2009, p. 12). Frequencies appear in a spectrogram through fast Fourier transformation, which is converted into MIDI notes and saved as waveform (.wav) audio file format. Pitch undulations heard on playback also signify the energy landscape inferred within the Twitter network in noisy fluxes. Expression of “pacing” (pitch rapidity between start and end of each cycle) effecting the energy cascades by over damping (from community scale to a global threshold) highlights the power of influential nodes. Pitching of the sound depends on an array of values seeded to generate nonuniform discrete or random frequencies.

Model-based sonification is more recommended than mapping data features (Neuhoff, 2019, p. 329) due to the challenges of (a) sorting between signal-related and perceptual-related components (Grond & Berger, 2011, p. 370) and (b) conducting analysis of high-dimensional data (Hermann, 2011, p. 419; Hermann & Ritter, 1999), more importantly, looking for “exploratory patterns in [*the*] data” (Emsley & Roure, 2017, p. 1). However, parameter mapping turned out to be more practical to implement. The original audio file was reprocessed: sound pitches were traced in order to replace them with clicks of a Geiger counter and thus, mimicking particle signals and its pattern. Such particle detection analogy is contingent to the interpretation of energy decay.

Signal Sonification and Analysis

Table 55. Coding for sonification and plotting of spectral decomposition.

```
1. import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
2. from scipy import signal
3. from scipy.io import wavfile
```

```
4.  
5. sample_rate, samples = wavfile.read('./dataset/spectrogram_audio.wav')  
6. frequencies, times, spectrogram = signal.spectrogram(samples, sample_rate)  
7.  
8. plt.figure(figsize=(4,8))  
9. plt.pcolormesh(times, frequencies, spectrogram)  
10. plt.imshow(spectrogram)  
11. plt.ylabel('Frequency [Hz]')  
12. plt.xlabel('Time [sec]')  
13. plt.gca().invert_yaxis()  
14. plt.show()  
15. plt.savefig("./figures/audio_generated_spectrogram.png")
```

Figure 86. Original audio spectrogram.

In the spectrogram of the original audio (Figure 86), energy is tightly clumped (compressed) until 20 Hertz (Hz) . If we zoom in, the frequency granularizes into audible tones at higher frequencies or longer wavelengths as radio waves. There are so many more details that can be studied, but those will only make sense if optimized and patterns are decoded by sonification techniques.

The original Waveform (WAV) Audio File Format ([1. Spectrogram audio.wav](#)) is converted to Geiger counter clicks and melodic harp, and then merged. Harp musical notes were chosen as the background sound because background sounds must be "...suitably pleasant and unobtrusive" (Ballora et al., 2012, p. 6), which makes listening to changes in the foreground sound easily detectable.

Sample rate of the original audio file has been increased to 4800 Hz from 4000 Hz in Digital Audio Workstation (DAW) Pro Tools HD 12. Converted audio file ([2. Converted From Original Spectrogram Audio File.mp3](#)) became 10 times faster at .08 seconds than the original at about 1 second. Elastic properties in DAW Pro Tools HD 12 stretched the converted audio file to 13.5 seconds ([3. Stretched Audio to 13.5 Secs.wav](#)). (Figure 90)

In this study, modification of the sample rate from 4000 Hz to 4800 Hz was justified as "minor enhancement" (Dubus & Bresin, 2013). Audio frequencies ranging from 2 to 7 kiloHertz, KHz (2000 to 7000 Hz) "...carry a lot of detail" (Arnold, 2020, p. 65). "Boosting these frequencies [*for example, through an audio conversion*] can help the listener hear subtle detail that may otherwise be overlooked" (Arnold, 2020, p. 65). This is statistically demonstrated by $M = 29.36$, $SD = 157.72$ (*original audio*) versus $M = 305.67$, $SD = 1166.03$ (*converted audio*) in Table 56. However, (enhanced) autocorrelation in Audacity® 3.1.3 generates a time shift or a lag from the original signal (Archer, 2018) in order to correlate signals and to

reduce them into clusters. So, the actual sound duration of 14 seconds is condensed over a spectrum (size of 2048) beginning at .00025 seconds through .25575 seconds.

In the results, the original sound would only carry details from .00025 seconds to .0005 seconds, which would be too short if they were not boosted at the rate of 4800 *Hz*. After the rate increment, sounds were quantizable into critical energy levels at .00025 seconds through .06 seconds. On the other hand, frequencies at 250 *Hz* through 2 *KHz* (2000 *Hz*) produce “tinny sounds” (Arnold, 2020, p. 65) and noise. The noise range is from .006 seconds through .048 seconds. Sounds dull from 60 to 250 *Hz* (Arnold, 2020, p. 65), but this allows isolation of overlapping events and these frequencies were heard at .048 seconds through .20 seconds. At 20 to 60 *Hz*, sounds fall under the “muddy range” or “low base frequencies” (Arnold, 2020, p. 65), which were at .20 seconds until ending at .25575 seconds.

Polyphonic decay algorithm was implemented in Celemony Melodyne 4, a third-party plugin for DAW Pro Tools HD 12, to create the melodic harp tunes in a Musical Instrument Digital (MIDI) Interface file format ([4. Midi Conversion From Stretched Audio.mid](#)).

One clicking sound in WAV format was isolated ([6. Isolated One Geiger Counter Click.wav](#)) from a YouTube video by Ryhindor (2011), which was downloaded as mp3 file ([5. Geiger Counter Sound.mp3](#)), to customize an instrument plug-in for replicating Geiger counter clicks in Kontakt 5 Player, which is another third-party plugin for DAW Pro Tools HD 12.

The isolated click sound was loaded one by one to all the notes in the melodic harp audio ([4. Midi Conversion From Stretched Audio.mid](#)) using the MIDI controller for MIDI mapping in Kontakt 5 Player so a full-length Geiger counter audio

is reproduced. The resulting sound file is in WAV format ([7. Midi Converted to Geiger Counter Sound.wav](#)).

Harp Preset in Air Music Tech Xpand!2, another third-party plugin for DAW Pro Tools HD 12, was used on the melodic harp audio (**4. Midi Conversion From Stretched Audio.mid**) to refine the tunes especially for timbre ([8. Midi Converted to Harp Instrument Sound.wav](#)).

The two-instrument track was combined ([9. Midi to Combined Harp and Geiger Counter Sound.wav](#)). The Geiger counter audio (as foreground sound) represents a coded communication equivalent to energy spikes by influential nodes while the harp audio (as background sound) represents entropy.

Audio waveforms are visualized and analyzed in Audacity® 3.1.3, a free and open-source audio software (Audacity, 2021). Enhanced autocorrelation is implemented for pitch detection and clustering without the unwanted harmonics by “peak pruning” (Robert, 2013). Spectral density estimation is based on signal frequency with Welch's method in consideration of non-stationarities (nonlinearity) of signals (Cohen, 2019a) throughout their decomposition that need to be smoothed for power analysis (Cohen, 2019b) and for quality of estimation (Jwo et al., 2021). Amplitude is displayed in decibels (dB) and its equivalent frequency (f), in Hertz (Hz), is shown for the highest peak. Duration of playback is in seconds. QR codes are created for each audio spectrogram using “QR Code Generator” by Bitly (2021) to access the sounds directly from the GitHub folder “**Computer Electrical Sound Conversion Files**” under “**COVID-19_infodemics**”.

An important feature that makes sounds appear musical to the listener (i.e., in terms of its acoustics and structure) is “periodicity,” which refers to the “beats” (by pulses of energy in this study) that occur simultaneously (isochronous) and these, in

turn, determine the rhythm (Oesch, 2019). Another feature is “synchrony,” whenever events appear at the same time (Oesch, 2019). Simultaneity is defined on a moving timeframe and is explicit with the combined audio (**9. Midi to Combined Harp and Geiger Counter Sound.wav**) as tones converge during playback.

Analyzing “periodicity” and “synchrony,” is “...actually listening to a multiplicity of sounds that form the harmonic series” (Alvira, 2006b). Two kinds of intervals are contrasted: harmonic interval and melodic interval. The former are notes (or tones) sounding simultaneously while the latter are notes in succession (Alvira, 2006a). These are scrutinized in frequency ratios.

Figure 87. Representation of intervals by musical notation.

SOURCE: Alvira, 2006a.

Calculation of the mathematical ratio (or size of intervals) is by dividing the succeeding frequency by the preceding frequency (Alvira, 2006a). Time moves by .00025 seconds on the spectrogram. Harmonic ratio of the original audio file (**1. Spectrogram_audio.wav**) and new audio files (**7. Midi Converted to Geiger Counter Sound.wav**, **8. Midi Converted to Harp Instrument Sound.wav**, **9. Midi to Combined Harp and Geiger Counter Sound.wav**) inflated from .50 at .00025

seconds until it reached 1.00 at .05025 seconds and through .2555 seconds. Variations between the calculated harmonic ratios (every .001 seconds) abated to zero at .051 seconds, which can suggest a depreciation of entropy from energy decaying in the field after (mis)information has seeded locally.

With the emulated Geiger “clicks” audio and the combined Geiger “clicks” and harp tones, the highest frequency (Hz) or pitch is found in the beginning (Figure 91 and Figure 93) whereas it tends to boost shortly with the original sound and harp tones version from the spectrograms in Audacity® 3.1.3. On the other hand, by flipping the representation with intensity (dB) using a scatter plot with straight lines in Microsoft® Excel® 2019, the preliminary state of nodes oscillates under a low power flux ($<25\ dB$) then drops to a brief equilibrium (Figure 89). They are energized while shifting to another frequency and surge up on an average of $94.12\ dB$ and $2090.91\ Hz$ as revealed with the Geiger “clicks” audio and the merged sound graphs respectively (Figure 89). Likewise, energy is imbibed from the energy draining into the network through “energy loss” and collects back as “base energy” (Figure 24) when other (neighboring) nodes return to their pre-excited state on a different synchronization timeline. Hence, energy is conserved.

How an energy-laden field such as the Twitter network is (supremely) regulated remains obscure. The influential nodes’ activities externalizing the mass of (mis)information is causal to the distortion of base energy of uninfected nodes (Figure 24), but balancing energy consumption and distribution spatially is tricky. In the immediate field, there must be energy scavenger nodes that replicate the transmission of a contagion (misinformation) not because they are autonomous or programmed into it (in the case of Twitter bots), but because they actively cycle a viral behavior to exacerbate the energy gradient by their spatiotemporality.

The cycling is favorable in the sense that more rogue nodes can diffuse and more connections can be ratified. Thus, misinformation flows liberally as though it is endorsed with tenable content and ends up being acceptable to the receiving nodes. Furthermore, there must be potency behind the fluidity of the “Twitterverse” since the energy permeating its unbounded field (i.e., consequential to the destruction and reconstitution of the information and matrices) allows for a disequilibrium-driven spontaneity so it will not cease.

Waveform spikes in Audacity® 3.1.3 reflect the instantaneous or momentary peak volume (the dark blue areas further above and below zero) that are the recognizable events in the audio track, where the average volume over a linear time observation (the light blue areas) is the root mean square (RMS) or simply the average audible sound (Adams, 2020) within a relative equilibrium boundary. Sound is distorted harshly (heard as loud bursts) when peaks (both in positive and negative deflections) get too high or low as deviations (SD) from the RMS. Many distortions run in all audio tracks in the snipped images (Figure 90 through Figure 93).

Moreover, change in pitch (towards decrescendo) marks a transition and shows energy evolving auditorily and spectrographically by waveform metamorphoses as it “materializes” into a “pre-critical mass” equivalent to potential energy of cascading misinformation. Muffling sounds impart turbulent or chaotic data points resembling “fibrillatory waves” on the spectrogram or may be as unclear as intrusive, distinctively changing foreground sound, but with superpositioning (background) noise. It has been underscored in the literature that contrasting between chaos and noise is tough (Kulp & Zunino, 2014 cited in Toker et al., 2020). However, a recent study argues that, if k value is greater than .99 the data is chaotic otherwise it is periodic while rising entropies reveal a stochastic data (Toker et al., 2020).

Based on the spectrograms, energy fluctuations were periodic from .00025 to .05 seconds but turned chaotic from .05025 to .25575 seconds. Time to critical mass may be declared at .00025 seconds and at the same moment tremendous influential node synchronization and local energy spill is ignited. The results show that bursts of energy occur periodically and towards decomposition in a chaotic pattern. Melodic interval is more useful with periodic tones which "...can be either ascending or descending" (Ellinger, 2012), for example, by Geiger "clicks" and musical harp representations. There are 70 to 80 tones unpacking intermittently (into pulses) before getting sparse. The count per minute (cpm) can be calculated by multiplying the number of audible tones by 20 (Fleming, 2020), which gives a range of 3.5 to 4.0 cpm. Theoretical decay can be expressed in microsieverts per hour ($\mu Sv/hr$) by multiplying cpm to .0057 using a reference detector size (Parlante, 2012), which averages at .02 $\mu Sv/hr$ or a radiation dose of 2.0 milli roentgen equivalent man, *mrem*. This is equal to a chest x-ray (United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2021).

On the other hand, chaotic tones could suggest that mass is compounded and will be accentuated potentially until another critical event happens. Thus, prediction can be rendered by machine learning. It was shown that decomposition time of frequencies is longer when bursts of energies are noisy at lower fluctuations compared to a denoised sound (Figure 88). Intensities impulse at varying levels at the beginning to resonate from potential energy and then will depreciate. Sounds get eloquent at maximum peak in the source audio, in converted Geiger sound, and in merged Geiger and harp sound except that the source audio has a wide dampening and long quiescent interval to decomposition with a small mount (Figure 89). On the other hand, melodic sound has not shown to resonate and decomposition is sharp.

Correlation and variance analysis by single-factor ANOVA between sonic representations of data was performed. Frequency patterns (Table 58) with the converted Geiger sound and combined Geiger and harp sounds are strongly correlated, $r(1021) = 0.74$, $p = < .05$ (0.7 to 0.9 is high positive correlation according to Jaadi, 2019) or they have very similar information. However, comparing in decibels (Table 57), original sound is the most course and intense on the average ($M = 18.93$, $SD = 35.77$) when compared to Geiger sound ($M = 1.58$, $SD = 6.64$), harp sound ($M = 1.62$, $SD = 3.44$), and merged sounds ($M = 2.21$, $SD = 7.78$), which were significant (Table 59) by one-way ANOVA ($F(3, 4088) = 215.25$, $p = < .05$).

The original sound has the highest variance (1279.37). It has enormously lowered in the merged Geiger and harp sounds (60.47). This can show that about 91% is noise $\left(\frac{1279.37 - 60.47}{1279.37 + 60.47} = 0.9097 \right)$ which is filtered through Welch method. The results can imply as well that optimization of sonification is achieved with variance decrease. Chaotic sound waves are consummated to noise indicating energy loss through conservation. On the other hand, skewness and kurtosis are all positive as gleaned from decomposition. The original sound has the lowest skewness (2.25), which is .37 below the harp audio (2.62) because these sound waves are very compact.

Table 56. Characteristics of the sound frequencies (*Hz*).

	<i>Original</i>	<i>Converted</i>
Count (<i>n</i>)	1023.00	1023.00
Mean (<i>M</i>)	29.36	305.67
Median	7.81	93.66
Standard Deviation (<i>SD</i>)	157.72	1166.03
Standard Error of the Mean (<i>SEM</i>)	4.93	36.47
Confidence Level (95%)	9.68	71.57
Kurtosis	423.58	215.76
Skewness	18.66	13.03
Range	3996.09	23953.08
Minimum	3.91	46.92
Maximum	4000.00	24000.00

Table 57. Characteristics of the sound intensities (*dB*).

	<i>Original</i>	<i>Geiger</i>	<i>Harp</i>	<i>Merged</i>
Count (<i>n</i>)	1023.00	1023.00	1023.00	1023.00
Mean (<i>M</i>)	18.93	1.58	1.62	2.21
Median	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Standard Deviation (<i>SD</i>)	35.77	6.64	3.44	7.78
Standard Error of the Mean (<i>SEM</i>)	1.12	0.21	0.11	0.24
Confidence Level (95%)	2.19	0.41	0.21	0.48
Kurtosis	5.22	93.54	7.31	90.37
Skewness	2.25	8.80	2.62	8.45
Range	232.88	90.58	19.91	97.66
Minimum	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Maximum	232.88	90.58	19.91	97.66

Table 58. Correlation of sound intensities.

	<i>Intensity in Original Audio</i>	<i>Intensity in Geiger Audio</i>	<i>Intensity in Harp Audio</i>	<i>Intensity in Merged Audio</i>
Intensity in Original Audio	1.00			
Intensity in Geiger Audio	-0.04	1.00		
Intensity in Harp Audio	0.06	-0.03	1.00	
Intensity in Combined Audio	-0.01	0.74	.43	1.00

Table 59. Analysis of variance for sound intensities.

SUMMARY				
<i>Groups</i>	<i>Count</i>	<i>Sum</i>	<i>Average</i>	<i>Variance</i>
Intensity in Original Audio	1023	19366.15	18.93	1279.37
Intensity in Geiger Audio	1023	1616.06	1.58	44.02
Intensity in Harp Audio	1023	1658.23	1.62	11.85
Intensity in Combined Audio	1023	2261.29	2.21	60.47

ANOVA (Single Factor)						
<i>Source of Variation</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>F crit</i>
Between Groups	225316.32	3	75105.44	215.25	.00	2.61
Within Groups	1426424.07	4088	348.93			
Total	1651740.38	4091				

Figure 88. Comparison by frequency decomposition with time.

Figure 89. Comparison by intensity decomposition with frequency.

Figure 90. Original audio track on top with highest peak at 208.446 *dB* (14 *Hz*) ; stretched audio track (13.5 sec) below with highest peak at 468.407 *dB* (57 *Hz*).

Frequencies that transition between slow ($\approx 20 \text{ Hz}$) and fast ($>40 \text{ Hz}$) follow the human pattern of information processing, i.e., towards a conscious interaction (de la Fuente et al. 2021). Bots' artificial intelligence include producing awareness of neighbor nodes' activity from an information-driven engagement.

Figure 91. Geiger "clicks" audio track with highest peak at 91.018 dB (2695 Hz).

Figure 92. Harp audio track with highest peak at 20.005 dB (148 Hz).

Figure 93. Combined audio track with highest peak at 3013 *dB* (97.676 *Hz*).

Chapter VI

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary

Misinformation spreads more frequently with user replies than with retweets either by human accounts or hybrid bots and faster through interlayer edges. Bot tweets is about 46%. False human accounts were more prolific (67%) than traditional bots (33%) but were more often spammers (27%). Bots form a single focal group. They target a central human hub using more outbound links or out-going communication. Super spreaders were detected using centrality-based metrics. Bots that have high betweenness and eigenvector centralities, random walk score, and PageRank score were false human accounts.

Bot cliques emerge inconsistently by edge entanglement with humans. False human accounts were central spreaders and were detectable by an increase in percolation centrality, random walk and PageRank scores. Spammers were peripheral spreaders with scores decreased or that have not changed whenever indirectly connected to human hubs. On an average, 2.69345 edge is added per .011 secs by extrapolation of the Fast Incremental von Neumann Graph Entropy values. Spambots are entangled ubiquitously. False human accounts connect by power-law distribution. Many cross-links were shown to exist between bots and humans.

Bots have a shorter time to synchronize but do so only partially around 400 seconds (6.67 minutes) with a peak before reaching 200 seconds (3.33 minutes). Most influential bots oscillate in many small, low degree clusters. Spambots have faster

tunneling time to cross interlayers of the Twitter network. Based on wavefunction simulation, a 29.45% network energy inflation brought about by a 13.55% tweet increase will cause viral (mis)information spread owing to a bot-mediated human dynamics of about 70% or a virality index at .70 within nine months (peaked at 7th month).

A climb to 50 J is reached over .26 seconds with bots; hence, infodemic mitigation should aim to cancel out this energy level by injection of counteracting bots. Bots utilize two energy plateaus to remain active (and resilient). Energy was assumed to be conserved within 1.12 to 1.34 seconds gap. Energy from critical mass (acted on by Twitter bots) can be approximated at 9.61×10^6 J bursting from .0015 seconds. This is time to 'critical threshold' (mass of misinformation becomes massive). Nonetheless, Twitter bots were catalysts.

Phase transition of nodes (randomness) can be as fast as .0003 seconds when highly energized. A bot mass of 9.51×10^{-30} can equal to 1.58×10^{-13} J of kinetic energy per 2.14×10^{-18} J energy increment in the network where energy in network can rise exponentially to 70000 J. Based on before and after percolation tests, spectral gaps in centrality rankings showed the temporality of bot activity every .0687 seconds. Two energy plateaus prevent complete bot inactivity. Energy is transferred between waves from .50 to 1.00 seconds. Bots generate narrowband, sinusoidal signals that fast-drift after a burst. Pre-critical bot activity consisted of signal anomalies lasting from .006 until .048 seconds. Bots began to oscillate in low power flux (<25 dB) and transitioned to a brief equilibrium before reaching 94.12 dB at 2090.91 Hz where 91% was noise. Time to critical mass by spectrogram of bots alone was estimated at .00025 seconds. Virality of bots was found to be equivalent to a maximum of 80 simultaneous Geiger "clicks" and musical harp sounds unpacking intermittently into pulses before

dissipating. Energy projection was also equivalent to $.02\mu Sv/hr$ or $2.0\ mrem$ similar to receiving a (small dose of ionizing radiation) for a plain chest x-ray.

Overall, bots (re)produced the intrinsic “virality” of tweets (by volume of tweets) with human users. Their interactions were regulated through entangled processes and redundant connections (signal loops in place of feedback loops). The study of “COVID-19 infodemic” on Twitter is an epitome of a complex network analysis (to claim) for advancing “infodemiology”. Data sonification proved to be very useful in the interpretation of signal anomalies that supported detection of Twitter bots and gave the way to reveal their unreported energetic nature.

Conclusions

Research Proposition 1: COVID-19 vaccine ‘infodemic’ (misinformation spread) has linear and nonlinear mechanisms.

As much as 41% of Twitter bots have been detected at a $\geq .43$ Botometer[®] threshold score but around 17% were most influential by degree calculation. Misinformation spread occurred more significantly via replies than by retweets suggesting human users who were involved were influenced by bots a lot of times, and it validated actor network theory which was regulated by second-order cybernetics.

It is plausible too that most influential bots assumed these human accounts and were sophisticated enough to generate replies. **Bot tweets are discontinuous with**

a decreasing monotonic sequence after a critical mass splurge. Inter tweet (break periods) pattern every three months showed more bots can remain active than with burst tweets of activity.

Bot layer contains 562 nodes with 316 edges. Human layer contains 824 nodes with 533 edges. Tweet layer contains 1374 nodes with 693 edges. There are 24 edges between bot layer and human layer while 61 edges are between human layer and tweet layer. A total of 139 vertices are connected (entangled) and believed to undergo 'superpositioning' across three layers.

The number of assumed deceptive accounts or false human accounts was high at 67% ($n=64$) while only 33% ($n=31$) were traditional bots, in particular, 24% ($n=23$) were "**spambots**" out of the most influential nodes ($n=95$) in the bot layer. On the other hand, derived from total cases ($N=1374$) in the tweet layer, "**spambots**" were around 27% ($n=375$).

Mass of bot tweets is approximately 46% and spread faster via interlayer edges—the multilayer entanglements. Mass of bots alone is degree-dependent in favor of where information flows.

Bots form a single focal group while humans have multiple large groups. Tweet layers undergo human-like clustering and bots conform (graft) around them. By Circos plots, bots show dense, traversing, and conflating edges that form a stretched triangular shape.

By adjacency matrix, bots were more connected into small groups compared to humans. Hybrid bots technically provide ties between users and the central hub and can moderate the formed echo chamber. Bot infiltration may segregate users into small (functional) groups.

By assortativity, bots work in proximity with other bots and absorb more energy. Bot types engage in a more heterogenous or 'disassortative' (-0.64) manner than humans (-0.50). However, 'disassortativity' of users with tweets (-0.51) is convincingly more human-related than bots. Bots converge through synchronicity with other local bots.

By Louvain modularity, bots form small connected communities and are responsible for connections to and from human hubs.

By k -core decomposition, most influential bots connect themselves in a nonagon structure where two bots interlude the chain and can be speculated at least as hubs in the 'connectome' resembling a Markov chain neural network.

By betweenness centrality and eigenvector centrality (**first network analysis**), bot distribution abruptly increments towards the central hub while a human pattern wanes linearly with tweets away from the central hub. Bots emulate human users via in-degree connections; however, there were more outbound links than inbound links discovered. They do not have the large central hub so they disperse exponentially into small but highly-linked homogenous clusters.

Bots will attack the central human hub indirectly through individual and small clusters of human users at the periphery of the network. Bots are characterized in terms of high betweenness and eigenvector centralities (most especially if values undulate with percolations), random walk score, and PageRank score are false human accounts (e.g., "**bev768**"). Random walk and PageRank scores do not become very useful with heterogenous multiplex networks. Super spreaders are detected using centrality-based metrics.

By clique formation and entanglement, the number of cliques escalates inconsistently in the bot layer but diminishes in the human layer. Bots do not bud off

from their central hub. On the other hand, peripherally-oriented clusters are held together by a central hub in the human layer. Bot clusters graft themselves to the central human hub by edge entanglement. These bots are classified as “other,” “self-declared,” and “spammers” (e.g., “**ronnoconiv**,” “**NFL**,” “**dansiddiqui**,” “**StefanLazar10**,” and “**santa_tzu**”).

Research Proposition 2: The “Twitterverse” is perturbable (easily affected internally and externally) as any open system and pliable as any social media network; and

Research Proposition 6: The von Neuman entropy corresponds to network evolution, at least with regard to edge formation.

The global structural information divergence by von Neumann graph entropy (VNGE) was calculated using the Fast Incremental von Neumann Graph Entropy (FINGER) algorithm was 3.2549 versus 2.1320 approximated over a time complexity of .0109. This suggests that 2.69345 (averaged) edge is added per .011 seconds. VNGE increases from bot layer to human layer (the major source of divergence) and spreads in the tweet layer where the value lowers. Human layer is most influential across all layers. Twitter feeds were uploaded by all users. Any tweet inputs will modify the internal dynamics.

By entropy from node entanglements in the network, spambots are entangled ubiquitously (e.g., “**Left_of_You**” and “**Daniel2510G**”) while the false human accounts (e.g., “**CobyJayJr42**” and “**babibelle33**”) connect by power-law distribution. Entanglements (structural) were more frequent from bots (intensity at .4161) than from

humans (.0038). Many cross-links existed between bots and humans thus a low entanglement homogeneity (<1) was calculated.

Research Proposition 3: Twitter bots are key players with the same agency as human accounts but are much more prolific spreaders (super spreaders). Twitter bots, however, are designed amplifiers of information whether factual or not (dis- or misinformation).

By the second round of network analytics, negative entanglement has confirmed the mixed but temporal states of nodes. Bots work in proximity among themselves in one to two large cliques since total closeness centrality is high (>1). Intermediating bots are infrequent since betweenness centrality is low (<1).

On the other hand, there can be many bots competing to direct and redirect human users to low credibility tweets using multiple edges, thus random walk and PageRank scores are low (<1).

Spectral gap across centrality rankings proved the temporality of bot influence every .0687 seconds based on fast changing internal node states and in response to before and after percolation tests.

Critical bot threshold after virality lowers following the break of critical mass. Bots will need less energy to reactivate owing to energy conservation. After percolation, central spreaders (mostly false human accounts) have increased percolation centrality, random walk and PageRank scores while peripheral spreaders (mostly spammers) have decreased. Accounts that did not change in values (again mostly spammers) have indirect connections and are diffused across the network.

Energy scavenger nodes are supposed to subsist. They replicate the transmission of misinformation and actively cycle a viral behavior and then energy gradient is exacerbated on the basis of spatiotemporality. The cycling will favor more rogue node diffusion and ratification of more connections. Misinformation flows are at the advantage of the fluidity of the “Twitterverse” by energy permeation within its unbounded quantum field which is an energy disequilibrium-driven spontaneity to a non-zero decay.

Research Proposition 4: Critical mass corresponds to the (kinetic) energy peak; and
Research Proposition 8: Distribution of critical mass into energy corresponds to wave peaks.

By energy quantization using the Schrödinger equation, (unbounded) energy moves in quasi-continuous bands of waves where bots create unnatural perturbations or energy is added synthetically and unequally in the network, thus kurtosis of energy in the network prevails (wave packets centralizing on the left of the potential well or at Region II). They induce local excitation using narrow impulses and bring the local field to a higher (quantum) potential energy.

Diffusion of bots and misinformation as energy crossing the multilayers can be represented with tunneling time where, in reference to a lower β , (fast-phasing) spammer (e.g., **newsmax**) and false human account bots (e.g., **JonPort79449036**) were notorious.

Disruptive shifts at peak energy potential at $99.9 J^{-2}s^{-2}$ with $1.68 \times 10^{-1} J^{-2}s^{-2}$ (pseudo) threshold from the (1) spreading of mass concentrations and (2)

discontinuous behavior of bots was shown as wavefunction decoherence and quasi-disentangled phase (overriding events but alternating eigenstates, >1 and <1) respectively, i.e., high intensity by seven months for total tweets of 1374. Intuitively, 29.45% of energy will ramp up with 13.55% increase in tweets.

Gaps in energy were suggestive of mass conservation but will show minimal recovery. More (mis)information has to enter into the network. About 18 J (36%) of energy is lost thermodynamically at the start. First, energy is intensified (.02 to .24 seconds). Second, energy is scattered (.46 to 1.12 seconds). Finally, energy is decomposed (1.34 to 1.56 seconds).

Seventy percent of local energy perturbation (i.e., reflecting node dynamics) is bot-mediated. They amend the network energy incrementation exponentially faster to 70000 J while bot clusters increase with energy in the network. From a near critical mass, it may take .0015 seconds to unleash the tide of energy chaos theoretically. The energy overspill will be 9.61×10^6 J. Phase (inactive node to active node) transition may be claimed around .0003 seconds.

Furthermore, bots re-extract energy from low energy fluctuations in the network to steady, finer fluctuations. In simulation, a sharp increment from a very low potential energy up to 50 J is reached at .26 seconds. However, without the bots, network energy threshold is reached longer at .29 seconds through multiple potentiating steps. Threshold difference was statistically significant ($p = .0397$). Bots were energy catalysts and energy gates.

Infodemic mitigation should aim to polarize the 50 J threshold by injection of new massive information and perhaps using counteracting bots. The uneven distribution of tweet creation matches the energy landscape. Bots contour misinformation flow resulting to an 'overdamp' (saturation) of mass within the radius

of their degree of node connections. Overall, bot activity pattern is monotonic: increasing along with critical mass and decreasing after the infodemic loses kinetic energy (i.e., no additional or new misinformation inputs were made by users).

Non-Gaussian energy fluctuations will likely indicate the flourishing energy of bots and partly the sequestration of energy out of the potential well (1.12 to 1.34 seconds gap). This period is the changeover into unbound state where bots can multiply their activities through other infected nodes.

By eigen decomposition, bots' potential energy cannot fall quick because of two energy plateaus which will prevent their complete inactivation and will allow a larger energy gradient for recovery. They may be energized with a large (incoming) impulse by the network and/or other nodes progressing to (outgoing) sequential pulses (while redundancy increases) with narrowing intervals (after becoming energized) until energy lowers. The frequency amplitude shifts from Poisson to non-Poisson on a log-normal law.

Research Proposition 5: Entanglements correspond to the interlayer or any anomalous and/or alternate connections between nodes and the frequencies at the same energy level (nonstructural entanglement) allowing signals to “quantum jump” overcoming spatiotemporality limitations during unbound states of nodes in the field.

By signal plot simulation (spectrogram visualization), in-between frequency entanglements (energy level entanglements) may arise from .50 to 1.00 secs, which can permit energy transferring from wave to wave. Noisy signals represent the “chaotic entanglement” whenever degree (number of connections) will increase.

Signals were narrowband, fast-drifting and scattering after a burst. This is showing chaos to randomness. Bots magnify chaos in the network by resonating misinformation within a two-second cycle. Detection will be flawed because node states are mixed: information about users and neighbor users imbricate so well. Nonlinear and linear physics intersect; thereby nodes have complex interactions. Entanglements exist both at a topological level and energy level. There is “co-entanglement” in the massive spread of misinformation.

Research Proposition 7: Node synchronization corresponds to the fundamental force (i.e., by coupling strength) in network dynamics.

By node synchronization using the Kuramoto model, the relative ‘strength of interaction’ (critical coupling) among bots was higher ($K_c = .21$) than among humans ($K_c = .11$) and tweets ($K_c = .14$). Bots take a shorter time to synchronize (but only partially) around 400 seconds (6.67 minutes) with a peak before reaching 200 seconds (3.33 minutes) than humans.

It was shown that at $K_c = .15$ no bot synchronization and phase-locking happen or with a low coupling strength, i.e., $K_c \leq .20$ and with a 15% reduction of active bots. They may have split dynamics (simultaneous synchronization and desynchronization, but one-way dependent on other nodes) based on missing natural frequency values, which is a trademark of artificial intelligence.

Multi stability (two equilibrium periods) may be inferred from plateaus before and after the frequency generated by bots. Bots are signal drivers on a sinusoidal waveform, but tend to be nonuniform or asymptotic. They are capable of increasing

resistance to information flow. Core bots oscillate in many small (low degree) clusters and cause small, continual perturbations if connected to large human hubs.

Research Proposition 9: The Twitter bots' audio footprint corresponds to their level of "virality" or brute effects.

By audio spectrogram, energy rages above 120 *Hz* or to longer radio wavelengths until 4800 *Hz* with signal sonification. At this level of detection, pre-critical bot activity will be presumed as signal anomalies lasting from .006 until .048 seconds before turning surreptitious. This alludes for the pre-bot attack detection. Overlapping (entangled) events appear at .048 seconds through .20 seconds. Small (cluster) perturbations come at .20 seconds until .25575 seconds.

Increasing harmonic ratio variations will indicate decreasing entropy (return to equilibrium). Bots oscillate initially in low power flux (<25 *dB*) and are then dropping to a brief equilibrium. They get energized while on frequency transition and surge up to 94.12 *dB* at 2090.91 *Hz*.

By root mean square (RMS), sound distorts harshly (loud bursting) when peaks get too high or low deviations occur (*SD*). Rising entropies were the change in pitch (towards decrescendo) and waveform metamorphoses. Both were perceived as signs of evolution of energy.

Energy in the network and bot energy materializes into a pre-critical mass and will reach criticality if misinformation continues to build inside Twitter. Muffled sounds indicated 'chaotic events' (the "virality" unfolding) seen as fibrillatory waveforms on the spectrogram and the changing foreground sound with superimposed background noise. Sonification underscored the stochastic (ever-changing) character of bots.

There were periodic energy fluctuations from .00025 to .05 seconds (mixed anomalies) while massive turmoil (post critical mass) was from .05025 to .25575 seconds. So, time to critical mass will be at .00025 seconds parallel to influential node synchronization and local energy spill from the potential well.

Data sonification using combined Geiger “clicks” and musical harp sounds revealed 70 to 80 tones unpacking intermittently into pulses before getting sparse. The chosen sound representation was strongly correlated, $r(1021) = 0.74$, $p = < .05$. The sound signature is declared for most influential bots. Total energy equivalent was close to $.02 \mu Sv/hr$ or $2.0 mrem$ like a chest x-ray exposure.

Within a chaotic data, bursts of energies were noisier at lower fluctuations and frequency decomposition is longer. Raw audio analysis proved there was a wide dampening and long quiescent interval to decomposition after strong, varying fluctuations at the beginning.

Transitioning into noise was an indication of energy loss. However, optimization of sonification will require a significant decrease in sound variance (from 1279.37 to 60.47). Actually, 91% was all about noise. Positive skewness and kurtosis of sound waves were attributed to a nonsymmetric energy decomposition. Parameter mapping was instrumental to make more sense out of the unprocessed audio.

Research Proposition 10: The “virality” of Twitter bots corresponds to the quantized network energy measured through Twitter bots’ activity on top of human activity (their dynamic expanse is over tweets exchanged).

By (particle) equation models, a Twitter bot mass of 9.51×10^{-30} will give 1.58×10^{-13} J of kinetic energy. The other half is the potential energy required. The energy in the network is 2.14×10^{-18} J which is much lower than bots, but energy in a network has a linear noisy profile. Bots add energy in the network and significant noise per human user activity. The “virality” of Twitter bots was calculated at .70 or concluding that 70% of local energy perturbation (reflecting node dynamics) in the network was bot-mediated. However, Twitter bots and humans (genuine Twitter accounts and humans orchestrating bot attacks) were both key infodemic players. Bots co-create “virality” with human users in the “Twitterverse” by entangled processes and redundant connections (signal loops, i.e., exceeding classical topology).

Recommendations

It is highly recommended that the proposed models and the coded pipeline are further investigated. A full length of twitter data sonification is needed. Logical and seed values will have to be standardized.

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